

PAsCAL

Enhance driver behaviour & Public Acceptance
of Connected & Autonomous vehicles

Grant agreement no.: 815098

D7.3 – Data analysis of user acceptance from trials and simulations

Date of publication: 31-08-2022

Disclaimer

This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 815098.

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D7.3 – Data analysis of user acceptance from trials and simulations

Work package No.	7	Work package Title	Impact Assessment
Tasks involved in the reported results	Task 7.3 Integrated data analysis		
Deliverable owner	UNIVLEEDS		
Dissemination level	PU		
Due date	31/07/2022		
Delivery date	31/08/2022		

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Version History		
Version	Date	Summary of changes
0.1	22/11/2021	Table of Content and responsibilities agreed
0.2	04/04/2022	Chapter 2 for pilot 1 analysis completed
0.3	11/07/2022	Chapters 4 & 6 for pilot 3 & 5 analysis completed
0.4	15/07/2022	Chapter 5 for pilot 4 analysis completed
0.5	18/07/2022	Chapter 7 for cross-pilot analysis completed
0.6	18/07/2022	Chapter 8 for none-pilot analysis completed
0.7	14/08/2022	Chapter 9 for HELIFLIGHT-R analysis completed
0.8	16/08/2022	Pilot 2 results added in Chapter 3, and all sections completed for peer-reviews
0.9	26/08/2022	Review comments considered
1.0	31/08/2022	Final check/submission

List of acronyms	
Acronym	Meaning
ABS	Automatic Braking System
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AP	Automatic Parking

CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
BPS	Blind and Partially Sighted
EBU	European Blind Union
ELD	Elder person
FDG	Focus Discussion Group
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LK	Lane Keeping
LR	Likelihood Ratio
PT	Public Transportation
SCI	Spinal Cord Injuries
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TMC	Temporary Mobility Constraints
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

Notice

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Executive summary

The aim of PAsCAL is to develop a holistic, user-centric Guide-to-Autonomy concept aimed at accelerating the user-friendly evolution of connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) and transport systems. In doing so, it addresses important issues relating to the role of humans in this evolution, ranging from real-time driving control to long-term training needs for jobs, in particular appropriate interactions of the autonomous vehicles with different road users including disabled people and non-drivers.

As part of the study, PAsCAL has conducted thorough studies in public acceptance via surveys (e.g. online, face-to-face interviews), driving scenarios in simulation as well as training and education. To validate the findings from these studies, PAsCAL carried out five real-world pilots which cover different vehicles, user groups, levels of automation, and driving experiences in a range of complex operating environments, especially as regards any problems inside and outside the autonomous vehicle, and the connectivity of transport systems with emphasis on vulnerable road users. To understand how these real-world activities were designed, planned and executed, please refer to Deliverable 6.3 – “Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

This deliverable reports the results of the data analysis of these pilots, together with an online survey to reach out to the wider community as well as a use case of an autonomous air taxi to assess and elaborate common issues, approaches and lessons learned across different transport modes, with a specific focus on investigating and providing insights regarding user acceptance.

The analysis was done separately per user category, namely: age, gender, willingness to pay and mobility need, where appropriate. Users’ preferences for future services and future use of CAVs and the stakeholders’ acceptance, opinions and willingness to use CAVs were studied. The data from each pilot were examined individually, as each pilot had a different focus and research questions to investigate. However, cross-pilot analysis was also conducted to better understand common “global” factors that influence acceptance.

Pilot 1 “High-capacity autonomous bus operations” suggested that the absence of a human driver may be perceived as a major issue that could hinder acceptance. Moreover, unexpected malfunctioning events (doors not opening in this case) may negatively influence acceptance levels. The

latter could be an indication of the heightened expectations of users with respect to the performance of automated vehicles. Given the potential negative implications of the automated technology and the absence of human staff, users may be expecting flawless performance to trust and use the technology. Actions need to be considered to compensate these negative implications of unexpected situations. Participants who felt more confident by the presence of the system were also more likely to accept the technology. To that end, enhancing confidence and trust via advanced technological communication solutions could be a future direction.

Pilot 2 “Autonomous driving training” mainly focused on the effects of driver training on acceptance. With respect to that aspect, a positive attitude towards the training was correlated with positive responses towards acceptance-related questions. However, adequacy, efficiency, and whether participants would suggest similar training to others were found to have little correlation with the responses to acceptance-related questions. Vehicle reactions and difficulty to use were two additional factors that had a considerable impact on acceptance.

Pilot 3 “Autonomous bus line” investigated the acceptance of a fully autonomous and connected electric bus with autonomy level 4. An interesting finding regarding this pilot was that regarding performance of the vehicle. Acceptance levels were higher when the latter was perceived as better compared to a human driver. That is, even if performance was perceived as equal, the public might decide to keep using conventional and familiar solutions, unless additional benefits from the CAV use are perceived.

Pilot 4 “Shared connected transport” further highlighted the importance of vehicle performance on acceptance. Performance needs to be perceived as “more comfortable” compared to the conventional experience to ensure high acceptance levels. Similarly, the performance of the vehicle needs to be better than a human driver, as any other outcome (including performing the same as a human driver) may not suffice to ensure acceptance. Moreover, CAV reactions perceived as “very good” were significantly related to acceptance. This is a finding that also occurred in pilot 2.

Finally, pilot 5 “Experience of vulnerable travellers with connected transport environment” investigated the acceptance of connected transport environment and apps. Obstacle frequency was significantly and positively correlated to two of the acceptance related questions (willingness to use and willingness to pay). In the same direction, participants who considered independence while travelling as important were also more likely to have higher acceptance levels. These are

potentially the attributes that such connected environment applications should promote and highlight as their main functionalities to enhance acceptance levels.

The cross-pilot analysis compared pilots using public transport modes and passenger cars. Feelings during the experience were in general significantly related to acceptance. The most commonly significant feeling expressed was that of feeling trustful. Trust is a major concept related to acceptance and it needs to be ensured in order to enhance acceptance. Another shared finding regards anticipation; participants positively surprised by the performance of CAVs were more likely to have higher levels of acceptance (even compared to those who perceived the experience “as expected”). It has been mentioned that CAVs need to outperform conventional solutions and this finding has been observed consistently across pilots. Difficulty to use and general confidence in CAVs were also consistently significant across passenger cars. Finally, it should be mentioned that participants’ background characteristics were significant only in a few cases. This suggests that the findings presented in the current document may be applicable to the average user regardless of their background; factors such as feelings, vehicle performance, safety, and difficulty to use are more important than demographic characteristics to enhance acceptance.

In addition to the aforementioned pilots, Task 7.3 carried out an online survey with wider society to better understand the people’s preferences (i.e. non-users of the PAsCAL innovations) towards autonomous public transport bus/shuttle and their needs from autonomous public transport vehicles. The key conclusions obtained from the study include:

- ‘Using mobile applications’, ‘large fonts on HMI display’ and ‘auditory communication’ are preferred HMI methods by respondents.
- For requirements towards in-vehicle assistance and information, respondents prefer ‘communication with the vehicle for special assistance’, ‘visual communication with the vehicle such as HMI and mobile apps’ and the ‘presence of steward’.
- A high proportion of individuals responded ‘don’t know’ for improvement in passenger safety and improvement in other road safety by autonomous bus/shuttle.

Finally, this deliverable also reports the study of a non-road transport use case to address common issues, approaches and lessons learned (e.g. HMI, “driver” behaviour, ethical decision making) across different transport modes. It explored attitudes to an autonomous air taxi before and after

simulated flight. The work aimed to assess the current attitudes of people to autonomous air taxis and the potential to influence these attitudes via simulated flight trials. As a result of this work, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Current Attitudes:

- People are, on the whole, positive about the concept of an autonomous air taxi. This is in terms of the safety, trust and future use of such systems.
- People are neutral about requiring consent from the user for the system's actions.
- There is a preference for the system to have only partial control over complete control of a user journey.

Correlations:

- There is a positive correlation between the attitudes of people and their increasing education level.
- There is a negative correlation between attitude and the age of the participant and driving experience
- There is no correlation definite correlation between the attitude of people and with the level of autonomy experience they have.

Change in Attitude:

- The simulated flight trials provide a broadly positive increase in opinions of people towards autonomous air taxis.
- Using autonomy by consent provides larger increase in people's opinion that by exception, although both modes still produce a positive increase in opinion.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and organization of the document

This deliverable (D7.3) presents the findings of the analysis of the data collected in five real-world pilots, namely:

- “High-capacity autonomous bus operations” (Chapter 2);
- “Autonomous driving training” (Chapter 3);
- “Autonomous bus line” (Chapter 4);
- “Shared connected transport” (Chapter 5);
- “Experience of vulnerable travellers with connected transport environment” (Chapter 6).

These pilots were defined to capture the user acceptance of different vehicles, targeted users, levels of automation, and driving experiences in a range of complex operating environments. A cross-pilot analysis was also carried out to better understand common “global” factors that influence acceptance, as described in Chapter 7.

Chapter 8 presents the findings from an online survey with wide society, in particular non-users of the PAsCAL innovations.

Chapter 9 presents the CAVs work in air transport using the HELIFLIGHT-R simulator to explore attitudes to an autonomous air taxi before and after simulated flight.

1.2 Intended audience of this document

The work reported in this document has made different kinds of contributions including:

- Empirical contribution, the results of the particular surveys conducted and analysed, which has important implications for the future design of CAV systems;
- Methodological contribution, in terms of how the user acceptance analysis was conducted, which others interested in user acceptance of CAVs could replicate in the future;
- Research contribution, in identifying important gaps in knowledge and/or unexpected outcomes of the surveys;

- Policy contribution, in terms of providing evidence that may guide future policy on regulating or promoting adoption of CAV systems and vehicles.

The main audience for this document is the consortium members of the PAsCAL project, specifically partners responsible for analysing the datasets and information collected during the execution of these pilots. They can profit from the context in which the data were gathered and potentially measure the impact of deviations of any kind on the responses participants gave.

Furthermore, this document can be understood as a guideline for future research involving mobility or CAV pilots, which require feedback from users and data collection for impact assessment. The lessons learnt during this process are invaluable for acceptance analysis, as well as the future design, planning and execution of CAV pilots.

Finally, the results of the pilots can be of interest to the following professional groups:

- Manufacturers of CAVs and developers of CAV technologies;
- Researchers and academic bodies;
- Organisations of focus groups (vulnerable persons including persons with mobility constraints or the blind and partially sighted);
- Policy makers and legislative bodies;
- Public transport planners and operators;
- Developers of Information & Communication Technology (ICT), Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs), Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS).

2 Pilot 1: High-Capacity Autonomous Bus Operations

2.1 Introduction

Pilot 1 focused on the acceptance of an automated bus system. The pilot was organised and conducted by EBUS, while recruitment of participants was done jointly by EBUS, LIST, LuxMobility and EBU. Data collection took place in the Truck & Bus Centre in Livange, Luxembourg. The pilot was focused on a highly automated bus implemented via a Wizard-of-Oz approach; driver/personnel was on-board controlling the bus, although participants were unaware of this. A total of 51 participants took part in the experiment which was conducted in two waves. The second wave consisted of blind or partially sighted (BPS). Participants acted as passengers and evaluated aspects related to their experience and the absence of human staff on board. The details of the pilot and data collection have been presented in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

2.2 Data collection

In pilot 1, a total of 51 participants took part in five batches and two waves of experiments, executed in the period of May-November 2021. In each batch, a specific scenario was simulated with the aim to provoke different viewpoints and reservations towards PT automation. After each experiment, participants’ experiences were collected via questionnaires and discussion.

Participants also attended a 15-minute presentation. The presentation stuck to a generic focus on the future of transportation, which combines electrification, connectivity, digitalisation and automation. Topics covered were the general objective of the PAsCAL project, the potential benefits of emerging technologies on transportation systems and finally, details related to the pilot execution. Two types of scenarios were tested – a “control scenario” and an “event scenario”. The former consisted of a simple trajectory, on which it was not planned that the bus would experience any incidences. The latter included technical and operational simulated malfunctions, referred to as events of which three were tested: “long idling”, “doors issue”, and “car blocking the path of the bus”. Also participants experienced either a basic or advanced ICT system to partially replace the role of a human driver. The extended system allowed to launch

an incoming videocall from the control centre informing the passengers about the events taking place. The final route together with events are illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Additional qualitative information was collected, such as Incidence Report Forms for each batch of participants, photos and video recordings. All qualitative data has been documented and analysed in detail in Deliverable D6.3 “Pilot implementation and evaluation”. All participants signed a GDPR-compliant form to agree to the processing of the gathered datasets and also audio-visual materials gathered during the pilot execution. All datasets have been anonymised previous to the analysis of the datasets to ensure the protection of each individual’s privacy and identity.

Figure 2.1: Pilot 1, Test route overview and location of special events

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 Analysis

Given the categorical nature of the data, the Chi-Square test of independence (via cross-tabulation analysis) was used to evaluate the relation of the variables presented in Section 2.3.2 with the other questions

included in the surveys. The chi-squared test follows a commonly known formula, wherein O stands for the observed values and E for the expected values.

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

X²: Chi – squared

O_i: Observed value

E_i: Expected value

The analysis itself consists of 4 distinct steps:

1. Case processing to define the validity of the data collected; this part involved either identification of missing/invalid values or recoding the responses to different groups to ensure a higher number of observed responses within each response group.
2. Crosstabulation in absolute numbers, containing both the expected values and actual values;
3. The actual chi-squared test, yielding a minimum expected count & asymptotic significance level (2-sided);
4. Symmetric measures including approximate significance.

A widely accepted rule of thumb is that within each cell, the expected count of observations (the count that one would expect to observe if two variables are completely independent) should be at least 5. If more than 20% of cells have less than five observations, then the reliability of the test decreases. When that assumption was not met, the Likelihood-ratio (LR) test was considered instead (McHugh, 2013). The likelihood ratio (else G-test) is specified as

$$G = 2 \sum_i \sum_j \left[O_{ij} \ln \left(\frac{O_{ij}}{E_{ij}} \right) \right]$$

where O_{ij} and E_{ij} are the observed and expected variables respectively in the i th row and j th column of the cross-tabulation matrix. With the increase of the sample size as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the test statistic follows an asymptotic χ^2 distribution with degrees of freedom $(I-1)(J-1)$, where I and J represent the number of rows and columns of a cross-tabulation matrix. The significance

of the likelihood ratio test is evaluated based on the aforementioned degrees of freedom.

Other researchers have suggested the use of *exact tests*, such as Fisher's test. However, the latter has been considered as conservative (Lin et al., 2015) and was not considered in the present report. The significance of the Chi-Square test is reflected in the p-value provided in each of the tables. The p-values are colour coded to indicate the level of significance. In particular, **green colour**, indicates significance at the 0.05 level, **orange colour** indicates significance at the 0.1 level and **brown colour** indicates insignificant results. The interpretation of the Chi-Square tests was conducted via compared the observed counts of an outcome versus the expected counts, if the two groups involved were totally unrelated. For instance, an observed count value higher than the expected indicates that this relationship is more likely to occur, than expected; hence there is a pattern and association between the two groups involved.

As mentioned, given that the number of observations per category within each question, on some occasions, responses have been aggregated (recoded) in order to obtain higher representativeness and strengthen the power of the statistical analysis. These have been documented throughout the report.

2.3.2 Indicators of acceptance

The aim of the current document is to analyse and provide further insights with respect to CAVs' level of acceptance. That is, a series of questions from participants' survey was considered as indicators of acceptance. The relationship of the latter was investigated with regards to other variables available in the survey.

Table 2.1 presents the questions that as indicators of CAV acceptance. Each question is assigned a code that is used for the remainder of the document for convenience. The original code of the question as documented in Deliverable D6.3 is also provided in brackets. The columns of *indicator category* and *indicator* were derived from "Deliverable 6.2 – Pilot Setup".

Due to the low sample size and the low frequency in some of the responses, the latter were recoded, in order to increase the statistical power of the tests presented in Section 2.1.2. The recoded groups are presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.1: Indicators of acceptance

Code	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)
Q1.1 (Q44 in D6.3)	If autonomous buses were available I would use them	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q1.2 (Q46 in D6.3)	Do you think autonomous buses can significantly improve citizens' everyday mobility (make public transport more attractive)?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Quality of life
Q1.3 (Q30 in D6.3)	Would you let other members of your family or close circle use autonomous buses?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to let others use
Q1.4 (Q29 in D6.3)	Could you see yourself using autonomous buses in the future?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Attitudes and human factors
Q1.5 (Q45 in D6.3)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use autonomous buses. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 2.2: Original and recoded groups

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q1.1	- I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	No edits

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses - I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible 	
Q1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I don't know - No - Yes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Other than yes
Q1.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certainly - Depends on how the technology evolves - Probably - Not at all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes (Certainly) - Other than yes (Certainly)
Q1.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certainly - Depends on how the technology evolves - Probably - Probably not 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes (Certainly) - Other than yes (Certainly)
Q1.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad. - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses. (Any other response was removed)

2.4 Results

2.4.1 The impact of visual impairment

Despite the lower number of blind and partially sighted (BPS) participants (Wave 2) the responses to the questions of the surveys were investigated with respect to their similarity between Waves 1 and 2. Similar patterns in

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the responses (no significant differences), would allow the responses of both waves to be considered simultaneously and increase the sample size. Table 2.3 presents some questions that significantly differed. For the variables that had significant differences, analysis was conducted both considering and excluding participants from Wave 2.

Table 2.3: Wave 1 & 2 tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Navigation	Likelihood-ratio (LR)	4.840	0.028	51
Bike sharing	LR	4.645	0.031	51
Ride sharing	LR	6.055	0.014	51
Driver assistance	LR	2.835	0.092	51
Shared mobility app	LR	4.009	0.045	51
Reduced price	LR	3.705	0.054	51
Bus emergency	LR	4.009	0.045	51
Passenger vulnerability	LR	3.155	0.076	51

Table 2.4 to Table 2.7 refer to responses at the question “Q8 - What kind of Connected and/or Automated Vehicle (CAV) have you tried?”, as presented in D6.3. Participants could select as many of the available options (These have been documented as 0 if an option was not selected and 1 if it was selected).

The results suggested that significant differences occurred with respect to navigation & routing services, bike-, scooter-, Car-sharing services, ride sharing and use of driver assistance. Despite the significance in the results, the differences between the expected and observed counts are small (which is expected given the low number of individuals in Wave 2). The differences are expected as, BPS possibly are not able to drive and use the services reported in the aforementioned tables.

Table 2.4: Use of navigation between the two waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Navigation	0	Count	0	1
		Expected Count	.9	.1
	1	Count	46	4
		Expected Count	45.1	4.9

Table 2.5: Use of bike sharing services between the two waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Bike sharing	0	Count	28	5
		Expected Count	29.8	3.2
	1	Count	18	0
		Expected Count	16.2	1.8

Table 2.6: Use of ride sharing services between the two waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Ride sharing	0	Count	24	5
		Expected Count	26.2	2.8
	1	Count	22	0
		Expected Count	19.8	2.2

Table 2.7: Use of driver assistance services between the two waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Driver assistance	0	Count	19	4
		Expected Count	20.7	2.3
	1	Count	27	1
		Expected Count	25.3	2.7

Table 2.8 refers to the “Shared mobility application” option from question “Q15 - Do you use one or several of the following applications?”, as presented in D6.3. Similar to Q8, participants could respond with a multiple-choice form. With reference to the results, BPS are less likely to use this type of application.

Table 2.8: Use of shared mobility app between the waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Shared mobility app	0	Count	30	5
		Expected Count	31.6	3.4
	1	Count	16	0
		Expected Count	14.4	1.6

Table 2.9 refers to question “ Q27 - Which potential benefits do you see in using autonomous buses?”. Participants could select between as many of the listed benefits. A significant difference was observed only with respect to the opinion about lower prices. In particular, participants from Wave 1 were more likely to consider lower prices as a potential benefit.

Table 2.9: Lower price as a CAV benefit between the waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Lower price (Benefits)	0	Count	31	5
		Expected Count	32.5	3.5
	1	Count	15	0
		Expected Count	13.5	1.5

Table 2.10 and Table 2.11 refer to “Q32 - Do you think that emergency situations will be more difficult to handle without a driver?” and “Q34 - Do you think that users of autonomous buses will be more vulnerable to robbers/pickpocketing/violent passengers?” from D6.3 respectively. BPS people may have higher risk perception regarding the automated bus operations

Table 2.10: Perception about emergency situations between the waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Emergency situations	0	Count	16	0
		Expected Count	14.4	1.6
	1	Count	30	5
		Expected Count	31.6	3.4

Table 2.11: Perception about passenger vulnerability between the waves

		Wave		
		1	2	
Passenger vulnerability	0	Count	28	1
		Expected Count	26.2	2.8
	1	Count	18	4
		Expected Count	19.8	2.2

2.4.2 The impact of scenarios and ICT type

Participants were assigned in two different conditions. In the control condition, no specific events took place during the pilot. In the second conditions as series of scenarios (automation malfunctions) occurred. The impact of events was investigated with respect to acceptance. As shown in Table 2.12 (codes in “Variable” column follow the codes presented in 2.3.2), no significant associations were found, except for Q1.1.

Table 2.12: Events occurrence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	7.646	0.022	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.370	0.543	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	0.004	0.947	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.253	0.615	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.732	0.392	43

Table 2.13 shows the relationship between event occurrence with question Q1.1. The results suggest that participants were less willing to use the technology in the “events” condition while they were more likely to state “avoiding” using the technology. This finding could be an indication of heightened performance expectations by the users; people may expect flawless performance to use the CAV technologies.

Table 2.13: The association of event occurrence with Q1.1.

		Scenario type		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	10	17
		Expected Count	11.1	15.9
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	11	8
		Expected Count	7.8	11.2
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	0	5
		Expected Count	2.1	2.9

Participants were assigned in two different levels of ICT support namely, the basic and the extended level. The impact of ICT support level on acceptance was investigated via Chi-Square tests. As shown in Table 2.25, no significant associations were found, except for Q1.2.

Table 2.14: ICT level tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	7.646	0.800	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	3.563	0.059	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	0.855	0.355	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.855	0.355	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.148	0.700	43

Table 2.15 shows the relationship between ICT support level with question Q1.2. The results were counter intuitive, as extended ICT support was related to lower perception of improvements in mobility. Hence, there was no indication of a positive impact of extended ICT system support on acceptance.

Table 2.15: The association of event occurrence with Q1.2.

		ICT level		
		basic	extended	
Q1.2	Other than yes	Count	12	10
		Expected Count	15.1	6.9
	Yes	Count	23	6
		Expected Count	19.9	9.1

2.4.3 The impact of perception towards scenarios and ICT

The “doors risk” question regards the scenario-related question “Q41 - Did you feel at risk when the bus stopped, but the doors did not open as expected?” presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential response was yes, no and I didn’t notice. This question was only responded by participants who experienced a “malfunction” scenario during the pilot. Other similar questions were Q39 and Q30 (presented in deliverable D6.3 “Pilot implementation and evaluation”) however, responses were heavily skewed towards one outcome and hence were not examined. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 2.16.

Table 2.16: Doors risk scenario tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	1.150	0.563	25
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.371	0.543	25
Q1.3	Chi-Square	6.997	0.008	25
Q1.4	Chi-Square	6.740	0.009	25
Q1.5	LR	3.956	0.047	21

Variable: Doors risk scenario risk

Positive responses both regarding use of automated buses by family members (Q1.3 - Table 2.17) or willingness to use after the experience (Q1.4 - Table 2.18) were related to less perceived risk by the door malfunctioning scenario. On the other hand, non-positive responses were related to higher perceived risk. That is, higher levels of acceptance could be related to lower levels of perceived risk.

Table 2.17: Association of door scenario risk with Q1.3

			Doors risk	
			No	Yes
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	2	9
		Expected Count	5.3	5.7
	Yes	Count	10	4
		Expected Count	6.7	7.3

Table 2.18: Association of door scenario risk with Q1.4

			Doors risk	
			No	Yes
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	3	10
		Expected Count	6.2	6.8
	Yes	Count	9	3
		Expected Count	5.8	6.2

Table 2.19 presents the cross-tabulation results between Q1.5 and perceived risk by the door malfunctioning scenario. The results suggested that participants who feel “great” about the wider adoption of automated buses perceived less risk compared to the participants who responded “good”.

Table 2.19: Association of door scenario risk with Q1.5

		Doors risk		
		No	Yes	
Q1.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	7	3
		Expected Count	4.8	5.2
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	3	8
		Expected Count	5.2	5.8

The “IT confidence” variable is related to “Q42 - Did the IT solutions help increase your confidence during the "autonomous driverless experience"?” from deliverable D6.3. The potential answers were yes, no, I didn’t notice, and I don’t know. The variable was recoded into “yes” and “other than yes” responses. The results of the Chi-square tests are presented in Table 2.20.

Table 2.20: IT confidence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	0.199	0.905	30
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.475	0.491	30
Q1.3	Chi-Square	5.129	0.024	30
Q1.4	Chi-Square	6.652	0.010	30
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.158	0.691	26

Variable: IT confidence

Table 2.21 and Table 2.22 present the results of questions Q1.3 and Q1.4 respectively, related to confidence increase due to the presence of the IT system. In both cases, a positive answer was related to a higher likelihood of confidence due to the voice announcement system. It might be important to ensure that participants do not feel isolated or vulnerable in the absence of a human driver. Enhancing confidence towards this issue might also enhance acceptance levels.

Table 2.21: Association of IT confidence with Q1.3

		IT confidence		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	11	3
		Expected Count	7.9	6.1
	Yes	Count	6	10
		Expected Count	9.1	6.9

Table 2.22: Association of IT confidence with Q1.4

		IT confidence		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	12	3
		Expected Count	8.5	6.5
	Yes	Count	5	10
		Expected Count	8.5	6.5

2.4.4 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

2.4.4.1 Feelings after the experience

This section presents the results related to the question “Q24 - How were your feelings during the "autonomous driverless experience"?”, as presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential responses to that question were: Trustful, Insecure, Safe, Nervous, Curious and Unaffected. The question followed a multiple-choice format and participants could select yes or no for any of the aforementioned feelings (selected options have been indicated as 1 and not selected as 0). Given that including both significant and insignificant results (as in Section 2.4.6.1) would result in tables of large size, only the former are presented in Table 2.23.

Table 2.23: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	Nervous	LR	5.391	0.068	51
Q1.2	Curious	LR	3.854	0.050	51
Q1.3	Safe	Chi-Square	5.230	0.022	51
	Trustful	Chi-Square	6.888	0.009	51
Q1.4	Insecure	LR	6.415	0.011	51
	Safe	Chi-Square	5.230	0.022	51
	Trustful	Chi-Square	6.888	0.009	51

Q1.5	Insecure	LR	2.924	0.087	43
	Unaffected	LR	6.319	0.012	43

Variable: Feelings

The “Nervous” response was only significantly related to Q1.1 (Table 2.24). The main differences were found with respect to the “avoid” group of Q1.1 that was more likely to be nervous and the “use if IT support available” that was less likely to be nervous. Regarding the “willing to use” group, expected and observed values were very close.

Table 2.24: Association of “Nervous” feeling with Q1.1.

			Nervous	
			0	1
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	24	3
		Expected Count	22.2	4.8
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	16	3
		Expected Count	15.6	3.4
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	2	3
		Expected Count	4.1	.9

The only significant association related to Q1.2 was with the “Curious” feeling. More particularly, participants reported feeling curious were less likely to perceive benefits in the transport system due to autonomous buses. Curiosity during the experiment could have been triggered by difficulty in anticipating the bus behaviour.

However, “curious” feeling did not have a significant association with any other question hence its interpretation is less clear.

Table 2.25: Association of “Curious” feeling with Q1.2.

		Curious		
		0	1	
Q1.2	Other than yes	Count	2	20
		Expected Count	4.7	17.3
	Yes	Count	9	20
		Expected Count	6.3	22.7

Question Q1.3 had a significant relation with “Safe” and “Trustful” feelings. In both cases, the feelings were associated to the positive response about the use of the technology by family members or friends.

Table 2.26: Association of “Safe” feeling with Q1.3.

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	15.1	8.9
	Yes	Count	13	14
		Expected Count	16.9	10.1

Table 2.27: Association of “Trustful” feeling with Q1.3.

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	20	4
		Expected Count	15.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	13	14
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5

Question Q1.4 had very similar response patterns to Q1.3. Compared to the latter, the “Insecure” feeling also had a significant relation on top of “Safe” and “Trustful”. The former was related to smaller intention to use the technology while the two latter were related to higher intention to use.

Table 2.28: Association of “Insecure” feeling with Q1.4.

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	20	4
		Expected Count	22.1	1.9
	Yes	Count	27	0
		Expected Count	24.9	2.1

Table 2.29: Association of “Safe” feeling with Q1.4.

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	15.1	8.9
	Yes	Count	13	14
		Expected Count	16.9	10.1

Table 2.30: Association of “Trustful” feeling with Q1.4.

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	20	4
		Expected Count	15.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	13	14
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5

Finally, Q1.5 was significantly related to the “Insecure” feeling in the same way as Q1.4. Moreover, “Unaffected” individuals were more likely to have higher public acceptance levels.

Table 2.31: Association of “Insecure” feeling with Q1.5.

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q1.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	16	0
		Expected Count	14.9	1.1
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	24	3
		Expected Count	25.1	1.9

Table 2.32: Association of “Insecure” feeling with Q1.5.

		Unaffected	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	13	3
	Expected Count	14.9	1.1
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	27	0
	Expected Count	25.1	1.9

2.4.4.2 Anticipation

Anticipation was related to question “Q25 - Was this experience as you had anticipated?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential outcomes were: positively surprised, negatively surprised, it was as I expected and I don’t know. These were recoded to “positively surprised” and “other than positively surprised”. The results of the Chi-square test of independence are presented in Table 2.33.

Table 2.33: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	0.221	0.895	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.085	0.771	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	1.776	0.183	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	1.776	0.183	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	5.795	0.016	43

Variable: CAV anticipation

Table 2.34 shows the cross-tabulation between Q1.5 and the anticipation question. It is observed that participants that perceive as “great” the mass adoption of CAVs were more likely to find the experience “as expected”. On the other hand, those who replied “good” in Q1.5 were more likely to be in the “positively surprised” group. This finding could imply the need for developing vehicles that behave consistently with the mental model of the users.

Table 2.34: Association of anticipation with Q1.5.

		CAV anticipation	
		Other than positive	Positively surprised
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	12	4
	Expected Count	8.2	7.8
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	10	17
	Expected Count	13.8	13.2

2.4.4.3 The impact of quality of travel on acceptance

Comfort was related to question “Q26 - Was the experience comfortable compared with a conventional bus ride?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential outcomes were: more comfortable, less comfortable, no difference and I don’t know. In order to increase the number of observations per category, the variable was recoded with two main outcomes namely, “more comfortable” and “other than more comfortable”. As shown in Table 2.35, only Q1.1 had a significant association with perceived comfort.

Table 2.35: Perceived comfort tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	7.633	0.022	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.724	0.395	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	0.587	0.443	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.587	0.443	51
Q1.5	LR	3.075	0.380	43

Variable: Perceived comfort

Table 2.36 presents the cross-tabulation between Q1.1 and comfort. The results suggest that significance with respect to this question is a result of the group willing to switch to automated buses if the latter were IT

supported. Also, the group that would avoid the use of automated buses did not also find them more comfortable.

Table 2.36: Association of comfort with Q1.1

		CAV comfort		
		Other than more comfortable	More comfortable	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	12	15
		Expected Count	15.4	11.6
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	12	7
		Expected Count	10.8	8.2
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	2.8	2.2

2.4.4.4 The impact of perception towards the technology effects on users

The “bus emergency” variable is related to question “Q32 - Do you think that emergency situations will be more difficult to handle without a driver?”. The potential outcomes were: yes, no, no difference and I don’t know. Given the lower frequencies in some of the aforementioned groups the variable was recoded in two groups namely, “yes” and “other than yes”.

The results of the Chi-Square tests (Table 2.37) suggested only one significant relationship with Q1.2. Given that participants’ responses between the two waves differed significantly (Section 2.4.1), the Chi-Square tests were also applied excluded Wave 2 participants. However, no changes were observed in the significance (or absence of significance); hence these results are not presented in detail.

Table 2.37: Bus emergency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	0.374	0.829	51
Q1.2	Chi-square	3.127	0.077	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	0.855	0.355	51

Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.855	0.355	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	2.563	0.109	43

Variable: Bus emergency

The results presented in Table 2.38 suggest that participants who perceive emergency situations as more difficult to handle are less likely to perceive improvements in daily mobility due to automated buses. This could indicate a negative influence of lowered expectations with respect to the capability of CAV technologies.

Table 2.38: Association of perceived emergency with Q1.2

		Bus emergency	
		Other than yes	Yes
Q1.2 Other than yes	Count	4	18
	Expected Count	6.9	15.1
Yes	Count	12	17
	Expected Count	9.1	19.9

The driver absence variable is related to question “Q33 - Would you feel stressed without a driver whom you can ask for information?”, presented in D6.3. The question had four possible outcomes, namely, Yes, No, No difference and I don’t know. The variable was further recoded and only two outcomes were considered: “Yes” and “Other than yes”.

The results of the Chi-square tests are presented in Table 2.39. Except for Q1.5, the remaining relationships were significant, highlighting the potential importance of this variable.

Table 2.39: Driver absence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	6.068	0.048	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	3.664	0.056	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	7.070	0.008	51

Q1.4	Chi-Square	7.070	0.008	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.148	0.700	43

Variable: Driver absence

Table 2.40 presents the association between Q1.1 and driver absence. The results suggested that participants less affected by the driver absence were also more likely to be willing to use the automated bus. On the other hand, participants who stated that they would try to avoid the use of the automated bus were more likely to be affected by the driver absence.

Table 2.40: Association of driver absence with Q1.1

		Stress no driver		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	17	10
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	15	4
		Expected Count	12.3	6.7
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	1	4
		Expected Count	3.2	1.8

Table 2.41 shows the association between Q1.2 and driver absence. The results indicated that participants more likely to perceive improvements in mobility, as a result of the automated buses were less likely to be stressed by the absence of a human driver. The opposite was found for participants that did not perceive positive benefits in mobility by the automated buses.

Table 2.41: Association of driver absence with Q1.2

		Stress no driver		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.2	Other than yes	Count	11	11
		Expected Count	14.2	7.8
	Yes	Count	22	7
		Expected Count	18.8	10.2

Table 2.42 presents the association between Q1.3 and driver absence. The results showed that participants more positive if their family members or friends used automated buses were also less stressed by the absence of driver.

Table 2.42: Association of driver absence with Q1.3

		Stress no driver		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	11	13
		Expected Count	15.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	22	5
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5

Table 2.43 presents the association between Q1.4 and driver absence. The results showed that participants more willing to use automated buses after the experience were also less stressed by the absence of driver.

Table 2.43: Association of driver absence with Q1.4

		Stress no driver		
		Other than yes	Yes	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	11	13
		Expected Count	15.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	22	5
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5

Passenger vulnerability refers to question “Q34 - Do you think that users of autonomous buses will be more vulnerable to robbers/pickpocketing/violent passengers?”, as presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential outcomes were yes, no, no difference and I don’t know. The variable was recoded with only two outcomes namely, “Yes” and “other than yes”. No significance results were found with respect to this variable (Table 2.44). Given that participants’ responses between the two waves differed significantly, the Chi-Square tests were also applied excluded Wave 2 participants. However, no changes were observed in the significance (or absence of significance); hence these results are not presented in detail.

Table 2.44: Passenger vulnerability tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	1.915	0.384	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.743	0.389	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	2.248	0.134	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.870	0.351	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.199	0.655	43

Variable: Passenger vulnerability

Impact on disabled people refers to question “Q36 - How do you think autonomous buses will affect the lives of people with disabilities?”, as presented in deliverable D6.3. The potential outcomes were improve them, may cause some problems, no difference and I don't know. The variable was recoded with only two outcomes namely, “Yes” and “other than yes”. No significance results were found with respect to this variable (Table 2.45).

Table 2.45: Impact on disabled people tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	0.916	0.632	51
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.370	0.543	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	1.457	0.227	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.004	0.947	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.189	0.663	43

Variable: Impact on disabled people

2.4.5 The impact of perceived benefits and shortcomings on acceptance

2.4.5.1 Benefits

Perceived benefits refer to question “Q27 - Which potential benefits do you see in using autonomous buses?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. Participants could select as many benefits as they wished. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented in this section.

Table 2.46: Perceived benefits tests

Variable	Benefits	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	Better service	LR	7.633	0.039	51
	Less congestion	LR	6.354	0.042	51
Q1.2	Increased punctuality	Chi-Square	4.581	0.032	51
Q1.3	Increased safety	Chi-Square	5.509	0.019	51
Q1.4	Increased safety	Chi-Square	3.158	0.076	51
Q1.5	Lower price	LR	4.647	0.031	43
	Time savings	LR	4.789	0.029	43

Variable: Benefits

Table 2.47 shows the relationship between Q1.1 and better service as a benefit. Participants willing to use the service were more likely to perceive better service while the other two groups were less likely to provide a positive answer regarding this benefit.

Table 2.47: Association of better service with Q1.1

		Better service		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	26	1
		Expected Count	23.8	3.2
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	14	5
		Expected Count	16.8	2.2
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	4.4	.6

Table 2.48 shows the relationship between Q1.1 and less congestion as a benefit. Participants willing to use the service were more likely to perceive less congestion while the other two groups were less likely to provide a positive answer regarding this benefit. The pattern is similar to Table 2.47 about better service.

Table 2.48: Association of less congestion with Q1.1

		Less congestion		
		0	1	
Use_upon_availability	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	25	2
		Expected Count	22.8	4.2
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	13	6
		Expected Count	16.0	3.0
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	4.2	.8

Table 2.49 presents the association between Q1.2 and increased punctuality as a benefit. Participants perceiving improvements in mobility due to automated buses (Q1.2) were also more likely to perceive benefits in punctuality.

Table 2.49: Association of increased punctuality with Q1.2

		Increased punctuality		
		0	1	
Q1.2	Other than yes	Count	15	7
		Expected Count	11.2	10.8
	Yes	Count	11	18
		Expected Count	14.8	14.2

Table 2.50 presents the association between Q1.3 and increased safety as a benefit. Participants perceiving positive if family members or friends used the technology were also more likely to perceive improvements in safety.

Table 2.50: Association of increased safety with Q1.3

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	14	10
		Expected Count	9.9	14.1
	Yes	Count	7	20
		Expected Count	11.1	15.9

Table 2.51 presents the association between Q1.4 and increased safety as a benefit. Participants intending to use the technology after the experience were more likely to perceive improvements in safety.

Table 2.51: Association of increased safety with Q1.4

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	13	11
		Expected Count	9.9	14.1
	Yes	Count	8	19
		Expected Count	11.1	15.9

Table 2.52 presents the relation between Q1.5 and lower price as a benefit. The results suggest that participants perceiving adoption of the automated buses by large parts of the population as great were also more likely to perceive benefits in price.

However, a different pattern was observed in Table 2.53 with respect to perception about time saving. In particular, higher likelihood of perceiving that benefit was linked to participants reported as “good” the adoption of the technology by larger parts of the population. The finding could be an indication that price may be a more important factor however, given that benefits in cost and time savings did not result in significant results for any other indicators of acceptance further analysis is required in the future.

Table 2.52: Association of lower price with Q1.5

		Lower price	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	8	8
	Expected Count	11.2	4.8
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	22	5
	Expected Count	18.8	8.2

Table 2.53: Association of time saving with Q1.5

		Time saving	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	15	1
	Expected Count	12.3	3.7
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	18	9
	Expected Count	20.7	6.3

2.4.5.2 Shortcomings

Perceived shortcomings refer to question “Q28 - Which potential shortcomings do you see about using autonomous buses?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. Participants could select as many shortcomings as they wished, as a result of the automated buses presence in the transport system. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented in this section (Table 2.54).

Table 2.54: Perceived shortcomings tests

Variable	Shortcoming	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	Less security	LR	6.842	0.033	51
Q1.3	Loss of jobs	Chi-Square	4.647	0.031	51
	Decreased safety	Chi-Square	3.586	0.058	51
	None	Chi-Square	3.065	0.080	51
Q1.4	Less security	LR	8.153	0.004	51
	Decreased safety	LR	4.734	0.030	51
	None	Chi-Square	3.065	0.080	51
Q1.5	Less security	LR	3.963	0.047	43
	Less information onboard	LR	2.933	0.087	43
	Decreased safety	LR	2.924	0.087	43
	None	LR	4.320	0.038	43

Variable: Shortcomings

Table 2.55 presents the relation between Q1.1 and less security as a shortcoming. Considering the lower frequency in the “avoid” group, significance was more likely a result of the other two groups. In particular, none of the participants willing to switch to automated buses reported security as a shortcoming whereas participants willing to switch to automated buses only if the latter were IT supported, were more likely to perceive less security as a shortcoming.

Table 2.55: Association of time saving with Q1.5

		Less security		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	22	5
		Expected Count	24.4	2.6
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	19	0
		Expected Count	17.1	1.9

I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
	Expected Count	4.5	.5

Table 2.56 suggests that participants perceiving loss of jobs as an issue were also more likely not to be positive if their family members or friends used the technology. Despite the lower frequencies, decreased safety had some similar patterns to loss of jobs, with respect to its association with Q1.3. Finally, participants who selected “none of the above” were more likely to be positive if family members and friends used automated buses.

Table 2.56: Association of loss of jobs with Q1.3

		Loss of jobs		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	7	17
		Expected Count	10.8	13.2
	Yes	Count	16	11
		Expected Count	12.2	14.8

Table 2.57: Association of decreased safety with Q1.3

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	22.6	1.4
	Yes	Count	27	0
		Expected Count	25.4	1.6

Table 2.58: Association of no shortcomings with Q1.3

		None		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	18.4	5.6
	Yes	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	20.6	6.4

Question Q1.4 which was related to intention to use after the experience resulted in similar outcomes with question Q1.3. In particular similar patterns were observed with decreased safety (Table 2.60) and “none of the above” (Table 2.61). Moreover, perceived less security was associated with non-positive intention to use (Table 2.59).

Table 2.59: Association of less security with Q1.4

		Less security		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	21.6	2.4
	Yes	Count	27	0
		Expected Count	24.4	2.6

Table 2.60: Association of decreased safety with Q1.4

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	22.6	1.4
	Yes	Count	27	0
		Expected Count	25.4	1.6

Table 2.61: Association of no shortcomings with Q1.4

		None		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	18.4	5.6
	Yes	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	20.6	6.4

The significant associations related to question Q1.5 suggested some similar patterns with Q1.3 and Q1.4. In particular, participants who provided a “great” response were less likely to perceive security (Table 2.62) and safety (Table 2.64) as shortcomings while they were also more likely not to perceive any shortcomings (Table 2.65). Moreover, this group of participants was less likely to report less information onboard as a shortcoming (Table 2.63).

Table 2.62: Association of less security with Q1.4

		Less security	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	16	0
	Expected Count	14.5	1.5
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	23	4
	Expected Count	24.5	2.5

Table 2.63: Association of less information onboard with Q1.4

		Less information onboard	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	15	1
	Expected Count	13.0	3.0
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	20	7
	Expected Count	22.0	5.0

Table 2.64: Association of decreased safety with Q1.5

		Decreased safety	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	16	0
	Expected Count	14.9	1.1
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	24	3
	Expected Count	25.1	1.9

Table 2.65: Association of no shortcomings with Q1.5

		None	
		0	1
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	9	7
	Expected Count	11.9	4.1
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	23	4
	Expected Count	20.1	6.9

Unlike benefits, shortcomings yielded more consistent patterns with respect to acceptance. This might be an indication that expected benefits are less likely to develop a positive attitude and increased used, as these may be expected to be the norm. On the other hand, any failure of the technology to meet the users’ expectations might negatively affect acceptance.

2.4.6 The impact of participants’ background on acceptance

Table 2.66 presents the relationship of acceptance with gender. No significant correlations were found except for Q1.1. The “avoid” option of Q1.1 was removed to investigate if it was related to the significance of the result. Indeed, after removing this option from the analysis, the correlation between Q1.1 and gender changed to insignificant.

Table 2.66: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	7.722	0.021	51
Q1.1 (Avoid option removed)	LR	0.025	0.875	46
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.473	0.492	51
Q1.3	Chi-Square	1.574	0.210	51
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.481	0.488	51
Q1.5	Chi-Square	0.832	0.362	43

Variable: Gender

As reported earlier, the significance of gender was mainly a result of the “avoid” group in Q1.1 (Table 2.67). In particular, female participants were more likely to pick this option than male.

Table 2.67: Association of gender with Q1.1

		Gender		
		Female	Male	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	12	15
		Expected Count	13.2	13.8
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	8	11
		Expected Count	9.3	9.7
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5

In order to reduce low frequencies, income was further recoded into three groups namely, under 2000€, > 2000€ & ≤ 3000€, and above 3000€. A fourth group of respondents who did not state their income was also generated but not included in the analysis. No significant results were obtained except for Q1.5 (Table 2.68).

Table 2.68: Income tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	0.165	0.997	39
Q1.2	LR	2.110	0.348	39
Q1.3	LR	2.397	0.122	39
Q1.4	LR	2.237	0.122	39
Q1.5	LR	4.698	0.030	32

Variable: Income

The main differences regarding impact are observed with respect to the highest impact category which was also more likely to report “great” the higher levels of automated bus adoption by the general population (Table 2.69). Given that this was the only significant relationship, inference might

be inaccurate. However, it might be an indication that higher income people are more positive towards the presence of automated vehicles.

Table 2.69: Association of income with Q1.5

		Income		
		Up to 2000 €/month	2000-3000 €/month	3000+ €/month
Q1.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	1	2	12
	Expected	2.3	3.8	8.9
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	4	6	7
	Expected	2.7	4.3	10.1

Commute frequency tests are presented in Table 2.70. No significant relationships were found.

Table 2.70: Commute frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	1.813	0.404	43
Q1.2	Chi-Square	0.264	0.607	43
Q1.3	Chi-Square	0.017	0.897	43
Q1.4	Chi-Square	0.196	0.658	43
Q1.5	Chi-Square	1.990	0.158	36

Variable: Commute frequency

Commute frequency tests are presented in Table 2.70. No significant relationships were found, except for Q1.3.

Table 2.71: Commute distance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	6.482	0.166	43
Q1.2	LR	0.349	0.840	43
Q1.3	Chi-Square	4.921	0.085	43
Q1.4	Chi-Square	4.408	0.110	43
Q1.5	LR	0.184	0.911	36

Variable: Commute distance

As shown in Table 2.72, the main differences are observed in the first two categories of commute distance. However, inferences with respect to this finding are unclear.

Table 2.72: Association of income with Q1.3

		Commute distance			
		Up to 5 km	5-15 km	15+ km	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	8	5	5
		Expected Count	5.0	8.0	5.0
	Yes	Count	4	14	7
		Expected Count	7.0	11.0	7.0

User type referred to CAV experience as a passenger, driver or both. Two of the participants did not provide an answer to this question. No significant correlations were found except for Q1.3 (Table 2.73).

Table 2.73: User type tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	4.067	0.397	49
Q1.2	LR	0.343	0.843	49

Q1.3	LR	5.344	0.069	49
Q1.4	LR	0.538	0.764	49
Q1.5	LR	2.601	0.457	43

Variable: User type

As presented in Table 2.74, participants experienced CAVs both as passengers and drivers were more likely to provide a positive answer in Q1.3. This could be an indication that familiarity with the system increases trust for close people to use them too.

Table 2.74: Association of user type with Q1.3

		CAV user type			
		A driver	A passenger	Both	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	3	13	7
		Expected Count	1.4	12.7	8.9
	Yes	Count	0	14	12
		Expected Count	1.6	14.3	10.1

The past experience with a CAV shuttle was also investigated. This question also included an “I don’t know” option. The latter might not lead to any insightful inferences hence, significance was tested both considering and excluding it, to ensure that any significant results in the former case did not occur due to the presence of the “I don’t know option”. The results are presented in Table 2.75.

Table 2.75: CAV shuttle experience tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	4.810	0.307	49
Q1.2	LR	5.636	0.060	49
Q1.3	LR	7.033	0.022	49
Q1.4	LR	7.033	0.022	49
Q1.5	LR	1.358	0.507	41

Q1.1 (I don't know excluded)	LR	2.837	0.242	44
Q1.2 (I don't know excluded)	Chi-Square	0.003	0.956	44
Q1.3 (I don't know excluded)	Chi-Square	4.940	0.026	44
Q1.4 (I don't know excluded)	Chi-Square	4.940	0.026	44
Q1.5 (I don't know excluded)	LR	1.358	0.507	41

Variable: CAV shuttle experience

After excluding the “I don't know” option, questions Q1.3 (Table 2.76) and Q1.4 (Table 2.77) led to significant results. In both cases, experience with CAV shuttle was positively related to a positive answer in the two acceptance-related questions.

Table 2.76: Association of CAV shuttle experience with Q1.3

		CAV shuttle experience		
		No	Yes	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	14	5
		Expected Count	10.4	8.6
	Yes	Count	10	15
		Expected Count	13.6	11.4

Table 2.77: Association of CAV shuttle experience with Q1.4

		CAV shuttle experience		
		No	Yes	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	14	5
		Expected Count	10.4	8.6
	Yes	Count	10	15
		Expected Count	13.6	11.4

CAV “frequency of use” tests are presented in Table 2.70. No significant relationships were found except for Q1.3 (Table 2.78).

Table 2.78: CAV frequency of use tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	10.705	0.219	49
Q1.2	LR	3.314	0.507	49
Q1.3	LR	8.167	0.086	49
Q1.4	LR	3.654	0.455	49
Q1.5	LR	2.592	0.628	41

Variable: CAV frequency of user

Frequency of use cross-tabulation (Table 2.79) indicated some differences between the expected and observed counts in the “Never” and “Rarely” groups. Participants who have never used the technology may be less likely to be positive if members of their family used it.

Table 2.79: Association of CAV frequency of use with Q1.5

		CAV frequency of use				
		Never	Only once	Rarely	Occasionally	Systematically
Q1.3 Other than yes	Count	6	5	4	5	3
	Expected Count	3.3	4.2	7.5	5.2	2.8
Yes	Count	1	4	12	6	3
	Expected Count	3.7	4.8	8.5	5.8	3.2

2.4.6.1 Confidence in CAVs

This section presents the results related to the question “Q12 - How confident are you with CAVs?”, as presented in deliverable D6.3. The question had three potential outcomes namely, barely confident, medium confident and very confident. Table 2.80 outlines the Chi-Square test

results related to confidence in CAVs and their association to acceptance as reflected in the questions presented in Section 2.3.2. Questions Q1.1, Q1.3 and Q1.4 resulted in significant associations which are further explored.

Table 2.80: Confidence in CAVs tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	LR	8.397	0.078	49
Q1.2	LR	4.207	0.122	51
Q1.3	LR	22.320	0.000	51
Q1.4	LR	18.637	0.000	51
Q1.5	LR	2.617	0.270	43

Variable: Confidence in CAVs

The results presented in Table 2.81 indicate that individuals very confident in CAV were more likely to switch to autonomous buses. Also, medium confident participants were more likely to use autonomous buses if the latter were equipped with IT support while barely confident participants were also more likely to avoid use.

Table 2.81: Association of confidence in CAVs with Q1.1

		CAV confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	3	16	7
		Expected	4.2	12.7	9.0
		Count			
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	2	7	9
		Expected	2.9	8.8	6.2
		Count			
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	3	1	1
		Expected	.8	2.4	1.7
		Count			

Table 2.82 and Table 2.83 suggest that very confident participants were more likely to use CAVs after the experience or allow family members and friends use them. On the other hand medium confident and especially barely confident were less likely to reply yes (certainly in the original data structure). Overall, confidence in CAVs were more related to personal use of the technology or use by the family while no associations were found with questions Q1.2 and Q1.5 which refer to larger scale adaptation.

Table 2.82: Association of confidence in CAVs with Q1.3

		CAV confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	8	14	2
		Expected Count	3.8	12.2	8.0
	Yes	Count	0	12	15
		Expected Count	4.2	13.8	9.0

Table 2.83: Association of confidence in CAVs with Q1.4

		CAV confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	8	13	3
		Expected Count	3.8	12.2	8.0
	Yes	Count	0	13	14
		Expected Count	4.2	13.8	9.0

2.4.6.2 Use of CAV services

CAV services refer to a series of CAV-related services that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available services as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these services could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.3 are outlined in Table 2.84.

Table 2.84: CAV services considered in the survey

CAV services
Navigation & routing services (GoogleMaps, Waze,...)
Bike-, Scooter-, Car-sharing services (ShareNow, Free2Move, Lime,...)
Ride-sharing (Uber, Cabify, taxi apps,...)
Carpooling (BlaBlaCar, Leadmee,...)
Connected features (next stop indicator in buses,...)
Driver assistance (speed limit indicator, blind spot detection, lane assist,...)
Adaptative cruise control (the vehicle controls the speed according to traffic)
Automatic steering (autonomous parking or vehicle keeping itself in lane)
I don't know
I have never tried a CAV before

The significant results are presented in Table 2.85. The cross-tabulation tables of the significant results have been appended in Annex 1.

Table 2.85: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	Bike sharing	LR	5.565	0.062	51
	Ride sharing	LR	7.375	0.025	51
	ACC	LR	5.722	0.057	51
	Carpooling	LR	8.481	0.014	51
Q1.3	Ride sharing	Chi-Square	0.194	0.002	51
	Driver assistance	Chi-square	3.207	0.073	51
	Auto steering	Chi-square	4.151	0.042	51
	Carpooling	Chi-square	4.694	0.030	51

Q1.4	Ride sharing	Chi-square	6.080	0.014	51
	Driver assistance	Chi-square	3.207	0.073	51
	Carpooling	Chi-square	4.694	0.030	51
Q1.5	Ride sharing	Chi-square	3.465	0.063	43

Variable: CAV services

Except for Q1.2, all the remaining questions had a significant association with at least one of the CAV services considered in the survey. In all cases (as shown in the respective tables in Annex 1), experience with the CAV services is related to higher acceptance of the CAV technology.

2.4.6.3 Use of CAV applications

CAV applications refer to a series of CAV-related applications that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available applications as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these applications could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.3 are outlined in Table 2.86. Less significant cases were observed, compared to the CAV services variable in Section 2.4.6.2. Only, shared mobility and public transport led to some significant results. Use of these apps was linked to answer more positively related to the acceptance of automated buses.

Table 2.86: CAV applications tests

Variable	CAV app	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q1.1	Shared mobility	LR	4.770	0.092	51
Q1.2	Shared mobility	Chi-Square	3.127	0.077	51
	Public transport	Chi-square	6.279	0.012	51
Q1.3	Public transport	Chi-square	4.293	0.038	51

Variable: CAV applications

2.5 Summary

The current section provides a summary of all findings presented in Section 2. First, it was found that in most cases there were no significant differences in the responses between Waves 1 and 2. Hence, visual impairment did not affect patterns related to the acceptance of automated buses.

The occurrence of events did not have a significant effect on most of the indicators of acceptance. This finding is expected as with the exception of the door malfunctioning scenario, participants did not perceive risk (D6.3, Q38-Q41). Increased risk perception on the door malfunctioning scenario was related to reduced acceptance of the automated bus. Moreover, the type of ICT did not have significant associations with acceptance. However, participants who felt more confident by the presence of the system were also more likely to accept the technology. Among the potential negative implications on users, the most significant was the absence of a human driver. A human driver may not only provide assurance that a trained person is controlling the vehicle but can also act as a figure of authority and prevent cases of violence or harassment.

The feelings that stemmed from the experience of the system were also related to its acceptance. The feelings most commonly observed to have some significant relationship with acceptance were “Safe”, “Trustful” and “Insecure”. Hence, it is important that the technology provides solutions that allow for the development of a safe and trustful perception towards the technology. Moreover, the overall performance and behaviour of the vehicle is important to be consistent with the mental model and the expectations of the end users. Except for the feelings during the pilots, general confidence in automated vehicles was also positively related to acceptance.

The negative extensions on safety and security were also observed on the impact of perceived shortcoming of the technology on acceptance. Moreover, it was found that perceived shortcomings were more related to acceptance than perceived benefits. This finding may highlight double standards with respect to the performance of automated buses. Expected benefits are less likely to develop a positive attitude and increased used, as these may be expected to be the norm. On the other hand, any failure of the technology to meet the users’ expectations might negatively affect acceptance.

Past experience with automated shuttles resulted in some significant results with respect to acceptance. In the same direction, increased use of CAV services was positively related in several cases with acceptance. Hence, it is suggested that incentives to promote the use of CAVs need to be considered as the latter is in positive correlation with acceptance.

3 Pilot 2: Autonomous Driving Training

3.1 Introduction

Pilot 2 investigated the impact of dedicated trainings on subjective attitudes towards integrated Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) in L2 (or higher) CAVs. The pilot examined aspects such as knowledge and awareness of the ADAS functionalities, trust, acceptance of the technology, and management of critical situations. Participants used a vehicle with ADAS, to test the training methodology developed in WP5. In particular, the level 2 ADAS tested were Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC), Automatic Parking (AP), Lane Keeping (LK), and Automatic Braking System (ABS).

3.2 Data collection

The data was collected over four waves; each wave consisted of two batches of participants. The pilot took place at the ACI SARA Safe Driving Centre in Lainate. The Centre has a track and 4 areas dedicated to safe driving and equipped with the state-of-the-art technologies for the development of controlled emergency situations and maximum safety for drivers. The availability of a Centre and ACI Safe Driving instructors allowed for the combination of the tests on ADAS with safe driving exercises, in order to establish not only the theoretical level determined by the questionnaires, but also the level of practical preparation as drivers of the test participants, regardless of the curriculum they presented.

The data were collected over the period January-February 2022. In total, 91 participants took part in this pilot. Six distinct exercises were prepared, which can be split into safe driving tests that can be conducted with any car (either conventional or automated) to assess the driving skills of the participants and ADAS driving tests, which were specific to vehicles with autonomous features (Figure 3.1).

Safe driving exercises, see sub-chapter Safe Driving Exercises:

- “Slide – skid control” Safe Driving Exercise 1
- “Downhill hairpin” Safe Driving Exercise 2

ADAS tests, see sub-chapter ADAS Test Exercises:

- “Asphalt area” test ADAS 1 “Automatic Emergency Braking”
- Straight test ADAS 2 “Lane Keeping”

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- Complete circuit test ADAS 3 “Adaptive Cruise Control”
- Parking area test ADAS 4 “Automatic parking

The exercises have been documented in detail in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

Figure 3.1: Pilot 2, Overview over exercises on test track

Three different kinds of surveys were collected and are analysed in their respective sub-sections:

- Initial evaluation survey, to assess each individual participants’ abilities and experience at the beginning of the day
- Instructor evaluation survey, which assessed the actual individual driving abilities after on-site tests
- PAsCAL survey, containing comparable KPIs across all pilots. Batch 1 included participants who have not been trained previous to the ADAS exercises, while batch 2 included those who received a specific training before the tests. This order is always the same for each wave.

All participants signed a GDPR-compliant form to agree to the processing of the gathered datasets and also audio-visual materials gathered during the pilot execution. All datasets have been anonymised previous to the analysis of the datasets to ensure the protection of each individual’s privacy and identity. Further details with respect to the data collection of Pilot 2 are presented in “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 Analysis

The data of Pilot 2 were analysed via a series of cross-tabulation and Chi-Square tests. The details of this approach have been reported in Section 2.3.1. Each question presented in Section 3.4 has been documented in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

3.3.2 Indicators of acceptance

Table 3.1 presents the questions that were considered as indicators of CAV acceptance. Each question is assigned a code that is used for the remainder of the document for convenience. The columns of *indicator category* and *indicator* were derived from “Deliverable 6.2 – Pilot Setup”. Due to the sample size-related issues and the low frequency in some of the responses, the latter were recoded, in order to improve the statistical power of the tests. The recoded groups are presented in Table 5.2.

Table 3.1: Indicators of acceptance

Code	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)
Q2.1 (Q23 in D6.3)	After this experience, would you use a partially-automated car for your daily trips?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q2.2 (Q24 in D6.3)	Would you encourage your family or friends to use partially-automated cars?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to let others use
Q2.3 (Q27 in D6.3)	If partially-automated cars were available, I would use them.	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q2.4 (Q28 in D6.3)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use partially-automated cars. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 3.2: Original and recoded groups

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q2.1	Certainly, Probably, Depends on how the technology evolves, Probably not, Not at all	Certainly, Probably, Depends on how the technology evolves (remaining groups removed due to low representativeness).
Q2.2	Certainly, Probably, Depends on how the technology evolves, Probably not, Not at all	Certainly, Probably, Depends on how the technology evolves (remaining groups removed due to low representativeness).
Q2.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am willing to accept the effort to switch to partially-automated cars (e.g. special courses). - The switch to partially-automated cars is unacceptable. - I would not like to use partially-automated cars. - I would try to avoid partially-automated cars as much as possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am willing to accept the effort to switch to partially-automated cars (e.g. special courses). - Any other group
Q2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad. - The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars. 	No edits

3.4 Results

3.4.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

3.4.1.1 *Feelings after the experience*

Table 3.3 presents the significant Chi-Square tests with respect to the question “Q13 – How did you feel while traveling in a CAV?”. The participants could select multiple options among trustful, careful, insecure, safe, nervous, curious, critical, and unaffected. The significant results are further presented via cross tabulation analysis.

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Table 3.3: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Curious	Chi-Square	8.267	0.016	84
	Careful	Chi-Square	5.776	0.040	84
	Trustful	Chi-Square	7.431	0.024	84
	Nervous	LR	5.973	0.050	84
Q2.2	Nervous	LR	8.074	0.018	87
	Critical	LR	6.435	0.040	87
Q2.3	Insecure	LR	3.472	0.062	88
Q2.4	Careful	LR	6.136	0.047	88
	Critical	LR	10.310	0.006	88

Variable: Feelings

Regarding Q2.1, the main differences are observed regarding the “depends” group as these individuals were more likely, than expected, to provide a response to the curious feeling (Table 3.4). It might be the cases that these individuals have higher levels of uncertainty would not be early adopters of the technology.

Table 3.4: The association of curious feeling with Q2.1

		Curious		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	34	7
		Expected Count	32.2	8.8
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	5	6
		Expected Count	8.6	2.4
	Probably	Count	27	5
		Expected Count	25.1	6.9

According to Table 3.5, careful participants were more likely to provide a “certainly” response on Q2.1. This finding is unexpected and inconsistent to findings from the other studies; hence it requires further investigation. Low observed frequencies in the positive “careful” statements could pose an issue towards the reliability of this result, due to the low representativeness.

Table 3.5: The association of careful feeling with Q2.1

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	32	9
		Expected Count	35.6	5.4
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	10	1
		Expected Count	9.6	1.4
	Probably	Count	31	1
		Expected Count	27.8	4.2

According to Table 3.6, “trustful” feeling was positively associated with intention to use supporting previous findings. Similarly, the “nervous” feeling was negatively associated to use (as reflected in the “certainly” group in Table 3.7). However, given the low frequencies, this result needs to be treated with caution.

Table 3.6: The association of trustful feeling with Q2.1

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	25	16
		Expected Count	29.8	11.2
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	11	0
		Expected Count	8.0	3.0
	Probably	Count	25	7
		Expected Count	23.2	8.8

Table 3.7: The association of nervous feeling with Q2.1

		Nervous		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	41	0
		Expected Count	39.5	1.5
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	11	0
		Expected Count	10.6	.4
	Probably	Count	29	3
		Expected Count	30.9	1.1

The pattern between the “nervous” feeling and Q2.2 was similar to the pattern observed with respect to Q2.1. Nervous individuals were less likely to be positive towards letting others use the technology. The same issues about low representativeness of some groups also applies in this case.

Table 3.8: The association of nervous feeling with Q2.2

		Nervous		
		0	1	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	42	0
		Expected Count	40.1	1.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	12	0
		Expected Count	11.4	.6
	Probably	Count	29	4
		Expected Count	31.5	1.5

As outlined in Table 3.9, participants who selected the “critical” response were more likely to be willing to let others use. This finding is counter intuitive and could be a result of lower observed frequencies of certain responses in the cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 3.9: The association of critical feeling with Q2.2

		Critical		
		0	1	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	38	4
		Expected Count	39.1	2.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	10	2
		Expected Count	11.2	.8
	Probably	Count	33	0
		Expected Count	30.7	2.3

Table 3.10 suggests that insecure feeling is positively related to intention to use the technology. This is another example of an unexpected outcome that requires further analysis in the future.

Table 3.10: The association of insecure feeling with Q2.3

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q2.3	Willing to accept the effort	Count	47	3
		Expected Count	48.3	1.7
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	38	0
		Expected Count	36.7	1.3

As shown in Table 3.11, careful participants were also more likely to provide the “it feels bad” response regarding public acceptance. The same individuals were less likely to provide the “it feels great” response. Hence, perceived safety may be in close correlation to public acceptance, as higher risk is negatively related to the latter.

Table 3.11: The association of careful feeling with Q2.4

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q2.4	I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	19	0
		Expected Count	16.8	2.2
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	20	5
		Expected Count	22.2	2.8
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	39	5
		Expected Count	39.0	5.0

Participants who responded positively about the critical feeling were more likely to provide the “it feels good”, compared to the “great” and “bad” options (Table 3.12). The “critical” response has yielded an unexpected pattern also previously and any findings related to it need to be treated with caution.

Table 3.12: The association of careful feeling with Q2.4

		Critical		
		0	1	
Q2.4	I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	19	0
		Expected Count	17.5	1.5
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	25	0
		Expected Count	23.0	2.0
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	37	7
		Expected Count	40.5	3.5

3.4.1.2 CAV Anticipation

CAV anticipation refers to “Q14 – Was using a CAV the experience you had anticipated?”. The potential responses were “positively surprised”, “it was as I expected”, “negatively surprised” and “I don’t know”. The two latter options were removed from the Chi-Square analysis due to their low number of occurrences, in order to improve the statistical power of the

tests. As shown in Table 3.13, no significant relationships were found between anticipation and acceptance related questions.

Table 3.13: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Chi-Square	1.190	0.552	76
Q2.2	Chi-Square	0.170	0.919	78
Q2.3	Chi-Square	0.752	0.386	78
Q2.4	Chi-Square	2.346	0.310	78

Variable: CAV anticipation

3.4.1.3 CAV behaviour

The CAV behaviour question regards “Q15 – How well do you think that the partially-automated car performed regarding steering, acceleration and braking?”. The potential responses were “better than a human driver”, “same as the human driver”, “worse than a human driver”, and “just different”. The of the Chi-Square tests showed only on significant correlation with Q2.1 (Table 3.14).

Table 3.14: CAV behaviour tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	17.638	0.007	84
Q2.2	LR	10.286	0.113	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	3.016	0.389	88
Q2.4	LR	5.128	0.527	88

Variable: CAV behaviour

The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 3.15 suggests that respondents likely to use the technology in the future either perceived the

CAV behaviour as better or different to a human driver. The response “worse than a human driver” was more likely, than expected, to occur in the “depends” and “probably” answers.

Table 3.15: The association of CAV behaviour with Q2.1

		CAV_performance				
		Better than a human driver	Just different	Same as a human driver	Worse than a human driver	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	19	14	7	1
		Expected Count	17.6	10.7	7.8	4.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	1	4	2	4
		Expected Count	4.7	2.9	2.1	1.3
	Probably	Count	16	4	7	5
		Expected Count	13.7	8.4	6.1	3.8

3.4.1.4 CAV reactions

The CAV reactions refer to “Q16 – How do you describe the partially-automated car reactions?”. The potential responses were “very good”, “safe”, “neutral”, “unpredictable”, and “dangerous”. The initial tests suggested a significant correlation only with Q2.4 (Table 3.16).

However, given the low frequency of the “unpredictable” response, the latter was removed, and the analysis was performed again (Table 3.19), in order to further investigate this variable.

Additional significant results were observed upon removal, suggesting that the low count of the aforementioned response could have affected the results.

Table 3.16: CAV reactions tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	10.655	0.100	83
Q2.2	LR	8.913	0.179	86
Q2.3	Chi-Square	3.016	0.389	88
Q2.4	LR	13.911	0.031	87

Variable: CAV reactions

Table 3.17 suggests that responses perceived as “very good” were more likely to occur in the “certainly” outcome. On the other hand, “safe” was more likely (than expected) to occur in the “probably” outcome while no considerable differences between the expected and the observed outcome were observed regarding the “depends” response.

Table 3.17: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.1

		CAV_reactions			
		Neutral	Safe	Unpredictable	Very good
Q2.1 Certainly	Count	5	16	4	15
	Expected	5.3	20.2	3.4	11.1
Depends on how the technology evolves	Count				
	Count	4	5	1	1
	Expected	1.5	5.6	.9	3.0
Probably	Count				
	Count	2	21	2	7
	Expected	4.2	16.2	2.7	8.9
	Count				

Table 3.18 suggest some mixed findings regarding the relationship between public acceptance and CAV reactions. In particular, both “very good” and “safe” outcomes were more likely to occur in the “great” category however, “very good” was also more likely to occur in the “bad” category; the latter is counter intuitive and required further investigation.

Table 3.18: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.4

		CAV_reactions			
		Neutral	Safe	Unpredictable	Very good
Q2.4 I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	0	12	0	6
	Expected Count	2.5	9.1	1.7	4.8
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	3	11	2	9
	Expected Count	3.4	12.6	2.3	6.6
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	9	21	6	8
	Expected Count	6.1	22.3	4.0	11.6

Table 3.19: CAV reactions tests - reduced

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	11.145	0.025	76
Q2.2	LR	8.295	0.081	78
Q2.3	Chi-Square	1.829	0.401	79
Q2.4	LR	9.476	0.050	79

Variable: CAV reactions

Table 3.20 indicates that when CAV reactions were perceived as very good, it was more likely to observe a positive answer with respect to willingness to adopt. Other differences between the observed and expected counts were found between “safe” and “depends” groups and “neutral” with “probably”.

Table 3.20: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.1

		CAV_reactions			
		Neutral	Safe	Very good	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	5	16	15
		Expected Count	5.2	19.9	10.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	4	5	1
		Expected Count	1.4	5.5	3.0
	Probably	Count	2	21	7
		Expected Count	4.3	16.6	9.1

The cross-tabulation results presented in Table 3.22 indicate that responses in the “very good” category were more likely to be observed in the “certainly” group, compared to the expected outcome. On the other hand, “safe” was more likely (than expected) to occur in the “probably” group. This pattern is similar to the relationship of CAV reactions with Q2.1.

Table 3.21: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.2

		CAV_reactions			
		Neutral	Safe	Very good	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	4	18	17
		Expected Count	5.5	22.0	11.5
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	2	8	1
		Expected Count	1.6	6.2	3.2
	Probably	Count	5	18	5
		Expected Count	3.9	15.8	8.3

The mixed findings presented in Table 3.18 also persist in Table 3.22. “Very good” and “safe” outcomes were more likely to occur in the “great” category. Also, “very good” was also more likely to occur in the “bad” category, which is a finding that requires further investigation.

Table 3.22: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.4

		CAV_reactions		
		Neutral	Safe	Very good
Q2.4 I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	0	12	6
	Expected Count	2.7	10.0	5.2
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	3	11	9
	Expected Count	3.5	12.8	6.7
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	9	21	8
	Expected Count	5.8	21.2	11.1

3.4.1.5 User reactions

User reactions refer to “Q17 - Which was your reaction to cars manoeuvres?”. The potential responses were “no reaction”, “I followed the training”, “I had a different reaction”. Due to the responses distribution, the latter were recoded to “I followed the training” and “Other reaction”. As indicated in Table 3.23, no significant results were found regarding this variable.

Table 3.23: User reactions tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Chi-Square	0.439	0.803	84
Q2.2	LR	10.286	0.113	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	0.048	0.827	88
Q2.4	Chi-Square	2.771	0.250	88

Variable: User reactions

3.4.1.6 Difficulty of use (CAV stress)

Difficulty of use is related to “Q18 - How difficult and stressful was to use a real partially-automated car?”. The potential responses were “very difficult”, “moderately difficult”, “not very difficult”, and “not difficult at all”. Table 3.24 suggests a few significant associations which were further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 3.24: Difficulty to use tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	16.384	0.012	84
Q2.2	LR	11.590	0.072	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	3.443	0.330	88
Q2.4	LR	14.375	0.026	88

Variable: Difficulty of use

The results presented in Table 3.25 regarding the potential impacts of difficulty to use, led to some mixed findings. In particular, both participants who perceived the technology as “very difficult” to use and not difficult at all were more likely (than expected) to provide a “certainly” outcome. Moreover, the differences between observed and expected counts were more distinct in the former group. Another considerable difference with respect to the observed and expected counts was found between the “not difficult at all” and the “probably” groups.

Table 3.25: The association of CAV stress with Q2.1

		CAV_stress			
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	Very difficult
Q2.1 Certainly	Count	6	14	14	7
	Expected Count	8.3	13.2	15.1	4.4
	Count	5	0	6	0

Depends on how the technology evolves	Expected Count	2.2	3.5	4.1	1.2	
	Probably	Count	6	13	11	2
		Expected Count	6.5	10.3	11.8	3.4

Similarly, the results presented in Table 3.26 regarding Q2.2, are not always consistent with expectations. For instance, the “certainly” response in Q2.2 was related to higher, than expected, counts with both the “not difficult at all” and “very difficult responses”. Although some patterns can be observed, the overall findings with respect to this relationship are inconclusive. Similarly, despite significant results, the interpretation of the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 3.27 is unclear.

Table 3.26: The association of CAV stress with Q2.2

		CAV_stress				
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	Very difficult	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	6	15	14	7
		Expected Count	8.7	14.0	15.0	4.3
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	2	2	8	0
		Expected Count	2.5	4.0	4.3	1.2
	Probably	Count	10	12	9	2
		Expected Count	6.8	11.0	11.8	3.4

Table 3.27 shows that difficulty to use could be related to public acceptance. In particular, participants who perceive mass adoption as “bad” were more likely to also find the technology difficult to use while on the other hand, participants who responded “good” were more likely to have higher observed frequencies in the “not very difficult” group and lower observed frequencies in the “very difficult” group.

Table 3.27: The association of CAV stress with Q2.4

		CAV_stress			
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	Very difficult
Q2.4 I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	6	5	6	2
	Expected Count	3.9	6.3	6.9	1.9
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	3	11	5	6
	Expected Count	5.1	8.2	9.1	2.6
The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	9	13	21	1
	Expected Count	9.0	14.5	16.0	4.5

The difficulty to use variable was further investigated, considered a reduced version of the variable. That is, the “very difficult” group was removed, due to its low frequency of occurrence. The results of the Chi-Square tests presented in Table 3.28 indicated only on single relationship with Q2.1.

Table 3.28: Difficulty to use tests - reduced

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	11.621	0.020	75
Q2.2	LR	6.655	0.155	78
Q2.3	Chi-Square	2.832	0.243	79
Q2.4	LR	6.479	0.165	79

Variable: Difficulty of use

The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 3.29 suggested that users who reported “certainly” or “probably” were more likely to provide a “not difficult at all” answer. The opposite was found for those who selected “depends on how the technology evolves”.

Table 3.29: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.1

		CAV_stress		
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult
Q2.1 Certainly	Count	6	14	14
	Expected Count	7.7	12.2	14.1
Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	5	0	6
	Expected Count	2.5	4.0	4.5
Probably	Count	6	13	11
	Expected Count	6.8	10.8	12.4

3.4.1.7 Simulator experience

The simulator experience section focused on “Q20 – Did you notice any difference in the car behaviour compared to the simulation?”. The potential responses were “no difference”, “yes”, and “no”. Table 3.30 suggests some significant correlations with respect to the difference of the CAV behaviour in the simulator and the field track settings.

Table 3.30: Difference in CAV behaviour tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	12.178	0.016	84
Q2.2	LR	4.657	0.324	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	5.446	0.065	88
Q2.4	LR	3.106	0.540	88

Variable: Difference in user behaviour

As shown in Table 3.31 participants who did not perceive any difference between the two settings were more willing to adopt the technology. In the same direction, Table 3.32 suggested higher intention to use once the technology is available, for the same individuals.

Table 3.31: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.1

		CAV_behaviour_sim			
		No	No difference	Yes	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	6	29	6
		Expected Count	5.9	25.4	9.8
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	0	4	7
		Expected Count	1.6	6.8	2.6
	Probably	Count	6	19	7
		Expected Count	4.6	19.8	7.6

Table 3.32: The association of CAV reactions with Q2.3

		CAV_behaviour_sim			
		No	No difference	Yes	
Q2.3	Willing to accept the effort	Count	4	34	12
		Expected Count	8.0	30.7	11.4
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	10	20	8
		Expected Count	6.0	23.3	8.6

3.4.1.8 Perception about training

The impact of training on acceptance was also investigated. The training related questions were “Q21 – Do you think that the training received improved your reactions?”, “Q22 - Do you think that the training received was adequate?”, and “Q25 - Would you advise others to follow a similar training?”. The original response categories for each question were as follows (with their recoding presented in brackets):

Q21: Yes; Partially; No; I don’t know (Yes; Other than yes)

Q22: Yes; Partially; No; I don’t know (Yes; Other than yes)

Q25: Yes; No; I don't know

The results of the Chi-Square tests in Table 3.33 showed only one significant association between reaction improvement due to training and Q2.1.

Table 3.33: Training improvement tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Chi-Square	1.423	0.491	84
Q2.2	Chi-Square	7.632	0.022	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	1.544	0.214	88
Q2.4	Chi-Square	0.278	0.870	88

Variable: Training improvement

Table 3.34 shows that a positive attitude towards the training had a higher likelihood of occurrence regarding the certainly answer with respect to letting others use the technology.

Table 3.34: The association of training improvement with Q2.2

		Training_improvement1		
		Non positive	Positive	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	5	37
		Expected Count	10.1	31.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	3	9
		Expected Count	2.9	9.1
	Probably	Count	13	20
		Expected Count	8.0	25.0

Table 3.35 indicated that that training adequacy had a significant relationship with Q2.3. As shown in Table 3.36, a positive answer towards training adequacy was related to a higher likelihood of a positive answer on use the technology, once this is available.

Table 3.35: Training adequacy tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Chi-Square	3.612	0.164	84
Q2.2	Chi-Square	1.248	0.536	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	3.979	0.046	88
Q2.4	LR	0.713	0.699	88

Variable: Training adequacy

Table 3.36: The association of training adequacy with Q2.3

		Training_adequacy1		
		Non positive	Positive	
Q2.3	Willing to accept the effort	Count	6	44
		Expected Count	9.7	40.3
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	11	27
		Expected Count	7.3	30.7

Regarding suggesting the training to others, a significant correlation was found with Q2.3 (Table 3.37). This latter is further explored in Table 3.38. In particular, the results indicated that individuals more likely to use the technology when it becomes available were also more likely to suggest the others to follow similar training.

Table 3.37: Training others tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	0.716	0.701	83
Q2.2	Chi-Square	2.244	0.326	86
Q2.3	Chi-Square	15.617	<0.001	88
Q2.4	Chi-Square	1.909	0.385	88

Variable: Training others

Table 3.38: The association of training adequacy with Q2.3

		Training_others1	
		Non positive	Positive
Q2.3 Willing to accept the effort	Count	5	45
	Expected Count	13.1	36.9
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	18	20
	Expected Count	9.9	28.1

3.4.2 The impact of participants’ background

Participants’ background and its potential effects on acceptance were investigated and the results are presented in this section.

Table 3.39 suggests a significant correlation of gender with Q2.4. The most notable differences with respect to the latter can be observed in the “bad” response category, otherwise the interpretation is inconclusive.

It should be noted that any other than female or male response was removed due to the low number of occurrences.

Table 3.39: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	4.211	0.122	82
Q2.2	LR	4.409	0.110	85
Q2.3	LR	0.753	0.385	86
Q2.4	LR	4.818	0.090	86

Variable: Gender

Table 3.40: The association of gender with Q2.4.

		Gender		
		Female	Male	
CAV_population	It is great	Count	2	16
		Expected Count	1.5	16.5
	It feels bad	Count	0	24
		Expected Count	2.0	22.0
	It feels good	Count	5	39
		Expected Count	3.6	40.4

Table 3.41 shows that commute frequency was not significantly related with any of the acceptance related questions. The same holds regarding commuting distance (Table 3.42).

Table 3.41: Commute frequency

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	1.037	0.904	87
Q2.2	Chi-Square	1.601	0.449	85
Q2.3	Chi-Square	0.279	0.597	86
Q2.4	Chi-Square	1.462	0.481	86

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 3.42: Commute distance

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	3.482	0.901	87
Q2.2	LR	6.553	0.162	85
Q2.3	Chi-Square	0.526	0.769	86
Q2.4	LR	2.225	0.694	86

Variable: Commute distance

3.4.2.1 Confidence in CAVs

Confidence in CAVs was not related to any of the acceptance related questions. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 3.43.

Table 3.43: Confidence in CAVs tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	LR	4.237	0.375	84
Q2.2	LR	8.8861	0.227	87
Q2.3	Chi-Square	2.787	0.248	88
Q2.4	LR	5.642	0.228	88

Variable: Commute distance

3.4.2.2 Use of CAV services

The relationship between the use of CAV services with CAV acceptance is investigated as a potential proxy of tech-affinity or familiarity to the latter. In particular, participants could choose (in a multiple choice question) between a series of CAV related services (which are in detail documented in deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”). Each of the potential responses were examined individually with the acceptance related questions from Section 3.3.2. A few significant associations were found; the general trend suggested that the use of some CAV technologies was positively associated to acceptance-related questions, supporting to

some extend the hypothesis of the positive influence of technology familiarity.

Table 3.44: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.1	Auto-steering	LR	8.266	0.016	84
	No CAV	LR	6.717	0.035	84
Q2.2	Navigation	Chi-Square	8.100	0.017	87
Q2.3	Bike Sharing	LR	4.667	0.031	88
Q2.4	ACC	LR	5.592	0.061	88

Variable: CAV services

Table 3.45: The association of auto-steering service use with Q2.1

		Auto_steering		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	35	6
		Expected Count	37.1	3.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	9	2
		Expected Count	10.0	1.0
	Probably	Count	32	0
		Expected Count	29.0	3.0

Table 3.46: The association no CAV experience with Q2.1

		No_CAV_tried		
		0	1	
Q2.1	Certainly	Count	40	1
		Expected Count	38.6	2.4
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	8	3
		Expected Count	10.3	.7
	Probably	Count	31	1
		Expected Count	30.1	1.9

Table 3.47: The association no CAV experience with Q2.2

		Navigation		
		0	1	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	10	32
		Expected Count	15.4	26.6
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	8	4
		Expected Count	4.4	7.6
	Probably	Count	14	19
		Expected Count	12.1	20.9

Table 3.48: The association of bike sharing with Q2.3

		Bike_sharing		
		0	1	
Q2.3	Willing to accept the effort	Count	46	4
		Expected Count	47.7	2.3
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	38	0
		Expected Count	36.3	1.7

Table 3.49: The association of bike sharing with Q2.4

		ACC		
		0	1	
CAV_population	I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars.	Count	19	0
		Expected Count	17.1	1.9
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad.	Count	23	2
		Expected Count	22.4	2.6
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good.	Count	37	7
		Expected Count	39.5	4.5

3.4.2.3 Use of CAV applications

The use of CAV related applications was investigated in a similar matter to the CAV services. The main hypothesis was that familiarity with the use of the technology would be positively related to acceptance. Only few significant associations were found and presented in Table 3.50.

An interesting finding is that participants who did not report use of such apps were less likely to provide positive responses to the acceptance related indicators. The detailed results of the Chi-Square tests are presented from Table 3.51 to Table 3.53.

Table 3.50: CAV applications tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q2.2	No apps	LR	5.088	0.079	87
Q2.3	Shared mobility app	LR	4.029	0.045	88
	No app	LR	3.673	0.055	88

Variable: CAV services

Table 3.51: The association of no app use with Q2.2

		No_app		
		0	1	
Q2.2	Certainly	Count	41	1
		Expected Count	38.1	3.9
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	10	2
		Expected Count	10.9	1.1
	Probably	Count	28	5
		Expected Count	30.0	3.0

Table 3.52: The association of shared mobility app use with Q2.3

		Shared_mobility_app		
		0	1	
Q2.3	Positive	Count	45	5
		Expected Count	47.2	2.8
	Negative	Count	38	0
		Expected Count	35.8	2.2

Table 3.53: The association of no app use with Q2.3

		No_app		
		0	1	
Q2.3	Positive	Count	48	2
		Expected Count	45.5	4.5
	Negative	Count	32	6
		Expected Count	34.5	3.5

3.5 Summary

Training and familiarity with the technology could prove crucial for developing positive attitudes and eventually acceptance of CAVs. To that end, Pilot 2 investigated such impacts via a series of scenarios and exercises that took place in a test track environment. Participants had the opportunity to experience the use of different automated features in a variety of situations.

With respect to perceived feelings during the experience, participants were not likely to provide a positive answer for any of the potential alternatives. Nervous and insecure, were two options related to lower likelihood of a positive answer towards acceptance related questions, while trust only showed a significant correlation with Q2.1, question related to intention to adopt after the experience. However, stated feelings after the experience did not allow for the deduction of solid conclusions but some indications only.

With respect to anticipation, no significant results were found; however, this could as well be related to the distribution of the responses as around

two thirds of the participants reported “positively surprised”. On the other hand, vehicle reactions were significantly related to several acceptance related question. An interesting finding however with respect to this variable is only when these were perceived as “very good”, acceptance increased.

Another factor that resulted in some significant results was difficulty to use the vehicle. This concept could be considered as the opposite of ease of use which has been extensively used as a component of the technology acceptance model (TAM). Difficulty to use the system had a negative correlation to use only when a reduced form of the variable was considered. Hence, unlike what was expected, the interpretation of the variable was not straightforward.

It is also interesting to examine how past experience in an immersive virtual environment could have affected the mental model of participants. Driving simulators have been extensively used in the past for human factors and AV related studies. Results indicated that when the behaviour of the AV was not perceived as different, compared to the test track, there was higher likelihood for an individual to accept the technology. Simulator validity has been considered as a main issue; hence it is necessary to ensure the development of accurate mental models and user expectations. That is, users with higher awareness levels with respect to what they should anticipate from a CAV might be more likely to accept it, rather than having unrealistic expectations.

The effects of training were investigated via three different questions related to the adequacy, efficiency, and whether participants would suggest similar training to others. Some correlations were found with willingness to adopt or let others use however, this finding was not observed across all indicators of acceptance. It should be mentioned though that a positive attitude towards the training was correlated with positive responses towards acceptance related questions.

Finally, most of the variables related to participants’ background did not result in any significant outcomes. This finding might as well imply that findings related to feelings, attitudes towards training, and others are unrelated to individuals’ characteristics and might on average apply regardless background. It should be mentioned that confidence in CAVs was included in background characteristics without resulting in any significant outcomes. Most participants (56 out of 90), reported “medium confident” and the skewness towards this response might have affected the results as there was not sufficient variance.

4 Pilot 3: Autonomous Bus Line

4.1 Introduction

This pilot consisted of a fully operational autonomous bus line within in the public transport system of Madrid, Spain. The line is part of a wider network and connects to several other modes of transport within the system, making it multi-modal and accessible to the paying general public. The bus itself is a level 4 autonomous vehicle, which operates on a public road, where it shares a lane with other traffic participants such as individual traffic and pedestrians as well as commercial busses.

During the execution of the pilot, the majority of participants acted as passengers of the shuttle bus, simulating a multi-modal trip to explore the adequacy of the bus line to bridge the gap between an interurban train station and an interurban bus station. Some additional participants consisted of pedestrians, cyclists, car drivers and other road users, who shared the space with the shuttle in mixed traffic conditions.

4.2 Data Collected

Within the pilot, 3 different kinds of quantitative datasets were collected during the execution of the pilot (from September 2021 until February 2022 in the form of 3 separate pilot waves), which are presented below in designated sub-sections:

1. Survey for bus passengers;
2. Survey for bus co-road users;
3. GPS data from on-board tracker.

Additionally, some qualitative information has been gathered and documented, such as Incidence Report Forms for each batch of participants, photos and video material. Two formal stakeholder interviews were also conducted. All qualitative data has been documented and analysed in detail in Deliverable D6.3 “Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

Finally, all participants signed a GDPR-compliant form to agree to the processing of the gathered datasets and also audio-visual materials gathered during the pilot execution. All datasets have been anonymised previous to the analysis of the datasets to ensure the protection of each individual’s privacy and identity. They also attended a briefing, which explained to them the objective of the research they are participating in.

4.2.1 Survey for bus passengers

This survey is the main focus of the analysis within this deliverable. Participants who rode the bus themselves were asked to complete a survey of 24 questions. These questions were separated into 2 distinct categories (background and technical) and attributed a set of predetermined KPIs for universal comparability across all pilots. In total, 158 participants completed this survey. The survey can be found in full in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

A descriptive analysis of this survey is included in the aforementioned deliverable of a previous WP of this project.

4.2.2 Survey for bus co-road users

Due to the relatively small sample size of participants for this survey (53 participants in total), this dataset has been excluded from the data analysis in this deliverable.

A descriptive analysis of the data has already been conducted within the preceding report of WP6.

4.2.3 GPS data from on-board tracker

During the pilot execution, a tablet device was installed in the interior of the bus, which on the one hand displayed helpful information concerning the timetables of the connected multimodal stops and on the other hand recorded the GPS location of the bus in order to identify any deviations from the route and other incidences of the vehicle (such as emergency brakes).

The tablet recorded also both the speed and the acceleration of the vehicle, which was matched up directly with the trace of the GPS coordinates. No incidences were recorded through the execution of the pilot, such as application of the emergency brakes or deviations from the set bus route.

From the data, it is clearly visible where the bus slowed down either due to the routing (in case of roundabouts or crossings) or because a regular bus stop is located on the route.

Furthermore, two areas without sufficient connection were detected. In one case, the road passes through an underbridge and at another point, no mobile network connection is available.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 4.1: Example data of the pilot batch on 03 February 2022 from 09:10 until 10:00 CET in form of a) heatmap of GPS tracking; b) acceleration of the vehicle on three axes; c) speed of the vehicle.

4.3 Methodology

4.3.1 Chi-squared Tests

The data of Pilot 3 were mainly analysed via a series of cross-tabulation and Chi-Square tests. The details of this approach have been reported in Section 2.3.1. Each question presented in Sections 4.4 and 4.5 has been documented in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

4.3.2 Crosstabulation & Heat-tables

Some additional analysis was also conducted to obtain a clearer image of the correlation between some factors presented in the heat tables. These were created using Excel.

4.3.3 Graphs

Finally, in cases of multiple-choice questions, except for chi-squared analysis, the data were also cross-matched and displayed in a graph to allow some descriptive analysis of visible correlations.

4.3.4 Indicators of acceptance

Table 4.1 outlines the questions that were considered as indicators of CAV acceptance. Each question is assigned a code that is used for the remainder of the document for convenience purposes. The codes from deliverable D6.3 have been included in brackets. The columns of *indicator category* and *indicator* were derived from “Deliverable 6.2 – Pilot Setup”. Due to the sample size-related issues and the low frequency in some of the responses, the latter were recoded, in order to improve the statistical power of the tests. The editing in the response groups is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.1: Indicators of acceptance

Code	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)

Q3.1 (Q23)	If the autonomous shuttle were available to me, I would use it.	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q3.2 (Q22)	Do you believe that the transport system as a whole can be improved by the integration of such kind of autonomous shuttle services?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Quality of life
Q3.3 (Q17)	Would you let other members of your family or close circle use an autonomous shuttle service?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to let others use
Q3.4 (Q21)	Would you pay for using an autonomous shuttle service?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to pay
Q3.5 (Q24)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use the autonomous shuttle. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 4.2: Original and recoded groups

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q3.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am willing to accept the effort to switch to autonomous shuttles (e.g. special courses). - The switch to autonomous shuttles is unacceptable. - I would not like to use autonomous shuttles. - I would try to avoid autonomous shuttles as much as possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Willing to accept the effort - Not willing to accept the effort <p>(Some invalid responses were also removed e.g. some individuals selected both “willing to accept” and “unacceptable” options)</p>
Q3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I don't know - It makes no difference - No - Yes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Other than yes

Q3.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certainly - Depends on how the technology evolves - Probably - Not at all (no occurrences) 	No edits
Q3.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I would not pay for this kind of service - Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee - Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass) 	No edits
Q3.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad. - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses. <p>(Any other response was removed)</p>

4.4 Data analysis - Users

4.4.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

4.4.1.1 *Feelings after the experience*

Table 4.3 shows the significant Chi-Square tests with respect to the question “Q13 – How did you feel while traveling in a CAV?”.

The participants could select multiple options among trustful, careful, insecure, safe, nervous, curious, critical, and unaffected. The significant results are further presented via cross tabulation analysis.

Table 4.3: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	Critical	LR	3.810	0.051	146
Q3.2	Trustful	Chi-Square	5.225	0.022	151
	Insecure	LR	6.860	0.009	151
	Unaffected	LR	3.426	0.064	151
Q3.3	Trustful	Chi-Square	24.438	<0.001	151
	Careful	Chi-Square	9.351	0.009	151
	Safe	Chi-Square	6.630	0.036	151
	Insecure	LR	9.490	0.009	151
Q3.4	Curious	Chi-Square	10.031	0.007	151
Q3.5	Nervous	LR	3.662	0.056	151

Variable: Feelings

The results with respect to the critical feeling indicate that these participants were also more likely to adopt the technology (Table 4.4). However, give the lower frequencies of the “true” (selected) critical cases, the results need to be treated with caution.

Table 4.4: The association of critical feeling with Q3.1

		Critical	
		0	1
Q3.1	Willing to accept the effort	Count	114 19
		Expected Count	115.7 17.3
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	13 0
		Expected Count	11.3 1.7

Trustful feeling was positively associated with the expectation of system improvements due to the presence of AVs (Table 4.5). Hence, trust may not only be related to personal intention to use but also the anticipation for benefits at the societal level.

Table 4.5: The association of trustful feeling with Q3.2

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q3.2	Other than yes	Count	21	7
		Expected Count	15.6	12.4
	Yes	Count	63	60
		Expected Count	68.4	54.6

The results related to the insecure feeling suggest that the former was negatively related to positive attitude towards system improvement (Table 4.6). Once again, although the result is intuitive, this finding needs to be treated with caution due to small observed frequencies of “positive” answers.

Table 4.6: The association of insecure feeling with Q3.2

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q3.2	Other than yes	Count	26	2
		Expected Count	27.6	.4
	Yes	Count	123	0
		Expected Count	121.4	1.6

Unaffected participants were less likely to report a positive answer towards perceived system improvement (Table 4.7). That is, unless the experience is perceived as positive (and not neutral), users may not perceive any benefits due to the use of technology.

Table 4.7: The association of unaffected feeling with Q3.2

		Unaffected		
		0	1	
Q3.2	Other than yes	Count	24	4
		Expected Count	26.3	1.7
	Yes	Count	118	5
		Expected Count	115.7	7.3

The trustful feeling also had a significant and positive impact on willingness to let others use (Table 4.8). In particular a “Certainly” answer was more likely to occur, than expected, for “true” answers in the trustful feeling. This finding further highlights the importance of trust.

Table 4.8: The association of trustful feeling with Q3.3

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	42	59
		Expected Count	56.2	44.8
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	13	2
		Expected Count	8.3	6.7
	Probably	Count	29	6
		Expected Count	19.5	15.5

The careful feeling was associated with less likelihood to observe a “certainly” answer and a higher likelihood to observe a “depends” answer (Table 4.9). This finding implies that higher vigilance during the experience could be related to less willingness to let others use (potentially due to lower levels of trust).

Table 4.9: The association of careful feeling with Q3.3

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	78	23
		Expected Count	71.6	29.4
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	6	9
		Expected Count	10.6	4.4
	Probably	Count	23	12
		Expected Count	24.8	10.2

Similar to trustful, the safe feeling had a positive influence on the willingness to let others use (Table 4.10). This could be an indication that trust and perceived safety are related concepts, both positively affecting acceptance.

Table 4.10: The association of safe feeling with Q3.3

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	66	35
		Expected Count	72.2	28.8
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	14	1
		Expected Count	10.7	4.3
	Probably	Count	28	7
		Expected Count	25.0	10.0

The insecure feeling was, as expected, negatively associated to letting others use the technology (Table 4.11).

However, the observed frequencies of a “positive” insecure answer were very low and hence this result needs to be treated with caution.

Table 4.11: The association of insecure feeling with Q3.3

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	101	0
		Expected Count	99.7	1.3
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	13	2
		Expected Count	14.8	.2
	Probably	Count	35	0
		Expected Count	34.5	.5

The curious feeling was positively associated with willingness to pay for the CAV service if the latter was included in the monthly ticket (Table 4.12). Hence, curious individuals are not negative towards using or paying for the technology however, some incentives may be anticipated by them.

Table 4.12: The association of curious feeling with Q3.4

		Feeling_curious		
		0	1	
Q3.4	I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	11	14
		Expected Count	9.1	15.9
	Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	13	7
		Expected Count	7.3	12.7
	Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	31	75
		Expected Count	38.6	67.4

Finally, the nervous feeling was associated with a higher likelihood to perceive mass adoption as “good”, compared to “great” (Table 4.13). This finding indicates the potentially harmful impact on negative feelings after experiencing the technology towards public acceptance.

Table 4.13: The association of insecure feeling with Q3.5

		Nervous	
		0	1
Q3.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	70	1
	Expected Count	67.7	3.3
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	72	6
	Expected Count	74.3	3.7

4.4.1.2 Anticipation

Table 4.14 presents the Chi-Square tests results with respect to the anticipation regarding the experience (“Q14 – Was using a CAV the experience you had anticipated?”). Given the lower number of responses in the “Negatively surprised” and “I don’t know” groups (5 and 4 respectively), these options were removed from further analysis. The significant results were further examined via cross tabulation analysis.

Table 4.14: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	Chi-Square	8.019	0.005	137
Q3.2	Chi-Square	1.342	0.247	142
Q3.3	Chi-Square	3.521	0.172	142
Q3.4	Chi-Square	6.110	0.047	142
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.067	0.796	140

Variable: CAV anticipation

Table 4.15 suggests that positively surprised individuals were more likely to be willing to adopt the technology. As mentioned earlier with respect to the unaffected feeling, if the experience does not positively influence the users, willingness to use might not increase. Hence, providing automated services “equally good” to conventional one might not suffice.

Table 4.15: The association of CAV anticipation with Q3.1

		CAV_anticipation	
		It was as I was expected	Positively surprised
Q3.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	51	74
	Expected Count	55.7	69.3
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	10	2
	Expected Count	5.3	6.7

The finding with respect to Q3.1 was further validated regarding Q3.4. In particular, users positively surprised were more likely to be willing to pay for a separate fee (Table 4.16).

Table 4.16: The association of CAV anticipation with Q3.4

		CAV anticipation	
		It was as I was expected	Positively surprised
Q3.4 I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	13	9
	Expected Count	9.6	12.4
Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	4	15
	Expected Count	8.3	10.7
Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	45	56
	Expected Count	44.1	56.9

4.4.1.3 VRU safe

The potential implications of automated vehicles were also examined with respect to vulnerable road users via the “VRU safe” variable (Q15 - Do you think this kind of vehicle is safe to use for vulnerable users? (wheelchair users, visually impaired persons, the elderly, injured

persons)). However, no significant associations were found with any of the acceptance indicators (Table 4.17).

Table 4.17: VRU safe tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	0.193	0.660	146
Q3.2	LR	1.877	0.598	151
Q3.3	Chi-Square	0.151	0.927	151
Q3.4	Chi-Square	2.556	0.279	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.065	0.799	149

Variable: VRU safe

4.4.2 CAV emissions

The indicators of acceptance were investigated with respect to the impact of autonomous bus shuttles on emissions and sustainability (Q20 - Do you believe that CAVs can lower emissions and contribute to making transport networks more sustainable?). Among all indicators, only a significant association was found with Q3.5 (Table 4.18).

Table 4.18: CAV emissions tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	2.316	0.128	146
Q3.2	LR	1.447	0.229	151
Q3.3	LR	0.253	0.875	151
Q3.4	LR	12.288	0.139	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	4.259	0.039	149

Variable: CAV emissions

As shown in Table 4.19, a positive answer towards higher levels of sustainability was related to perceiving mass adoption as great. Hence, sustainability may be linked to issues of public acceptance.

Table 4.19: The association of CAV emissions with Q3.5

		CAV emissions	
		Other	Yes
Q3.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	3	68
	Expected Count	6.7	64.3
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	11	67
	Expected Count	7.3	70.7

4.4.3 Effects on traffic

The effects on traffic refer to “Q16a - What kind of influence have you witnessed?” which was a follow up question to “Q16 - Have you witnessed that the autonomous bus shuttle you have just tried influences the traffic conditions of the surrounding road users?” Influence types 3 and 5 occurred in two of the acceptance indicators while influence type 4 had one significant association (Table 4.20). The former types of influence are:

- Influence type 3: Decreased safety conditions on the road (higher risk of collision, dangerous overtaking, risky manoeuvres, etc.)
- Influence type 4: Increased degree of road anger and/or anxiety in other road users
- Influence type 5: Other road users respect the corridor defined for the autonomous shuttle

Table 4.20: Effects on traffic tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.2	Influence 3	LR	5.421	0.020	151
Q3.3	Influence 3	LR	5.928	0.036	151
	Influence 5	Chi-Square	4.840	0.089	151
Q3.4	Influence 4	Chi-Square	12.138	0.002	151
Q3.5	Influence 5	Chi-Square	2.797	0.094	149

Variable: Influence on traffic

The influence type 3 refers to decreased safety conditions due to the interactions of other users with the automated shuttle. This had a negative association was found with the perception towards the improvement of the system (Table 4.21) and also willingness to let others use the technology (Table 4.22). Hence, interactions of CAVs with the surrounding traffic and road users might be considered as very important towards accepting the technology.

Table 4.21: The association of influence 3 with Q3.2

			Influence3	
			0	1
Q3.2	Other than yes	Count	21	7
		Expected Count	24.8	3.2
	Yes	Count	113	10
		Expected Count	109.2	13.8

Table 4.22: The association of influence 3 with Q3.3

			Influence3	
			0	1
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	94	7
		Expected Count	89.6	11.4

Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	11	4
	Expected Count	13.3	1.7
Probably	Count	29	6
	Expected Count	31.1	3.9

With reference to Table 4.23, influence type 5 is less related than expected with the willingness of letting others use the technology.

Table 4.23: The association of influence 5 with Q3.3

		Influence5	
		0	1
Q3.3 Certainly	Count	80	21
	Expected Count	76.9	24.1
Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	8	7
	Expected Count	11.4	3.6
Probably	Count	27	8
	Expected Count	26.7	8.3

According to Table 4.24, perceived higher levels of road rage and anger (influence type 4) are related to lower willingness to pay for the technology.

Table 4.24: The association of influence 4 with Q3.4

		Influence4	
		0	1
Q3.4 I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	14	11
	Expected Count	19.2	5.8
Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	20	0
	Expected Count	15.4	4.6
Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	82	24
	Expected Count	81.4	24.6

Respect of the automated shuttle corridor by other users was related to higher public acceptance levels (Table 4.25). Harmonious coexistence could be a key factor for public acceptance.

Table 4.25: The association of influence 5 with Q3.5

		Influence5	
		0	1
Q3.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	50	21
	Expected Count	54.3	16.7
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	64	14
	Expected Count	59.7	18.3

4.4.4 Information sufficiency

The relation of acceptance and information provided on board was also examined (Q18 - Do you think that information inside the autonomous shuttle is sufficient for your usual trips?) and the results are presented in Table 4.26. No significant relationships was found however, this could be related to the positive answer provided by the vast majority of the sample; 126 out of 154 of the original data replied “yes”.

Table 4.26: Information sufficiency

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	1.065	0.302	146
Q3.2	Chi-Square	2.676	0.102	151
Q3.3	Chi-Square	3.178	0.204	151
Q3.4	LR	0.193	0.908	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.028	0.866	149

Variable: Information sufficiency

4.4.5 Features missing

The relation of acceptance and information provided on board was also examined (Q19 - Are you missing any features onboard the autonomous shuttle?). And the results are presented in Table 4.27. Only one significant correlation was found with Q3.3. In particular, a negative reply towards any missing feature was related to higher than expected willingness to let other use (as illustrated via the “certainly” response, Table 4.28).

Table 4.27: Features missing tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	1.793	0.181	146
Q3.2	Chi-Square	2.492	0.114	151
Q3.3	Chi-Square	5.996	0.050	151
Q3.4	Chi-Square	3.738	0.154	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	1.190	0.275	149

Variable: Features missing

Table 4.28: The association of missing features with Q3.3

		Features missing		
		Other	No	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	25	76
		Expected Count	30.8	70.2
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	8	7
		Expected Count	4.6	10.4
	Probably	Count	13	22
		Expected Count	10.7	24.3

4.4.6 The impact of participants' background

The impact of participants' background was also examined with respect to acceptance. Gender did not result in any significant correlations (Table 4.29). It should be mentioned that any response different than female or male was removed due to the low frequency of occurrence.

Table 4.29: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	Chi-Square	0.911	0.349	142
Q3.2	Chi-Square	0.605	0.437	147
Q3.3	Chi-Square	0.656	0.720	147
Q3.4	Chi-Square	2.914	0.233	147
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.003	0.956	145

Variable: Gender

A useful tool to better understand patterns in insignificant results is via heat tables. For instance, Table 4.30 shows that although both men and women state that they are certain that they would feel comfortable letting people they are close with use CAV technologies if they are available, more than 10% of them reported only probably feeling comfortable with this thought. In the case of other gender identities and persons who preferred not to reveal their gender identity, a similar conclusion can be made, although the sample size for these gender categories was too small to estimate the distribution of answers.

The table suggests some level of uncertainty for all gender groups with respect to letting others use the technology.

Table 4.30: Heat table for correlation between gender and willingness to let other persons use CAVs

Gender	Certainly	Depends on how the technology evolves	Probably
Female	28.8%	4.6%	12.4%
Male	35.3%	5.2%	11.1%
Other	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%
Prefer not to say	1.3%	0.0%	0.7%

Income only had a significant association with Q3.4 which is related to WTP (Table 4.31). More specifically, as shown in Table 4.32, individuals in the 250-1000 €/month were less likely to pay unless the price was included in the monthly ticket. Individuals in the 2000+ €/month group were more likely to be willing to pay.

Table 4.31: Income tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	2.916	0.405	146
Q3.2	Chi-Square	1.113	0.774	151
Q3.3	LR	2.765	0.838	151
Q3.4	LR	20.012	0.003	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	1.998	0.573	149

Variable: Income

Table 4.32: The association of income with Q3.4

		Income			
		No answer	250-1000 €/month	1000- 2000 €/month	2000+ €/month
Q3.4 I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	1	9	11	4
	Expected Count	3.0	10.1	6.8	5.1
Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	5	2	4	9
	Expected Count	2.4	8.1	5.4	4.1
Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	12	50	26	18
	Expected Count	12.6	42.8	28.8	21.8

The frequency of public transportation use was related to some of the acceptance indicators (Table 4.33).

Table 4.33: PT use frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	Chi-Square	1.628	0.443	146
Q3.2	Chi-Square	3.037	0.219	151
Q3.3	Chi-Square	2.574	0.631	151
Q3.4	LR	14.816	0.005	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	5.488	0.064	149

Variable: PT use frequency

It is interesting that daily or weekly users would be more likely to be willing to pay if the price was included in a monthly ticket. On the other hand, less frequent users were more likely to pay in general (Table 4.34). This finding

further suggests the potential need for the implementation of incentive schemes for different categories of users.

Table 4.34: The association of PT frequency of use with Q3.4

		Daily	PT use frequency	
			Less than once a week or never	Once or twice a week
Q3.4 I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	12	11	2
	Expected Count	11.6	9.8	3.6
Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	4	15	1
	Expected Count	9.3	7.8	2.9
Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	54	33	19
	Expected Count	49.1	41.4	15.4

Table 4.35 suggests that daily PT users were more likely, than expected, to respond “good” with respect to public acceptance. The same pattern was observed for weekly users while it was the less frequent users who responded “great” regarding the public acceptance question. This cross-tabulation analysis was significant only at the 0.1 level; however, it might require some further investigation as the response pattern could be considered against expectations (more frequent users were anticipated to be more positive with respect to public acceptance).

On the other hand, this specific test does not include the “bad” response, due to the low representation of this category in the sample (two occurrences only). The difference between the “great” and “good” responses might be “blurry” as both indicate a positive outcome.

Table 4.35: The association of PT frequency of use with Q3.5

		PT use frequency		
		Daily	Less than once a week or never	Once or twice a week
Q3.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	28	35	8
	Expected Count	32.4	28.1	10.5
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	40	24	14
	Expected Count	35.6	30.9	11.5

Table 4.36 suggests significant results regarding Q3.1 and commute frequency. In particular, daily commuters were more likely to be willing to use the technology, once this is available. (Table 4.37).

Table 4.36: Commute frequency

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	5.050	0.025	143
Q3.2	Chi-Square	0.005	0.942	148
Q3.3	Chi-Square	1.010	0.604	148
Q3.4	Chi-Square	2.408	0.300	148
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.019	0.899	146

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 4.37: The association of commute frequency with Q3.1

		Commute frequency	
		Everyday	2-6 a week or less
Q3.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	97	34
	Expected Count	93.4	37.6
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	5	7
	Expected Count	8.6	3.4

Unlike commute frequency, commute distance did not have any significant correlations with acceptance related questions, as denoted in Table 4.38.

Table 4.38: Commute distance

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	0.127	0.938	143
Q3.2	Chi-Square	2.123	0.346	148
Q3.3	LR	3.697	0.449	148
Q3.4	Chi-Square	4.979	0.289	148
Q3.5	Chi-Square	1.216	0.545	146

Variable: Commute distance

Mode choice only had a significant association with Q3.4 related to WTP (Table 4.39). More specifically, public transport users (either bus or subway) were more likely, than expected, to be willing to pay if the fee was incorporated in the monthly ticket (Table 4.40). On the other hand, private car users were more likely, than expected, to report willingness to pay a separate fee. These users are potentially expected to use the technology scarcely only hence, incentives need to be considered towards attracting existing public transport users.

Table 4.39: Mode choice tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	0.948	0.623	137
Q3.2	Chi-Square	3.806	0.149	142
Q3.3	LR	1.424	0.840	142
Q3.4	Chi-Square	10.231	0.037	142
Q3.5	Chi-Square	0.282	0.868	140

Variable: Mode choice

Table 4.40: The association of mode choice with Q3.4

		Mode choice		
		Private car	Public transport - Bus	Public transport - Subway
Q3.4 I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	11	3	10
	Expected Count	8.1	5.7	10.1
Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	11	4	4
	Expected Count	6.4	4.5	8.0
Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	26	27	46
	Expected Count	33.5	23.7	41.8

Table 4.41 presents the Chi-Square test results with respect to frequency of use CAVs. No significant results were observed with any of the acceptance related indicator.

Table 4.41: CAV frequency of use

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	4.537	0.406	146
Q3.2	LR	7.297	0.199	151
Q3.3	LR	4.931	0.424	151
Q3.4	LR	6.196	0.799	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	3.484	0.626	149

Variable: CAV frequency of use

Table 4.42 is a heat-table showing the distribution of percentages, providing some additional details with respect to the results presented in Table 4.40. It should be noted that most users of public transport modes (both bus and subway) already use a monthly transport ticket. They perceive autonomous services as an additional offer to the available service offering, which they can access today.

It is however unclear whether the users would expect an increase in the pricing of their ticket. Further it is notable that users of private cars are also willing to pay for CAVs but it is not clear whether this would encourage them to commit to a modal shift to public and shared services or whether it means that they would accept CAV technology features in their own private cars.

Table 4.42: Heat table for correlation between preferred mode of transport and willingness to pay

Preferred mode of transport	I would not pay for this kind of service	I would be willing to pay a separate fee	I would be willing to pay, if the fee was included in my monthly transport ticket
Private car	7.2%	7.9%	17.1%
Public transport (bus)	2.0%	2.6%	17.8%
Public transport (subway)	6.6%	2.6%	30.3%
Walking	0.7%	0.7%	3.3%
None of the above	0.0%	0.0%	1.3%

4.4.6.1 CAV confidence

Confidence in CAVs was considered via “Q6 - How much confidence do you have in CAVs?”. Two significant relationships were found with Q3.2 and Q3.3 (Table 4.43).

Table 4.43: CAV confidence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	LR	1.616	0.446	146
Q3.2	Chi-Square	6.291	0.043	151
Q3.3	LR	35.617	<0.001	151
Q3.4	LR	7.347	0.119	151
Q3.5	Chi-Square	4.347	0.114	149

Variable: CAV confidence

With reference to Table 4.44, very trusting or medium trusting individuals were more likely to report a positive answer towards the improvement of the transportation system by the introduction and user of CAVs. In the same direction, very trusting individuals were more likely to provide a “certain” answer towards willingness to let others use (Table 4.45). Medium trusting individuals were more likely to be in the “probably” category while barely trusting were more likely, than expected, to respond “depends on how the technology” evolves.

Table 4.44: The association of CAV confidence with Q3.2

		CAV confidence		
		Barely trusting	Medium trusting	Very trusting
Q3.2 Other answer	Count	6	16	6
	Expected Count	2.6	17.2	8.2
Yes	Count	8	77	38
	Expected Count	11.4	75.8	35.8

Table 4.45: The association of CAV confidence with Q3.3

		CAV confidence		
		Barely trusting	Medium trusting	Very trusting
Q3.3 Certainly	Count	7	52	42
	Expected Count	9.4	62.2	29.4
Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	5	10	0
	Expected Count	1.4	9.2	4.4
Probably	Count	2	31	2
	Expected Count	3.2	21.6	10.2

4.4.6.2 The impact of CAV services

The impact of CAV service use on acceptance was also investigated via a similar approach like Pilots 1 and 2.

However, only few significant associations were found (Table 4.46). As a general rule, higher experience with some of the CAV services is related to higher acceptance levels.

Table 4.46: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q3.1	Not tried CAV	LR	3.056	0.080	146
Q3.4	ACC	Chi-Square	11.696	0.003	151
Q3.5	Connected features	Chi-Square	5.622	0.018	149

Variable: CAV services

Table 4.47: The association of no CAV with Q3.1

		Not tried CAV		
		0	1	
Q3.1	Willing to accept the effort	Count	124	9
		Expected Count	122.1	10.9
	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	10	3
		Expected Count	11.9	1.1

Table 4.48: The association of no CAV with Q3.4

		ACC		
		0	1	
Q3.4	I would not pay for this kind of service	Count	21	4
		Expected Count	17.7	7.3
	Yes, I would be willing to pay a separate fee	Count	8	12
		Expected Count	14.2	5.8
	Yes, if the fee was included in my monthly ticket (public transport pass)	Count	78	28
		Expected Count	75.1	30.9

Table 4.49: The association of no CAV with Q3.5

		Connected features		
		0	1	
Q3.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses.	Count	17	54
		Expected Count	23.8	47.2
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good.	Count	33	45
		Expected Count	26.2	51.8

4.4.7 Further analysis of acceptance predictors

The variables related to acceptance have been already documented and analysed in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”. On top of the aforementioned analysis, it might be useful to further investigate these variables to better understand the relationship between factors affecting acceptance factors. Some of the most interesting relationships are presented in the present section. The codes in brackets refer to those used in D6.3.

4.4.7.1 Experience with CAVs (Q5b) and Confidence in CAVs (Q6)

The possible answers to question 5b of the survey “How many times have you ever used a CAV?”, “never”, “only once”, “rarely”, “occasionally”, “systematically”.

This question is correlated to the following question 6, “How much confidence do you have in CAVs?”, which was rated through the attributes “no trust at all”, “barely trusting”, “medium trusting” and “very trusting”.

The chi-squared test of 142 values rendered a p-value of 0.639. With 12 degrees of freedom and a calculated chi-square value of 9.74, the critical value of 9.889 is not reached, meaning that the data fit the model and the null hypothesis is not rejected. The distribution is shown in Table 4.50.

Table 4.50: Heat table for correlation between frequency of CAV usage and confidence in the technology

Frequency of previous CAV use	No trust at all	Barely trusting	Medium trusting	Very trusting
Never	0.0%	0.0%	3.5%	1.4%
Only once	0.7%	3.5%	12.7%	6.3%
Rarely	0.0%	2.1%	10.6%	4.2%
Occasionally	0.0%	2.1%	25.4%	9.2%
Systematically	0.0%	1.4%	9.2%	7.7%

This table shows that the level of trust and confidence of users who have previously been exposed the CAVs is significantly higher than of those

who have never tried a CAV before. What is notable is that the confidence level is immediately significantly higher after only one previous CAV experience.

4.4.7.2 Feelings during CAV usage (Q13) and Expectations of the CAV experience (Q14)

Since the participants were able to report more than just one emotion they felt during their trip, a chi-squared analysis is not possible since the same value can appear more than once.

Instead, it is possible to display the reported feelings according to whether or not they thought the experience matched with their previous expectations.

Question 13, “How did you feel while traveling in a CAV?” offered participants 8 possible answer options, “trustful”, “careful”, “insecure”, “safe”, “nervous”, “curious”, “critical”, “unaffected”. Question 14, “Was using a CAV the experience you had anticipated” allowed participants to rank the experience depending on their previous expectations in “it was as I expected”, “negatively surprised”, “positively surprised” and “I don’t know”. It should be noted that most participants reported that the experience was either as they expected or even better.

Figure 4.2: Graph displaying the feelings reported during CAV experience and the expectation of the experience prior

It is quite clear that the emotions, which can be summarised under “positive” emotions (trust, safety, curiosity) were especially high amongst those who were either positively surprised or had the right expectations. Overall, in all categories, participants reported feeling curious the most often.

4.5 Data analysis – Users and Co-users

The data of co-users were analysed separately due to the lower sample size however they were examined in comparison to the users’ data. That is, for a series of common questions in both surveys, the impact of user type (user or co-user) was investigated.

4.5.1 Individual background characteristics

The background of individuals was investigated as a first step. This part of the analysis was performed to ensure that any differences in acceptance would be mainly related to the user type rather than background characteristics.

As shown in Table 4.51, no differences were observed with respect to gender. Marginally significant differences were found regarding commute frequency between the two groups of users (Table 4.52). Users had higher than expected frequencies with respect to “everyday” and “2-6 times” a week response. On the other hand, higher observed frequencies regarding the “more than once a day” group. Given these inconsistencies, the interpretation of these differences is unclear.

Table 4.51: Gender pilots

			Study	
			Users	Co-users
Gender	Female	Count	69	27
		Expected Count	70.9	25.1
	Male	Count	78	25
		Expected Count	76.1	26.9
Chi-Square = 0.382, p-value = 0.536, N = 199				

Table 4.52: Commute frequency pilots

			Study	
			Users	Co-users
Commute frequency	No answer	Count	3	2
		Expected Count	3.7	1.3
	2-6 times per week	Count	38	10
		Expected Count	35.5	12.5
	Everyday	Count	101	31
		Expected Count	97.7	34.3
	Less than a week	Count	5	3
		Expected Count	5.9	2.1
	More often than once a day	Count	4	5
		Expected Count	6.7	2.3
	Once a week	Count	0	2
		Expected Count	1.5	.5
LR = 11.018, p-value = 0.051, N = 204				

Participants in the two groups did not significantly differ in terms of commute distances (Table 4.53) or mode choice (Table 4.54).

Table 4.53: Commute distance pilots

			Study	
			Users	Co-users
Commute distance	No answer	Count	3	2
		Expected Count	3.7	1.3
	16-25 km	Count	32	5
		Expected Count	27.4	9.6
	26+ km	Count	28	9
		Expected Count	27.4	9.6
	5-15 km	Count	46	24
		Expected Count	51.8	18.2
	Up to 5 km	Count	42	13
		Expected Count	40.7	14.3
LR = 6.471, p-value = 0.167, N = 204				

Table 4.54: Mode choice pilots

		Study		
		Users	Co-users	
Mode choice	None of the above	Count	2	0
		Expected Count	1.5	.5
	Private car	Count	48	11
		Expected Count	43.9	15.1
	Public transport - Bus	Count	34	9
		Expected Count	32.0	11.0
	Public transport - Subway	Count	60	31
		Expected Count	67.7	23.3
	Walking	Count	7	1
		Expected Count	6.0	2.0
Chi-Square = 7.356, p-value = 0.118, N = 203				

As presented in Table 4.55, participants significantly differ regarding the frequency of public transport use. In particular, participants in the users group were more likely to report daily use and less likely to report no use of public transport.

Table 4.55: Public transport frequency of use

		Study		
		Users	Co-users	
PT frequency	Daily	Count	70	22
		Expected Count	68.4	23.6
	Less than once a week	Count	42	6
		Expected Count	35.7	12.3
	Never	Count	17	17
		Expected Count	25.3	8.7
	Once or twice a week	Count	22	7
		Expected Count	21.6	7.4
Chi-Square = 15.117, p-value = 0.002, N = 203				

Table 4.56 shows there were no significant differences with respect to the generic confidence in CAVs the participants in the two user groups had.

Table 4.56: Confidence pilots

		Users		Co-users
CAV confidence	Barely trusting	Count	14	6
		Expected Count	14.9	5.1
	Medium trusting	Count	93	30
		Expected Count	91.5	31.5
	Very trusting	Count	44	16
		Expected Count	44.6	15.4
Chi-Square = 0.333, p-value = 0.846, N = 203				

4.5.2 Acceptance

The analysis of indicators of acceptance is presented in this section. The codes follow the same numbering presented in Section 4.3.4.

No significant differences were found with respect to perceived improvements (quality of life) in the transportation system (Table 4.57) and willingness to use upon availability of the technology (Table 4.58).

Table 4.57: Quality of life (Q3.2)

		Study	
		Users	Co-users
Q3.2	Other answer	Count	28
		Expected Count	29.9
	Yes	Count	123
		Expected Count	121.1
Chi-Square = 0.597, p-value = 0.440, N = 202			

Table 4.58: Willingness to use upon availability (Q3.1)

		Study	
		Users	Co-users
Q3.1	Positive	Count	133
		Expected Count	130.4
	Negative	Count	13
		Expected Count	15.6
Chi-Square = 1.826, p-value = 0.177, N = 197			

The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 4.59 suggested significant differences with respect to the willingness to let others use. In particular, users were more likely to provide a “certainly” response. This finding could indicate that experience and familiarity with the technology could increase acceptance. In the same direction, users were more likely to respond “great” regarding mass population adoption, compared to co-users.

Table 4.59: Willingness to let others use (Q3.3)

		Study		
		Users	Co-users	
Q3.3	Certainly	Count	101	26
		Expected Count	94.9	32.1
	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	15	7
		Expected Count	16.4	5.6
	Probably	Count	35	16
		Expected Count	38.1	12.9
	Probably not	Count	0	2
		Expected Count	1.5	.5
LR = 8.557, p-value = 0.036, N = 202				

Table 4.60: Public acceptance (Q3.5)

		Study		
		Users	Co-users	
Q3.5	It feels great	Count	71	15
		Expected Count	64.3	21.7
	It feels bad	Count	2	4
		Expected Count	4.5	1.5
	It feels good	Count	78	32
		Expected Count	82.2	27.8
LR = 8.380, p-value = 0.015, N = 0.015				

4.6 Summary

Although the conclusions of the descriptive analysis of this dataset can be found in the previous deliverable D6.3 of WP6 of the PAsCAL project, some interesting insights can be gathered from this data analysis.

A finding that resonated with the findings documented in the previous deliverable D6.3 are the overall very positive and open emotions of the participants during the CAV experience. However, some significant associations were found between feelings and acceptance related questions. Among feelings after the experience, “trustful” and “insecure” had the highest number of occurrences. The indicators related to quality of life and willingness to let others use had the highest number of associations with the stated feelings. Results were consistent with expectations and “positive” responses to “trustful” or “safe” were associated with higher levels of acceptance whereas “insecure” or “nervous” with lower levels. It is important to ensure vehicle behaviour that enhances trust and decreases negative feelings related to lower safety.

They reported that the experience (in the form of anticipation of CAV performance) was mostly either as they expected or they were positively surprised, meaning that the technology rarely triggered negative reactions and that most of them did not make a bad experience with the vehicle. Anticipation was related to two of the acceptance indicators highlighting that CAV performance needs to be better than conventional solutions to be preferred. That is, even if performance perceived as equal, public might decide to keep using conventional and familiar solutions, unless additional benefits from the CAV use are perceived. This finding is particularly interesting with respect to WTP; individuals were more likely (than expected) to be willing to pay a separate fee if they were positively surprised.

Acceptance could be also related to the broader impacts of CAVs on the surrounding traffic. Decreased safety conditions or increase of road anger by the surrounding traffic could negatively influence acceptance.

In terms of background characteristics, although men and women reported almost the same distribution of willingness to let their close family members and friends adopt the technology (with most of them quite certain and some thinking they would probably accept this change), men are slightly more eager to do so. This could be because in general the affinity for new technologies is slightly higher in men than women (Wajcman, 2000).

A very important and striking insight is that experiencing a CAV even on a singular isolated occasion significantly influences the trust on these technologies, as occurred via heat table analysis. Specifically, it raises the trust in the technology and occasional use of the technology seems like the best way to safely and securely raise the overall acceptance of CAVs.

Further, participants who use mostly public transport services to move around are very receptive to also pay for additional offers such as CAV operations. Integrating CAVs, especially high-level autonomous vehicles, into existing public transport offerings are one of the most suitable and convincing method to expose the general public to higher levels of automation and connectivity. This can even increase the acceptance of the transport system as a whole and render public transport more attractive.

Finally, when compared to co-users (the users interacting with the CAVs as e.g. pedestrians), only a few differences were found with respect to background characteristics. In particular, no differences were observed for gender, mode choice, commute distance or general confidence in the CAVs. On the other hand, differences were found in the commute frequency and public transport frequency of use; participants coded as users were more likely to report daily use and less likely to report that they never use public transport. Regarding acceptance indicators, no differences were found for willingness to use the technology once this is available and quality of life. On the other hand, the users group was more likely to be positive towards letting others use and public acceptance of the technology. Hence, direct experience with the vehicle might assist in improving CAV acceptance levels.

5 Pilot 4: Shared Connected Transport

5.1 Introduction

The Shared Connected transport pilot study focussed on assessing attitudes and perceptions of “drivers” and passengers toward different types of shared connected vehicles. This included an autonomous shuttle and a shared car fleet including an electric vehicle with autonomous features (such as autopilot, automatic or guided parking and other autonomous features that would become available). These transport modes were allowed for operation on public roads at the time of this subtask.

The goal of this pilot is to better understand attitudes and public acceptance to different kinds of shared vehicles (by size, by type and by availability of autonomous features) and to various associated incentives. This pilot study allows operators of shared fleets to:

1. optimally design and operate fleets of shared vehicles;
2. design well-suited incentive mechanisms to increase public acceptance and improve attitudes towards different kinds of shared vehicles.

The pilot was divided into two sub-pilots:

During the **shared car fleet sub-pilot**, the employees of the University of Luxembourg, which already have a fleet of shared vehicles available, were asked to drive a shared vehicle with autonomous features (level 2 automation) and to provide relevant information in form of a survey on their driving experience. The vehicles of this shared fleet were provided by Moovee¹, a car shared fleet operator based in Luxembourg. The main objective of this pilot was to collect both qualitative and quantitative information on the acceptance of CAVs in the current daily life of professionals. The experiment took place during two weeks in November on an open road in the Belval area, which is located in the South of Luxembourg and close to the French border. An additional wave was organised during two weeks in March in Contern, within a business campus close to Luxembourg city. The sample size consisted of 103 participants.

¹ <https://moovee.lu/en/>

For the **autonomous shuttle bus sub-pilot**, an autonomous electric shuttle was used, which is operated by Sales-Lentz² in Contern, within a business campus. The shuttle is a Autonom Shuttle Evo model provided by the manufacturer of the vehicle, Navya³. During two weeks in April/May, 51 participants took part in the pilot at Campus Contern. Participants were asked to use the autonomous shuttle for their last-mile trip during their commute to work. This included either to use the shuttle from the train station to their workplace in the morning or use the shuttle on their return trip from their workplace to the train station. The sample size of the autonomous bus shuttle consisted of 51 participants.

Within WP6, the data analysis of the questionnaire results only included the results of the shared car fleet sub-pilot. The aim of this data analysis is to extend the WP6 data analysis with the additional results of autonomous shuttle bus sub-pilot. The data of the two sub-pilots is combined and a comparison is made of the public acceptance between two different users (drivers and passengers) and of two different transport modes (car and shuttle).

5.2 Data collection

5.2.1 Reports and surveys

The data for the shared connected transport pilot includes two types of data:

1. **Quantitative data in form of questionnaire results:** Each participant had to fill out the questionnaire after the trip with the car with autonomous features. These results allow to make first conclusions on the attitudes and perceptions of “drivers” and passengers toward shared connected vehicles.
2. **Qualitative data in form of Incidence Report Forms:** Two staff members were present during the test drives to observe the reactions of the participants and to respond to questions/comments if needed. In order to capture information regarding the context and setting of the pilot, but also the remarks or feelings of the participants, a specific Incidence Reporting Form

² <https://www.sales-lentz.lu/en/>

³ <https://navya.tech/en/>

was used. This small digital survey helped to quickly and simply link contextual or external information with the participants' surveys. The incidence reports collect the following information: Pilot name; wave number; incidents related to the pilot (if any); incidents unrelated to the pilot (if any); weather conditions; size of batches; additional comments & feedback.

In order to be consistent, similar data and information was collected for the two different sub-pilots. Concerning data protection rules, all the participants read and agreed to sign a GDPR compliant form at the end of the questionnaire. All data collected is being anonymised, so that none of the persons who have filled out the survey are identifiable through the dataset. Participants were informed that they can access the data, rectify it, request its deletion or exercise their rights to limit the processing of their data if needed.

5.2.2 Collected data

The main aim of this analysis is to do a comparison between the different type of users (drivers and passengers) of the two different transport modes (car and shuttle). The analysis of the complete dataset is based on:

1. **Demographic questions** including gender, age, occupation, education level and commute to work (frequency and distance of the commuting trip).
2. **Questions which are cross-matched and presented in a graph/table to obtain a clearer image on possible factors for the correlation:**
 - Opinion on the self-driving performance of the vehicles in relation to the mode of transport (presented in a graph)
 - Confidence of the participant while using a CAV in relation to the duration of having a full driving license (presented in a graph).
 - Type of user in relation to the experience using a CAV (presented in a graph).
 - Gender in relation to the usage of CAVs (how often did the person use a CAV) (presented in a table).
 - Type of user in relation to the willingness to use a shared connected vehicle for trips after the pilot experience (presented in a table).
 - Type of user in relation to the willingness to pay a higher price for a shared vehicle with autonomous features (presented in a table).

- Type of user in the relation to the potential use of a shared fleet composed of CAVs if it will be available (presented in a table).

3. In the case of multiple-choice questions, the data was also cross-matched and displayed in a table to allow some descriptive analysis of visible correlations:

Type of transport mode in relation to the feeling while traveling in a CAV.

5.3 Methodology

5.3.1 Descriptive analysis

The data collected as part of pilot 4 was documented and analysed only partially in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”. In particular, the data of the automated shuttle sub-pilot were not covered in the aforementioned document. Hence, a comprehensive descriptive statistics analysis has been documented in the present document in Section 5.4.

5.3.2 Chi-Squared tests

The data of Pilot 4 were analysed via a series of cross-tabulation and Chi-Square tests. The details of this approach have been reported in Section 2.3.1.

5.3.3 Indicators of acceptance – shared fleet sub-pilot

Table 5.1 presents the questions that were considered as indicators of CAV acceptance. Each question is assigned a code that is used for the remainder of the document for convenience (The question codes used in D6.3 were included in brackets). The columns of *indicator category* and *indicator* were derived from “Deliverable 6.2 – Pilot Setup”.

Due to the sample size-related issues and the low frequency in some of the responses, the latter were recoded, in order to improve the statistical power of the tests. The recoded groups are presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.1: Indicators of acceptance – Pilot 4

Code	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)
Q4.1 (Q24)	After this experience, would you use a shared connected vehicle for your daily trips?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q4.2 (Q25)	Would you encourage your family or friends to use shared connected vehicles?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to let others use
Q4.3 (Q26)	Would you pay a higher price for a shared vehicle with autonomous features?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to pay
Q4.4 (Q29)	If a shared fleet composed of CAVs were available, I would use them.	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q4.5 (Q30)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use shared fleets of CAVs. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 5.2: Original and recoded groups

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q4.1	Yes; No; I don't know; Depends how the technology evolves	Yes; Other than yes
Q4.2	Yes; No; I don't know; Depends how the technology evolves	Yes; Other than yes

Q4.3	Yes, No; I don't know, Depends how the technology evolves	Yes; No; Depends on how technology evolves
Q4.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am willing to accept the effort to switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs (e.g. special courses). - The switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs is unacceptable. - I would not like to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs. - I would try to avoid a shared fleet composed of CAVs as much as possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Willing to accept the effort - Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.
Q4.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad. - The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs. 	No edits

5.3.4 Indicators of acceptance – shuttle sub-pilot

The indicators of acceptance used for the shuttle sub-pilot are presented in Table 5.3. The original categories and recoded categories of the responses are presented in Table 5.4. The questions have been derived from deliverable 6.2 “Pilot Setup”.

Table 5.3: Indicators of acceptance – Pilot 4 (Shuttle)

Code (D6.2 code)	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)
Q4.2.1 (Q21)	After this experience, would you use a shared connected vehicle for your daily trips?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt

Q4.2.2 (Q22)	Would you encourage your family or friends to use shared connected vehicles?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to let others use
Q4.2.3 (Q23)	Would you pay a higher price for a shared vehicle with autonomous features?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to pay
Q4.2.4 (Q26)	If a shared fleet composed of CAVs were available, I would use them.	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q4.2.5 (Q27)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use shared fleets of CAVs. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 5.4: Original and recoded groups – Pilot 4 (Shuttle)

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q4.1	Yes; No; I don't know; Depends how the technology evolves	Yes; Other than yes
Q4.2	Yes; No; I don't know; Depends how the technology evolves	Yes; Other than yes
Q4.3	Yes, No; I don't know, Depends how the technology evolves	No; Depends on how technology evolves (Other responses were removed due to low number of occurrences)
Q4.4	- I am willing to accept the effort to switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs (e.g. special courses).	- Willing to accept the effort - Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs is unacceptable. - I would not like to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs. - I would try to avoid a shared fleet composed of CAVs as much as possible. 	
Q4.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad. - The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good. - I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs. 	No edits

5.4 Descriptive statistics data analysis

In total 154 persons participated in the shared connected transport pilot, out of which 103 participated in the shared car fleet sub-pilot and 51 in the autonomous bus shuttle sub-pilot. 86 participants were drivers and 17 were passengers for the shared fleet sub-pilot. Some of the participants answered being both (driver and passenger), as they were already passengers in vehicles with autonomous features before the PAsCAL trials. 51 persons participated in the autonomous shuttle sub-pilot, out of which 13 were drivers (from Sales-Lentz). The current section presents the analysis of the two sub-pilots combined.

5.4.1 Demographics

Figure 5.1 shows that out of the 154 participants, 84 participants are aged between 18 and 35 years (out of which 53 are male, 28 are female and 3 other participants didn't want to specify their gender). 50 out of 154 participants are aged between 36 and 49 years (out of which 36 are male, 13 are female and one didn't prefer to say). 20 participants out of 154 are aged between 50 and 72 years (7 are male and 13 are female). The majority of participants were men (96 out of 154).

Figure 5.1: Age and gender of participants

Table 5.5 shows that most of the participants (102 out of 154) have a high education with a university degree. Out of these 102, 87 participants are working full-time (over 30 hours a week), 8 are still students and 4 already retired. 17 out 154 participants have a high school diploma out of which 15 are working full-time and 8 are still students. In total, 123 participants are working full-time. This means that most of the participants have a high education level. Some of the participants also commented that they work or worked in the automotive sector and are familiar with CAVs.

Table 5.5: Education level and current occupation of the participants

	Full-time work	Student	Retired	Other	N/A	Grand Total (Counts)
<i>Polytechnic degree, university of applied sciences degree, other university degree</i>	87	8	4	3		102
<i>A levels, high school diploma or other university entrance qualification</i>	15	2				17
<i>Advanced Vocational Certificate of Education, vocational baccalaureate diploma, technical diploma</i>	11	1				12

<i>Completed apprenticeship</i>	3	2	5
<i>Elementary or lower secondary school qualification</i>	1		1
<i>Middle School, High School or Secondary School or equivalent qualification</i>	4	2	6
<i>School finished without school leaving certificate</i>	2		2
<i>Still at school</i>		3	1
<i>N/A</i>			5
Grand Total (Counts)	123	14	8
		3	6
			5
			154

When asking the participants how they commute to work (see *Figure 5.2*), 76 mentioned that they commute every day. 22 out of these 76 participants travel more than 26km each day. 21 participants commute between 16-25km and 20 participants commute 5-15km between their workplace and home. 13 participants only live up to 5km from their workplace. 54 out of the 154 participants indicated that they commute 2-6 times per week to work, out of which 18 live between 16 to 25km from their workplace. 4 participants travel only once a week to their workplace, followed by 3 participants commuting even less than once a week. As most of the participants have to commute almost the whole week over 15km to their workplace, a shared connected transport service is of advantage for at least the last-mile of their commuting trip. A question which was not asked in the questionnaire but was asked before the test drive, was which kind of mode of transport participants use for their daily commute. Most of them answered that they take their car or the train.

Figure 5.2: Frequency and distance of commuting to work

5.4.2 Feelings during CAV usage

Figure 5.3 shows the opinion on the self-driving performance of the vehicles in relation to the mode of transport. 33 out of 103 participants who have used the level 2 car indicate that the car performs the same as a human driver. 29 participants indicate that the performance is just different and 29 indicate that the car performs worse than a human driver. 18 participants even say that the car is performing even better than a human driver.

For the autonomous shuttle, 18 participants indicated that the shuttle performed same as the human driver, followed by 11 participants saying that the shuttle performed worse than a human driver.

Figure 5.3: Opinion on the self-driving performance of the vehicles in relation to the mode of transport

Figure 5.4 shows the relation between the level of confidence while using a CAV and the level of driving experience (duration of driving license

ownership). 69 participants indicated that they have a driving license for over 15 years.

Figure 5.4: Confidence during CAV usage in relation to their experience of driving

Out of these 69 participants, 32 participants felt medium confident followed by 25 participants feeling very confident. 9 participants indicated feeling barely confident and 3 feeling not confident at all while using a CAV.

33 out of the 154 participants own their driving license between 10 and 15 years. 16 out of them feel medium confident while using a CAV, followed by 8 feeling very confident and 9 feeling barely confident. This shows that even if you are experienced driver, there is still a lack of confidence while using a CAV and a trust issue while using a new technology.

Figure 5.5 shows that 75 participants indicated to feel careful while using one of the vehicles with autonomous features, out of which 61 used the level 2 car and 14 used the autonomous shuttle. 69 participants indicated that they felt curious, out of which 56 were using the level 2 car and 13 used the autonomous shuttle. 58 participants were feeling trustful, out of which 39 used the car and 19 used the shuttle. The least participants felt unaffected (1 using the car and 5 using the shuttle) This is followed by 14 participants indicating feeling insecure (11 used the car and 3 the autonomous shuttle).

Figure 5.5 Feeling when using a CAV by mode of transport

Looking at Figure 5.6, 31 participants which were drivers indicated that they are positively surprised after their trip with a CAV. 14 drivers indicated that it was as expected. Only 4 participants indicated that they are negatively surprised. As for passengers, 22 participants are positively surprised, followed by 12 passengers saying it was as expected. Only one participant mentioned that she/he is negatively surprised. The participants which were drivers as well as passengers indicated that the experience was as expected, followed by 17 participants indicating that they are positively surprised.

Figure 5.6: Type of user/Expectation of the trip

5.4.3 Willingness to use a CAV

Table 5.6 shows the usage of CAVs by gender. 38 out of 154 participants answered that they only used a CAV once, followed by 32 (21 male and

11 female) participants using CAVs rarely. 27 participants indicated that they occasionally use CAVs (19 male, 7 female and 1 other). 20 participants indicated that they never used a CAV, followed by 19 participants not indicating how many times they used a CAV.

Table 5.6: Gender/Usage of CAVs

Gender/How many times used a CAV?	Never	Occasionally	Only once	Rarely	Systematically	N/A	Grand Total
<i>Female</i>	8	7	19	11	6	3	54
<i>Male</i>	12	19	18	21	12	14	96
<i>Other</i>		1					1
Grand Total (Count)	20	27	38	32	18	19	154

Table 5.7 shows the type of user and the willingness to pay for a CAV service in the future. 34 percent of the users are not willing to pay more for a CAV service. Out of these 34%, 12% of the participants were drivers, 10% were passengers and 9% were passengers as well as drivers. 31% of the participants indicated that they would be willing to pay more for using a CAV service, depending on how the technology evolves in the future. Out of these 31%, 11% were again drivers who would be more eager to pay more for a CAV service. Only 8% were passengers, who would be willing to pay more depending on how the technology evolves. Only 18% of the participants would be willing to pay more to use a CAV service.

Table 5.7: Type of user/Willingness to pay

Type of user/Willingness to pay	Depends on how technology evolves	I don't know	No	Yes	N/A
Driver	11,04%	3,25%	12,34%	7,79%	0,65%
Passenger	8,44%	2,60%	10,39%	3,90%	0,00%

Both	7,79%	2,60%	9,74%	5,84%	1,30%
N/A	3,90%	1,95%	1,95%	1,30%	3,25%
Grand Total (%)	31,17%	10,39%	34,42%	18,83%	5,19%

Table 5.8 shows the relationship between the type of user and the willingness to use. 44% of the participants are willing to use a CAV service in the future, out of which 16% were drivers and 13% were both, so driver and passenger. 33% of the participants are willing to use a CAV service depending on how the technology evolves. Out of these 33%, 11% were drivers and 12% were passengers.

In comparison to the table above, here passengers are way more willing to use a CAV service, however, not so willing to pay for it.

Table 5.8: Type of user/Willingness to use

Type of user/Willingness to use	Depends on how technology evolves	I don't know	No	Yes	N/A
Driver	11,04%	3,25%	3,90%	16,23%	0,65%
Passenger	11,69%	1,30%	2,60%	9,74%	0,00%
Both	9,74%	1,30%	1,95%	12,99%	1,30%
N/A	1,30%	1,95%	0,65%	5,19%	3,25%
Grand Total (%)	33,77%	7,79%	9,09%	44,16%	5,19%

Table 5.9 shows that 55% of the participants are willing to accept the effort to switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs. Out of these 55%, 22% were drivers and only 12% were passengers. 16% indicated that they were both, drivers and passengers. Only 23% of the participants are willing to accept the effort to switch to CAVs. Only 7% would not like to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.

Table 5.9: Type of user/Willingness to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs

<i>Type of user/willingness to use a shared fleet of CAVs</i>	<i>I am willing to accept the effort to switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs (e.g. special courses).</i>	<i>I am willing to accept the effort to switch to CAVs (e.g. special courses).</i>	<i>I would not like to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs .</i>	<i>I would not like to use CAVs.</i>	<i>I would try to avoid a shared fleet composed of CAVs as much as possible.</i>	<i>The switch to CAVs is unacceptable.</i>	<i>N/A</i>
Driver	22,08%	5,84%	3,25%	1,95%	1,30%	0,00%	0,65%
Passenger	12,34%	8,44%	1,95%	0,00%	0,65%	0,65%	0,00%
Both	16,23%	7,14%	1,30%	0,65%	0,65%	0,00%	1,30%
N/A	5,19%	1,95%	0,65%	0,65%	0,00%	0,00%	3,25%
Grand Total (%)	55,84%	23,38%	7,14%	3,25%	2,60%	0,65%	5,19%

5.5 Data analysis – shared fleet

5.5.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

5.5.1.1 Feelings after the experience

This section presents the results related to the question “15 - How did you feel while traveling in a CAV?”, as presented in deliverable D6.3 (Annex III). The potential responses to that question were: Trustful, Careful, Insecure, Safe, Nervous, Curious, Critical and Unaffected. Participants could select yes or no for as many of the aforementioned feelings, as the question had a multiple choice format. Given that including both significant and insignificant results would result in tables of large size, only the former are presented in Table 5.10.

The results suggest that the “Trustful” and “Nervous” options resulted in significant results most times. The former were followed by “Careful”, “Critical” and “Insecure”.

Table 5.10: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Careful	Chi-Square	2.918	0.088	101
	Nervous	Chi-square	5.034	0.025	101
	Critical	LR	6.579	0.010	101
Q4.2	Careful	Chi-Square	8.991	0.003	101
	Trustful	Chi-Square	5.891	0.015	101
	Critical	LR	5.680	0.017	101
Q4.3	Insecure	LR	4.176	0.010	101
	Trustful	Chi-Square	11.316	0.003	101
Q4.4	Insecure	LR	3.605	0.058	101
	Safe	LR	11.645	<0.001	101
	Nervous	LR	4.421	0.035	101
Q4.5	Trustful	Chi-Square	7.213	0.027	101
	Nervous	Chi-Square	4.690	0.096	101

Variable: Feelings

The “careful” feeling potentially indicates lack of trust as participants might have had higher alert levels and monitoring the environment more frequently.

As shown in Table 5.11, careful feeling was associated with lower levels of intention to use shared CAV after the experience. In the same direction “nervous” feeling (Table 5.12) was also associated with lower levels of intention to use. With respect to the same question (Q4.1), participants with a critical stance were also less likely to state intention to use the CAV technology. This might be an indication that disapproval of the CAV behaviour could act as a barrier towards use.

Table 5.11: The association of careful feeling with Q4.1

			Careful	
			0	1
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	16	35
		Expected Count	20.2	30.8
	Yes	Count	24	26
		Expected Count	19.8	30.2

Table 5.12: The association of nervous feeling with Q4.1

			Nervous	
			0	1
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	37	14
		Expected Count	41.4	9.6
	Yes	Count	45	5
		Expected Count	40.6	9.4

Table 5.13: The association of critical feeling with Q4.1

			Critical	
			0	1
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	43	8
		Expected Count	46.5	4.5
	Yes	Count	49	1
		Expected Count	45.5	4.5

Table 5.14: The association of careful feeling with Q4.2

			Careful	
			0	1
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	9	32
		Expected Count	16.2	24.8
	Yes	Count	31	29
		Expected Count	23.8	36.2

Following the findings related to Q4.1, the results related to question Q4.2 suggested that a trustful stance towards the CAV increased a positive attitude towards the use of the technology by family members (Table 5.15). Moreover, a critical feeling (Table 5.16) resulted in a non-positive attitude towards the use of CAV by family members. This outcome is consistent with the findings related to Q4.1.

Table 5.15: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	31	10
		Expected Count	25.2	15.8
	Yes	Count	31	29
		Expected Count	36.8	23.2

Table 5.16: The association of critical feeling with Q4.2

		Critical		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	34	7
		Expected Count	37.3	3.7
	Yes	Count	58	2
		Expected Count	54.7	5.3

Regarding WTP (Q4.3), a sense of insecurity did not affect individuals willing to pay more, as the observed counts were very close to the expected (Table 5.17). On the other hand, participants not willing to pay were also more likely to report as “insecure”. In the same direction participants willing to pay or willing to pay depending on the technology involvement were also more likely to report as “trustful” (Table 5.18). On the other hand, the opposite outcome was found for individuals not willing to pay more who reported lower levels of trust.

Table 5.17: The association of insecure feeling with Q4.3

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	33	0
		Expected Count	29.7	3.3
	No	Count	27	6
		Expected Count	29.7	3.3
	Yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	21.6	2.4

Table 5.18: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.3

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	15	18
		Expected Count	19.4	13.6
	No	Count	27	6
		Expected Count	19.4	13.6
	Yes	Count	11	13
		Expected Count	14.1	9.9

The insecure feeling was also found to have a significant correlation to Q4.4. In particular, the former was negatively related to the willingness to use the technology, once this is available (Table 5.19). On the other hand, the “safe” feeling had a positive relationship with willingness to use the technology (Table 5.20). Finally, similarly to Q4.1, nervous feeling had a negative association also to Q4.4 and willingness to use (Table 5.21).

Table 5.19: The association of insecure feeling with Q4.4

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	79	7
		Expected Count	76.6	9.4
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort	Count	11	4
		Expected Count	13.4	1.6

Table 5.20: The association of safe feeling with Q4.4

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	56	30
		Expected Count	60.5	25.5
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	15	0
		Expected Count	10.5	4.5

Table 5.21: The association of nervous feeling with Q4.4

		Nervous		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	73	13
		Expected Count	69.8	16.2
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	9	6
		Expected Count	12.2	2.8

Finally, “trustful” feeling was also positively related to perceive wider use of shared CAVs as “great” (Table 5.22). This finding further suggests that trust can be a main drive of public acceptance. However, the “nervous” feeling resulted in opposite effects (Table 5.23).

Table 5.22: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.5

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	18	18
		Expected Count	22.1	13.9
	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	12	1
		Expected Count	8.0	5.0
	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	32	20
		Expected Count	31.9	20.1

Table 5.23: The association of nervous feeling with Q4.5

		Nervous	
		0	1
Q4.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	32	4
	Expected Count	29.2	6.8
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	8	5
	Expected Count	10.6	2.4
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	42	10
	Expected Count	42.2	9.8

5.5.1.2 Anticipation

The anticipation question refers to “Q16 – Was using a CAV the experience you had anticipated?” presented in deliverable D6.3. The possible responses were “positively surprised”, “it was as I expected”, “negatively surprised” and “I don’t know”. Given the low frequencies in the two latter cases (each occurred 5 times), they were not considered in the analysis. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 5.24.

Table 5.24: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	2.214	0.137	91
Q4.2	Chi-Square	7.487	0.006	91
Q4.3	Chi-Square	2.428	0.297	82
Q4.4	Chi-Square	0.642	0.423	91
Q4.5	Chi-Square	0.602	0.740	91

Variable: CAV anticipation

Anticipation had a significant relationship only with question Q4.2. In particular, positively surprised participants were more likely to agree for their family members to use the technology, compared to those who found

the experience as they expected. However, given that no other significant relationships were found, anticipation might not be the most representative drive of CAV acceptance.

Table 5.25: The association of CAV anticipation with Q4.2

		CAV anticipation	
		It was as I expected	Positively surprised
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	18
		Expected Count	12.0
	Yes	Count	15
		Expected Count	21.0

5.5.1.3 Comfort

The comfort variable refers to “Q17 – Was the trip comfortable compared with a conventional vehicle?” presented in deliverable D6.3. Given the low frequency in the “I don’t know” group (occurred 5 times), this response was not considered in the analysis. The other potential responses were “more comfortable”, “less comfortable” and “no different”. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 5.26. The results suggest that perceived comfort compared to a conventional vehicle had a significant impact almost on all indicators of acceptance.

Table 5.26: CAV comfort tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	12.333	0.002	97
Q4.2	Chi-Square	12.445	0.002	97
Q4.3	LR	24.287	<0.001	
Q4.4	LR	5.757	0.056	97
Q4.5	LR	6.916	0.140	97

Variable: CAV comfort

Table 5.27 suggests that higher levels of intention to use the shared CAV technology were positively associated only to a “more comfortable” experience. This finding may consist an indication that even “equally” comfortable experience with a conventional vehicle might not be sufficient to stimulate higher acceptance.

Table 5.27: The association of comfort with Q4.1

		CAV comfort			
		Less comfortable	More comfortable	No different	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	7	22	21
		Expected Count	5.2	30.4	14.4
	Yes	Count	3	37	7
		Expected Count	4.8	28.6	13.6

In the same direction to Q4.1, more comfortable experience also had a more positive relationship with a positive answer in Q4.2 (Table 5.28). On the other hand, the opposite effects were found with respect to no different or less comfortable experience who were more likely to report no difference or less comfort.

Table 5.28: The association of comfort with Q4.2

		CAV comfort			
		Less comfortable	More comfortable	No different	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	6	16	18
		Expected Count	4.1	24.3	11.5
	Yes	Count	4	43	10
		Expected Count	5.9	34.7	16.5

Table 5.29 suggests that participants perceiving the experience as more comfortable were also more likely to be willing to pay more for the use of shared CAVs. On the other hand, participants on the “depends” were more likely to state “no different” levels of comfort while participants not willing

to pay more were more likely to state either “no difference” or “less comfortable”.

Table 5.29: The association of comfort with Q4.3

		CAV comfort		
		Less comfortable	More comfortable	No different
Q4.3 Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	3	15	12
	Expected Count	3.1	17.8	9.1
No	Count	6	13	13
	Expected Count	3.3	19.0	9.7
Yes	Count	0	23	1
	Expected Count	2.5	14.2	7.3

Table 5.30 indicates that participants perceived the experience as “more comfortable” compared to conventional vehicles were more likely to be willing to use the technology, once the latter is available. The opposite was found for participants in the “less comfortable” group.

Table 5.30: The association of comfort with Q4.4

		CAV comfort		
		Less comfortable	More comfortable	No different
Q4.4 Willing to accept the effort	Count	6	54	24
	Expected Count	8.7	51.1	24.2
Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	4	5	4
	Expected Count	1.3	7.9	3.8

5.5.1.4 CAV behaviour

The CAV behaviour variable refers to question “Q18 – How well do you think that the self-driving car performed regarding steering, acceleration,

brake?” from deliverable D6.3. The potential responses were “better than the human driver”, “same as the human driver”, “worse than the human driver”, “just different”. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 5.31. The results indicate that behaviour of the CAV had a significant influence almost on all indicators of acceptance.

Table 5.31: CAV behaviour tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	12.333	0.062	101
Q4.2	Chi-Square	11.397	0.010	101
Q4.3	Chi-Square	14.092	0.034	90
Q4.4	LR	5.757	0.006	101
Q4.5	LR	5.287	0.508	101

Variable: CAV behaviour

Table 5.32 indicates that perceiving the behaviour of the CAV better than a human driver was more likely to be related to a positive answer in Q4.1. On the other hand, a non-positive answer to Q4.1 was more likely to be related to perceiving the CAV behaviour worse, compared to a human driver. Similar patterns were also observed with respect to Q4.2 regarding the use of the technology by family members (Table 5.33).

Table 5.32: The association of CAV behaviour with Q4.1

		CAV behaviour				
		Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	4	16	18	13
		Expected Count	9.1	14.6	16.7	10.6
	Yes	Count	14	13	15	8
		Expected Count	8.9	14.4	16.3	10.4

Table 5.33: The association of CAV behaviour with Q4.2

		CAV behaviour				
		Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver	
Q4.2	Non-positive	Count	2	14	12	13
		Expected Count	7.3	11.8	13.4	8.5
	Yes	Count	16	15	21	8
		Expected Count	10.7	17.2	19.6	12.5

Table 5.34 indicates that willingness to pay is higher when driving behaviour is perceived better than a human driver. The opposite conclusion holds with respect to willingness to pay when the CAV behaviour is considered worse than a human driver. Another interesting finding is that participants who stated willingness to pay depending on the evolvement of the technology were more likely to perceive behaviour same as the human driver and less likely to perceive it worse.

Table 5.34: The association of CAV behaviour with Q4.3

		CAV behaviour				
		Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	6	10	14	3
		Expected Count	5.9	9.2	10.6	7.3
	No	Count	2	10	9	12
		Expected Count	5.9	9.2	10.6	7.3
	Yes	Count	8	5	6	5
		Expected Count	4.3	6.7	7.7	5.3

Finally, Table 5.35 suggests that perceiving the CAV behaviour better than the human driver increases willingness to use the technology, once the latter becomes available. On the other hand, perceiving the CAV behaviour worse than the human driver increased the likelihood of a “not willing” or “avoid” response. This pattern is consistent with the results between Q4.1 and CAV behaviour.

Table 5.35: The association of CAV behaviour with Q4.4

			CAV behaviour			
			Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	18	21	31	16
		Expected Count	15.3	24.7	28.1	17.9
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	0	8	2	5
		Expected Count	2.7	4.3	4.9	3.1

5.5.1.5 CAV reactions

CAV reactions refer to question “Q19 – How do you describe the self-driving car reactions?” from deliverable D6.3. The question was implemented in a multiple-choice manner hence, participants could select more than one from the available options. The latter were: very good; safe; neutral; unpredictable; and dangerous. The significant results are presented in Table 5.36.

The detailed cross-tabulation tables of the significant results have been appended in Annex 1.

Table 5.36: CAV reactions tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Dangerous	LR	2.773	0.096	101
Q4.2	Very good	Chi-Square	3.433	0.064	101
	Neutral	Chi-Square	5.482	0.019	101
	Dangerous	LR	3.666	0.056	101
	Safe	Chi-Square	4.611	0.032	101
Q4.3	Unpredictable	LR	5.707	0.059	101
Q4.4	Very good	LR	5.597	0.018	101
	Unpredictable	LR	4.546	0.033	101

Variable: CAV reactions

The perception about the reactions of the CAVs led to significant correlations with several of the indicators of acceptance. Perception of “very good” reactions was related to more positive levels of acceptance. The opposite was found with respect to the “unpredictable” and “dangerous” behaviours. Although the latter had a small number of occurrences and needs to be treated with caution, it still consists of potential indicators regarding the effect of CAV reactions, when these are perceived as dangerous. Moreover, the negative impact of “unpredictable” behaviour highlights the importance of developing accurate mental models of behaviour. Users need to be aware about the behaviour of CAVs and their expectations need to be appropriately calibrated, as the latter could affect acceptance levels.

5.5.1.6 Driver reactions

Driver reactions refer to question “Q20 - Which was your reaction to the car manoeuvres?” from deliverable D6.3. Driver reactions might reflect trust on the technology and consequently acceptance. The possible responses were “I was totally confident”, “I watched carefully but let the car take control” and “I took back control”. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 5.37.

Table 5.37: Driver reactions tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	LR	4.173	0.124	101
Q4.2	Chi-square	9.683	0.008	101
Q4.3	LR	13.259	0.010	90
Q4.4	LR	2.162	0.339	101
Q4.5	LR	6.441	0.148	101

Variable: Driver reactions

The results presented in Table 5.38 suggest that individuals who took back control were more likely to be non-positive if some member of their family used the technology. On the other hand, participants who monitored the situation closely without resuming control were more likely to be positive if the technology was used by their family members. This finding can be an indication with respect of the impact of trust in the CAV performance on acceptance.

Table 5.38: The association of driver reactions with Q4.2

		Driver reactions			
		I took back control	I was totally confident	I watched carefully but let the car take control	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	8	6	27
		Expected Count	3.7	6.1	31.3
	Yes	Count	1	9	50
		Expected Count	5.3	8.9	45.7

The reaction of drivers also had implications on WTP (Table 5.39). In particular, drivers who took back control were less likely to be willing to pay. It is interesting though that individuals who stated willing to pay depending on how the technology evolves were more likely to be

confident, compared to individuals willing to pay. The latter were more likely to monitor the situation without resuming control than taking manual control back.

Table 5.39: The association of driver reactions with Q4.3

		Driver reactions		
		I took back control	I was totally confident	I watched carefully but let the car take control
Q4.3 Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	0	7	26
	Expected Count	2.9	4.8	25.3
No	Count	7	4	22
	Expected Count	2.9	4.8	25.3
Yes	Count	1	2	21
	Expected Count	2.1	3.5	18.4

5.5.2 The impact of service difficulty to use

5.5.2.1 Booking difficulty

The booking difficulty variable refers to question “Q21 - How difficult did you find it to book and access the shared connected vehicle?”, presented in deliverable D6.3.

The responses groups were “very difficult”, “moderately difficult”, “not very difficult” and “not difficult at all”. The “moderately difficult” group had only two occurrences and removed from the analysis. No significant effects of booking difficulty were found regarding acceptance (Table 5.40). This finding is expected as the majority participants did not perceive the booking process as difficult (most responses were either in the “not very difficult” or “not difficult at all” groups).

Table 5.40: Booking difficulty tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	0.412	0.521	99
Q4.2	Chi-Square	0.001	0.972	99
Q4.3	Chi-Square	0.905	0.669	88
Q4.4	Chi-Square	0.008	0.929	99
Q4.5	Chi-Square	0.269	0.874	99

Variable: Booking difficulty

5.5.2.2 Use difficulty

The use difficulty variable refers to question “Q22 - How difficult and stressful was to use the shared connected vehicle?”, presented in deliverable D6.3. The responses to this question were “very difficult”, “moderately difficult”, “not very difficult” and “not difficult at all”. No significant effects of booking difficulty were found regarding acceptance (Table 5.41). This finding is expected as the majority participants did not perceive the using the service as difficult (most responses were either in the “not very difficult” or “not difficult at all” groups).

Table 5.41: Use difficulty tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	2.137	0.344	101
Q4.2	Chi-Square	1.449	0.488	101
Q4.3	LR	1.169	0.883	90
Q4.4	Chi-Square	0.805	0.669	101
Q4.5	LR	6.035	0.197	101

Variable: Use difficulty

5.5.2.3 Return difficulty

The return difficulty variable refers to question “Q23 - How difficult and stressful was to return the shared connected vehicle?”, presented in deliverable D6.3. The responses to this question were “very difficult”, “moderately difficult”, “not very difficult” and “not difficult at all”. The “Moderately difficult” group had five occurrences and removed from the analysis. No significant effects of booking difficulty were found regarding acceptance (Table 5.42). This finding is expected as the majority participants did not perceive the return process as difficult (most responses were either in the “not very difficult” or “not difficult at all” groups).

Table 5.42: Return difficulty tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	1.990	0.158	95
Q4.2	LR	0.754	0.385	95
Q4.3	Chi-Square	0.641	0.726	87
Q4.4	LR	1.303	0.254	95
Q4.5	Chi-Square	3.490	0.175	95

Variable: Return difficulty

5.5.3 The impact of perceived benefits and shortcomings on acceptance

5.5.3.1 Benefits

Perceived benefits refer to question “Q27 - Which potential benefits do you see in using a shared fleet composed of CAVs?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. Participants could select as many benefits as they preferred. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented in this section.

Table 5.43: Perceived benefits tests

Variable	Benefits	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Increased safety	Chi-Square	6.647	0.010	101
Q4.2	Increased safety	Chi-Square	6.590	0.010	101
	Better service	Chi-Square	4.455	0.035	101
Q4.3	Increased safety	Chi-Square	5.509	0.064	90
Q4.4	Increased safety	Chi-Square	17.161	<0.001	101
Q4.5	Lower pollution	Chi-Square	4.768	0.092	101

Variable: Benefits

Among all potential benefits, increased safety resulted in significant associations with most of the acceptance indicators. In general, perceiving increased safety was significantly related to a more positive view towards AVs.

Table 5.44: The association of increased safety with Q4.1

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	26	25
		Expected Count	19.7	31.3
	Yes	Count	13	37
		Expected Count	19.3	30.7

Table 5.45: The association of increased safety with Q4.2

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	22	19
		Expected Count	15.8	25.2
	Yes	Count	17	43
		Expected Count	23.2	36.8

Table 5.46: The association of increased better service with Q4.2

		Better service		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	35	6
		Expected Count	30.4	10.6
	Yes	Count	40	20
		Expected Count	44.6	15.4

Table 5.47: The association of increased safety with Q4.3

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	13	20
		Expected Count	12.8	20.2
	No	Count	17	16
		Expected Count	12.8	20.2
	Yes	Count	5	19
		Expected Count	9.3	14.7

Table 5.48: The association of increased safety with Q4.4

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	26	60
		Expected Count	33.2	52.8
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	13	2
		Expected Count	5.8	9.2

Table 5.49: The association of lower pollution with Q4.5

		Lower pollution	
		0	1
Q4.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	13	23
	Expected Count	18.2	17.8
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	7	6
	Expected Count	6.6	6.4
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	31	21
	Expected Count	26.3	25.7

Another significant positive correlation occurred between perceived better service and Q4.2 (Table 5.46). Finally, environmental benefits were positively associated with a higher acceptance of the AV adoption by large parts of the population (Table 5.49). This finding could be an indication that public acceptance is more related to benefits at the societal level.

5.5.3.2 Shortcomings

Perceived benefits refer to question “Q28 - Which potential shortcomings do you see in using a shared fleet composed of CAVs?” as presented in deliverable D6.3. Participants could select as many shortcomings as they preferred. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented (Table 5.50).

Table 5.50: Perceived shortcomings tests

Variable	Shortcomings	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Loss of jobs	Chi-Square	4.567	0.033	101
	Less security	Chi-Square	13.156	< 0.001	101
	Decreased safety	Chi-Square	4.648	0.031	101
Q4.2	Less security	Chi-Square	7.474	0.006	101
	Decreased safety	Chi-Square	4.993	0.025	101
	None	Chi-Square	4.665	0.031	101

Q4.3	Worse service	LR	8.352	0.015	90
	Less security	Chi-Square	10.753	0.005	90
	Higher price	Chi-Square	6.545	0.038	90
	None	LR	6.509	0.039	90
Q4.4	Worse service	LR	2.892	0.089	101
	Less security	LR	3.464	0.064	101
	Decreased safety	LR	3.464	0.063	101
	None	LR	4.879	0.027	101
Q4.5	Less security	Chi-Square	23.673	<0.001	101

Variable: Shortcomings

As a general comment, the issue of less security had a significant relationship with all indicators of acceptance. This finding suggests increased levels of perceived vulnerability when sharing a vehicle with other users. Moreover, decreased safety also had a significant correlation with several of the indicators. The shortcomings of less security and decreased safety are potentially the main ones need to be resolved in order to increase AV acceptance levels.

Another interesting finding regards not perceiving any of the suggested shortcomings. The latter was related with higher acceptance levels.

Table 5.51: The association of loss of jobs with Q4.1

		Loss of jobs		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	39	12
		Expected Count	42.9	8.1
	Yes	Count	46	4
		Expected Count	42.1	7.9

Table 5.52: The association of less security with Q4.1

		Less security		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	33	18
		Expected Count	40.4	10.6
	Yes	Count	47	3
		Expected Count	39.6	10.4

Table 5.53: The association of decreased safety with Q4.1

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	36	15
		Expected Count	40.4	10.6
	Yes	Count	44	6
		Expected Count	39.6	10.4

Table 5.54: The association of less security with Q4.2

		Less security		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	27	14
		Expected Count	32.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	53	7
		Expected Count	47.5	12.5

Table 5.55: The association of decreased safety with Q4.2

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	28	13
		Expected Count	32.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	52	8
		Expected Count	47.5	12.5

Table 5.56: The association of no shortcomings with Q4.2

		None		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	39	2
		Expected Count	35.3	5.7
	Yes	Count	48	12
		Expected Count	51.7	8.3

Table 5.57: The association of worse service with Q4.3

		Worse service		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	33	0
		Expected Count	31.5	1.5
	No	Count	29	4
		Expected Count	31.5	1.5
	Yes	Count	24	0
		Expected Count	22.9	1.1

Table 5.58: The association of less security with Q4.3

		Less security		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	21	12
		Expected Count	25.7	7.3
	No	Count	25	8
		Expected Count	25.7	7.3
	Yes	Count	24	0
		Expected Count	18.7	5.3

Table 5.59: The association of higher price with Q4.3

		Higher price		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	12	21
		Expected Count	11.0	22.0
No		Count	6	27
		Expected Count	11.0	22.0
Yes		Count	12	12
		Expected Count	8.0	16.0

Table 5.60: The association of higher price with Q4.3

		None		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	29	4
		Expected Count	29.0	4.0
No		Count	32	1
		Expected Count	29.0	4.0
Yes		Count	18	6
		Expected Count	21.1	2.9

Table 5.61: The association of worse service with Q4.4

		Worse service		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	84	2
		Expected Count	82.6	3.4
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	13	2
		Expected Count	14.4	.6

Table 5.62: The association of lower security with Q4.4

		Lower security		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	71	15
		Expected Count	68.1	17.9
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	9	6
		Expected Count	11.9	3.1

Table 5.63: The association of decreased safety with Q4.4

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	71	15
		Expected Count	68.1	17.9
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	9	6
		Expected Count	11.9	3.1

Table 5.64: The association of no shortcomings with Q4.4

		None		
		0	1	
Q4.4	Willing to accept the effort	Count	72	14
		Expected Count	74.1	11.9
	Avoid or not willing to accept the effort.	Count	15	0
		Expected Count	12.9	2.1

Table 5.65: The association of less security with Q4.5

		Less security	
		0	1
Q4.5 I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	34	2
	Expected Count	28.5	7.5
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	4	9
	Expected Count	10.3	2.7
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	42	10
	Expected Count	41.2	10.8

Regarding other potential shortcomings, loss of jobs was negatively associated to Q4.1 (Table 5.54). Also, worse service was associated to Q4.3 (Table 5.57) and Q4.4 (Table 5.61). This finding indicates that services provided by CAV solutions should provide higher standards to balance this negative perception. Finally, perceived higher price is related to less willingness-to-pay (Table 5.59). Price of CAV services need to be competitive compared to conventional solutions in order to attract higher number of users.

5.5.4 The impact of participants' background

Table 5.66 presents the relationship of acceptance with gender. No significant correlations were found except for Q1.1. The “avoid” option of Q1.1 was removed to investigate if it was related to the significance of the result. Indeed, after removing this option from the analysis, the correlation between Q1.1 and gender changed to insignificant.

Table 5.66: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	1.433	0.231	99
Q4.2	Chi-Square	3.380	0.066	99

Q4.3	Chi-Square	0.337	0.845	89
Q4.4	Chi-Square	1.191	0.275	99
Q4.5	Chi-Square	6.647	0.036	99

Variable: Gender

The results in Table 5.67 suggested that male participants were more positive if members of their family used the technology. In the same direction, male participants were also more likely to perceive wider use of CAVs by the population as “great” and less likely to perceive it as “bad” (Table 5.68).

Table 5.67: The association of gender with Q4.2

		Gender		
		Female	Male	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	18	22
		Expected Count	13.7	26.3
	Yes	Count	16	43
		Expected Count	20.3	38.7

Table 5.68: The association of gender with Q4.5

		Gender		
		Female	Male	
Q4.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	7	28
		Expected Count	12.0	23.0
	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	7	5
		Expected Count	4.1	7.9
	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	20	32
		Expected Count	17.9	34.1

Table 5.69 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding commute frequency. No significant associations were found with any of the acceptance indicators.

Table 5.69: Commute frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	1.214	0.270	99
Q4.2	Chi-Square	1.524	0.217	99
Q4.3	Chi-Square	8.503	0.204	89
Q4.4	LR	0.530	0.912	99
Q4.5	Chi-Square	1.274	0.529	99

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 5.70 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding commute distance. No significant associations were found with any of the acceptance indicators.

Table 5.70: Commute distance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	2.868	0.412	99
Q4.2	Chi-Square	2.479	0.479	99
Q4.3	Chi-Square	0.417	0.812	89
Q4.4	Chi-Square	0.243	0.622	99
Q4.5	LR	4.287	0.638	99

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 5.71 shows the Chi-Square test results regarding user types of CAVs. No significant associations were found with any of the acceptance indicators.

Table 5.71: User type tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	0.723	0.697	92
Q4.2	Chi-Square	0.141	0.932	92
Q4.3	Chi-Square	2.598	0.627	83
Q4.4	LR	0.634	0.728	92
Q4.5	LR	5.376	0.251	92

Variable: User type

5.5.4.1 Confidence in CAVs

Confidence in CAVs had a significant correlation with several of the acceptance indicators (Table 5.72). This finding suggests that a sense of increased confidence needs to be developed to increase the use of the technology. The original response groups were “not confident at all”, “barely confident”, “medium confident” and “very confident”. The first of the aforementioned groups occurred only three times and was incorporated in the “barely confident” group.

Table 5.72: Confidence in CAVs tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Chi-Square	13.402	0.001	101
Q4.2	Chi-Square	5.108	0.078	101
Q4.3	Chi-Square	4.560	0.335	90
Q4.4	LR	2.275	0.517	101
Q4.5	LR	8.949	0.062	101

Variable: Confidence in CAVs

The results in Table 5.73 indicate that higher confidence in CAVs is linked to higher likelihood of providing a positive answer on intention to use after the pilot experience. Moreover, the same was observed with respect to the responses related to the use of the technology by family members (Table 5.74). Finally, confidence in CAVs might also be an indicator of public acceptance, as it was related to higher likelihood of perceiving mass adoption as “great” (Table 5.75).

Table 5.73: The association of confidence in CAVs with Q4.1

		CAV confidence			
		Barely or not confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	13	29	9
		Expected Count	9.6	23.7	17.7
	Yes	Count	6	18	26
		Expected Count	9.4	23.3	17.3

Table 5.74: The association of confidence in CAVs with Q4.2

		CAV confidence			
		Barely or not confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	10	22	9
		Expected Count	7.7	19.1	14.2
	Yes	Count	9	25	26
		Expected Count	11.3	27.9	20.8

Table 5.75: The association of confidence in CAVs with Q4.5

		CAV confidence			
		Barely or not confident	Medium confident	Very confident	
Q4.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs.	Count	4	15	17
		Expected Count	6.8	16.8	12.5

The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad.	Count	3	9	1
	Expected Count	2.4	6.0	4.5
The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good.	Count	12	23	17
	Expected Count	9.8	24.2	18.0

5.5.4.2 The impact of CAV services

CAV services refer to a series of CAV-related services that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available services as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these services could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.3 are outlined in Table 2.84. The significant results are presented in Table 2.85. The cross-tabulation tables of the significant results have been appended in Annex 1. The use of ride sharing services was positively associated to some of the acceptance indicators. Moreover, it should be mentioned that no experience with CAV services was negatively associated with acceptance.

Table 5.76: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Ride sharing	Chi-Square	2.859	0.091	101
	No CAV service experience	Chi-Square	3.159	0.075	101
Q4.2	Driver assistance	Chi-Square	3.082	0.079	101
	ACC	Chi-Square	3.026	0.082	101
Q4.3	Connected features	Chi-Square	5.712	0.057	101
Q4.5	Ride sharing	Chi-Square	5.615	0.060	101
	No CAV service used	LR	7.049	0.030	101

Variable: CAV services

5.5.4.3 The impact of CAV applications

CAV applications refer to a series of CAV-related applications that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available applications as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these applications could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.3 are outlined in Table 2.86. Only one significant relationship was found (Table 5.77), hence it may be concluded that CAV-related applications might not be the most suitable explanatory factors of acceptance.

Table 5.77: CAV applications tests

Variable	CAV application	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.1	Shared mobility	Chi-Square	2.866	0.090	101

Variable: CAV services

5.6 Data analysis – shuttle passengers

5.6.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

5.6.1.1 Feelings after the experience

This section presents the results related to the question “15 - How did you feel while traveling in a CAV?”, as presented in deliverable D6.2 (Annex I). The potential responses to that question were: Trustful, Careful, Insecure, Safe, Nervous, Curious, Critical and Unaffected. Participants could select yes or no for as many of the aforementioned feelings. Given that including both significant and insignificant results would result in tables of large size, only the former are presented in Table 5.78.

The results suggest that the “Trustful” response had the highest impact in terms of association to the acceptance indicators.

Table 5.78: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Trustful	Chi-Square	7.348	0.007	45
Q4.2.2	Insecure	LR	3.959	0.047	45
	Trustful	Chi-Square	6.253	0.012	45
Q4.2.3	Careful	LR	7.887	0.005	35
	Trustful	Chi-Square	5.600	0.018	35
Q4.2.4	Trustful	LR	5.104	0.024	45
Q4.2.5	Trustful	Chi-Square	9.489	0.009	45

Variable: Feelings

Table 5.79: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2.1

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	20	7
		Expected Count	15.6	11.4
	Yes	Count	6	12
		Expected Count	10.4	7.6

The insecure feeling had a significant relationship to Q4.2.2 (Table 5.80) however, due to the low number of responses regarding the positive answers this outcome needs to be treated with caution.

Table 5.80: The association of insecure feeling with Q4.2.2

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	22.4	1.6
	Yes	Count	21	0
		Expected Count	19.6	1.4

Table 5.81: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2.2

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	18	6
		Expected Count	13.9	10.1
	Yes	Count	8	13
		Expected Count	12.1	8.9

The findings with respect to Q4.2.3 which is related to WTP suggest different patterns compared to the other indicators of acceptance. In particular, scepticists (those willing to pay depending on the technology evolvement), were more likely to feel “careful” (Table 5.82) and less “trustful” (Table 5.83) during the experience. On the other hand the results suggest that participants not willing to pay also felt less “careful” and more “trustful” which is not consistent with previous findings. This pattern is likely to have occurred as a result of the WTP patterns as about half participants stated not willing to pay.

Table 5.82: The association of careful feeling with Q4.2.3

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.3	Depends on how technology evolves	Count	7	8
		Expected Count	10.7	4.3
	No	Count	18	2
		Expected Count	14.3	5.7

Table 5.83: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2.3

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.3	Depends on how technology evolves	Count	12	3
		Expected Count	8.6	6.4
	No	Count	8	12
		Expected Count	11.4	8.6

Table 5.84: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2.4

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	8	1
		Expected Count	5.2	3.8
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	18	18
		Expected Count	20.8	15.2

Table 5.85: The association of trustful feeling with Q4.2.5

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q4.2.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	3	9
		Expected Count	6.9	5.1
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad.	Count	5	5
		Expected Count	5.8	4.2
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	18	5
		Expected Count	13.3	9.7

5.6.1.2 Anticipation

Table 5.86 shows the results related to anticipation, and its association to CAV acceptance (“Q16 - Was using a CAV the experience you had anticipated?”, from D6.2). No significant results were found with respect to this variable

Table 5.86: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	0.424	0.515	34
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	0.071	0.790	34
Q4.2.3	LR	0.035	0.851	26
Q4.2.4	LR	0.596	0.440	34
Q4.2.5	LR	2.965	0.231	34

Variable: CAV anticipation

5.6.1.3 Comfort

Table 5.87 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding question “Q17 - Was the trip comfortable compared with a conventional vehicle?”, from deliverable D6.2.

Table 5.87: CAV comfort tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	LR	2.454	0.293	40
Q4.2.2	LR	4.011	0.135	40
Q4.2.3	LR	0.496	0.780	31
Q4.2.4	LR	6.084	0.048	40
Q4.2.5	LR	7.313	0.120	40

Variable: CAV comfort

The results in Table 5.88 suggest that participants who perceived the experience as more comfortable, compared to a human driver, were more likely to be willing to switch towards CAVs. However, this has been the only significant outcome with respect to perceived comfort.

Table 5.88: The association of comfort with Q4.2.5

		CAV comfort			
		Less comfortable	More comfortable	No different	
Q2.4.5	Not willing to	Count	2	1	4
	accept the effort	Expected Count	2.1	3.3	1.6
	Willing to accept	Count	10	18	5
	the effort.	Expected Count	9.9	15.7	7.4

5.6.1.4 CAV behaviour

Table 5.89 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding question “Q18 - How well do you think that the self-driving car performed regarding steering, acceleration and braking?”, from deliverable D6.2. No significant correlations were found with respect to this variable.

Table 5.89: CAV behaviour tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	LR	5.311	0.150	45
Q4.2.2	LR	5.292	0.152	45
Q4.2.3	LR	2.941	0.401	35
Q4.2.4	LR	0.510	0.912	45
Q4.2.5	LR	6.688	0.351	45

Variable: CAV behaviour

5.6.1.5 CAV reactions

Table 5.90 presents the significant Chi-Square test results regarding question “Q19 - How do you describe the self-driving car reactions?”, from deliverable D6.2. The question was implemented in a multiple choice manner hence, participants could select more than one from the available options. The latter were: very good; safe; neutral; unpredictable; and dangerous. The detailed cross-tabulation tables of the significant results have been appended in Annex 1.

Table 5.90: CAV reactions tests

Variable	Reaction	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Neutral	Chi-Square	7.951	0.005	45
Q4.2.2	Very good	LR	2.855	0.091	45
	Neutral	Chi-Square	7.188	0.007	45
Q4.2.4	Neutral	LR	3.600	0.058	45
Q4.2.5	Neutral	LR	9.819	0.007	45
	Unpredictable	LR	8.938	0.011	45

Variable: CAV reactions

The most noteworthy relationship in Table 5.89 regards the CAV reaction perceived as “neutral”. In particular, the latter was linked to a lower tendency of participants to provide a positive answer to the indicators of acceptance. This finding possibly further highlights that CAV will have to perform better compared to a human driver to be preferred, as equally good performance may not be perceived as sufficient by the users. In this direction, reactions perceived as “very good” had a significant positive relation with Q4.2.2

5.6.2 The impact of service difficulty to use

Table 5.91 shows the relationship between question “Q20 - How difficult did you find it to book and access the shared connected vehicle?” (D6.2) and the indicators of acceptance.

Table 5.91: Access difficulty tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	2.717	0.099	39
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	4.542	0.033	39
Q4.2.3	Chi-Square	0.027	0.870	31
Q4.2.4	LR	3.456	0.063	39
Q4.2.5	LR	3.496	0.174	39

Variable: Access difficulty

The results in Table 5.92 indicate that participants who did not find it difficult at all accessing the service were more likely to use it. On the other hand, the opposite finding occurred with respect to those who stated “not very difficult”.

Table 5.92: The association of access difficulty with Q4.2.1

		Access difficulty		
		Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	11	14
		Expected Count	13.5	11.5
	Yes	Count	10	4
		Expected Count	7.5	6.5

Similarly, Table 5.93 suggests that participants who did not find it difficult at all accessing the service were more positive if their relatives used it. The opposite outcome was found regarding the “not very difficult” response.

Table 5.93: The association of access difficulty with Q4.2.2

		Access difficulty		
		Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	8	13
		Expected Count	11.3	9.7
	Yes	Count	13	5
		Expected Count	9.7	8.3

Table 5.94 shows that patterns related to Q4.2.4 were similar to the previously reported outcomes. In particular, participants who did not find it difficult at all to access the service were more likely to be willing to accept the effort to switch towards the use of CAVs.

Table 5.94: The association of access difficulty with Q4.2.4

		Access difficulty		
		Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	2	6
		Expected Count	4.3	3.7
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	19	12
		Expected Count	16.7	14.3

5.6.3 The impact of perceived benefits and shortcomings on acceptance

5.6.3.1 Benefits

Perceived benefits refer to question “Q27 - Which potential benefits do you see in using a shared fleet composed of CAVs?” as presented in deliverable D6.2. Participants could select as many benefits as they preferred. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented in this section (Table 5.95).

Table 5.95: Perceived benefits tests

Variable	Benefit	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Lower prices	LR	6.486	0.011	45
Q4.2.2	Increased safety	Chi-Square	6.282	0.012	45
	Punctuality	Chi-Square	3.813	0.051	45
	Better price	Chi-Square	3.973	0.046	45
Q4.2.4	None	LR	3.659	0.056	45
Q4.2.5	Safety	LR	5.037	0.081	45

Variable: CAV benefits

Table 5.96 indicates that participants who expected lower prices were more likely to use the technology. This finding suggests the importance of price as an incentive.

Table 5.96: The association of lower prices with Q4.2.1

		Lower prices		
		0	1	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	24	3
		Expected Count	20.4	6.6
	Yes	Count	10	8
		Expected Count	13.6	4.4

Table 5.97 shows that participants who expected increased safety were more likely to be positive if a member of their family used a CAV. The importance of safety as a factor related to acceptance is validated in this case.

Table 5.97: The association of increased safety with Q4.2.2

		Increased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	14.9	9.1
	Yes	Count	9	12
		Expected Count	13.1	7.9

Table 5.98 reveals another interesting aspect, as increased punctuality was positively related to a supportive attitude towards members of the family using the technology. CAVs should be competitive compared to other conventional modes of transport, in order to be preferred, not only in terms of safety and security but also cost and travel time and punctuality.

Table 5.98: The association of increased punctuality with Q4.2.2

		Increased punctuality		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	15	9
		Expected Count	11.7	12.3
	Yes	Count	7	14
		Expected Count	10.3	10.7

Table 5.99 shows that decreased prices also had a significant correlation to Q4.2.2, further highlighting the relationship of this users' expectation with acceptance.

Table 5.99: The association of lower prices with Q4.2.2

		Lower prices		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	18.1	5.9
	Yes	Count	13	8
		Expected Count	15.9	5.1

Table 5.100 suggests that participants who did not perceive none of the benefits suggested in the survey as likely to occur were also less likely to be willing to switch towards CAVs. This finding shows the importance of promoting the benefits related to CAVs but also proving these in real life conditions.

Table 5.100: The association of no perceived benefits with Q4.2.4

		None		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing	Count	5	4
		Expected Count	7.2	1.8
	Willing to switch	Count	31	5
		Expected Count	28.8	7.2

Table 5.101 presents another example related to the importance of improved safety regarding the acceptance of CAVs. More specifically, increased safety as a perceived benefit was positively related to reporting mass adoption of CAVs as “good” or “great” while on the other hand, it was negatively related to the “bad” response.

Table 5.101: The association of increased safety with Q4.2.5

		Benefits_safety		
		0	1	
Q4.2.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	6	6
		Expected Count	7.5	4.5
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad.	Count	9	1
		Expected Count	6.2	3.8
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	13	10
		Expected Count	14.3	8.7

5.6.3.2 Shortcomings

Perceived benefits refer to question “Q25 - Which potential shortcomings do you see in using a shared fleet composed of CAVs?” as presented in deliverable D6.2. Participants could select as many shortcomings as they preferred. Given the high number of potential tests, only the significant results are presented in this section (Table 5.102).

Table 5.102: Shortcomings tests

Variable	Shortcoming	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Price	Chi-Square	2.732	0.098	45
Q4.2.2	Service	LR	3.959	0.047	45
	Information	LR	3.225	0.073	45
Q4.2.3	Information	LR	9.130	0.003	35
Q4.2.4	Service	LR	3.370	0.066	45
	Jobs	LR	5.341	0.021	45
	Safety	LR	3.659	0.056	45

Variable: CAV shortcomings

Table 5.103 shows that price perceived as a shortcoming is positively related with the intention to use. This finding is counter intuitive and given the marginal significance at the 0.1 level, it needs to be treated with caution.

Table 5.103: The association of increased price with Q4.2.1

		Increased price		
		0	1	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	20	7
		Expected Count	17.4	9.6
	Yes	Count	9	9
		Expected Count	11.6	6.4

Table 5.104 suggests that participants who are concerned for worse service are also less positive if their relatives used the technology. The finding needs to be treated with caution however, given the low values of observed counts in several categories.

Table 5.104: The association of worse service with Q4.2.2

		Worse service		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	22.4	1.6
	Yes	Count	21	0
		Expected Count	19.6	1.4

Table 5.105 indicates that participants who are concerned for less information onboard are also less positive if their relatives used the technology. The finding needs to be treated with caution however, given the low values of observed counts in several categories.

Table 5.105: The association of less information onboard with Q4.2.2

		Less information onboard		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	22	2
		Expected Count	19.7	4.3
	Yes	Count	15	6
		Expected Count	17.3	3.7

Table 5.106 indicates that participants who are concerned for less information on-board are also not willing to pay extra for the service. Despite the low values of observed counts in several categories, this finding might be an indication of the high expectations with respect to the quality of the service overall.

Table 5.106: The association of less information on-board with Q4.2.3

		Less information on-board		
		0	1	
Q4.2.3	Depends on how technology evolves	Count	15	0
		Expected Count	12.0	3.0
	No	Count	13	7
		Expected Count	16.0	4.0

Table 5.107 suggests that participants who are concerned for worse service are also less likely to accept the effort to switch to CAVs. However, the “positive” values have very low number of occurrences and the result needs to be treated with caution.

Table 5.107: The association of worse service with Q4.2.4

		Worse service		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	7	2
		Expected Count	8.4	.6
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	35	1
		Expected Count	33.6	2.4

Table 5.108 suggests the potential negative impacts of societal aspects of CAVs on acceptance. For instance, potential loss of jobs may act as a barrier towards accepting the effort to switch to CAVs.

Table 5.108: The association of loss of jobs with Q4.2.4

		Loss of jobs		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	3	6
		Expected Count	6.0	3.0
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	27	9
		Expected Count	24.0	12.0

The aspect of safety occurred in several occasions in Section 5.6.3.1. However, participants who expect negative safety issues as a result of CAVs, are also less likely to be willing to accept the effort to switch towards using these vehicles (Table 5.109)

Table 5.109: The association of decreased safety with Q4.2.4

		Decreased safety		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	5	4
		Expected Count	7.2	1.8
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	31	5
		Expected Count	28.8	7.2

5.6.4 The impact of participants' background

Table 5.110 presents the relationship of acceptance with gender. No significant correlations were found.

Table 5.110: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	2.252	0.133	43
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	2.386	0.122	43
Q4.2.3	Chi-Square	0.260	0.610	34
Q4.2.4	LR	0.657	0.418	43
Q4.2.5	LR	0.271	0.874	43

Variable: Gender

Table 5.111 presents the relationship of acceptance with income. No significant correlations were found.

Table 5.111: Income tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	0.259	0.611	33
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	0.259	0.611	33
Q4.2.3	Chi-Square	0.004	0.951	26
Q4.2.4	LR	0.515	0.473	33
Q4.2.5	LR	0.347	0.841	33

Variable: Income

Table 5.112 presents the relationship of acceptance with commute frequency. Significant correlations occurred with some of the acceptance indicators. In particular, significant results were found with respect to

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Q4.2.2 (Table 5.113), Q4.2.3 (Table 5.114) and Q4.2.4 (Table 5.115). The results with respect to the first and the latter of these indicators suggest that increased commute frequency is related to higher levels of acceptance. This could be an indication that competitive CAV services could be used more often by daily commuters. On the other hand, the results regarding Q4.2.3 suggest that daily commuters are not willing to pay extra for the service. This finding could be related to the implementation of the WTP variable (as discussed in Section 5.6.1.1) however, it may also be an indication that commuters are not willing to bear any extra cost for the regular use of the CAV services.

Table 5.112: Commute frequency

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	1.950	0.163	39
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	3.337	0.068	39
Q4.2.3	Chi-Square	6.099	0.014	32
Q4.2.4	LR	3.660	0.056	39
Q4.2.5	LR	0.098	0.952	39

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 5.113: The association of commute frequency with Q4.2.2

		Commute frequency		
		Not everyday	Everyday	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	10	12
		Expected Count	7.3	14.7
	Yes	Count	3	14
		Expected Count	5.7	11.3

Table 5.114: The association of commute frequency with Q4.2.3

		Commute frequency		
		Not everyday	Everyday	
Q4.2.3	Depends on how technology evolves	Count	9	6
		Expected Count	5.6	9.4
	No	Count	3	14
		Expected Count	6.4	10.6

Table 5.115: The association of commute frequency with Q4.2.2

		Commute frequency		
		Not everyday	Everyday	
Q4.2.4	Not willing to accept the effort	Count	5	3
		Expected Count	2.7	5.3
	Willing to accept the effort	Count	8	23
		Expected Count	10.3	20.7

Table 5.116 presents the relationship of acceptance with commute distance. No significant correlations were found.

Table 5.116: Commute distance

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	0.894	0.640	39
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	3.435	0.180	39
Q4.2.3	LR	2.371	0.306	32
Q4.2.4	LR	3.698	0.157	39
Q4.2.5	LR	4.663	0.324	39

Variable: Commute distance

Table 5.117 presents the relationship of acceptance with user types. No significant correlations were found.

Table 5.117: User type tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Chi-Square	0.443	0.801	40
Q4.2.2	Chi-Square	0.819	0.664	40
Q4.2.3	LR	2.264	0.322	32
Q4.2.4	LR	1.276	0.528	40
Q4.2.5	LR	2.446	0.654	40

Variable: User type

5.6.4.1 The impact of CAV services

CAV services refer to a series of CAV-related services that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available services as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these services could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.2 are outlined in Table 2.84. The significant results are presented in Table 5.118.

Table 5.118: CAV services tests

Variable	Service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q4.2.1	Ride sharing	Chi-Square	3.750	0.053	45
Q4.2.2	Bike sharing	LR	5.459	0.019	45
	Ride sharing	Chi-Square	6.429	0.011	45

Variable: CAV services

Similar to the case of CAV drivers (results presented in Section 5.5.4.2), ride sharing is the CAV services that resulted in significant results.

Table 5.119: The association of ride sharing service use with Q4.2.1

		Ride sharing		
		0	1	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	21	6
		Expected Count	18.0	9.0
	Yes	Count	9	9
		Expected Count	12.0	6.0

Table 5.120: The association of bike sharing service use with Q4.2.2

		Bike sharing		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	23	1
		Expected Count	20.3	3.7
	Yes	Count	15	6
		Expected Count	17.7	3.3

Table 5.121: The association of ride sharing service use with Q4.2.2

		Ride sharing		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	20	4
		Expected Count	16.0	8.0
	Yes	Count	10	11
		Expected Count	14.0	7.0

5.7 Data analysis – across pilot

5.7.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

5.7.1.1 Feelings after the experience

This section investigates the differences between the samples of drivers and passengers with respect to feelings after the experience. The significant results are presented in Table 5.122.

Table 5.122: Feelings tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Insecure	LR	0.653	0.419	147
Curious	Chi-Square	8.483	0.004	147
Safe	Chi-Square	3.183	0.074	147
Careful	Chi-Square	10.287	0.001	147
Trustful	Chi-Square	0.208	0.649	147
Nervous	Chi-Square	7.149	0.007	147
Critical	LR	0.947	0.331	147
Unaffected	LR	7.501	0.006	147

The results in Table 5.123 show that participants in the passenger condition were less likely to report a curious feeling compared to the driver condition.

Table 5.123: Curious feeling cross-tabulation

		Fleet	Shuttle		
Curious	0	Count	46	32	78
		Expected Count	54.1	23.9	78.0
	1	Count	56	13	69
		Expected Count	47.9	21.1	69.0

Table 5.124 suggests that participants in the driver condition (shared car fleet) were more likely to report safe, compared to the passenger condition. This could be an indication that the possibility of resuming manual control could increase perceived safety.

Table 5.124: Safe feeling cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Safe	0	Count	72	38
		Expected Count	76.3	33.7
	1	Count	30	7
		Expected Count	25.7	11.3

The results in Table 5.125 indicate that participants in the passenger (shuttle) condition were less likely to report a careful feeling compared to the driver condition.

Table 5.125: Careful feeling cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Careful	0	Count	41	31
		Expected Count	50.0	22.0
	1	Count	61	14
		Expected Count	52.0	23.0

The results in Table 5.126 suggest that participants in the passenger condition were less likely to report a nervous feeling compared to the driver condition.

Table 5.126: Nervous feeling cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Nervous	0	Count	83	44
		Expected Count	88.1	38.9
	1	Count	19	1
		Expected Count	13.9	6.1

Table 5.127 shows that participants in the driver condition less more likely to report unaffected, compared to the passenger condition.

Table 5.127: Unaffected feeling cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Unaffected	0	Count	101	40
		Expected Count	97.8	43.2
	1	Count	1	5
		Expected Count	4.2	1.8

5.7.1.2 Anticipation

As shown in Table 5.128, significant differences in the participants of the two studies were found with respect to their anticipation CAV experience. In particular, participants in the “drivers” condition were more likely to be positively surprised. A higher number of “I don’t know” responses was observed in the passengers’ experiment.

Table 5.128: CAV anticipation cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
CAV anticipation	I don't know	Count	5	10
		Expected Count	10.4	4.6
	It was as I expected	Count	33	15
		Expected Count	33.2	14.8
	Negatively surprised	Count	5	1
		Expected Count	4.2	1.8
	Positively surprised	Count	58	19
		Expected Count	53.3	23.7
	Chi-Square= 10.9741; p-value = 0.012; sample = 146			

5.7.1.3 Comfort

Table 5.129 indicates that significant differences were found regarding comfort. Participants in the drivers (fleet) experiment were more likely to perceive the experience as more comfortable, compared to a human driver. On the other hand, participants in the passengers experiment had higher response rates with respect to perceiving as less comfortable or responding “I don’t know”.

Table 5.129: CAV comfort cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
CAV comfort	I don't know	Count	4	5
		Expected Count	6.2	2.8
	Less comfortable	Count	10	12
		Expected Count	15.2	6.8
	More comfortable	Count	59	19
		Expected Count	54.0	24.0
	No different	Count	28	9
		Expected Count	25.6	11.4
	Chi-Square= 10.650; p-value = 0.014; sample = 146			

5.7.1.4 CAV behaviour

The results in Table 5.130 show that no significant differences occurred with respect to the perception of the CAV behaviour between the two pilot studies.

Table 5.130: CAV behaviour cross-tabulation

		Pilot			
			Fleet	Shuttle	
CAV behaviour	Better than the human driver	Count	18	6	
		Expected Count	16.6	7.4	
	Just different	Count	29	18	
		Expected Count	32.5	14.5	
	Same as the human driver	Count	33	10	
		Expected Count	29.7	13.3	
	Worse than the human driver	Count	21	11	
		Expected Count	22.1	9.9	
	Chi-Square= 2.957; p-value = 0.398; sample = 146				

5.7.1.5 CAV reactions

The Chi-Square test results regarding the reactions of the CAV are presented in Table 5.131. No significant differences were found regarding this variable.

Table 5.131: CAV reactions tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Very good	Chi-Square	0.815	0.367	147
Neutral	Chi-Square	0.003	0.955	147
Unpredictable	Chi-Square	0.004	0.949	147
Dangerous	LR	0.011	0.918	147
Safe	Chi-Square	0.046	0.831	147

5.7.2 The impact of perceived benefits and shortcomings on acceptance

5.7.2.1 Benefits

With respect to perceived benefits, some significant differences were found between the two cases (Table 5.132).

Table 5.132: Perceived benefits tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Increased safety	Chi-Square	6.648	0.010	147
Increased punctuality	Chi-Square	1.804	0.179	147
Reduced prices	Chi-Square	1.161	0.281	147
Time savings	Chi-Square	4.442	0.035	147
Better service	Chi-Square	0.955	0.328	147
Less congestion	Chi-Square	0.707	0.400	147
Less pollution	Chi-Square	6.397	0.011	147
None	Chi-Square	2.256	0.133	147

Table 5.133 suggests that participants in the driver condition were more likely to anticipate benefits from CAVs compared to participants in the passenger condition.

Table 5.133: Increased safety cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Increased safety	0	Count	40	28
		Expected Count	47.2	20.8
	1	Count	62	17
		Expected Count	54.8	24.2

As shown in Table 5.134, participants in the driver condition were less likely to expect time benefits compared to their counterparts in the passenger condition.

Table 5.134: Time savings cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Time savings	0	Count	60	18
		Expected Count	54.1	23.9
	1	Count	42	27
		Expected Count	47.9	21.1

Finally, participants in the driver condition were more likely to expect environmental benefits, compared to those in the passenger condition (Table 5.135).

Table 5.135: Less pollution cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Less pollution	0	Count	52	33
		Expected Count	59.0	26.0
	1	Count	50	12
		Expected Count	43.0	19.0

5.7.2.2 Shortcomings

Table 5.136 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding perceived shortcomings by the use of CAVs. More significant differences were found, compared to the case of perceived benefits.

Table 5.136: Perceived shortcomings tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Worse service	LR	0.490	0.484	147
Loss of jobs	Chi-Square	5.843	0.016	147
Less security	Chi-Square	3.028	0.082	147

Higher prices	Chi-Square	10.016	0.002	147
Less information onboard	Chi-Square	7.997	0.005	147
Decreased safety	Chi-Square	0.007	0.935	147
None	Chi-Square	6.121	0.013	147

As presented in Table 5.137, participants in the passenger condition were more likely to perceive loss of jobs as a shortcoming, compared to the participants in the driver condition.

Table 5.137: Loss of jobs cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Loss of jobs	0	Count	86	30
		Expected Count	80.5	35.5
	1	Count	16	15
		Expected Count	21.5	9.5

On the other hand, participants in the driver condition were more likely to report less security as a shortcoming (Table 5.138).

Table 5.138: Less security cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		41.00	42.00	
Less security	0	Count	81	41
		Expected Count	84.7	37.3
	1	Count	21	4
		Expected Count	17.3	7.7

In the same direction, participants in the driver condition were more likely to report higher prices as a shortcoming (Table 5.139).

Table 5.139: Higher prices cross-tabulation

				Pilot	
				Fleet	Shuttle
Higher prices	0	Count	37	29	
		Expected Count	45.8	20.2	
	1	Count	65	16	
		Expected Count	56.2	24.8	

With reference to Table 5.140, participants in the passenger condition were more likely to report less available information onboard as a shortcoming (Table 5.140).

Table 5.140: Less information onboard cross-tabulation

				Pilot	
				Fleet	Shuttle
Less information onboard	0	Count	98	37	
		Expected Count	93.7	41.3	
	1	Count	4	8	
		Expected Count	8.3	3.7	

Finally, participants in the passenger condition were more likely to provide the “none” response, compared to the participants in the driver condition (Table 5.141).

Table 5.141: No shortcomings cross-tabulation

				Pilot	
				Fleet	Shuttle
None	0	Count	88	31	
		Expected Count	82.6	36.4	
	1	Count	14	14	
		Expected Count	19.4	8.6	

5.7.3 Indicators of acceptance

The indicators of acceptance were examined via Chi-Squared tests for potential differences between the two pilots. The results of the tests did not show any significant difference. Hence, despite the differences

observed with respect to individuals' background and attitudes towards their experience in the pilot and CAVs overall, these did not affect the overall acceptance levels as reflected in questions presented in Sections 5.3.3 and 5.3.4.

Table 5.142: Q4.1 and Q4.2.1 cross-tabulation

			Pilot	
			Fleet	Shuttle
Q4.1 – Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	51	27
		Expected Count	54.0	24.0
	Yes	Count	50	18
		Expected Count	47.0	21.0
Chi-Square= 1.130; p-value = 0.288; sample = 146				

Table 5.143: Q4.2 and Q4.2.2 cross-tabulation

			Pilot	
			Fleet	Shuttle
Q4.2 - Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	41	24
		Expected Count	45.0	20.0
	Yes	Count	60	21
		Expected Count	56.0	25.0
Chi-Square= 2.045; p-value = 0.153; sample = 146				

Table 5.144: Q4.3 cross-tabulation (all groups)

			Pilot	
			Fleet	Shuttle
Q4.3 - Q4.2.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	33	15
		Expected Count	33.2	14.8
	I don't know	Count	11	5
		Expected Count	11.1	4.9
	No	Count	33	20
		Expected Count	36.7	16.3
	Yes	Count	24	5
		Expected Count	20.1	8.9
Chi-Square= 3.702; p-value = 0.295; sample = 146				

Table 5.145: Q4.3 cross-tabulation (analysis format)

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Q4.3 - Q4.2.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	33	15
		Expected Count	31.4	16.6
	No	Count	33	20
		Expected Count	34.6	18.4
Chi-Square= 0.468; p-value = 0.494; sample = 101				

Table 5.146: Q4.4 cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Q4.4 - Q4.2.4	Not willing to make the effort	Count	86	36
		Expected Count	84.4	37.6
	Willing to make the effort	Count	15	9
		Expected Count	16.6	7.4
Chi-Square= 0.601; p-value = 0.438; sample = 146				

Table 5.147: Q4.5 cross-tabulation

		Pilot		
		Fleet	Shuttle	
Q4.5 - Q4.2.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	36	12
		Expected Count	33.2	14.8
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad.	Count	13	10
		Expected Count	15.9	7.1
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	52	23
		Expected Count	51.9	23.1
Chi-Square= 2.492; p-value = 0.288; sample = 146				

5.8 Summary

5.8.1 Shared car fleet sub-pilot

The results regarding the shared car fleet pilot suggested that variables related to the performance of the CAVs led to more significant outcomes compared to difficulties in using the technology; no significant results were

found with respect to booking difficulty, use difficulty and return difficulty. In general, most participants did not face difficulties in using the technology. On the other hand, participants already had some experience using a shared car fleet hence increased familiarity could have affected the response patterns.

Performance of vehicle is highly relevant to acceptance both in terms of comfort (compared to conventional) and in terms of deviation from human driver behaviour. However, performance needs to be perceived as “more comfortable” compared to the conventional experience to ensure acceptance levels. Same, the performance of the vehicle needs to be better than a human driver, as any other outcome (including same as a human driver) may not suffice to ensure acceptance. Following the aforementioned discussion regarding performance, perceiving CAV reactions as “very good” was significantly related to acceptance. Moreover, “unpredictable” reactions were negatively related to acceptance. This finding highlights the importance of developing accurate mental models of behaviour and generate accurate expectations.

Acceptance was reflected within the perceived feelings during the pilot. In particular, significant outcomes regarding feeling trustful and nervous towards the technology occurred the most times, compared to other feelings. Other significant associations were found for careful, critical and insecure feelings. Results were consistent suggesting that emotions could be used as a valid tool to approximate acceptance.

Finally, some gender differences were found regarding acceptance with male participants being more positive towards CAVs. However, this was the only one of the typical individual characteristics that resulted in significant differences. Confidence in CAVs also had a significant relationship to acceptance. Accurate mental models and expectations regarding the behaviour of CAVs could improve trust, confidence and consequently acceptance.

5.8.2 Automated shuttle sub-pilot

With respect to passenger, trust was the feeling with the highest relevance to acceptance as it resulted in significant results with all acceptance indicators. However, not many other stated feelings were related to acceptance.

It is interesting that unlike the shared car fleet, the variables of anticipation and comfort and vehicle reactions did not result in any significant results.

On the other hand, difficulty in accessing the service might have a negative impact on acceptance. This is relevant to the ease-of-use issue.

Finally, among background characteristics, commute frequency resulted in some significant results. Daily commuters were more likely to use CAVs which might imply that these individuals are expecting benefits after the introduction of the technology. This finding highlights the need for specific incentives to attract this user group.

It is worth mentioning that the data between the two sub-pilots were investigated for potential differences. Despite the significant differences found in variables such as feelings or anticipation, the overall levels of acceptance did not differ between the two sub-pilots.

5.8.3 General conclusions and lessons learned

Almost all of the participants of the shared connected transport pilot travel each working day to their workplace, which is located over 15km away from their home. Most of the persons who participated in the pilot, drive by car to work. Therefore, it was even more of importance to present the participants the possibility of a shared connected transport service. A CAV service like a shared connected car fleet or an autonomous shuttle for their last-mile trip would allow the employees to use the shared services instead of using their own car. However, it needs to be considered that for now it would only be possible to use this service as an addition to the use of public transport or own car. Employees can use the shared car if they urgently need a car or have to do a business trip. The shuttle can be used as a last-mile transport mode, which connects in this case the working place with the train station 2km far away.

Considering the expectations and feelings of the participants during their drives, most of the participants who have over 10 years of driving experience, barely felt confident. Most of the participants indicated that they felt careful, followed by curious and trustful, while using the car and the autonomous shuttle. Based on the observations made during the trials, it can be added, that especially those participants who already have used a CAV before, were trustful and felt safe. Most of the drivers and passengers, however, felt positively surprised or as they expected.

When asked if the participants are willing to use CAVs and related services, more than half of the participants answered that they would be willing to use CAVs and a shared fleet composed of CAVs. However, also a lot of participants mentioned that their use will depend on how technology evolves. When asked if they would be willing to pay more, most

of the participants answered no or that it depends on the evolution of the technology.

These main learnings from the pilot allows shared fleet operators to adapt their offers and study the possibility to integrate new technologies and CAVs in their shared fleets. For car sharing operators, autonomous features can be associated with more safety or more comfort and thus represent an added value for their service offer. However, it needs to be considered, that users are not directly willing to pay more to use autonomous features. If the operator includes new technologies in his service offer, it also means that it must increase its budget for having a vehicle with autonomous features in the fleet of shared vehicles. These test drives allow the shared fleet operator Moovee and the transport operator Sales-Lentz to study their user's needs or potential new user's needs. It allows them to promote their services and improve their future services based on the opinions of the test drive users.

The next steps for LuxMobility, which was responsible for this pilot, is to provide an additional questionnaire to Campus Contern, which was one of the pilot study areas. This questionnaire will especially concentrate on how the employees commute to work and back home. With the results of the questionnaires, a mobility plan for this business campus (which hosts several companies) in Contern will be developed. This will also include the integration of CAV services in the mobility plan.

It is worth mentioning that although no significant differences were observed between the acceptance related questions between the shared car fleet and the shuttle pilots, participants of the former pilot were more positive towards accepting the technology. This finding is consistent with the outcomes within WP3. The large scale surveys conducted indicated that citizens are slightly more willing to use privately owned CAVs than shared or public CAVs and see them as more comfortable and efficient. This results in the need to make CAV shared service more attractive. Companies and public authorities should provide affordable and attractive alternatives to privately owned vehicles. Therefore, public campaigns and service providers need to highlight the advantages of shared solutions (e.g., no maintenance cost for users, no search for parking slots due to circulating systems, better utilization of each vehicle, reduced emissions). Once people become aware of the multiple ways shared CAVs could benefit our society, their attitude towards CAVs in general should become more positive. A shift to shared modes of transport would not only significantly reduce emissions (even when assuming about 11% more travel of CAVs to reach "next-in-line" travellers), but also reduce the costs

per trip significantly. It would decrease the perceived and self-reported stress for users. Affordable and flexible access to a vehicle should increase the acceptance for CAVs as a technology.

The use of public transport CAVs (instead of privately owned CAVs) could be more attractive with the implementation of CAVs and CAV services to serve first/last-mile connections to public transport in high demand areas, and to provide on-demand and door-to-door service in low demand areas. Shared CAV services should integrate instead of competing with public transport, including (CAV) bus and rail. Such integration can make CAV services more accessible for users, both in terms of service availability and cost, while also contribute to sustainable mobility. It can also help enhance public acceptance of CAVs and encourage people to try the CAV services. Ultimately, this can help enhance public transport service quality, stimulate patronage and revenue, and reduce car dependence. The implementation of such interventions is further discussed in WP8 of the PAsCAL project (D8.2 and D8.3), where the Guide2Autonomy framework and 100 recommendations and guidelines are documented.

6 Pilot 5: Experience of Vulnerable Travellers with Connected Transport Environment

6.1 Introduction

This last pilot focused on four distinct activities to gather the view, acceptance and potential of connected transport environments for vulnerable travellers:

1. Real-world testing of a connected mobile application (Apertum), which removes non-accessible stops from public transport itineraries and calculates a fully accessible route for users in Madrid (Spain);
2. UI/UX testing of the same application to assess its accessibility and usability in Madrid (Spain);
3. Stakeholder interviews with regional and municipal public transport operators and authorities to capture the commercial and operational potential of CAVs of Madrid (Spain);
4. Focus Discussion Groups (FDGs) with blind and partially sighted persons in collaboration with EBU's member UICI in Rome, Florence, Bologna and Naples (Italy).

Although in all of these pilot activities some kind of datapoints were gathered, the main dataset consists of the survey responses of the first activity, the real-world testing of Apertum.

In total, 165 persons participated in this activity alone, yielding the largest amount of data of the entire pilot. The data was collected via 3 separate pilot waves over the course of 3 months and included various different kinds of participants. On the one hand, a fixed percentage of users consisted of elderly citizens and disabled users and on the other hand of students, which were equipped with temporary mobility constraints (pushchairs, crutches, wheelchairs, heavy suitcases).

6.2 Data Collected

Within the pilot, 3 different kinds of quantitative datasets were collected during the execution of the pilot, which are presented below in designated sub-sections:

- Survey for Apertum users;
- Survey for UI/UX testers;
- Survey for FDG participants.

D7.3 – Data analysis of user acceptance from trials and simulations

Additionally, some qualitative information has been gathered and documented, such as Incidence Report Forms for each batch of participants, photos and video material. Two formal stakeholder interviews were also conducted. All qualitative data has been documented and analysed in detail in Deliverable D6.3 “Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

Finally, all participants signed a GDPR-compliant form to agree to the processing of the gathered datasets and also audio-visual materials gathered during the pilot execution. All datasets have been anonymised previous to the analysis of the datasets to ensure the protection of each individual’s privacy and identity. They also attended a briefing, which explained to them the objective of the research they are participating in.

6.2.1 Survey for Apertum users

This survey is the main focus of the analysis within this deliverable. Participants who tested the application themselves were asked to complete a survey of 24 questions. These questions were separated into 2 distinct categories (background and technical) and attributed a set of predetermined KPIs for universal comparability across all pilots. As previously mentioned, 165 participants completed this survey. The survey can be found in full in ANNEX II of deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”.

A descriptive analysis of this survey is included in the aforementioned deliverable of a previous WP of this project.

6.2.2 Survey for UI/UX testers

The UI/UX testing of the mobile application was conducted with 2 separate groups of testers with 10 persons per group. One of the groups consisted of only elderly participants, while the other consisted of students, in order to draw some meaningful conclusions from the testing for both digital nomads (persons who grew up without the use of digital technologies) and with reduced hand mobility and for digital natives.

The conclusions drawn from the testing can also be found in the aforementioned deliverable. The testing sample was too small to conduct a meaningful statistical analysis which could be included in this deliverable. The questionnaire consisted of 32 questions in total.

6.2.3 Survey for FDG participants

Although the main insight gathered from the FDGs lay in the open discussion about the participants’ hopes, fears, questions, concerns, ideas and contributions to the accessible design and conducting of CAVs, they also filled out a survey, which consisted of 33 questions and was completed by 51 participants.

6.3 Methodology

6.3.1 Analysis

The analysis conducted in the present chapter has taken the form of Chi-Square tests, cross-tabulation analysis, heat tables and figures. These processes have been documented in Sections 2.3.1, 4.3.2 and 4.3.3.

6.3.2 Indicators of acceptance

Table 6.1 presents the questions that were considered as indicators of CAV acceptance. Each question is assigned a code that is used for the remainder of the document for convenience. The code used in the original survey is included in brackets. The columns of *indicator category* and *indicator* were derived from “Deliverable 6.2 – Pilot Setup”. Due to the sample size-related issues and the low frequency in some of the responses, the latter were recoded, in order to improve the statistical power of the tests. The recoded groups are presented in Table 6.2.

Table 6.1: Indicators of acceptance

Code	Question	Indicator category (source: D6.2)	Indicator (source: D6.2)
Q5.1 (Q20)	Would you use connected transport applications in the future?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q5.2 (Q22)	Would you pay for using a connected transport environment?	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to pay

Q5.3 (Q23)	If CAVs were available to me, I would use it.	Indicators of acceptance by end users	Willingness to adopt
Q5.4 (Q24)	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use CAVs. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Indicators of society level acceptance	Public acceptance

Table 6.2: Original and recoded groups

Code	Original groups	Processed groups
Q5.1	Yes; No; I don't know;	Yes; Other than yes
Q5.2	< 5 €/month; 5-10 €/month; > 10 €/month	
Q5.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am willing to accept the effort to switch to CAVs (e.g. special courses). - The switch to CAVs is unacceptable. - I would not like to use CAVs - I would try to avoid CAVs as much as possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Willing to accept the effort - Not willing to accept the effort
Q5.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs. - The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad - The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good. 	No edits

6.4 Analysis

6.4.1 Safety and accessibility

The variable regarding safety distance corresponds to “Q10 - What distance do you feel safe to travel on your own?”. The potential responses in the raw data were <1 km, 1-3 km, 3-7 km and > 7 km. However, due to the responses pattern (135 out of 165 responded >7 km) and distribution, the variable was recoded to a dummy variable as ≤7 km and >7 km. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 6.3. Marginally significant results were observed only regarding Q5.2.

Table 6.3: Safety distance

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	3.757	0.053	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	2.954	0.086	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	2.118	0.347	165
Q5.4	LR	4.077	0.253	154

Variable: Safety distance

The results presented in Table 6.4 suggest that participants willing to use the technology are more likely to perceive safe distances up to 7 km. This finding could possibly imply that CAVs and other connected technologies might be considered more useful for shorter trips.

Table 6.4: The association between distance perceived safe and Q5.1

		Safety distance		
		Up to 7 km	7+ km	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	29	115
		Expected Count	26.2	117.8
	Other than yes	Count	1	20
		Expected Count	3.8	17.2

With reference to the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6.5, participants feeling safe at distances up to 7 km were more likely to use the technology if this was available. This pattern is similar to the one discussed regarding the results presented in Table 6.4.

Table 6.5: The association between distance perceived safe and Q5.2

		Safety distance		
		Up to 7km	7+ km	
Q5.2	Yes	Count	22	76
		Expected Count	17.8	80.2
	Other than yes	Count	8	59
		Expected Count	12.2	54.8

The variable of obstacle frequency was relevant to “Q14 - When using public transport for your urban trips, how often are you facing unexpected obstacles?”. Only one significant association was found with Q5.3 (Table 6.6).

Table 6.6: Obstacle frequency

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	13.147	0.004	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	1.423	0.700	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	11.333	0.079	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	2.945	0.400	154

Variable: Obstacle frequency

The cross-tabulation results in Table 6.7 show that individuals who reported obstacle frequency very often were more likely to be willing to use CAVs. On the other hand, the opposite was found for participants who reported that never face any obstacles.

Table 6.7: The association of obstacle frequency with Q5.1

		Obstacle frequency				
		Very often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	34	44	56	10
		Expected Count	30.5	42.8	55.9	14.8
	Other than yes	Count	1	5	8	7
		Expected Count	4.5	6.2	8.1	2.2

As presented in Table 6.8, a strange pattern occurred with respect to obstacle frequency and willingness-to-pay. In particular, participants facing obstacles very often were either more willing (than expected) to pay above 5 €/month or they were not willing to pay. The latter could potentially represent users’ disapproval for the current state of the infrastructure. On the other hand, those who responded “sometimes” or “rarely” were more willing to pay <5 €/month. However, the former was also more likely to pay

higher while the latter were not willing to pay. No considerable patterns were observed regarding the “never” group.

Table 6.8: The association of obstacle frequency with Q5.3

		Obstacle frequency				
		Very often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Q5.3	Not willing to pay	Count	22	22	34	10
		Expected Count	18.7	26.1	34.1	9.1
	< 5 Euros/ month	Count	4	18	24	5
		Expected Count	10.8	15.1	19.8	5.3
	> 5 Euros/ month	Count	9	9	6	2
		Expected Count	5.5	7.7	10.1	2.7

The network accessibility variable regards “Q15 - Do you think that the current transport network offers sufficient accessibility and information?”. Potential responses were totally sufficient, very sufficient, sufficient and not sufficient. No significant results were found with respect to this question (Table 6.9).

Table 6.9: Network accessibility

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	0.587	0.746	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	3.490	0.175	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	2.240	0.692	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	1.611	0.447	154

Variable: Network accessibility

The independence importance variable represented “Q16 - Is being able to travel independently important for you?”. The “I don’t know” response was removed from the current analysis given it only occurred twice.

Moreover, the “less” and “not” important groups were merged into the same group. As shown in Table 6.10, a significant association was observed with Q5.4.

Table 6.10: Independence importance

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	5.688	0.058	163
Q5.2	Chi-Square	3.414	0.181	163
Q5.3	LR	1.820	0.769	163
Q5.4	Chi-Square	13.941	<0.001	152

Variable: Independence importance

Table 6.11 shows the cross tabulation analysis results between the independence importance variable and Q5.1. The results suggested that individuals who consider independence as very important were more likely to be willing to use the technology.

Table 6.11: The association of independence importance with Q5.1

		Independence importance		
		Very important	Important	Less or not important
Q5.1 Yes	Count	95	37	10
	Expected Count	90.6	39.2	12.2
Other than yes	Count	9	8	4
	Expected Count	13.4	5.8	1.8

The cross-tabulation results presented in Table 6.12 suggest that individuals considering independent travelling as very important were also more likely to perceive mass use of CAVs as “great” while the other two groups were less likely (than expected) to respond, “very important” and lean towards some of the other categories.

Table 6.12: The association of independence importance with Q5.4

		Independence importance		
		Very important	Important	Less or not important
Q5.4 The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	21	17	9
	Expected Count	30.3	12.4	4.3
I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	77	23	5
	Expected Count	67.7	27.6	9.7

6.4.2 Independence CAV and time benefit

The CAVs independence represented “Q17 - Do you think that a connected transport environment will help you use public transport independently?”. The “I don’t know” responses were removed in the current comparison due to the low number of occurrences and uncertainty of interpretation. Any significant outcomes refer to the remaining response categories. As shown in Table 6.13, significant associations were found with Q5.1.

Table 6.13: Independence CAVs tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	9.463	0.009	160
Q5.2	LR	1.103	0.576	160
Q5.3	LR	3.186	0.527	160
Q5.4	LR	3.911	0.142	149

Variable: Independence CAVs

Table 6.14 shows that participants responded “yes” regarding the assistance on trip independence due to the connected environment were more likely to be willing to use the technology. This finding might suggest that heightened positive expectations related to independence might raise acceptance levels.

Table 6.14: Association between CAVs related independence and Q5.1

		Independence CAV			
		Yes	Partially	No	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	128	10	4
		Expected Count	123.4	14.2	4.4
	Other than yes	Count	11	6	1
		Expected Count	15.6	1.8	.6

The time benefit variable was related to “Q21 - Do you think these applications will save you time in your daily life?”. The “I don’t know” responses were removed in the current comparison due to the low number of occurrences and uncertainty of interpretation. The Chi-Square test results in Table 6.15 did not show any significant associations.

Table 6.15: Time benefit tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	26.563	<0.001	157
Q5.2	LR	1.153	0.562	157
Q5.3	LR	3.512	0.476	157
Q5.4	LR	2.718	0.257	147

Variable: Independence CAVs

Table 6.16 suggests that individuals who expect time benefits are more likely to be positive towards using the technology. Following the discussion regarding the results presented in Table 6.14, it might be the case that heightened positive expectations might be linked to higher acceptance levels.

Table 6.16: The association between time benefits and Q5.1

		Time benefit			
		Yes	Possibly	No	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	100	34	5
		Expected Count	90.3	41.6	7.1
	Other than yes	Count	2	13	3
		Expected Count	11.7	5.4	.9

6.4.3 Important information

The information variable represented “Q18 - Which information do you consider important in a connected trip?”. The aforementioned question had a multiple-choice format and participants could choose among any of the following:

- Station/stop information (accessibility level, elevator, distance to lane, etc.)
- Accessible routes inside stations
- Real-time information about arrivals
- Learn in advance if the station/stop is fully-accessible, partially accessible or non-accessible
- Routing adapted to the type of non-conventional user (e.g. maximum walking distance, etc.)

As shown in Table 6.17, significant associations were observed regarding Q5.1 (willingness to use) and Q5.3 (willingness-to-pay). It is worth mentioning that two of the potential types of information show in both Q5.1 and Q5.3 which might imply that they could be the most important to be considered to increase acceptance. Also, it might be the case that certain users could be willing to pay more to have specific type of information available.

Table 6.17: Information tests

Variable	Information	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Real time information	Chi-Square	2.891	0.089	165
	Stop in advance	Chi-Square	2.946	0.086	165
Q5.3	Info station	Chi-Square	7.626	0.022	165
	Accessible routes	Chi-Square	4.979	0.083	165
	Real time information	Chi-Square	5.004	0.082	165
	Stop in advance	Chi-Square	10.510	0.005	165

Variable: Feelings

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6.18 and Table 6.19 indicate that participants who consider as important real time information and in advance information about if next stop is fully accessible are more likely to use the technology. These findings consist of an indication regarding the information that should be provided by future automated transport system to enhance their acceptance.

Table 6.18: The association of station information with Q5.1

		Info real time		
		0	1	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	42	102
		Expected Count	45.4	98.6
	Other than yes	Count	10	11
		Expected Count	6.6	14.4

Table 6.19: The association of station information with Q5.1

		Info stop in advance		
		0	1	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	54	90
		Expected Count	57.6	86.4
	Other than yes	Count	12	9
		Expected Count	8.4	12.6

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis in Table 6.20 showed that those considered information about station/stop as important were more likely (than expected) to report WTP up to 5 €/month but less likely to report WTP a higher price.

Table 6.20: The association of station information with Q5.3

		Info station		
		0	1	
Q5.3	Not willing to pay	Count	24	64
		Expected Count	21.3	66.7
	< 5 Euros/ month	Count	6	45
		Expected Count	12.4	38.6
	> 5 Euros/ month	Count	10	16
		Expected Count	6.3	19.7

As shown in Table 6.21, information about accessible routes inside stations was considered as very important. In particular, participants were more likely to pay in order to have such information available than not being willing to pay.

Table 6.21: The association of accessible routes information with Q5.3

		Info accessible routes		
		0	1	
Q5.3	Not willing to pay	Count	41	47
		Expected Count	34.1	53.9
< 5 Euros/ month		Count	16	35
		Expected Count	19.8	31.2
> 5 Euros/ month		Count	7	19
		Expected Count	10.1	15.9

The cross-tabulation results with respect to real time information about arrivals (Table 6.22) showed a similar pattern to station/stop information. More specifically, participants were more likely to report WTP up to 5 €/month and less likely to report WTP a higher price.

Table 6.22: The association of accessible routes information with Q5.3

		Info real time		
		0	1	
Q5.3	Not willing to pay	Count	29	59
		Expected Count	27.7	60.3
< 5 Euros/ month		Count	11	40
		Expected Count	16.1	34.9
> 5 Euros/ month		Count	12	14
		Expected Count	8.2	17.8

Finally, some similar WTP were found regarding in advance station/stop accessibility information (Table 6.23). However, the difference between expected and observed counts regarding the “not willing to pay” response was more obvious here suggesting that this type of information is expected to be provided without any additional cost.

Table 6.23: The association of in advance stop information with Q5.3

		Info stop in advance		
		0	1	
Q5.3	Not willing to pay	Count	43	45
		Expected Count	35.2	52.8
	< 5 €/ month	Count	11	40
		Expected Count	20.4	30.6
	> 5 €/ month	Count	12	14
		Expected Count	10.4	15.6

6.4.4 The impact of participants’ background

The association between gender and acceptance related questions was investigated via a series of Chi-Square tests. The results presented in Table 6.24 did not indicate any significant correlations.

Table 6.24: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	1.785	0.182	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	0.060	0.807	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	2.109	0.348	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	0.038	0.846	154

Variable: Gender

Although results with respect to gender were insignificant, it is possible to derive useful conclusions via heat table analysis. For instance, focusing on Q5.1 (Q23 in the original survey) “If Apertum were available to me, I would use it.” The original available responses were “I am willing to accept the effort to switch to Apertum (e.g. special courses).”, “The switch to Apertum is unacceptable.”, “I would not like to use Apertum.”, “I would try to avoid Apertum as much as possible.”. This question is correlated to the gender of the participants, which were divided into 4 separate options (“female”, “male”, “other” and “prefer not to say”). The Chi-Square test is not significant however, the exact distribution is documented in the Table 6.25 in the form of a heat table.

Table 6.25: Heat table for correlation between gender and willingness to adopt CAVs

Gender	I'm willing to accept an effort to switch to CAVs	The switch to CAVs is unacceptable	I don't want to use a CAV	I avoid the CAV as much as I can
Female	33.9%	0.0%	1.8%	22.6%
Male	25.5%	1.8%	1.8%	14.5%

This table shows that both men and women are very polarized when it comes to their willingness to accept the switch to CAV technologies. Overall, the participants were more open to dedicating some effort for the switch, but many also said that they would try to avoid switching to CAVS as much as they can.

Women are overall very slightly more willing to accept some kind of effort to switch to CAVs than men.

It is important to note that the participants group consisted of slightly more women than men (46.4% women, 43.6% male) and no persons who declared identifying as another gender or preferred not to declare their gender.

The possible answers to question 22 of the survey “Would you pay for using a connected transport environment?” were “I would not pay for this kind of service.”, “<5€ per month.”, “5€ to 10€ per month.”, “>10€ per month.”. This question is correlated to the gender of the participants, which were divided into 4 separate options (“female”, “male”, “other” and “prefer not to say”). The chi-squared test of 165 values rendered a p-value of

0.102. With 3 degrees of freedom and a calculated chi-square value of 6.2, the critical value of 6.251 is not reached, meaning that the data fit the model and the null hypothesis is not rejected. The exact distribution is documented in the table below.

Table 6.26: Heat table for correlation between gender and willingness to pay

Gender	I would not pay	<5€ per month	5€ to 10€ per month	>10€ per month
Female	27.9%	20.0%	6.1%	2.4%
Male	25.5%	10.9%	7.3%	0.0%

Although both men and women reported that mostly they would not want to pay for connected transport environments, the responses of those willing to vary vastly. In total, 28.5% of women reported being willing to pay for the service and only 18.2% of men (regardless of the amount they are willing to pay).

It seems that overall, the willingness to pay for connected transport environments is higher with women than men, though there is little difference in the amount of money they are willing to spend. A monthly amount of less than 5€ seems ideal to monetise this kind of service effectively and capture the largest market share.

Table 6.27 presents the Chi-Square test results regarding the relationship between income and acceptance related questions. A significant outcome occurred with Q5.4.

Table 6.27: Income tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	9.581	0.022	129
Q5.2	Chi-Square	4.325	0.228	129
Q5.3	LR	2.772	0.837	129
Q5.4	Chi-Square	13.602	0.004	119

Variable: Income

Table 6.28 suggests that only participants earning 1000-2000 €/month are more likely (than the expected values) to use the technology. However, given the low number of occurrences in the “other than yes” group combined with the high number of group categories in the income variable, it is difficult to obtain a definite meaningful interpretation.

Table 6.28: The association of income with Q5.1

		Income			
		Less than 250 €/month	250-1000 €/month	1000-2000 €/month	2000+ €/month
Q5.1 Yes	Count	38	36	30	9
	Expected Count	39.4	34.2	27.2	12.3
Other than yes	Count	7	3	1	5
	Expected Count	5.6	4.8	3.8	1.7

Table 6.29 suggests that lower income groups were more likely to perceive mass adoption of CAVs as great. However, it is difficult to derive any further certain conclusions based on the observed patterns.

Table 6.29: The association of income with Q5.4

		Income			
		Less than 250 €/month	250-1000 €/month	1000- 2000 €/month	2000+ €/month
Q5.4 The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	9	10	7	9
	Expected Count	12.1	10.9	8.5	3.5
I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	32	27	22	3
	Expected Count	28.9	26.1	20.5	8.5

Table 6.30 presents the Chi-Square test results related to frequency of CAV use. The significant results were further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 6.30: CAV frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	10.923	0.012	130
Q5.2	Chi-Square	1.614	0.657	130
Q5.3	Chi-Square	6.188	0.402	130
Q5.4	Chi-Square	2.765	0.429	123

Variable: CAV frequency

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6.31 show that individuals who have systematically used CAVs may be more willing to use the technology. This finding could suggest that experience is a factor that positively contributes to acceptance.

Table 6.31: The association of CAV frequency of use with Q5.1

		CAV frequency			
		Only once	Rarely	Occasionally	Systematically
Q5.1 Yes	Count	13	29	41	30
	Expected Count	14.8	31.3	40.9	26.1
Other than yes	Count	4	7	6	0
	Expected Count	2.2	4.7	6.1	3.9

Table 6.32 and Table 6.33 present the Chi-Square test results with respect to the association of commute frequency and commute distance with acceptance related questions respectively. No significant results were found regarding these two variables.

Table 6.32: Commute frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	4.154	0.125	120
Q5.2	Chi-Square	2.829	0.243	120

Q5.3	Chi-Square	3.202	0.525	120
Q5.4	Chi-Square	2.027	0.363	113

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 6.33: Commute distance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	2.533	0.469	120
Q5.2	Chi-Square	2.741	0.433	120
Q5.3	Chi-Square	7.508	0.276	120
Q5.4	Chi-Square	0.401	0.940	113

Variable: Commute distance

Table 6.34 presents the results of the Chi-Square tests related to the relationship between acceptance and mode choice. Given the low number of responses, the “walking” and “other” categories were removed from the analysis. Hence, the results refer to private car, bus and subway.

Table 6.34: Mode choice tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	2.728	0.256	151
Q5.2	Chi-Square	5.760	0.218	151
Q5.3	Chi-Square	0.379	0.827	151
Q5.4	Chi-Square	0.120	0.942	140

Variable: Mode choice

Table 6.35 shows the results regarding the frequency of use public transport. Only one significant relationship was found with Q5.2.

Table 6.35: PT use frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	2.428	0.489	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	13.548	0.035	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	0.616	0.893	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	0.858	0.836	154

Variable: PT use frequency

Table 6.36 presents the cross-tabulation analysis regarding the relationship of frequency of public transport use with Q5.2 (related to willingness-to-pay). The differences between observed and expected outcomes were minor regarding the > 5 €/month group; main differences are observed with respect to the “not willing to pay” and < 5 €/month group. In particular, participants who reported “never” or use less than once a week were more likely to pay. This could be an indication that these individuals might be willing to pay due to the low frequency of use. On the other hand, individuals who use public transportation on a weekly basis might be less likely to be willing to pay.

Table 6.36: The association of public transport frequency of use with Q5.2

		PT use frequency			
		Less than once a week	1-2 times a week	Daily	Never
Q5.2 Not willing to pay	Count	20	38	22	8
	Expected Count	24.5	30.9	21.3	11.2
< 5 Euros/ month	Count	17	11	11	12
	Expected Count	14.2	17.9	12.4	6.5
> 5 Euros/ month	Count	9	9	7	1
	Expected Count	7.2	9.1	6.3	3.3

6.4.4.1 Trust in CAVs

The Chi-Square tests regarding the association of trust in CAVs with acceptance related questions did not result in any significant outcomes (Table 6.37).

Table 6.37: CAV trust

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Chi-Square	0.446	0.800	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	1.264	0.531	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	2.673	0.614	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	2.782	0.249	154

Variable: CAV trust

6.4.4.2 Scenario and group

The relationship of scenarios with acceptance related questions was investigated via a series of Chi-Square tests (Table 6.38). The four scenarios have been presented in deliverable D6.2 – Pilot Setup. A significant correlation was found with Q5.4.

Table 6.38: Scenario

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	3.720	0.293	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	4.325	0.228	165
Q5.3	Chi-Square	2.147	0.906	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	6.667	0.083	154

Variable: Scenario

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6.39 suggest that participants in scenario 4 were more likely to perceive mass

adoption of CAVs while the opposite was found for scenario 1 hence showing higher levels of public acceptance.

Table 6.39: The association of scenario with Q5.4

		Scenario ID			
		1	2	3	4
Q5.4 The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	18	13	13	3
	Expected Count	14.0	14.0	11.0	7.9
I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	28	33	23	23
	Expected Count	32.0	32.0	25.0	18.1

Except for the correlations with scenario, the correlations with group type were also investigated through Chi-Square tests (Table 6.40). The significant associations were further investigated with cross-tabulation analysis. The three user groups were elderly persons (ELD) above 65 years old, persons with Temporary Mobility Constraints (TMC) and persons with Spinal Cord Injuries (SCI).

Table 6.40: Group

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	LR	1.103	0.612	165
Q5.2	Chi-Square	4.803	0.091	165
Q5.3	LR	1.827	0.767	165
Q5.4	Chi-Square	11.543	0.003	154

Variable: Group

With reference to Table 6.41 participants in ELD group were more likely to use the technology. The opposite was found for participants in the SCI group while no major differences were observed with respect to participants of the TCM group.

Table 6.41: The association of group with Q5.2

		User group		
		ELD	TCM	SCI
Q5.2 Yes	Count	23	62	13
	Expected Count	18.4	63.0	16.6
Other than yes	Count	8	44	15
	Expected Count	12.6	43.0	11.4

The results presented in Table 6.42 indicate that participants in the ELD group were more likely to perceive mass use of CAV as “good” while those of the SCI group as great. This finding is not consistent with the results presented in Table 6.41 about intention to use. Hence, no safe conclusions can be derived with respect to the relationship between acceptance and group type. However, given that both concepts presented in Table 6.42 are positive (either good or great), hence participants’ interpretation of the question might have been affected.

Table 6.42: The association of group with Q5.4

		User group		
		ELD	TCM	SCI
Q5.4 The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	15	29	3
	Expected Count	8.5	30.5	7.9
I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	13	71	23
	Expected Count	19.5	69.5	18.1

6.4.4.3 The impact of CAV services

CAV services refer to CAV-related services or functionalities that participants may have experienced or not. Participants could select as many of the available services as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these services could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The full description of the services as presented in deliverable D6.3 are outlined in Table 6.43.

Table 6.43: CAV services considered in the survey

CAV services
Navigation & routing services (GoogleMaps, Waze,...)
Vehicle sharing services (ShareNow, Zity, Lime, BiciMAD,...)
Ride-sharing (Uber, Cabify, taxi apps,...)
Carpooling (BlaBlaCar, Leadmee,...)
Connected features (next stop indicator in buses,...)
Driver assistance (speed limit indicator, blind spot detection, lane assist,...)
Adaptative cruise control (the vehicle controls the speed according to traffic)
Automatic steering (autonomous parking or vehicle keeping itself in lane)
I don't know
I have never tried a CAV before

Table 6.44 presents the significant results of the Chi-Square tests with respect to CAV services for all acceptance related questions. Only two significant relationships were found. The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6.45 and Table 6.46 indicates that although ridesharing was positively related to willingness to use, the opposite was found regarding willingness to use upon availability and experience with ACC. Hence, unlike previous examples the results with respect to CAV services are inconclusive.

Table 6.44: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Ridesharing	Chi-Square	4.637	0.031	165
Q5.2	ACC	Chi-Square	4.557	0.059	165

Variable: CAV services

Table 6.45: The association of ridesharing use with Q5.1

		Ridesharing		
		0	1	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	81	63
		Expected Count	85.5	58.5
	Other than yes	Count	17	4
		Expected Count	12.5	8.5

Table 6.46: The association of ACC use with Q5.2

		ACC		
		0	1	
Q5.2	Yes	Count	93	5
		Expected Count	89.7	8.3
	Other than yes	Count	58	9
		Expected Count	61.3	5.7

6.4.4.4 CAV applications

CAV applications refer to a series of CAV-related applications that participants may have used or not. Participants could select as many of the available applications as they preferred. It is expected that higher level of use of these applications could be related to higher levels of acceptance. The significant results of the Chi-Square tests are presented in Table 6.47. A significant association was found only regarding routing and guidance applications with Q5.1 and Q5.4. The respective cross-tabulation analysis outlined in Table 6.48 and Table 6.49 suggests a positive relation between the use of routing and guidance applications with the acceptance related questions.

Table 6.47: CAV services tests

Variable	CAV service	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q5.1	Routing and guidance	Chi-Square	3.702	0.054	165
Q5.4	Routing and guidance	Chi-Square	4.658	0.031	154

Variable: CAV services

Table 6.48: The association of routing and guidance application use with Q5.1

		Routing guidance		
		0	1	
Q5.1	Yes	Count	39	105
		Expected Count	42.8	101.2
	Other than yes	Count	10	11
		Expected Count	6.2	14.8

Table 6.49: The association of routing and guidance application use with Q5.4

		Routing guidance		
		0	1	
Q5.4	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	19	28
		Expected Count	13.4	33.6
	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	25	82
		Expected Count	30.6	76.4

6.4.5 Further analysis of acceptance predictors

The variables related to acceptance have been already documented and analysed in Deliverable “D6.3 – Pilot implementation and evaluation”. On top of the aforementioned analysis, it might be useful to further investigate these variables to better understand the relationship between factors affecting acceptance factors and derive further insights. Some of the most interesting relationships are presented in the current section. The codes in brackets refer to those used in D6.3.

6.4.5.1 Gender (Q1) and perceived effectiveness of CAVs (Q17)

The possible answers to question 22 of the survey “Do you think that a connected transport environment will help you use public transport independently?” were “Yes.”, “Partially.”, “No.”, “I don’t know.”.

This question is highly correlated to the gender of the participants, which were divided into 4 separate options (“female”, “male”, “other” and “prefer not to say”).

The chi-squared test of 165 values rendered a p-value of 0.996. With 3 degrees of freedom and a calculated chi-square value of 0.0573, the critical value of 6.251 is not reached, meaning that the data fit the model and the null hypothesis is not rejected. The exact distribution is documented in the table below.

Table 6.50: Heat table for correlation between gender and perceived effectiveness to increase autonomy of mobility

Gender	Yes	Partially	No	I don't know
Female	47.3%	5.5%	1.8%	1.8%
Male	37.0%	4.2%	1.2%	1.2%

It is striking that most persons believe that an enhanced connected transport environment can help them to travel with increasing levels of independence. Women seem to be the most convinced of being able to profit from this change and most in favour of adopting connected offers.

6.4.5.2 Age (Q2) and confidence in the CAV technologies (Q6)

The possible answers to question 2 of the survey “What is your age?” were “≤25.”, “25 to 64.”, “≥65.”.

This question is correlated to question 6 of the survey, asking the participants how much they trust CAVs (“No trust at all.”, “Barely trusting.”, “Medium trusting.” and “Very trusting.”).

The chi-squared test of 165 values rendered a p-value of 0.695. With 6 degrees of freedom and a calculated chi-square value of 3.87, the critical value of 4.314 is not reached, meaning that the data fit the model and the null hypothesis is not rejected. The exact distribution is documented in the table below.

Table 6.51: Heat table for correlation between age and confidence in CAV technologies

Age	No trust at all	Barely trusting	Medium trusting	Very trusting
≤25	2.4%	3.6%	33.9%	16.4%
25 to 64	0.6%	1.2%	12.7%	9.7%
≥65	1.2%	1.8%	8.5%	7.9%

In this analysis it is interesting to see that young people seem to be significantly more trusting than middle aged or elderly participants. The trust reduces over age and the difference between the categories “medium trusting” and “very trusting” become less striking:

- In the youngest age group, only 48.37% (approximately half) of the number of persons who reported being “medium trusting” reported feeling “very trusting”. There seemingly is a big difference between these two responses in this age group.
- On the other hand, the same analysis for middle aged persons shows a more balanced response pattern with 76.38% of those responses applied to “very trusting”;
- In the elderly age group, the difference is basically unnoticeable. With 92.94%, almost the same amount of people reported feeling medium than very trusting.

6.4.5.3 *Kinds of mobile applications used (Q12b) and frequency of encountering obstacles (Q14)*

Question 12b of the survey asked the participants whether they are using different kinds of mobile applications (“No I don’t.”, “Public transport application.”, “Routing and guidance application.”, “Shared mobility application.”).

This question is correlated to question 14 of the survey, asking the participants how often they encounter obstacles in the public transport system (“Very often.”, “Sometimes.”, “Rarely.” and “Never.”).

Since the participants were able to choose more than just one mobile application they are using, a chi-squared analysis is not possible since the same value can appear more than once.

Figure 6.1: Graph displaying the kind of mobile applications used today and the frequency of encountering obstacles

This is of course the basis of an intuitive assumption: Persons who never encounter obstacles in public transport probably don't use any kind of public transport or shared services (or at least not frequently).

Those who use public transport and routing and guidance applications (by far the most common answers) reported encountering obstacles much more often, though the level of these answers subsides with the frequency of encountering obstacles.

Interestingly, this same pattern cannot be observed for persons who use shared mobility applications or no applications at all.

6.4.5.4 Satisfaction with current accessibility information (Q15) and perceived effectiveness of CAV technologies (Q17)

Question 15 of the survey asked participants about their overall satisfaction with the quality and amount of accessibility information available today in the current transport system. They were able to rate their satisfaction by "Totally sufficient.", "Very sufficient.", "Sufficient." and "Not sufficient."

This question is correlated to question 17 of the survey, asking the participants whether it would help them to use public transport independently ("Yes.", "Partially.", "No." and "I don't know.").

The chi-squared test of 165 values rendered a p-value of 0.695. With 9 degrees of freedom and a calculated chi-square value of 13.1, the critical value of 14.684 is not reached, meaning that the data fit the model and the null hypothesis is not rejected. The exact distribution is documented in the table below.

Table 6.52: Heat table for correlation between the perceived sufficiency of accessibility information available today and perceived adequacy of CAVs to raise the autonomy of mobility

Satisfaction	Yes, I would travel more independently	Partially	No, I would not travel more independently	I don't know
Totally sufficient	1.8%	1.2%	0.6%	0.0%
Very sufficient	15.8%	1.8%	1.2%	0.0%
Sufficient	32.7%	3.0%	0.0%	1.8%
Not sufficient	33.9%	3.6%	1.2%	1.2%

While the vast majority of all participants believe that they would be able to travel more independently with in a connected transport environment and with more accessibility information at hand, within this group the opinions of the quality and availability of the current information is extremely polarised. Almost the same number of persons reported feeling that the current information is sufficient than those who said it is not sufficient.

It is clear however, that with 40% not thinking that the current information is sufficient and “only” 60% believing the opposite, action is needed to ensure that all public transport users can travel safely and comfortably without help.

6.5 Summary

Although the conclusions of the descriptive analysis of this dataset can be found in the previous deliverable D6.3 of WP6 of the PAsCAL project, some interesting insights can be gathered from this data analysis.

With respect to the distance considered as safe to travel, it was found that acceptance levels were higher when the former was up to 7 km. This outcome could be an indication that CAVs and connected transport environment might be considered more useful for shorter trips.

Obstacle frequency was significantly correlated to two of the acceptance related questions (willingness to use and willingness to pay). These acceptance indicators were positively related to obstacle frequency; individuals who reported obstacle frequency very often were more likely to be willing to use connected environment technologies. However, it is interesting that participants facing obstacles very often were not only more willing (than expected) to pay more but also not willing to pay at all. The latter could potentially indicate disapproval for the current state of the infrastructure.

Individuals perceiving independence when travelling as important were more likely to be willing to use connected transport technologies and have higher public acceptance levels.

Independence and time benefits related to CAV technologies were significantly correlated only with willingness to use (among the four indicators of acceptance). The results suggested a positive association in both cases.

Also, among the information considered as necessary, significant associations were observed only with intention to use (5.1) and WTP (5.3) questions. Real-time information about arrivals and in advance if the station/stop is fully accessible were significant in both cases, suggesting that these could be some of the most important information related to acceptance levels.

Regarding individuals' background, no significant results were found regarding gender, commute frequency, commute distance, and trust in CAVs, while the significant outcomes related to income were also inconclusive. Systematic CAV frequency of use was positively related only with intention to use, among the indicators of acceptance.

Also, some significant results were found regarding participants' group. More specifically, individuals in group 1 were more likely to use the technology. The opposite was found for participants in group 3, while no major differences were observed with respect to participants of group 2. Also, individuals in group 1 were more likely to have higher levels of public acceptance compared to group 3.

On top of the statistical analysis, the analysis of the qualitative data could provide further insights with respect to acceptance. Gender may play a considerable role when it comes to the acceptance of CAV technologies, particularly in the way they are used, priced and deployed. During the discussions and conversations, we held with more than 200 persons (the majority of them being women), it became clear that women (whether disabled or not) feel much more receptive towards CAVs than men overall. This is due to an underlying feeling of uneasiness and insecurity when using public or shared mobility as it is today. The perspective of making more informed travel decision and/or traveling in autonomous vehicles represents for women an alternative in their autonomy of travel.

Another finding that has also been reflected through the descriptive and qualitative analysis of the pilot documentation in the previously mentioned deliverable is that some persons “flee” public transport. This can be because they are getting older, have disabilities, feel unsafe in public transport or simply change their lifestyle (e.g., having children). What all of these have in common is that the more obstacles people encounter, the more likely they are to revert to private means of transport. It is therefore in the interest of society as a whole to avoid obstacles where possible and warn users ahead of time in case an obstacle is detected.

Finally, a whopping 40% of respondents believe that the current accessibility information is not sufficient and that simply having more information would help them to move more independently. This is a striking indication of the importance of additional and more detailed accessibility information and more importantly the high effectiveness this has.

7 Cross-Pilot Analysis

7.1 Introduction

In the previous chapters, acceptance of CAVs was evaluated via a series of questions, and the relevance of the latter to variables such as feelings, anticipation, vehicle performance, difficulty to use, users' background and others. However, it was not investigated whether the trends around acceptance share some common elements across pilots. To that end, the objective of the current chapter is to present some analysis that simultaneously considers data from different pilots. Two different cases were investigated. That is, there was an attempt to consider pilots that used relatively similar transport modes. In particular, Pilots 1 and 3 were treated as one case since in both experiments a public transportation mode was used (bus in pilot 1 and shuttle in pilot 3). In a similar manner, pilots 2 and 4 (sub-pilot 1) were considered as another case, given that in both pilots passenger cars were used (although the main objective of the two pilots differed). It should be highlighted that for the cross-pilot analysis only identical variables or variables with close relevance across pilots were considered. Hence, omitted variables that were available in individual datasets are not excluded as potential "global" common factors related to acceptance; however, their suitability was not feasible to be examined in the context of the present analysis.

The cross-pilot analysis followed two main steps:

- a) The difference between all common variables was investigated between the two pilots. This analysis was conducted via a series of Chi-Square tests and pilot was used as one of the two variables in each test.
- b) The relationship of acceptance-related variables to other variables collected as part of the surveys was investigated via a Chi-Square test, combining data from multiple pilots. If a significant result was found, it was not directly assumed that there was a cross-pilot correlation between these two variables, as significance might have arisen due to pilot related differences. To account for the latter, a logit model was also estimated following a significant Chi-Square test result. The logit models had an acceptance related question as dependent variable with a significant Chi-Square test. The other variable together with a dummy variable that represented the pilot differences were used as independent variables. If the parameter related to the explanatory variable was significant in the logit model

when the pilot related dummy variable was also included, it was assumed that the former could be treated as a “universal” factor that affects a specific acceptance related outcome.

7.2 Public transport CAVs (Pilot 1 and Pilot 3)

7.2.1 The impact of pilot

7.2.1.1 Feelings after the experience

Table 7.1 outlines the Chi-Square test results with respect to feelings after the experience. The significant results are further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 7.1: Feelings and pilots tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Insecure	LR	4.706	0.030	202
Curious	Chi-Square	3.824	0.051	202
Safe	Chi-Square	1.381	0.240	202
Trustful	Chi-Square	1.289	0.256	202
Nervous	LR	7.638	0.006	202
Unaffected	LR	1.795	0.192	202

Table 7.2 suggests that in pilot 3, participants were less likely to report “insecure” feeling. However, the representativeness of a positive response was low in both pilots. Therefore, results need to be treated with caution.

Table 7.2: The association of pilot with the insecure feeling

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Insecure	0	Count	47	149
		Expected Count	49.5	146.5
	1	Count	4	2
		Expected Count	1.5	4.5

As shown in Table 7.3, participants in pilot 3 were less likely to provide a response to the “curious” feeling. Nervous feeling showed a similar pattern (Table 7.4), which might imply that curiosity might be treated as an indicator of uneasiness while travelling with an AV.

Table 7.3: The association of pilot with the curious feeling

		Pilot	
		1	3
Curious 0	Count	11	55
	Expected Count	16.7	49.3
1	Count	40	96
	Expected Count	34.3	101.7

Table 7.4: The association of pilot with the nervous feeling

		Pilot	
		1	3
Nervous 0	Count	42	144
	Expected Count	47.0	139.0
1	Count	9	7
	Expected Count	4.0	12.0

7.2.1.2 CAV Anticipation

The findings with respect to CAV anticipation suggested no significant differences respect to the expectation regarding the experience between the two pilots (Table 7.5).

Table 7.5: The association of pilot with CAV anticipation

		Pilot	
		1	3
CAV anticipation I don't know	Count	2	4
	Expected Count	1.5	4.5
It was as I expected	Count	24	62
	Expected Count	21.7	64.3
Negatively surprised	Count	3	5
	Expected Count	2.0	6.0

Positively surprised	Count	22	80
	Expected Count	25.8	76.2
LR = 1.851, p-value = 0.604, N = 202			

7.2.1.3 Confidence in CAVs

As presented in Table 7.6 the levels of confidence in CAVs did not significantly differ between the participants of the two pilots; participants in the two studies did not differ with respect to the aspect.

Table 7.6: The association of pilot with confidence in CAVs

		Pilot	
		1	3
CAV confidence	Barely confident	Count 8	14
		Expected Count 5.6	16.4
	Medium confident	Count 26	93
		Expected Count 30.0	89.0
	Very confident	Count 17	44
		Expected Count 15.4	45.6
Chi-Square = 2.391, p-value = 0.303, N = 202			

7.2.1.4 Indicators of acceptance

Four questions were considered as indicators related to CAV acceptance. These are presented and analysed in the current section. The question related to willingness-to-pay was available only in Pilot 3 and was not considered in this chapter.

Willingness to use upon availability

The distribution of the question related to the willingness of letting others use in the two pilots is presented in Table 7.7. The responses of each response category are presented in brackets. The response categories between the two studies differed and they were recoded to be as similar as possible following some assumptions:

- The two “willing” groups of pilot 1 were merged in a single group
- Any response other than “willing” in pilot 3 was merged in one group

Table 7.7: Willingness to use upon availability and responses

	Pilot 1	Pilot 3
Questions	If autonomous buses were available I would use them.	If the autonomous shuttle were available to me, I would use it.
Potential outcomes	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses. (29)	I am willing to accept the effort to switch to autonomous shuttles (e.g. special courses). (138)
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus (e.g., allowing to connect to control centre). (27)	The switch to autonomous shuttles is unacceptable. (6)
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible. (5)	I would not like to use autonomous shuttles. (3)
		I would try to avoid autonomous shuttles as much as possible. (9)

For convenience, the willingness to use upon availability question will be mentioned for the remainder of the document as Q7.1.1. The cross-tabulation and Chi-Square test result related to potential differences between the two pilots is presented in Table 7.8.

Table 7.8: The association of pilot and Q7.1.1

		Pilot	
		1	3
Q7.1.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	46	133
	Expected Count	46.3	132.7
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	5	13
	Expected Count	4.7	13.3
LR = 0.036, p-value = 0.848, N = 197			

Public acceptance

The question related to public acceptance is presented in Table 7.9. No edits were applied to this variable.

Table 7.9: Public acceptance and responses

	Pilot 1	Pilot 3
Questions	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use autonomous buses. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use the autonomous shuttle. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?
Potential outcomes	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses. (21)	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous shuttles. (71)
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad. (2)	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous shuttles feels bad. (2)
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good. (27)	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous shuttles feels good. (78)

For convenience, the willingness to let others use question will be mentioned for the remainder of the document as Q7.1.2. The cross-tabulation and Chi-Square test results presented in Table 7.10 do not show significant differences between the two variables.

Table 7.10: The association between quality of life and Q 7.1.2

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Q7.1.2	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses	Count	21	71
		Expected	22.9	69.1
		Count		
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad	Count	2	2
		Expected	1.0	3.0
		Count		
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good	Count	27	78
		Expected	26.1	78.9
		Count		
Chi-Square = 1.597, p-value = 0.450, N = 201				

Willingness to let others use

The distribution of the question related to the willingness of letting others use in the two pilots is presented in Table 7.11 (response number in brackets). The responses were recoded based on the following assumptions:

- The “certainly” group was treated as “yes” in both pilots
- The remaining groups were reduced to one group which had the “other than yes” interpretation

Table 7.11: Willingness to let others use and responses

	Pilot 1	Pilot 3
Questions	Would you let other members of your family or close circle use autonomous buses?	Would you let other members of your family or close circle use an autonomous shuttle service?
Potential outcomes	Certainly (29)	Certainly (101)
	Depends on how the technology evolves (12)	Depends on how the technology evolves (16)
	Not at all (1)	Not at all (0)
	Probably (13)	Probably (37)
	Probably not (1)	Probably not (0)

For convenience, the willingness to let others use question will be mentioned for the remainder of the document as Q7.1.3. The processed version of Q7.1.2 was investigated via Chi-Square test analysis to investigate the differences between the two pilots. The results suggested a significance difference at the 0.1 level of significance (Table 7.12). In particular, individuals in pilot 3 were more likely to be willing to let others use.

Table 7.12: The association of pilot and Q7.1.3

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	24	50
		Expected Count	18.7	55.3
	Yes	Count	27	101
		Expected Count	32.3	95.7
Chi-Square = 3.194, p-value = 0.074, N = 202				

Quality of life

The questions related to quality of life are presented in Table 7.13. Given differences in the response groups between the two pilots and the low number of occurrences for some groups, the variables were recoded based on the following assumption:

- Any non-yes response was given an “other than yes” interpretation

Table 7.13: Quality of life and responses

	Pilot 1	Pilot 3
Questions	Do you think autonomous buses can significantly improve citizens' everyday mobility (make public transport more attractive)?	Do you believe that the transport system as a whole can be improved by the integration of such kind of autonomous shuttle services?
Potential outcomes	Yes (29)	Yes (123)
	No (7)	No (4)
	I don't know (15)	I don't know (18)
		It does not make a difference (6)

For convenience, the willingness to let others use question will be mentioned for the remainder of the document as Q7.1.4. The results of a Chi-Square test showed significant difference in the response patterns between the two pilots. In particular, participants in pilot 3 were more likely to anticipate improvements in the transportation system.

Table 7.14: The association between pilot and Q7.1.4

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Q7.1.4	Other than yes	Count	22	28
		Expected Count	12.6	37.4
	Yes	Count	29	123
		Expected Count	38.4	113.6
Chi-Square = 12.381, p-value < 0.001, N = 202				

As a brief conclusion the following outcomes were found with respect to acceptance related questions:

- Willingness to use upon availability (Q7.1.1): Insignificant difference
- Public acceptance (Q7.1.2): Insignificant difference
- Willingness to let others use (Q7.1.3): Significant difference (at 0.1 level)
- Quality of life (Q7.1.4): Significant difference

The significant differences suggested that participants in pilot 3 tended to have higher levels of acceptance.

7.2.1.5 Participants' background

Table 7.15 shows the relationship between gender and pilot. No significant differences were found.

Table 7.15: The association between gender and pilot

		Pilot	
		1	3
Gender 1	Count	25	69
	Expected Count	24.2	69.8
2	Count	26	78
	Expected Count	26.8	77.2
Chi-Square = 0.066, p-value = 0.798, N = 198			

Table 7.16 shows the association between income and pilot. The difference was significant. In particular, participants in pilot 3 were more likely to report income less than 250 €/month. In pilot 1, participants were more likely to report higher incomes.

Table 7.16: The association between income and pilot

		Pilot	
		1	3
Income 2000€-3000€	Count	11	16
	Expected Count	8.2	18.8
250€-1000€	Count	1	11
	Expected Count	3.6	8.4
3000€-5000€	Count	12	12
	Expected Count	7.3	16.7
5000€+	Count	9	3
	Expected Count	3.6	8.4
I do not want to answer that	Count	12	18
	Expected Count	9.1	20.9
Less than 250€	Count	3	50
	Expected Count	16.1	36.9
Chi-Square = 36.417, p-value < 0.001, N = 158			

Table 7.17 suggests significantly different patterns with respect to commute frequency between the two pilots. In pilot 3 participants were more likely to report commuting every day while in pilot 1, 2-6 times a week. However, no significant differences were found regarding commute distance (Table 7.18).

Table 7.17: The association between commute frequency and pilot

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Commute frequency	2-6 a week	Count	18	38
		Expected Count	12.6	43.4
	Everyday	Count	20	101
		Expected Count	27.2	93.8
	Less than a week	Count	1	5
		Expected Count	1.4	4.6
	More than once a week	Count	2	4
		Expected Count	1.4	4.6
	Once a week	Count	2	0
		Expected Count	.5	1.5
Chi-Square = 12.865, p-value = 0.018, N = 191				

Table 7.18: The association between commute distance and pilot

		Pilot		
		1	3	
Commute distance	16-25 km	Count	5	32
		Expected Count	8.3	28.7
	26+ km	Count	7	28
		Expected Count	7.9	27.1
	5-15 km	Count	19	46
		Expected Count	14.6	50.4
	Up to 5 km	Count	12	42
		Expected Count	12.2	41.8
	Chi-Square = 3.529, p-value = 0.317, N = 191			

Table 7.19 shows that frequency of using CAVs significantly differed between the two pilots. In particular, participants in pilot 3 were more likely to report “systematically” or “occasionally” while participants in pilot 1 “rarely”.

Table 7.19: The association between CAV frequency of use and pilot

		Pilot		
		1	3	
CAV frequency	Never	Count	7	6
		Expected Count	3.4	9.6
	Occasionally	Count	11	52
		Expected Count	16.4	46.6
	Only once	Count	9	32
		Expected Count	10.7	30.3
	Rarely	Count	16	24
		Expected Count	10.4	29.6
	Systematically	Count	6	25
		Expected Count	8.1	22.9
	Chi-Square = 12.742, p-value = 0.013, N = 188			

7.2.2 Acceptance analysis

7.2.2.1 Feelings after the experience

Table 7.20 outlines the significant Chi-Square test results with respect to feelings after the experience. Further to cross-tabulation analysis, logit models were estimated to investigate the impact of both feelings and pilot on acceptance simultaneously.

Table 7.20: Feelings with respect to acceptance and tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Trustful	Chi-Square	3.069	0.080	197
Q7.1.2	Unaffected	LR	6.601	0.037	201
Q7.1.3	Insecure	LR	5.721	0.017	202
	Safe	Chi-Square	9.458	0.002	202
	Careful	Chi-Square	2.982	0.084	202
	Trustful	Chi-Square	32.050	<0.001	202
	Nervous	Chi-Square	5.008	0.025	202
Q7.1.4	Insecure	LR	9.469	0.002	202
	Curious	Chi-Square	3.441	0.064	202
	Careful	Chi-Square	3.732	0.053	202
	Trustful	Chi-Square	7.049	0.008	202

Variable: Feelings

The results with respect to Q7.1.1 indicate that trustful responses were more likely to be associated with a positive response with respect to usage of the vehicles, if these were available (Table 7.21). The results of the logit model (Table 7.22) indicated that trust remained significant (at the 0.1 level of significance) even after accounting for the effect of pilot differences.

Table 7.21: The association of trustful feeling with Q.7.1.1

			Trustful	
			0	1
Q7.1.1	1.00	Count	101	78
		Expected Count	104.5	74.5
	2.00	Count	14	4
		Expected Count	10.5	7.5

Table 7.22: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.1 with trustful feeling and pilot

Q7.1.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
1.00	Intercept	2.978	.528	31.830	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	-.033	.559	.003	1	.953
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Trustful=0]	-.992	.588	2.848	1	.091
	[Trustful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.23 suggests that unaffected participants were more likely to provide a “great” response, with respect to CAV mass adoption by the general population. The results of the logit model (Table 7.24) suggested that response had a negative influence on both “good” and “bad” responses (compared to “great”) while no significant effects of pilot were found.

Table 7.23: The association of unaffected feeling with Q7.1.2

			Unaffected	
			0	1
Q7.1.2	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses	Count	82	10
		Expected Count	85.6	6.4
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad	Count	3	1
		Expected Count	3.7	.3
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good	Count	102	3
		Expected Count	97.7	7.3

Table 7.24: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.2 with unaffected feeling and pilot

Q7.1.2		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses	Intercept	1.277	.670	3.631	1	.057
	[Pilot=1]	-.209	.340	.377	1	.539
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Unaffected=0]	-1.446	.677	4.568	1	.033
	[Unaffected=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad	Intercept	-1.558	1.310	1.415	1	.234
	[Pilot=1]	.939	1.039	.816	1	.366
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Unaffected=0]	-2.301	1.308	3.094	1	.079
	[Unaffected=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.25 suggests that insecure feeling is related to less positive answers with respect to the technology being used by family members. This outcome remained significant also after accounting for the impact of pilot differences using the logit model (Table 7.26).

Table 7.25: The association of insecure feeling with Q.7.1.3

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	69	5
		Expected Count	71.8	2.2
	Yes	Count	127	1
		Expected Count	124.2	3.8

Table 7.26: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with insecure feeling and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	1.306	1.118	1.366	1	.243
	[Pilot=1]	.481	.338	2.019	1	.155
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Insecure=0]	-2.037	1.116	3.334	1	.068
	[Insecure=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Cross-tabulation analysis indicated that safe feeling was positively related to acceptance of use of the technology by family members (Table 7.27). The results of the logit model further supporting this outcome, capturing at the same time differences between pilots (Table 7.28).

Table 7.27: The association of safe feeling with Q.7.1.3

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	61	13
		Expected Count	51.3	22.7
	Yes	Count	79	49
		Expected Count	88.7	39.3

Table 7.28: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with safe feeling and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-1.580	.343	21.172	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	.722	.345	4.380	1	.036
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Safe=0]	1.154	.364	10.062	1	.002
	[Safe=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 7.29, shows that careful feeling was negatively associated to acceptance of the technology to be used by family members. This finding was further supported by the results of the logit model which also suggested significant effects of differences between pilots (Table 7.30).

Table 7.29: The association of careful feeling with Q.7.1.3

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	53	21
		Expected Count	57.9	16.1
	Yes	Count	105	23
		Expected Count	100.1	27.9

Table 7.30: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with careful feeling and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-.091	.302	.091	1	.763
	[Pilot=1]	.872	.355	6.029	1	.014
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Careful=0]	-.898	.372	5.832	1	.016
	[Careful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The cross-tabulation results presented in Table 7.31 indicate that the “trustful” feeling is positively related to willingness to let others use. This relationship was further investigated via a logit model to account the effect of pilot differences (Table 7.32). The results of the logit model confirmed the significant impact of the trustful feeling as the pilot variable did not have a significant effect.

Table 7.31: The association of trustful feeling with Q.7.1.3

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	62	12
		Expected Count	42.9	31.1
	Yes	Count	55	73
		Expected Count	74.1	53.9

Table 7.32: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with trustful feeling and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-1.931	.328	34.673	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	.516	.360	2.052	1	.152
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Trustful=0]	1.908	.364	27.493	1	<.001
	[Trustful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The results in Table 7.33 show that the “nervous” feeling is negatively associated with willingness to let others use. This effect was also significant (at a 0.1 level) in a binary logit model with “nervous” and pilot

differences as explanatory variables (Table 7.34). The effect of pilot difference was not significant.

Table 7.33: The association of nervous feeling with Q.7.1.3

		Nervous		
		0	1	
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	64	10
		Expected Count	68.1	5.9
	Yes	Count	122	6
		Expected Count	117.9	10.1

Table 7.34: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with nervous feeling and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	.257	.551	.219	1	.640
	[Pilot=1]	.462	.340	1.848	1	.174
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Nervous=0]	-1.012	.551	3.373	1	.066
	[Nervous=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The results presented in Table 7.35 show that “insecure” individuals were less likely to anticipate improvements in the transport system due to the presence of CAVs. This relationship was further investigated via a logit model (Table 7.36). The results of the model indicated that both pilot differences and the insecure feeling had a significant impact on perception about system improvements.

Table 7.35: The association of insecure feeling with Q.7.1.4

		Insecure		
		0	1	
Q.7.1.4	Other than yes	Count	45	5
		Expected Count	48.5	1.5
	Yes	Count	151	1
		Expected Count	147.5	4.5

Table 7.36: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.4 with nervous feeling and pilot

Q.7.1.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	.971	1.134	.734	1	.392
	[Pilot=1]	1.092	.363	9.070	1	.003
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Insecure=0]	-2.500	1.134	4.859	1	.027
	[Insecure=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

With reference to the results presented in Table 7.37, curious individuals are less likely to anticipate improvements in the transport system due to the presence of CAVs. However, as shown in Table 7.38, the results of the logit model indicated that this difference is mainly due to the pilot differences; once the latter is included in the model specification, the “curious” feeling does not have a significant impact.

Table 7.37: The association of curious feeling with Q.7.1.4

		Curious	
		0	1
Q7.1.4 Other than yes	Count	11	39
	Expected Count	16.3	33.7
Yes	Count	55	97
	Expected Count	49.7	102.3

Table 7.38: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.4 with curious feeling and pilot

Q7.1.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-1.298	.238	29.762	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	1.138	.356	10.246	1	.001
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Curious=0]	-.563	.391	2.070	1	.150
	[Curious=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 7.39 showed that more “careful” participants were also more likely to anticipate system improvements due to CAVS. However, this result turned

insignificant in the logit model that also accounted for the pilot differences (Table 7.40).

Table 7.39: The association of careful feeling with Q.7.1.4

		Careful		
		0	1	
Q7.1.4	Other than yes	Count	44	6
		Expected Count	39.1	10.9
	Yes	Count	114	38
		Expected Count	118.9	33.1

Table 7.40: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.4 with careful feeling and pilot

Q7.1.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-1.846	.439	17.655	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	1.075	.370	8.431	1	.004
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Careful=0]	.494	.500	.976	1	.323
	[Careful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.41 shows that “trustful” to the CAVs participants are also more likely to expect improvements in the transport system due to this technology. The results of the logit model presented in Table 7.42 further validated this outcome. In particular, although the pilot dummy variable had a significant effect, “trustful feeling” also had a significant impact; this finding confirmed the importance of trust on the CAV acceptance.

Table 7.41: The association of trustful feeling with Q.7.1.4

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q7.1.4	Other than yes	Count	37	13
		Expected Count	29.0	21.0
	Yes	Count	80	72
		Expected Count	88.0	64.0

Table 7.42: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.4 with trustful feeling and pilot

Q7.1.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-2.041	.333	37.589	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	1.168	.358	10.616	1	.001
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Trustful=0]	.898	.370	5.883	1	.015
	[Trustful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.2.2.2 CAV anticipation

Table 7.43 presents the results of the Chi-Square tests with respect to the impact of CAV anticipation. Only one significant impact was found, at the 0.1 level of significance and it is further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 7.43: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	LR	6.380	0.095	197
Q7.1.2	LR	5.060	0.536	196
Q7.1.3	LR	1.052	0.789	202
Q7.1.4	LR	3.180	0.365	202

Variable: CAV anticipation

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis regarding the relationship between CAV anticipation and willingness to use when the technology is available are presented in Table 7.44.

Moreover, the results of the logit model showed a significant difference between the “as I expected” group and the “positively surprised” group which was the reference group, while the effect of pilot was not significant. This finding further supports the importance of the CAV anticipation variable.

Table 7.44: The association of CAV anticipation with Q7.1.1

			CAV anticipation			
			I don't know	It was as I expected	Negatively surprised	Positively surprised
Q7.1.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	5	73	7	94	
	Expected Count	5.5	77.2	7.3	89.0	
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	1	12	1	4	
	Expected Count	.5	7.8	.7	9.0	

Table 7.45: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.1 with CAV anticipation and pilot

Q7.1.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Not willing to accept the effort	Intercept	3.157	.526	36.031	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	-.002	.564	.000	1	.998
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_anticipation=1]	-1.547	1.210	1.635	1	.201
	[CAV_anticipation=2]	-1.351	.599	5.091	1	.024
	[CAV_anticipation=3]	-1.211	1.188	1.039	1	.308
	[CAV_anticipation=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

A shorter version of CAV anticipation was also investigated. The purpose of this approach was twofold. First, this recoded version of CAV anticipation was also used in the analysis of pilots 1 and 3 presented in Chapters 2 and 4 respectively.

Moreover, two of the four CAV anticipation categories had a low number of observations and were removed to improve the statistical power of the analysis. However, as presented in Table 7.46, only the willingness to use the technology when this is available had a significant Chi-Square test result (higher significance compared to the original version of the CAV anticipation variable).

Table 7.46: CAV anticipation tests - reduced

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Chi-Square	5.746	0.017	183
Q7.1.2	LR	1.738	0.419	187
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	0.412	0.521	188
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	0.419	0.517	188

Variable: CAV anticipation

As shown in Table 7.47, willingness to use the technology was higher than expected to occur for individuals who were positively surprised. It has been also discussed previously that CAVs might have to outperform human drivers for acceptance to be enhanced. The results of the logit model presented in Table 7.48 confirmed the results presented regarding the full original version of the variable.

Table 7.47: The association of CAV anticipation (reduced) with Q7.1.1

		CAV_anticipation	
		It was as I expected	Positively surprised
Q7.1.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	73	94
	Expected Count	77.6	89.4
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	12	4
	Expected Count	7.4	8.6

Table 7.48: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.1 with CAV anticipation (reduced) and pilot

Q7.1.1	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	
Not willing to accept the effort	Intercept	3.134	.526	35.463	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	.106	.614	.030	1	.863
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_anticipation=2]	-1.358	.599	5.134	1	.023
	[CAV_anticipation=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.2.2.3 Confidence in CAVs

Confidence was another variable that was investigated with respect to its relationship with acceptance related questions. As shown in Table 7.49, CAV confidence was involved in significant Chi-Square test results most of the times.

Table 7.49: CAV confidence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Chi-Square	3.352	0.187	197
Q7.1.2	LR	10.423	0.034	201
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	37.912	<0.001	202
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	7.364	0.025	202

Variable: CAV anticipation

Table 7.50 suggests that very confident individuals were more likely (compared to the expected counts) to also report as “great” the mass use of CAVs. A similar pattern was observed between the medium confident participants and the “good” outcome. No concrete conclusions can be derived for the “bad” response group due to the low number of occurrences.

Table 7.50: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.1.2

		CAV_confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium Confident	Very confident	
Q7.1.2	I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses	Count	9	47	36
		Expected	10.1	54.0	27.9
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad	Count	2	1	1
		Expected	.4	2.3	1.2
	The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels good	Count	11	70	24
		Expected	11.5	61.6	31.9

The results of the respective logit model to the cross-tabulation presented in Table 7.50 are outlined in Table 7.51. The results suggest only one main significant difference between medium and very confident (reference group) responses regarding the preference towards the “great” outcome over the “good” outcome (reference choice group). The impact of pilot was always insignificant suggesting that confidence in CAVs may be a transferable factor related to acceptance across pilots.

Table 7.51: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.2 with CAV confidence and pilot

Q7.1.2		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
I think it is great if large sections of the population use autonomous buses	Intercept	.467	.281	2.758	1	.097
	[Pilot=1]	-.219	.342	.411	1	.521
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1]	-.593	.522	1.289	1	.256
	[CAV_confidence=2]	-.820	.326	6.340	1	.012
	[CAV_confidence=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous buses feels bad	Intercept	-3.489	1.140	9.363	1	.002
	[Pilot=1]	.793	1.052	.568	1	.451
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1]	1.418	1.283	1.221	1	.269
	[CAV_confidence=2]	-1.000	1.439	.483	1	.487
	[CAV_confidence=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.52 suggests that very confident individuals were more likely to also be willing to let others use. On the other hand, medium and barely confident were less likely (compared to the expected counts) to let others use. The results of the logit model in Table 7.53 showed that both the impact of CAV confidence and pilot were significant or letting other use. Moreover, both medium and barely confident participants were significantly less likely to let others use, compared to very confident (reference group).

Table 7.52: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.1.3

			CAV_confidence		
			Barely confident	Medium Confident	Very confident
Q7.1.3	Other than yes	Count	15	55	4
		Expected Count	8.1	43.6	22.3
	Yes	Count	7	64	57
		Expected Count	13.9	75.4	38.7

Table 7.53: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.3 with CAV confidence and pilot

Q7.1.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-2.933	.546	28.909	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	.785	.386	4.140	1	.042
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1]	3.437	.699	24.192	1	<.001
	[CAV_confidence=2]	2.610	.558	21.852	1	<.001
	[CAV_confidence=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The results of the cross-tabulation analysis in Table 7.54 show that very confident individuals were more likely to also be willing to let others use. On the other hand, barely confident were less likely (compared to the expected counts) to let others use while no notable differences were observed with respect to the medium confident group. The results of the logit model in Table 7.55 further supported this outcome; only barely confident group significantly differed from the very confident group (reference category). Also, pilot differences had a significant effect.

Table 7.54: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.1.4

			CAV_confidence		
			1	2	3
Q7.1.4	Other than yes	Count	10	30	10
		Expected Count	5.4	29.5	15.1
	Yes	Count	12	89	51
		Expected Count	16.6	89.5	45.9

Table 7.55: Parameter estimates, Q7.1.4 with CAV confidence and pilot

Q7.1.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-2.073	.391	28.156	1	<.001
	[Pilot=1]	1.222	.363	11.344	1	<.001
	[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1]	1.440	.572	6.350	1	.012
	[CAV_confidence=2]	.662	.420	2.486	1	.115
	[CAV_confidence=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.2.2.4 Participants' background

The current section examines the relationship between participants' background characteristics and acceptance related questions. As shown in Table 7.56 and Table 7.57, no significant correlations were found with respect to gender and income respectively.

Table 7.56: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Chi-Square	0.251	0.616	193
Q7.1.2	Chi-Square	0.172	0.678	193
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	1.642	0.200	198
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	1.138	0.286	198

Variable: Gender

Table 7.57: Income tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Chi-Square	6.926	0.328	197
Q7.1.2	Chi-Square	8.527	0.202	197
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	3.368	0.761	202
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	3.095	0.797	202

Variable: Income

Table 7.58 indicates a significant relationship between 7.1.1 (willingness to use when technology is available) and commute frequency. The results of the cross-tabulation analysis suggest that individuals commuting everyday may be more likely to accept the effort (Table 7.59). The effect of commute frequency remained significant also after accounting for the impact of pilot differences via a logit model (Table 7.60). These results suggest that daily commutes might be more willing to accept the new technologies and incentives need to be implemented in order to ensure that this group of users will be attracted and use CAVs.

Table 7.58: Commute frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	Chi-Square	8.462	0.004	186
Q7.1.2	Chi-Square	1.018	0.313	187
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	0.486	0.486	191
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	0.063	0.803	191

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 7.59: The association between commute frequency and Q7.1.1

		Commute frequency	
		Not every day	Every day
Q7.1.1 Willing to accept the effort	Count	55	115
	Expected Count	60.3	109.7
Not willing to accept the effort	Count	11	5
	Expected Count	5.7	10.3

Table 7.60: Parameter estimates, 7.1.1 with commute frequency and pilot

Q7.1.1	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
1.00 Intercept	3.108	.468	44.103	1	<.001
[Pilot=1]	.158	.625	.064	1	.800
[Pilot=3]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
[Commute_frequency_dummy=2.00]	-1.547	.570	7.371	1	.007
[Commute_frequency_dummy=3.00]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Finally, Table 7.61 and Table 7.62 suggest that there is no significant correlation between acceptance related questions with commute distance or CAV frequency of use.

Table 7.61: Commute distance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	LR	0.943	0.815	186
Q7.1.2	Chi-Square	0.987	0.804	187
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	2.212	0.530	191
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	2.883	0.410	191

Variable: Commute distance

Table 7.62: CAV frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.1.1	LR	4.518	0.369	183
Q7.1.2	LR	5.880	0.661	187
Q7.1.3	Chi-Square	6.208	0.184	188
Q7.1.4	Chi-Square	1.265	0.867	188

Variable: CAV frequency

7.3 Passenger car CAVs (Pilot 2 and Pilot 4)

7.3.1 The impact of pilot experience on acceptance

7.3.1.1 Feelings after the experience

The reported feelings after the experience were compared between pilots 2 and 4. The results are presented in Table 7.63. Significant differences were found for several of the feelings. These are further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 7.63: Feelings tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Insecure	Chi-Square	3.972	0.048	192
Curious	Chi-Square	21.352	<0.001	192
Safe	Chi-Square	0.006	0.937	192
Careful	Chi-Square	46.186	<0.001	192
Trustful	Chi-Square	2.903	0.088	192
Nervous	Chi-Square	9.121	0.003	192
Critical	Chi-Square	0.068	0.794	192
Unaffected	LR	1.340	0.247	192

As shown in Table 7.64 participants in Pilot 4 were more likely to report feeling insecure, compared to Pilot 2. Similarly, participants in Pilot 4 were more likely to report feeling curious (Table 7.65). Similar patterns were observed for all the remaining feelings which resulted in significant differences such as careful (Table 7.66), trustful (Table 7.67) and nervous (Table 7.68). At first, this finding might seem counter intuitive as certain feelings would be expected to result in opposite patterns (for instance, insecure and trustful). However, on closer inspection, the data indicated that participants in Pilot 2 had in general lower rates of selecting any of the potential feelings compared to those in Pilot 4. This might indicate some level of uncertainty with respect to how the former perceived the experience with the technology.

Table 7.64: The association between insecure feeling and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Insecure	0	Count	87	91
		Expected Count	83.4	94.6
1		Count	3	11
		Expected Count	6.6	7.4

Table 7.65: The association between curious feeling and pilot

		Pilot	
		2	4
Curious 0	Count	70	46
	Expected Count	54.4	61.6
1	Count	20	56
	Expected Count	35.6	40.4

Table 7.66: The association between careful feeling and pilot

		Pilot	
		2	4
Careful 0	Count	79	41
	Expected Count	56.3	63.8
1	Count	11	61
	Expected Count	33.8	38.3

Table 7.67: The association between trustful feeling and pilot

		Pilot	
		2	4
Trustful 0	Count	66	63
	Expected Count	60.5	68.5
1	Count	24	39
	Expected Count	29.5	33.5

Table 7.68: The association between nervous feeling and pilot

		Pilot	
		2	4
Nervous 0	Count	86	83
	Expected Count	79.2	89.8
1	Count	4	19
	Expected Count	10.8	12.2

7.3.1.2 CAV Anticipation

The results with respect to anticipation are presented in Table 7.69. Although participants in Pilot 2 were more likely to be positively surprised

and less likely to report “as expected”, compared to those in Pilot 4, the results were not significant. This finding could be related to the limited experience with CAVs participants in pilot 2 had.

Table 7.69: The association between CAV anticipation and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
CAV anticipation	I don't know	Count	7	5
		Expected Count	5.7	6.3
	It was as I expected	Count	17	33
		Expected Count	23.6	26.4
	Negatively surprised	Count	4	5
		Expected Count	4.2	4.8
Positively surprised	Count	62	58	
	Expected Count	56.5	63.5	

LR = 5.157, p-value = 0.161, N = 191

7.3.1.3 CAV performance

Participants between the two pilots evaluated significantly different the performance of the CAV, compared to a human driver (Table 7.70). In particular, participants in Pilot 2 were more likely to perceive the behaviour as better compared to the human driver. On the other hand, participants in Pilot 4 were more likely to evaluate the behaviour worse or same as the human driver.

Table 7.70: The association between CAV performance and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
CAV_performance	Better than the human driver	Count	36	18
		Expected Count	25.4	28.6
	Just different	Count	27	29
		Expected Count	26.4	29.6
	Same as the human driver	Count	16	33
		Expected Count	23.1	25.9
	Worse than the human driver	Count	11	21
		Expected Count	15.1	16.9

Chi-Square = 14.509, p-value = 0.002, N = 191

7.3.1.4 Difficulty to use

Participants between the two studies evaluated significantly different the difficulty to use the CAV (Table 7.71). In particular, participants in Pilot 2 perceived in general higher difficulties, compared to those in Pilot 4.

Table 7.71: The association between difficulty to use and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
CAV_stress	Moderately difficult	Count	18	12
		Expected Count	14.1	15.9
	Not difficult at all	Count	29	45
		Expected Count	34.7	39.3
	Not very difficult	Count	33	43
		Expected Count	35.6	40.4
	Very difficult	Count	9	1
		Expected Count	4.7	5.3
Chi-Square = 11.664, p-value = 0.009, N = 190				

7.3.1.5 CAV confidence

Participants between the two studies had significantly different levels of confidence regarding CAVs (Table 7.72). Participants in pilot 2 reported in general less confidence, compared to participants in pilot 4.

Table 7.72: The association between confidence in CAVs and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
CAV_confidence	Barely confident	Count	9	16
		Expected Count	11.7	13.3
	Medium confident	Count	56	48
		Expected Count	48.8	55.2
	Not confident	Count	5	3
		Expected Count	3.8	4.3
	Very confident	Count	20	35
		Expected Count	25.8	29.2
Chi-Square = 6.500, p-value = 0.090, N = 192				

7.3.1.6 Indicators of acceptance

Four questions were considered as indicators related to CAV acceptance. These are presented and analysed in the current section.

Willingness to use upon availability

Table 7.73 presents the questions related to the willingness to use the technology if this was available, as this was presented in pilots 2 and 4. The distribution of the responses have been included in brackets. Although the potential responses differed, the latter were recoded based on the following approach; the responses were recorded in two groups namely, “willing to accept the effort” and “not willing to accept” the effort. That is, any response that was not include in the first category (as presented in Table 7.73) for both pilots, was assigned to the latter group.

Table 7.73: Willingness to use when technology is available and responses

	Pilot2	Pilot 4
Questions	If partially-automated cars were available, I would use them.	If a shared fleet composed of CAVs were available, I would use them.
Potential outcomes	I am willing to accept the effort to switch to partially-automated cars (e.g. special courses) (50)	I am willing to accept the effort to switch to a shared fleet composed of CAVs (e.g. special courses). (86)
	I would not like to use partially-automated cars. (9)	I would not like to use a shared fleet composed of CAVs . (11)
	I would try to avoid partially-automated cars as much as possible. (6)	I would try to avoid a shared fleet composed of CAVs as much as possible. (4)
	The switch to partially-automated cars is unacceptable. (23)	

The processed version of this variable (for convenience it will be mentioned as Q7.2.1) was investigated via Chi-Square test analysis to examine the differences in the response patterns between the two pilots. The results are presented in Table 7.74. A significant difference was observed between the two pilots. In particular, participants in pilot 4 were more likely to be willing to use the technology.

Table 7.74: The association between willingness to use when technology is available and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Q7.2.1	not willing to accept the effort	Count	38	15
		Expected Count	24.7	28.3
	willing to accept the effort	Count	50	86
		Expected Count	63.3	72.7
Total		Count	88	101
		Expected Count	88.0	101.0
Chi-Square = 18.705, p-value < 0.001, N = 189				

Public acceptance

The distribution of the question related to public acceptance is presented in Table 7.79 (responses in brackets). No further edits were applied to the response groups of this question.

Table 7.75: Willingness to let others use and responses

	CAV_population	
	Pilot2	Pilot 4
Questions	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use partially-automated cars . To what degree do the following statements apply to you?	Please imagine that large sections of the population would use shared fleets of CAVs. To what degree do the following statements apply to you?

Potential outcomes	I think it is great if large sections of the population use partially-automated cars. (19)	I think it is great if large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs. (36)
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels bad. (25)	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels bad. (13)
	The idea that large sections of the population use partially-automated cars feels good. (44)	The idea that large sections of the population use a shared fleet composed of CAVs feels good. (52)

The results of the Chi-Square test investigating the difference in public acceptance between pilots is presented in Table 7.76. A significant difference was found between the two cases. For convenience, this variable will be reported in the remainder of the document as Q7.2.2.

Table 7.76: The association between public acceptance and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
CAV_population	I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Count	19	36
		Expected Count	25.6	29.4
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Count	25	13
		Expected Count	17.7	20.3
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good	Count	44	52
		Expected Count	44.7	51.3
Chi-Square = 8.858, p-value = 0.012, N = 189				

Willingness to use

The questions related to willingness to use in both pilots are presented in Table 7.77, including the responses in brackets. The responses were coded in a different way therefore they were recorded in order to account for this difference. In particular the following assumptions were followed:

- The “certainly” group of pilot 2 was treated as “yes” of pilot 4
- The remaining groups were reduced to one group which had the “other than yes” interpretation

Table 7.77: Willingness to use and responses

	Intention to use	
	Pilot2	Pilot 4
Questions	After this experience, would you use a partially-automated car for your daily trips?	After this experience, would you use a shared connected vehicle for your daily trips?
Potential outcomes	Certainly (41)	Yes (50)
	Depends on how the technology evolves (11)	Depends on how the technology evolves (34)
	Not at all (2)	No (9)
	Probably (32)	I don't know (8)
	Probably not (3)	

The processed version of the willingness to use variable was investigated via Chi-Square test analysis to examine the differences in the response patterns between the two pilots. No significant differences were observed (Table 7.78). For convenience, this variable will be reported in the remainder of the document as Q7.2.3.

Table 7.78: The association between willingness to use and pilot

		Pilot	
		2	4
Q7.2.3	Other than yes	Count 48	51
		Expected Count 46.4	52.6
	Yes	Count 41	50
		Expected Count 42.6	48.4
Total		Count 89	101
		Expected Count 89.0	101.0
Chi-square = 0.224, p-value = 0.636, N = 190			

Willingness to let others use

The distribution of the question related to the willingness of letting others use in the two pilots is presented in Table 7.79. The responses of each response category are presented in brackets. Given the differences in the response categories, the willingness to let others use were treated in a way similar to the willingness to use variable. In particular the following assumptions were followed:

- The “certainly” group of pilot 2 was treated as “yes” of pilot 4
- The remaining groups were reduced to one group which had the “other than yes” interpretation

Table 7.79: Willingness to let others use and responses

	Pilot2	Pilot 4
Questions	Would you encourage your family or friends to use partially-automated cars?	Would you encourage your family or friends to use shared connected vehicles?
Potential outcomes	Certainly (42)	Yes (60)
	Depends on how the technology evolves (12)	Depends on how the technology evolves (32)
	Not at all (1)	No (6)
	Probably (33)	I don't know (3)
	Probably not (1)	

The processed version of the willingness to let others use variable was investigated via Chi-Square test analysis to examined the differences in the response patterns between the two pilots. The results suggested a significance difference at the 0.1 level of significance (Table 7.80). In particular, individuals in pilot 4 were more likely to be willing to let others use. For convenience, this variable will be reported in the remainder of the document as Q7.2.4.

Table 7.80: The association between willingness to use and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Q7.2.4	Other than yes	Count	47	41
		Expected Count	41.2	46.8
	Yes	Count	42	60
		Expected Count	47.8	54.2
Total		Count	89	101
		Expected Count	89.0	101.0
		Chi-Square = 2.839, p-value = 0.092, N = 190		

As a brief conclusion the following outcomes were found with respect to acceptance related questions:

- Willingness to use upon availability (Q7.2.1): Significant difference
- Public acceptance (Q7.2.2): Significant difference
- Willingness to use (Q7.2.3): Insignificant difference
- Willingness to let others use (Q7.2.4): Significant difference (at 0.1 level)

The significant differences suggested that participants in pilot 4 tended to have higher levels of acceptance.

7.3.1.7 Participants' background

Table 7.81 shows a significant difference between the participants of the two pilots in terms of gender. In particular, participants in pilot 4 were more likely to be female.

Table 7.81: The association between gender and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Gender	Female	Count	7	34
		Expected Count	19.2	21.8
	Male	Count	81	66
		Expected Count	68.8	78.2
		Chi-Square = 18.621, p-value < 0.001, N = 188		

Table 7.82 presents the cross-tabulation analysis between commute frequency and pilot. Participants in pilot 4 were more likely to be more frequent commuters.

Table 7.82: The association between commute frequency and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Commute frequency	2-6 times a week	Count	16	42
		Expected Count	27.3	30.7
Everyday	Everyday	Count	33	50
		Expected Count	39.1	43.9
Less once a week	Less once a week	Count	12	3
		Expected Count	7.1	7.9
More than once a week	More than once a week	Count	9	2
		Expected Count	5.2	5.8
Once a week	Once a week	Count	18	2
		Expected Count	9.4	10.6
		Chi-Square = 37.274, p-value < 0.001, N = 187		

The Chi-Square test results in Table 7.83 suggest a significant difference. Participants in pilot 2 were more likely (than expected) to report commute distance above 26 km while participants in pilot 4 were more likely to report commute distance 16-25 km.

Table 7.83: The association between commute distance and pilot

		Pilot		
		2	4	
Commute distance	16-25 km	Count	14	29
		Expected Count	20.2	22.8
26+ km	26+ km	Count	40	27
		Expected Count	31.5	35.5
5-15 km	5-15 km	Count	24	25
		Expected Count	23.1	25.9
Up to 5 km	Up to 5 km	Count	10	18
		Expected Count	13.2	14.8
		Chi-Square = 9.447, p-value = 0.024, N = 187		

7.3.2 Acceptance analysis

7.3.2.1 The impact of feelings after the experience

Table 7.84 outlines the significantly related feelings to indicators of acceptance. The significant relationships were further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis. Moreover, logit modelling analysis was conducted to further account for the impact of pilot-related differences.

Table 7.84: Feelings tests

Variable	Feeling	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Curious	Chi-Square	3.986	0.046	189
	Safe	Chi-Square	5.651	0.017	189
	Careful	Chi-Square	3.905	0.048	189
Q7.2.2	Curious	Chi-Square	6.938	0.031	189
Q7.2.3	Trustful	Chi-Square	7.413	0.006	190
	Nervous	Chi-Square	7.173	0.007	190
	Critical	Chi-Square	3.670	0.055	190
	Unaffected	LR	5.983	0.014	190
Q7.2.4	Trustful	Chi-Square	8.047	0.005	190
	Unaffected	LR	5.051	0.025	190

Variable: Feelings

Findings with respect to Q7.2.1 suggested that positive responses for the curious (Table 7.85), safe (Table 7.87), and careful (Table 7.89) were positively related to the use of the technology, if this was available.

Table 7.85: The association between curious feeling and Q7.2.1

		Curious	
		0	1
Q7.2.1 not willing to accept the effort	Count	38	15
	Expected Count	32.0	21.0
willing to accept the effort	Count	76	60
	Expected Count	82.0	54.0

Table 7.86 shows the parameter estimates of the model related to the curious feeling. The results suggest that after accounting for the impact of pilot-related differences, the impact of feeling is no longer significant. Hence, the significant impact of the curious feeling reported in Table 7.84 was potentially a result of pilot-related differences and their impact on the former.

Table 7.86: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.1 with and curious feeling and pilot

Q7.2.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-1.850	.336	30.255	1	<.001
	[Curious=0]	.224	.385	.339	1	.560
	[Curious=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Pilot=2]	1.400	.372	14.128	1	<.001
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.87: The association between safe feeling and Q7.2.1

		Safe		
		0	1	
Q7.2.1	not willing to accept the effort	Count	44	9
		Expected Count	37.3	15.7
	willing to accept the effort	Count	89	47
		Expected Count	95.7	40.3

Table 7.88 indicates that after accounting for pilot effects, the impact of safe feeling remains significant. In particular, the parameters suggest that a non-positive response to safe feeling (Safe = 0) increases the probability of observing a non-positive outcome in question Q1a (positive is the reference category).

Table 7.88: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.1 with safe feeling and pilot

Q7.2.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-2.553	.456	31.305	1	<.001
	[Pilot=2]	1.522	.360	17.839	1	<.001
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Safe=0]	1.042	.427	5.960	1	.015
	[Safe=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.89: The association between careful feeling and Q7.2.1

		Careful	
		0	1
Q7.2.1 not willing to accept the effort	Count	39	14
	Expected Count	33.1	19.9
willing to accept the effort	Count	79	57
	Expected Count	84.9	51.1

Table 7.90 presents the parameter estimates of the model related to the careful feeling. The results suggest that after accounting for the impact of pilot-related differences, the impact of careful feeling is no longer significant. Hence, the significant impact of the latter reported in Table 7.84 was potentially a result of pilot-related differences.

Table 7.90: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.1 and careful

Q7.2.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
.00	Intercept	-1.700	.325	27.384	1	<.001
	[Pilot=2]	1.532	.418	13.438	1	<.001
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Careful=0]	-.119	.439	.074	1	.786
	[Careful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The cross-tabulation results presented in Table 7.91 (question Q7.2.2) indicate that participants who provided a positive response to the curious feeling were also more likely to perceive CAV adoption by the population as great and less likely to perceive it bad.

Table 7.91: The association between curious feeling and Q7.2.2

		Curious	
		0	1
Q7.2.2 I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Count	26	29
	Expected Count	33.2	21.8
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Count	28	10
	Expected Count	22.9	15.1
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good	Count	60	36
	Expected Count	57.9	38.1

Table 7.92 suggests no significant differences between CAV adoption perceived as “great” and “good” (reference group). On the other hand, pilot had a significant impact on the “bad” response whereas the impact of curious feeling remained insignificant. These results combined with those reported regarding Q1a suggest that any significant related of the curious feeling in the cross-tabulation analysis was mainly due to pilot-related differences.

Table 7.92: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.2 with and curious feeling and pilot

Q7.2.2		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Intercept	-.149	.263	.320	1	.572
	[Pilot=2]	-.300	.371	.652	1	.419
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Curious=0]	-.524	.362	2.095	1	.148
	[Curious=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Intercept	-1.525	.393	15.075	1	<.001
	[Pilot=2]	.741	.419	3.118	1	.077
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Curious=0]	.269	.450	.357	1	.550
	[Curious=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.93 indicates that participants who had a trustful feeling towards the experience were also more likely to provide a positive response on intention to use the technology (Q7.2.3). The opposite was observed regarding the nervous (Table 7.94) and critical (Table 7.95) feelings, while unaffected participants were more likely to provide a positive response (Table 7.96).

Table 7.93: The association between trustful feeling and Q7.2.3

		Trustful	
		0	1
Q7.2.3 Non-positive	Count	75	24
	Expected Count	66.2	32.8
Yes	Count	52	39
	Expected Count	60.8	30.2

Table 7.94: The association between nervous feeling and Q7.2.3

		Nervous		
		0	1	
Q7.2.3	Non-positive	Count	81	18
		Expected Count	87.0	12.0
	Yes	Count	86	5
		Expected Count	80.0	11.0

Table 7.95: The association between critical feeling and Q7.2.3

		Critical		
		0	1	
Q7.2.3	Non-positive	Count	87	12
		Expected Count	90.7	8.3
	Yes	Count	87	4
		Expected Count	83.3	7.7

Table 7.96: The association between unaffected and Q7.2.3

		Unaffected		
		0	1	
Q7.2.3	Non-positive	Count	99	0
		Expected Count	96.9	2.1
	Yes	Count	87	4
		Expected Count	89.1	1.9

Table 7.97 suggests that pilot did not have a significant impact when it was simultaneously considered with the trustful feeling. The latter had a significant impact suggesting that it could be a more comprehensive factor related to acceptance. The same applied to the nervous feeling, although (as expected) the impact of the latter was opposite (Table 7.98), compared to the trustful impact. The critical feeling had a significant impact regardless pilot differences, but only at the 0.1 level of significance (Table 7.99).

Table 7.97: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with trustful feeling and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-.502	.284	3.128	1	.077
	[Pilot=2]	.042	.299	.020	1	.888
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Trustful=0]	.846	.318	7.070	1	.008
	[Trustful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.98: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with nervous feeling and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	1.227	.508	5.836	1	.016
	[Pilot=2]	.333	.304	1.204	1	.272
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Nervous=0]	-1.457	.541	7.260	1	.007
	[Nervous=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.99: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with critical feeling and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	1.034	.591	3.064	1	.080
	[Pilot=2]	.151	.294	.264	1	.607
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Critical=0]	-1.105	.597	3.422	1	.064
	[Critical=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The results presented in Table 7.100 suggest that trustful feeling was positively related to a positive willingness to let others use (Q7.2.4). The same pattern was also observed with respect to unaffected participants (Table 7.101).

Table 7.100: The association between trustful feeling and Q7.2.4

		Trustful		
		0	1	
Q7.2.4	Other than yes	Count	68	20
		Expected Count	58.8	29.2
	Yes	Count	59	43
		Expected Count	68.2	33.8

Table 7.101: The association between unaffected and Q7.2.4

		Unaffected		
		0	1	
Q7.2.4	Other than yes	Count	88	0
		Expected Count	86.1	1.9
	Yes	Count	98	4
		Expected Count	99.9	2.1

The parameter estimates in Table 7.102 indicate that lack of trustful feeling was positively related to a non-positive outcome on Q7.2.4. This pattern is the same as in Q7.2.3.

Table 7.102: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.4 with trustful feeling and pilot

Q7.2.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-.929	.299	9.656	1	.002
	[Pilot=2]	.411	.300	1.878	1	.171
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[Trustful=0]	.862	.327	6.971	1	.008
	[Trustful=1]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.3.2.2 CAV Anticipation

Table 7.103 presents the association between anticipation and indicators of acceptance. Several significant relationships were found which are explained in detail via cross-tabulation and logit analysis.

Table 7.103: CAV anticipation tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	LR	7.162	0.046	189
Q7.2.2	LR	2.918	0.819	189
Q7.2.3	LR	7.237	0.065	190
Q7.2.4	LR	16.957	< 0.001	190

Variable: CAV anticipation

Table 7.104 shows that a positive response to Q7.2.1 was more likely for participants that found the experience as expected or were positively surprised.

Table 7.104: The association between CAV anticipation and Q7.2.1

		CAV anticipation			
		I don't know	It was as I expected	Negatively surprised	Positively surprised
Q7.2.1 not willing to accept the effort	Count	7	11	3	32
	Expected	3.1	14.0	2.5	33.4
willing to accept the effort	Count	4	39	6	87
	Expected	7.9	36.0	6.5	85.6

The parameter estimates presented in Table 7.105 suggest a significant impact of the pilot. Moreover, the main differences were observed between positively surprised with “I don’t know” categories. The latter may suggest that uncertainty towards the behaviour of the CAV could decrease acceptance.

Table 7.105: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.1 with CAV anticipation and pilot

Q7.2.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
not willing to accept the effort	Intercept	-1.901	.333	32.516	1	<.001
	[Pilot=2]	1.499	.366	16.767	1	<.001
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_anticipation=1]	1.716	.708	5.875	1	.015
	[CAV_anticipation=2]	-.014	.424	.001	1	.974
	[CAV_anticipation=3]	.451	.784	.331	1	.565
	[CAV_anticipation=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.106 suggests that participants positively surprised were more likely to provide a positive response to Q3a, compared to negatively surprised and those who responded, “I don’t know”. Table 7.107 further indicates that pilot did not have a significant effect towards these trends. As in Q7.2.1, the main significant difference occurred between positively surprised with the “I don’t know” group.

Table 7.106: The association of CAV anticipation with Q7.2.3

		CAV anticipation			
		I don't know	It was as I expected	Negatively surprised	Positively surprised
Q7.2.3 Other than yes	Count	10	27	6	56
	Expected Count	6.3	26.1	4.7	62.0
Yes	Count	2	23	3	63
	Expected Count	5.7	23.9	4.3	57.0

Table 7.107: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with CAV anticipation and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Non-positive	Intercept	-.193	.240	.643	1	.423
	[Pilot=2]	.146	.301	.235	1	.628
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_anticipation=1]	1.719	.796	4.657	1	.031
	[CAV_anticipation=2]	.304	.342	.786	1	.375
	[CAV_anticipation=3]	.822	.731	1.263	1	.261
	[CAV_anticipation=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Finally, Table 7.108 suggests similar findings for Q7.2.4 as in Q7.2.3. Unlike the previously examined cases, Table 7.109 indicates significant impacts (either at the 0.05 or 0.1 levels) of both pilot and anticipation. It is worth mentioning that with respect to anticipation, all categories were more likely to provide a non-positive response, compared to positively surprised participants.

Table 7.108: The association between CAV anticipation and Q7.2.4

		CAV anticipation				
		I don't know	It was as I expected	Negatively surprised	Positively surprised	
Q7.2.4	Other than yes	Count	11	26	6	45
		Expected Count	5.6	23.2	4.2	55.1
	Yes	Count	1	24	3	74
		Expected Count	6.4	26.8	4.8	63.9

Table 7.109: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.4 with CAV anticipation and pilot

Q7.2.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Non-positive	Intercept	-.804	.257	9.800	1	.002
	[Pilot=2]	.578	.313	3.406	1	.065
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_anticipation=1]	2.899	1.065	7.404	1	.007
	[CAV_anticipation=2]	.690	.350	3.879	1	.049
	[CAV_anticipation=3]	1.254	.740	2.873	1	.090
	[CAV_anticipation=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.3.2.3 CAV performance

As shown in Table 7.110, CAV performance was significantly related to Q7.2.3 and Q7.2.4. The relationships were further examined via cross-tabulation and logit analysis.

Table 7.110: CAV performance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	4.004	0.261	189
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	2.857	0.827	189
Q7.2.3	Chi-Square	10.877	0.012	190
Q7.2.4	Chi-Square	14.618	0.002	190

Variable: CAV performance

Table 7.111 indicates that CAV performance perceived as better or just different to human driver was more likely to be related to a positive response to Q7.2.3 (willingness to use the technology). The results of logit model indicated that pilot did not have a significant impact. On the other hand, all categories related to performance were more likely to significantly differ from performance perceived as worse than the human driver.

Table 7.111: The association between CAV performance and Q7.2.3

		CAV performance				
		Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver	
Q7.2.3	Other than yes	Count	21	27	27	24
		Expected Count	28.1	28.7	25.5	16.7
	Yes	Count	33	28	22	8
		Expected Count	25.9	26.3	23.5	15.3

Table 7.112: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with CAV performance and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	.967	.420	5.293	1	.021
	[Pilot=2]	.411	.317	1.681	1	.195
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_performance=1]	-1.697	.512	11.003	1	<.001
	[CAV_performance=2]	-1.198	.494	5.870	1	.015
	[CAV_performance=3]	-.894	.501	3.184	1	.074
	[CAV_performance=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.113 shows that (as in Q7.2.3) CAV performance perceived as better than human driver was more likely to be positive towards letting others use the technology. However, the opposite occurred for “just different” perception. The results of logit model indicated that pilot had a significant impact. Moreover, all categories related to performance were more likely to significantly differ from performance perceived as worse than the human driver, with the exception of the “just different” group.

Table 7.113: The association between CAV performance and Q7.2.4

		CAV performance			
		Better than the human driver	Just different	Same as the human driver	Worse than the human driver
Q7.2.4 Other than yes	Count	16	30	20	22
	Expected Count	25.0	25.5	22.7	14.8
Yes	Count	38	25	29	10
	Expected Count	29.0	29.5	26.3	17.2

Table 7.114: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.4 with CAV performance and pilot

Q7.2.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	.534	.397	1.812	1	.178
	[Pilot=2]	.829	.330	6.330	1	.012
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_performance=1]	-1.985	.516	14.806	1	<.001
	[CAV_performance=2]	-.736	.480	2.353	1	.125
	[CAV_performance=3]	-1.187	.488	5.917	1	.015
	[CAV_performance=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.3.2.4 Difficulty to use

Table 7.115 suggests that Q7.2.1 and Q7.2.2 were significantly associated to the difficulty to use the CAV (the variable is defined as CAV stress). These relationships were further explored with cross-tabulation and logit analysis.

Table 7.115: Difficulty to use tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	9.473	0.024	189
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	12.847	0.046	189
Q7.2.3	Chi-Square	3.931	0.269	190
Q7.2.4	Chi-Square	3.771	0.287	190

Variable: Difficulty to use

Table 7.116 indicates that as perceived difficulty increased, the likelihood for observing a positive response to Q7.2.1 decreased. However, logit analysis showed that the difference might be mainly a result of pilot-related differences. The main difference with respect to difficulty in use was observed between “very difficult” and “not difficult at all” groups at the 0.1 level of significance.

Table 7.116: The association between difficulty to use and Q7.2.1

		CAV stress			
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	Very difficult
Q7.2.1 not willing to accept the effort	Count	12	15	20	6
	Expected	8.4	20.8	21.0	2.8
willing to accept the effort	Count	18	59	55	4
	Expected	21.6	53.2	54.0	7.2

Table 7.117: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.1 with difficulty to use and pilot

Q7.2.1		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
not willing to accept the effort	Intercept	-.792	.736	1.159	1	.282
	[Pilot=2]	1.333	.363	13.515	1	<.001
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_stress=2]	-.465	.770	.365	1	.546
	[CAV_stress=3]	-1.226	.733	2.797	1	.094
	[CAV_stress=4]	-.888	.722	1.512	1	.219
	[CAV_stress=5]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.118 suggests that some differences between the expected and observed counts occurred mostly with respect to the “not very difficult” group. Table 7.119 indicates that pilots did not have a significant impact. On the other hand, participants in the “feels bad” group were more likely to find the technology difficult to use, than any other difficulty group.

Table 7.118: The association between difficulty to use and Q7.2.2

		CAV stress			
		Moderately difficult	Not difficult at all	Not very difficult	Very difficult
Q7.2.2 I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Count	8	19	26	2
	Expected Count	8.7	21.5	21.8	2.9
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Count	5	16	11	6
	Expected Count	6.0	14.9	15.1	2.0
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good	Count	17	39	38	2
	Expected Count	15.2	37.6	38.1	5.1

Table 7.119: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.2 with difficulty to use and pilot

Q7.2.2		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Intercept	.441	1.048	.177	1	.674
	[Pilot=2]	-.520	.361	2.079	1	.149
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_stress=2]	-.911	1.098	.689	1	.407
	[CAV_stress=3]	-.991	1.059	.875	1	.350
	[CAV_stress=4]	-.622	1.049	.352	1	.553
	[CAV_stress=5]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Intercept	.474	.902	.276	1	.599
	[Pilot=2]	.686	.417	2.699	1	.100
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_stress=2]	-2.169	.968	5.014	1	.025
	[CAV_stress=3]	-1.687	.888	3.608	1	.058
	[CAV_stress=4]	-2.077	.899	5.336	1	.021
	[CAV_stress=5]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.3.2.5 CAV confidence

As shown in Table 7.120, several significant associations between confidence in CAVs and the indicators of acceptance were found. This were further investigated via cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 7.120: CAV confidence tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	2.873	0.412	189
Q7.2.2	LR	15.424	0.017	189
Q7.2.3	LR	15.815	0.001	190
Q7.2.4	LR	9.911	0.019	190

Variable: CAV performance

The results presented in Table 7.121 suggest that very confident participants were more likely to perceive mass adoption of CAVs as great. On the other hand, any other level of confidence was more likely (compared to the expected counts) to be observed in the “feels bad” group. Table 7.122 suggests some pilot differences between “feel bad” and “feel good” groups. Moreover, confidence significantly affected perception with respect to the “feel great” category.

Table 7.121: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.2.2

		CAV confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Not confident	Very confident
Q7.2.2 I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Count	4	24	2	25
	Expected Count	7.3	29.4	2.3	16.0
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Count	6	26	2	4
	Expected Count	5.0	20.3	1.6	11.1
Count		15	51	4	26

The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good	Expected Count	12.7	51.3	4.1	27.9
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Table 7.122: Parameter estimates, Q7.2.2 with CAV confidence and pilot Q7.2.2

		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
I think it is great if large sections of the population use	Intercept	.117	.307	.145	1	.704
	[Pilot=2]	-.453	.359	1.594	1	.207
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1.00]	-1.310	.631	4.308	1	.038
	[CAV_confidence=2.00]	-.663	.377	3.083	1	.079
	[CAV_confidence=3.00]	-.557	.917	.369	1	.544
	[CAV_confidence=4.00]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad	Intercept	-2.243	.585	14.703	1	<.001
	[Pilot=2]	.758	.407	3.464	1	.063
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1.00]	1.008	.730	1.909	1	.167
	[CAV_confidence=2.00]	1.109	.594	3.492	1	.062
	[CAV_confidence=3.00]	1.022	1.030	.985	1	.321
	[CAV_confidence=4.00]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

Table 7.123 indicates that confidence in CAVs is positively related to a positive response on intention to use. The results of the logit model in Table 7.124 highlight that there are no differences related to pilots, while all confidence levels are significantly less likely to be linked to a positive response on Q7.2.3.

Table 7.123: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.2.3

		CAV confidence			
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Not confident	Very confident
Q7.2.3 Other than yes	Count	17	59	6	17
	Expected Count	13.0	53.1	4.2	28.7
Yes	Count	8	43	2	38
	Expected Count	12.0	48.9	3.8	26.3

Table 7.124:Parameter estimates, Q7.2.3 with CAV confidence and pilot

Q7.2.3		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-809	.313	6.692	1	.010
	[Pilot=2]	.013	.309	.002	1	.967
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1.00]	1.558	.519	9.027	1	.003
	[CAV_confidence=2.00]	1.118	.358	9.756	1	.002
	[CAV_confidence=3.00]	1.900	.871	4.760	1	.029
	[CAV_confidence=4.00]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

The cross-tabulation analysis related to Q7.2.4 (Table 7.125) produced very similar results to Q7.2.3. More specifically, confidence had a positive relationship to a positive response on the use of technology by family members. Very similar patterns occurred also with respect to the logit model (Table 7.126). The difference between “very confident” (reference category) and not confident was not significant however, potentially due to the lower occurrences of the latter.

Table 7.125: The association between CAV confidence and Q7.2.4

		CAV confidence				
		Barely confident	Medium confident	Not confident	Very confident	
Q7.2.4	Other than yes	Count	14	53	5	16
		Expected Count	11.6	47.2	3.7	25.5
	Yes	Count	11	49	3	39
		Expected Count	13.4	54.8	4.3	29.5
Total		Count	25	102	8	55
		Expected Count	25.0	102.0	8.0	55.0

Table 7.126:Parameter estimates, Q7.2.4 with CAV confidence and pilot

Q7.2.4		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Other than yes	Intercept	-1.048	.322	10.576	1	.001
	[Pilot=2]	.410	.304	1.815	1	.178
	[Pilot=4]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.
	[CAV_confidence=1.00]	1.144	.503	5.175	1	.023
	[CAV_confidence=2.00]	.906	.361	6.305	1	.012
	[CAV_confidence=3.00]	1.307	.794	2.708	1	.100
	[CAV_confidence=4.00]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.

7.3.2.6 Participants' background

The impact of participants' background characteristics was also investigated on acceptance related questions. The background variables that were considered were gender, commute frequency, commute distance and frequency of using CAVs. The results of the Chi-Square tests are presented from Table 7.127 to Table 7.130. No significant effects were found.

Table 7.127: Gender tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	1.156	0.282	185
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	1.816	0.403	185
Q7.3.3	Chi-Square	2.674	0.102	186
Q7.4.4	Chi-Square	1.836	0.175	186

Variable: Gender

Table 7.128: Commute frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	0.875	0.350	185
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	0.056	0.972	185

Q7.3.3	Chi-Square	0.194	0.660	186
Q7.4.4	Chi-Square	0.195	0.659	186

Variable: Commute frequency

Table 7.129: Commute distance tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	2.319	0.509	185
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	5.314	0.527	185
Q7.3.3	Chi-Square	0.187	0.980	186
Q7.4.4	Chi-Square	1.075	0.783	186

Variable: Commute distance

Table 7.130: CAV frequency tests

Variable	Test	Test value	p-value	Sample
Q7.2.1	Chi-Square	0.752	0.945	172
Q7.2.2	Chi-Square	6.830	0.555	172
Q7.3.3	LR	5.809	0.669	171
Q7.4.4	LR	5.292	0.726	171

Variable: CAV frequency

7.4 Summary

7.4.1 Public transport CAVs

The cross-pilot analysis that focused on public transport modes let to a series of interesting conclusions. With respect to variables that could be used as predictors of acceptance there was a significant different across pilots in feelings during the experience such as insecure curious and

nervous. On the other hand, no differences were found for safe, trustful and unaffected. Likewise, anticipation and confidence in CAV did not differ between the two studies.

Regarding acceptance related questions, significant differences were found in willingness to let others use and in the quality of life variables. In both cases, the significant differences suggested that participants in pilot 3 tended to have higher levels of acceptance. Differences could be transport mode related (pilot 1 used a larger vehicle) or familiarity of participants with automated technologies.

Regarding the association between indicators of acceptance and feelings, the “trustful” feeling has been consistently found to have significant correlations to acceptance related questions. This finding was supported also across pilots 1 and 3 as its effect remained significant after accounting for pilot related differences. The same finding also occurred with respect to “unaffected” participants and public acceptance. Willingness to let other use was one of the acceptance indicators found to significantly differ across pilots. When the impact of feelings was included different patterns were however observed. For instance, “insecure” and “nervous” feelings both remained significant (even at the 0.1 level of significance) but in these two cases, the impact of pilot differences changed to insignificant. However, in other cases such as “safe” or “careful” both feeling and pilot impacts were significant. These findings might imply that except for the differences due to pilot execution underlying beliefs and attitudes might as well be important. For the case of system improvement, not all feeling impacts were transferable. For instance, “curious” and “careful” turned insignificant when pilot differences were included. On the other hand, “insecure” and “trustful” remained significant. These findings suggest that some feelings may be globally accepted as indicators of acceptance.

Anticipation was another transferable variable as when expectations are not met, participants might be less willing to use the technology. Last but not least, confidence in CAVs was another transferable factor for most of the acceptance related questions. This finding further suggests that sufficient levels of trust need to be developed regardless system type or test location to enhance acceptance levels.

Finally, among participants’ background characteristics, only one significant relationship was found; commute frequency was significantly related to willingness to use the technology when it is available. This finding might indicate higher interest of frequent commuters towards automated vehicle technologies.

7.4.2 Passenger car CAVs

The cross-pilot analysis that focused on passenger car CAVs suggested that several feelings during the pilot differed. More specifically, significant differences were found regarding insecure, curious, careful, trustful (at the 0.1 level), and nervous feelings. Only safe, critical and unaffected did not significantly differ. Moreover, although the difference regarding anticipation was not significant, perceived performance, difficulty to use and confidence towards CAVs significantly differed.

With respect to the acceptance indicators, willingness to use when available, public acceptance and willingness to let others use significantly differed. The significant results suggested that participants in pilot 4 tended to have higher levels of acceptance.

With respect to the correlation between indicators of acceptance and other variables, the feelings found to have a significant effect were further tested by also accounting for the impact of other pilot differences. Some feelings such as “curious” and “careful” were not significant after the effect of pilot was considered, with respect to willingness to use upon availability. The same pattern was also observed in the analysis of pilots 1 & 3. However, the impact of “safe” remained significant. The same outcome with respect to “curious” was observed also with respect to public acceptance. Feelings such as “trustful” and “nervous” were significant in terms of willingness to use. These remained significant also after accounting for the impact of pilot differences. The same was also observed with respect to critical. The “trustful” feeling remains significant also regarding the willingness to let others use variable.

Anticipation also had a significant relationship with several of the acceptance indicators. However, after accounting for pilot differences only some results remained significant. Nevertheless, this finding still implies the need to meet users’ expectations or developing accurate mental models is a necessary practice to enhance acceptance.

Vehicle performance was another indicator that had a significant effect across the two pilots. Hence, the necessity to ensure behaviour better than the human (even equal performance might not suffice) remains regardless the pilot setting.

Difficulty to use (opposite of ease of use) had a significant relationship to public acceptance. Ease of use is a well-known indicator and part of the TAM. Its importance was confirmed as part of two different pilot tests and further validated its importance.

Finally, confidence (else trust) in CAVs was a significant indicator regardless pilot. Trust and confidence could be the two most important concepts that need to be developed (together with reliable vehicle performance) to enhance acceptance.

It should be mentioned that participants' background characteristics were investigated but no significant relationships were found.

8 Beyond the PAsCAL Pilots

8.1 Demand for autonomous bus/shuttle

On top of the pilot data collections, an online survey was undertaken to understand people's preferences towards autonomous public transport bus/shuttle and their needs from autonomous public transport vehicles. The online survey was conducted using a university survey platform as well as a paid survey engine tool. The survey complied with the university research ethics guidelines and was GDPR compliant.

The survey questionnaire asked respondents to make a choice in various hypothetical situations with autonomous public transport, conventional public transport and status quo as main alternatives in the choice tasks. Travel time, travel cost, journey information and vehicle interaction were the main attributes included in the choice tasks.

The respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement on whether autonomous bus/shuttle could improve travel (such as comfort, ease of use and safety). The respondents were also asked to indicate their feelings on autonomous bus use and key aspects such as real-time information, presence of steward and ramp operations that could affect their travel. Respondents were asked to indicate whether they would use an autonomous bus/shuttle if it was available in their area.

The following responses were obtained from the survey in terms of autonomous bus/shuttle characteristics perceived by 455 respondents and the preferences towards autonomous public transport bus.

8.1.1 Preferences towards autonomous bus use and its characteristics

This section provides the findings from the survey for autonomous bus use preferences and the different characteristics of autonomous bus use.

8.1.1.1 Using AB as replacement for the current mode

This question asked respondents whether they would be willing to use autonomous bus/shuttle, if it was available in their area. Respondents were asked to select a response from 'yes, as a replacement for my current mode of travel', 'yes, sometimes', 'yes, maybe', 'no, rarely/hardly' and 'no, I would not be comfortable using it'.

It was found that across the different age groups, 18-25 year old were more likely to select autonomous buses 'as a replacement' to their current

mode of transport, compared to older age groups. 18-25 year old were also found to be more likely to select a positive response as ‘yes, sometimes’ or ‘yes, maybe’, towards using autonomous buses/shuttle. This result is similar to findings obtained from previous research where younger respondents were found to be more positive towards autonomous vehicle use (Hilgarter and Granig, 2020).

The study also found that 56-70 year old respondents showed a marked variation in acceptance for autonomous bus/shuttle with most responses ranging from ‘yes, sometimes’ to ‘no, I would not be comfortable using it’. Similar results have also been obtained in previous studies where older individuals were found to have a positive attitude towards autonomous shuttles (Madigan *et al.*, 2016) as well as a negative approach towards autonomous shuttles (Madigan *et al.*, 2017).

The current study found that while 26-40 year old provided a positive response to using autonomous bus/shuttle, this age group also had the most responses compared to other age groups that provided a negative response such as ‘no, rarely/hardly’ or ‘no, I would not be comfortable using it’ for autonomous bus/shuttle use. Figure 8.1 provides the variation in autonomous bus acceptance across the different age groups.

Figure 8.1: Variation of autonomous bus acceptance across different age groups

In case of gender variation, it was found that women were less likely to select autonomous bus/shuttle as a ‘replacement’ to their current mode of

transport while they showed a more positive response towards using autonomous bus/shuttle ‘sometimes’ or ‘maybe’. However, women were also found to be more likely than men to reject using autonomous bus/shuttle as a replacement for their current mode of travel. This is in line with the conservative findings obtained from Hilgarter and Granig (2020), Liljamo *et al.* (2018), Schoettle and Sivak (2014) and Wali *et al.* (2021) who show that women have less positive attitude towards autonomous shuttles and autonomous vehicles compared to men. Figure 8.2 provides the variation in autonomous bus acceptance across the different gender groups.

Figure 8.2: Variation of autonomous bus acceptance across gender

8.1.1.2 HMI requirements on-board

Human machine interface (HMI) is an important feature of autonomous vehicles that affects the ease of use and acceptance of autonomous vehicles. For the autonomous public transport bus/shuttle within this study, the different HMI interface examined were: large fonts on HMI display, colour blindness friendly HMI display, adaptive HMI, auditory communication, using mobile applications and sending text messages through mobile phone. These HMI features were included considering that the features could be of significance for elderly and visually impaired users of autonomous public transport bus/shuttle.

It was found that the HMI preferences required on-board varied slightly across the different age groups. While using ‘mobile applications’ was found to be preferable across all the age groups, older respondents such as those aged 41-55 years and 56-70 years preferred to communicate with the vehicle using ‘large fonts on HMI display’ and ‘auditory communication’, in addition to ‘mobile applications’. Younger age groups such as 18-25 years and 26-40 years also showed preference towards adaptive HMI. ‘Sending text message through mobile phone’ was found to be the least preferred method to communicate with the vehicle across all the age groups. Figure 8.3 provides the on-board HMI preference across the different age groups.

Figure 8.3: On-board HMI preference across different age groups

Considering gender variation in on-board HMI preference, it was found that men and women had similar preferences for HMI. ‘Using mobile applications’ and having ‘large fonts on HMI display’ were found to be the two most preferred HMI across both the gender groups. Women also showed a considerably higher preference towards communicating with the vehicle by ‘sending text message through mobile phone’ compared to men. Figure 8.4 provides the preference for on-board HMI across the different gender groups.

Figure 8.4: On-board HMI preference variation across gender

8.1.2 Attitudinal responses towards autonomous buses

The attitudinal questions towards autonomous bus/shuttle comprised of a Likert scale question where respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement on each of the statements pertaining to the different characteristics of the autonomous bus/shuttle.

Attitudinal questions towards autonomous bus use obtained responses on autonomous bus/shuttle being easy to use, communication with the vehicle using HMI being easy to use, autonomous buses/shuttles being useful mode of transport, autonomous bus providing improvement on passenger safety, autonomous bus providing improvement on other road user safety and autonomous bus being comfortable to use. Respondents were asked to provide a response on a five-point Likert scale (from 'Definitely Yes' to 'Definitely No'). The responses were segmented based on different age and gender categories. The following results were obtained for each of the attitudinal questions:

8.1.2.1 Ease of use

Responses on autonomous bus perceived ease of use showed that across the different age groups (18-25 year and 26-40 year old), younger respondents considered the autonomous bus to be 'definitely' or 'maybe'

easy to use. Older respondents considered that autonomous buses would 'maybe' easy to use. Figure 8.5 provides the variation in perception towards ease of use across the different age groups.

Figure 8.5: Autonomous bus - ease of use. Variation across age groups

In terms of gender variation, it is seen that more women respondents consider the autonomous bus to be 'maybe' easy to use, with higher proportion of women respondents also providing 'don't know' or negative responses in comparison to men. More male respondents however considered that the autonomous bus would be 'definitely' easy to use. Figure 8.6 provides the gender variation across the perceived ease of use for autonomous bus/shuttle.

Figure 8.6: Autonomous bus - ease of use. Variation across gender

8.1.2.2 HMI ease to use

Most of the respondents across all the age groups considered that the autonomous bus HMI would be ‘maybe’ easy to use. Figure 8.7 provides the HMI ease of use across the different age categories.

Figure 8.7: Autonomous bus – HMI ease of use. Variation across age groups

Gender variation for HMI ease of use showed that male respondents were more positive towards HMI ease of use with lesser ‘don’t know’ and ‘maybe not’ responses. Female respondents however, provided a large number of ‘maybe yes’ responses. Moreover, female respondents also provided fewer ‘definitely yes’ responses and a larger proportion of ‘don’t know’ and ‘maybe not’ responses in comparison to men. Figure 8.8 provides the gender variation for HMI ease of use.

Figure 8.8: Autonomous bus – HMI ease of use. Variation across gender

8.1.2.3 Useful mode of transport

Age variation in responses for autonomous bus being useful mode of transport showed that most 18-25 year and 26-40 year old responded 'definitely yes' while 41-55 year old respondents while positive about usefulness of autonomous buses, responded 'maybe yes' to this attitudinal question.

Across the different gender groups, a marked difference was obtained in the responses from men and women participants. While a significant proportion of both the gender believed that autonomous bus/shuttle are 'definitely' a useful means of transport, more women respondents also showed 'maybe yes', ambivalent and negative responses compared to male participants.

Figure 8.9 and Figure 8.10 provides the finding obtained from this attitudinal question across the various age and gender categories.

Figure 8.9: Autonomous bus – useful mode of transport. Variation across age groups

Figure 8.10: Autonomous bus – useful mode of transport. Variation across gender groups

8.1.2.4 Improvement in passenger safety

The attitudinal question on the ability of the autonomous bus to improve passenger safety showed that while a significant proportion of respondents across the different age groups responded ‘maybe yes’, most of the 18-25 year and 26-40 year old responded ‘don’t know’ to whether autonomous bus could improve passenger safety. Across the different gender, it was found that most of the female respondents provided a ‘don’t know’ or negative response to the attitudinal question. Male respondents showed a relatively positive response with more ‘maybe yes’ and ‘definitely yes’ than female respondents. Figure 8.11 and Figure 8.12 provide the responses obtained across the different age and gender categories.

Figure 8.11: Autonomous bus improve passenger safety - age variation

Figure 8.12: Autonomous bus improve passenger safety - gender variation

8.1.2.5 Improvement in other road user safety

When asked whether autonomous bus could improve the safety of other road users, a larger proportion of respondents provided a 'maybe yes' or a 'don't know' response while more respondents regarded that autonomous bus would 'maybe not' improve the safety of other road users in comparison to 'definitely yes' responses. Figure 8.13 provides the responses obtained for this attitudinal question across the different age groups.

Figure 8.13: Autonomous bus improve the safety of other road users - age variation

Across the different gender categories it was found that more female respondents were uncertain whether autonomous buses could improve the safety of other road users. While large proportion of female respondents provided 'maybe yes' to the question, a substantially high proportion of female respondents also considered that autonomous buses would 'maybe not' or 'definitely not' improve the safety of other road users. Within this attitudinal question it was also found that men showed a more positive response compared to female respondents.

Figure 8.14 provides the responses obtained from this attitudinal question across both the gender.

Figure 8.14: Autonomous bus improve the safety of other road users - gender variation

8.1.2.6 Comfortable to use

Across the different age and gender categories, it was found that younger respondents in the age categories between 18-25 year and 26-40 year old considered the autonomous bus to be ‘comfortable to use’. 41-55 year old also responded ‘maybe yes’ that autonomous bus/shuttle would be comfortable to use. While some older respondents provided a positive response that autonomous bus would be comfortable to use, about a third of 56-70 year old provided uncertain or negative response to the expected perception of comfort for autonomous bus/shuttle. Figure 8.15 provides the response obtained for the attribute ‘comfortable to use’ for autonomous bus/shuttle.

Figure 8.15: Autonomous bus - comfortable to use. Variation across age groups

The gender variation for this attribute showed that men provided a positive response with more certainty (‘definitely yes’) than women participants. Women provided a more conservative approach by considering autonomous buses to be ‘maybe’ comfortable to use. Moreover, women also showed more uncertainty in their perception towards this attribute, as 7.5% women responded that they ‘don’t know’ if autonomous buses would be comfortable to use. Figure 8.16 provides the results obtained from the gender segmentation of this attribute. Results from the age and gender segmentation reiterate the findings from the literature that younger and male respondents have a more positive approach towards autonomous vehicles (Bansal *et al.*, 2016; Becker and Axhausen, 2017; Liljamo *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 8.16: Autonomous bus - comfortable to use. Variation across gender groups

8.1.3 In-vehicle assistance required from autonomous public transport bus

‘Communication with the vehicle’ was considered as a ‘very important’ aspect of in-vehicle assistance and information from autonomous buses. ‘Visual communication’ such as HMI or mobile app was also considered ‘important’ by most of the respondents. ‘Presence of steward’ was considered as another aspect ‘very important’ for in-vehicle assistance. The survey results show that respondents consider all the different factors for in-vehicle assistance and information to be either ‘very important’ or ‘important’. This is especially the case with ‘communication with vehicle for special assistance’ and ‘visual communication’ with the vehicle. Thus, respondents considered the ability to effectively communicate with the vehicle as the most important feature for in-vehicle assistance and information from the autonomous bus. The survey results are shown in the following figure.

Figure 8.17: In-vehicle assistance and information required in autonomous bus

8.2 Acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle

This section examines the acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle based on various factors underpinning the acceptance of a new technology. The section also provides results from the choice experiment and an advanced econometric model combining latent and experimental factors determining choice. Section 8.2.1 provides the analysis for the various factors affecting acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle while Section 8.2.2 provides the results from the choice experiment exercise along with the willingness to pay analysis for autonomous public transport vehicles.

8.2.1 Acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle

The technology acceptance model proposed by Davis (1985) suggests that users' motivation towards using a technology can be explained by factors such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and attitude towards using the technology. In addition, Davis (1993) also proposed that

perceived usefulness of the technology can have a direct influence on the actual technological use (Chuttur, 2009).

The technology acceptance model can be given as in Figure 8.18.

Figure 8.18: Technology acceptance model given in Davis (1993). Adapted from Chuttur (2009).

In order to examine the effect of various factors affecting users’ motivation towards autonomous bus/shuttle, a stepwise regression analysis was conducted with respondent’s stated intention to use the autonomous bus/shuttle as the dependent variable and attitudinal questions such as autonomous bus/shuttle ease of use, usefulness, passenger safety, other road user safety and comfort as the independent variables. The following results were obtained from the stepwise regression analysis:

Table 8.1: Stepwise regression analysis for factors affecting acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle use

Variable	Coefficient estimate (t-statistics)
Constant	0.684 (6.427)
Feeling towards autonomous bus use	0.402 (10.61)
Autonomous bus/shuttle usefulness	0.286 (5.55)
Autonomous bus/shuttle improvement to passenger safety	0.150 (3.68)
Adjusted R ²	0.465
Number of observations	452

Based on the results obtained from the stepwise regression analysis, it is found that feelings towards using an autonomous bus/shuttle (five-point scale from very excited – very anxious), perceived usefulness of autonomous bus/shuttle and respondent's perception on the improvement in passenger safety from autonomous bus/shuttle explain about 46% variance on the respondent's intention to use autonomous bus/shuttle if it was available in their area. The coefficient estimates obtained from the regression analysis show that feelings towards using the autonomous bus/shuttle has a significant effect on the acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle, followed by its usefulness and perceived improvement in passenger safety. In line with theoretical expectations of technology acceptance model (Davis 1989; Davis 1993), feelings towards the technology and its perceived usefulness are found to be significant indicators explaining the intention to use the technology.

8.2.2 Preferences and willingness to pay for autonomous bus/shuttle

This section provides the analysis of results obtained from the choice experiment exercise and the willingness to pay for the autonomous bus/shuttle use.

The choice experiment conducted with autonomous public transport, conventional public transport and status quo alternative as the main alternatives in the choice set comprised of alternative specific attribute levels for each of the attributes such as travel time, travel cost, journey information and vehicle interaction.

Section 8.2.2.1 provides the result from the multinomial logit econometric model while Section 8.2.2.2 provides results from the latent class model which combines latent factors such as attitude towards autonomous bus/shuttle into the econometric modelling.

8.2.2.1 Logit analysis and willingness to pay

A multinomial logit (MNL) model was conducted to analyse the factors that affect the choice of autonomous public transport vehicles in respondent's decision making.

The multinomial logit model to analyse choice experiment data is based on the random utility theory (Ben-Akiva and Lerman, 1985). Under the MNL model, the probability that an individual n chooses an alternative i in the choice set can be given by the following equation:

$$P_{ni} = \frac{e^{V_{ni}}}{\sum_j e^{V_{nj}}}$$

where, V_{ni} is the deterministic utility for individual n and alternative i (Train, 2003).

Results from the MNL model are given in Table 8.2.

Table 8.2: Multinomial logit model results from the choice exercise

Variable	Coefficient (t-ratio)
ASC	
Autonomous public transport	-2.892 (-4.61)
Conventional public transport	0.00 (fixed)
Status quo	-6.756 (-10.82)
Travel time	
Autonomous public transport	-0.0548 (-16.40)
Conventional public transport	-0.0755 (-12.71)
Travel cost	
Autonomous public transport	-0.743 (-18.67)
Conventional public transport	-1.446 (-8.21)
Journey information	
Autonomous public transport	
- Mobile app + Vehicle HMI	0.247 (4.40)
- Steward + Mobile app	0.302 (4.96)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + RTI at bus stop	-0.394 (-5.97)
- Driver + Mobile app	0.627 (4.56)
Vehicle interaction	
Autonomous public transport	
- Audio-visual HMI	0.177 (3.10)
- Adaptive visual HMI + vehicle buttons	0.106 (1.73)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + vehicle stop button	-0.424 (-4.97)
Number of observations	5460

Number of individuals	455
Final log-likelihood	-5065.151
Number of estimated parameters	13
Rho square	0.156
Adjusted Rho square	0.153

The MNL model results show that respondents provide a negative ASC value for autonomous public transport and the status quo alternative in comparison to the conventional public transport. The alternative specific constant (ASC) captures any unobserved factors affecting the choice of an alternative (Louviere *et al.*, 2000). In this case, it can be seen that respondents have a slightly lower preference for autonomous public transport vehicles in comparison to the conventional public transport vehicle. This preference is found to be more pronounced in case of the status quo alternative, where more respondents seem to prefer the conventional public transport alternative in comparison to the status quo alternative.

The coefficient estimates for the travel time and travel cost attributes across the autonomous and conventional public transport alternatives show the correct signs and high statistical significance. In this case it is found that respondents provide a higher disutility for travel time as well as travel cost in case of conventional public transport alternative. Based on the model results, it can be seen that respondents provide a positive and significant coefficient estimate for the autonomous public transport journey information such as using mobile app and vehicle HMI as well as getting journey information using steward and mobile app. In case of conventional public transport alternative, a negative and significant coefficient estimate is obtained for driver and RTI at bus-stop, implying that respondents view RTI at bus-stop as a disutility compared to getting journey information using the mobile app.

While respondents provide a positive and significant coefficient estimate for vehicle interaction using the audio-visual HMI in case of autonomous public transport vehicles, respondents provide a negative coefficient estimate for vehicle interaction using driver and vehicle stop buttons in case of conventional public transport vehicle.

Using the delta method for WTP estimation (Langford, 1994), the following results were obtained for the WTP measures:

Table 8.3: WTP estimates from multinomial logit model

Variable	WTP estimate (t-ratio)
Travel time	
Autonomous public transport	-0.074 (-16.65)
Conventional public transport	-0.052 (-17.84)
Journey information	
Autonomous public transport	
- Mobile app + Vehicle HMI	0.333 (4.34)
- Steward + Mobile app	0.407 (4.86)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + RTI at bus stop	-0.272 (-5.85)
- Driver + Mobile app	0.434 (8.43)
Vehicle interaction	
Autonomous public transport	
- Audio-visual HMI	0.239 (3.06)
- Adaptive visual HMI + vehicle buttons	0.143 (1.74)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + vehicle stop button	-0.293 (-7.81)

It is found that the willingness to pay to improve travel time is higher for autonomous public transport vehicles. In case of the autonomous public transport attribute levels for journey information, respondents provided a high and positive WTP for ‘steward and mobile app’. For conventional public transport alternative, respondents gave a negative WTP for obtaining journey information through ‘driver and RTI at bus-stop’, implying that respondents do not highly value obtaining journey information using RTI at bus-stop in case of conventional public transport vehicle. In contrast to this attribute level, respondents provided a positive WTP for journey information through ‘driver and mobile app’.

The WTP for vehicle interaction attribute level ‘audio-visual HMI’ for autonomous public transport alternative had a positive and significant

WTP while ‘adaptive visual HMI and vehicle buttons’ did not provide a statistically significant positive WTP estimate. Vehicle interaction attribute level ‘driver and vehicle stop button’ in case of conventional public transport alternative provided a significant and negative WTP estimate.

8.2.2.2 Latent class model:

The latent class (LC) model allows for combining latent factors affecting respondents’ choices in the econometric model to explain the variation in choice across the different individuals. The LC model thus allows for segregation of individuals based on various finite segments to allow for respondent heterogeneity (Lee *et al.*, 2021). The latent class model can be given as follows:

Figure 8.19: Latent class choice model (adapted from Sfeir *et al.*, 2021)

The latent class model was formed based on the attitudinal questions included in the survey. Thus, respondents’ attitudes towards the autonomous bus/shuttle such as autonomous bus ease of use, HMI ease of use, autonomous bus usefulness, improvement in passenger safety and other road user safety along with autonomous bus comfort were included in the latent class model. The following results were obtained from the latent class model:

Table 8.4: Latent class model

Variable	Coefficient (t-ratio)
ASC	
Autonomous public transport	1.247 (0.46)
Conventional public transport	0.00 (fixed)
Status quo	-5.648 (-4.46)
<u>Latent Class 1</u>	
Travel time	
Autonomous public transport	-0.075 (-4.00)
Conventional public transport	-0.046 (-3.11)
Travel cost	
Autonomous public transport	-0.752 (-4.02)
Conventional public transport	-0.307 (-0.68)
Journey information	
Autonomous public transport	
- Mobile app + Vehicle HMI	0.239 (1.54)
- Steward + Mobile app	0.485 (3.81)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + RTI at bus stop	-0.505 (-4.84)
- Driver + Mobile app	-0.533 (-1.14)
Vehicle interaction	
Autonomous public transport	
- Audio-visual HMI	0.476 (2.37)
- Adaptive visual HMI + vehicle buttons	0.498 (3.15)
Conventional public transport	
- Driver + vehicle stop button	0.246 (0.76)
<u>Latent Class 2</u>	
Travel time	
Autonomous public transport	-0.105 (-4.29)
Conventional public transport	-0.08 (-9.67)
Travel cost	
Autonomous public transport	-1.45 (-3.63)
Conventional public transport	-1.38 (-4.76)

<p>Journey information</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile app + Vehicle HMI - Steward + Mobile app <p>Conventional public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver + RTI at bus stop - Driver + Mobile app <p>Vehicle interaction</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audio-visual HMI - Adaptive visual HMI + vehicle buttons <p>Conventional public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver + vehicle stop button 	<p>-0.168 (-0.96)</p> <p>-0.215 (-0.39)</p> <p>-0.265 (-0.37)</p> <p>0.631 (1.96)</p> <p>0.493 (0.579)</p> <p>0.297 (0.619)</p> <p>-0.176 (-0.21)</p>
<p><u>Latent Class 3</u></p> <p>Travel time</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <p>Conventional public transport</p> <p>Travel cost</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <p>Conventional public transport</p> <p>Journey information</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile app + Vehicle HMI - Steward + Mobile app <p>Conventional public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver + RTI at bus stop - Driver + Mobile app <p>Vehicle interaction</p> <p>Autonomous public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audio-visual HMI - Adaptive visual HMI + vehicle buttons <p>Conventional public transport</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver + vehicle stop button 	<p>-0.005 (-0.08)</p> <p>-0.069 (-4.00)</p> <p>-3.963 (-7.58)</p> <p>-1.831 (-1.48)</p> <p>-3.985 (-1.07)</p> <p>0.835 (0.788)</p> <p>-0.149 (-0.46)</p> <p>1.183 (2.05)</p> <p>-3.82 (-1.16)</p> <p>0.137 (0.04)</p> <p>-0.958 (-3.12)</p>
<p>Class Allocation (probability)</p> <p>Latent class 1</p>	<p>0.549</p>

Latent class 2	0.290
Latent class 3	0.161
Latent class variables	
delta_a	5.668 (5.68)
Peou ab easy to use a	0.187 (0.27)
Peou hmi easy a	0.163 (0.42)
Att ab useful a	0.0089 (0.01)
Att ab passenger safety a	-0.424 (-1.05)
Att ab road user safety a	0.053 (0.21)
Att ab comfortable a	-0.045 (-0.078)
Bc ab feeling a	-0.094 (-0.15)
Bc ab use replacement a	-1.300 (-4.54)
Sn weighted social norm a	-0.424 (-0.76)
delta_b	4.481 (4.49)
Peou ab easy to use b	0.194 (0.27)
Peou hmi easy b	0.143 (0.473)
Att ab useful b	0.085 (0.13)
Att ab passenger safety b	-0.186 (-0.58)
Att ab road user safety b	0.034 (0.100)
Att ab comfortable b	-0.407 (-0.51)
Bc ab feeling b	-0.375 (-0.495)
Bc ab use replacement b	-0.797 (-2.21)
Sn weighted social norm b	-0.455 (-0.73)
Number of observations	5460
Number of individuals	455
Final log-likelihood	-4009.873
Number of estimated parameters	55
Rho square	0.3315
Adjusted Rho square	0.3223

Based on the results obtained from the latent class analysis (LCA), it can be seen that respondents in class one shows a positive and significant coefficient estimate for obtaining journey information from steward and mobile app with the autonomous public transport alternative. Respondents within this class show a negative coefficient estimates for journey information variables for conventional public transport. In case of vehicle interaction levels, respondents again show a positive and significant coefficient estimate for audio-visual HMI and adaptive visual HMI along with vehicle buttons for autonomous public transport. It can be seen that respondents within this class have a positive willingness to pay for autonomous public transport variables. Travel time and travel cost within this class has the expected negative value with higher significance level for the autonomous public transport alternative. Class one can thus be associated with respondents who have a higher interest in autonomous public transport attributes such as journey information and vehicle interaction but who regard the travel time from the autonomous public transport alternative as a higher disutility compared to conventional public transport alternative.

In case of class two, negative and significant coefficient estimates are obtained for travel time and travel cost variables across both the autonomous and conventional public transport alternatives. Within this class however, negative and statistically insignificant coefficient estimates are obtained for journey information and vehicle interaction variable levels for the autonomous public transport. In case of conventional public transport alternative, a positive and significant coefficient estimate is obtained for having journey information through driver and mobile app with the conventional public transport. Other variable levels for journey information and vehicle interaction are not found to be statistically significant within this latent class. The respondents within this latent class are found to have significant coefficient estimates for travel time and travel cost across both the autonomous and conventional public transport alternatives. This latent class can thus be associated with the group of people who regard the travel time and travel cost for autonomous public transport alternative as a higher disutility without a significant preference for other attributes in the autonomous public transport alternative such as, journey information and vehicle interaction.

For latent class three, respondents provide a significant coefficient estimate for conventional public transport travel time and autonomous public transport travel cost. The respondents within this class consider the travel cost of autonomous public transport and the travel time for

conventional public transport to be of a higher disutility. Journey information and vehicle interaction variable levels for the autonomous public transport alternative do not have a statistically significant coefficient estimate. In case of conventional public transport, respondents provide a positive and significant coefficient estimate for obtaining journey information from driver and mobile app. Respondents also provide a negative and significant coefficient estimate for interacting with conventional public transport vehicle through the driver and the vehicle stop buttons. This latent class belongs to respondents who value the disutility from autonomous and conventional public transport alternatives differently, while still preferring conventional public transport over autonomous public transport.

The latent class allocation shows that about 59% of respondents belong to class 1, 29% respondents belong to class 2 and 16% respondents belong to class 3. Based on the coefficient estimates obtained for the latent variables, it is found that respondent's willingness to use autonomous bus variable (Bc ab use replacement) has a significant coefficient estimate. Thus the main factors that affect the choice of the latent classes is the behavioural factor of using autonomous public transport vehicles. Results from the explanatory variables within the latent classes show that respondents who are more willing to switch to autonomous public transport are more likely to choose class one and class two over class three. This preference is found to be more pronounced in case of class one. The negative sign of the coefficient estimates results from the inverse scale of the variable in the questionnaire implying that a higher value of the scale corresponds to a lower willingness to use autonomous public transport.

The Likelihood ratio (LR) test provides the improvement in the model fit across the MNL and latent class models. The LR test is based on the final log-likelihood from the latent class and the MNL as well as the number of parameters estimated from both these models. The LR test statistics from the LC and MNL model show that the LC model offers substantial improvement in model fit compared to the MNL model.

8.3 Summary

8.3.1 Discussion of survey results

This study has aimed to examine the perception and acceptance towards autonomous bus and the willingness to pay towards using autonomous buses.

Based on the results obtained from the survey, the following conclusions can be made:

- Younger respondents (18-25 year and 26-40 year old) have a higher acceptance of autonomous bus/shuttle and consider the autonomous bus and HMI to be easier to use. Female respondents are more conservative in their attitude towards autonomous bus use and perceived ease of use.
- Respondents across all age and gender groups prefer communicating with the vehicle using 'mobile applications'. This is followed by 'auditory communication' with the vehicle and having 'large fonts on HMI display'.
- Younger respondents consider autonomous bus to be a useful mode of transport. Older respondents consider that autonomous bus 'maybe' a useful mode of transport. Male respondents are more certain of that autonomous bus can be 'useful'.
- Most respondents across all the age groups 'don't know' if autonomous buses can improve passenger safety or the safety of other road users. Women respondents are more uncertain and negative if autonomous buses can improve passenger safety or safety of other road users, in comparison to male respondents.
- Regression analysis for technological acceptance model show that the acceptance of autonomous bus use is dependent on feelings towards autonomous bus, perceived usefulness of autonomous bus/shuttle and perceived improvement in passenger safety by autonomous bus/shuttle.
- Logit analysis and WTP estimate show that respondents have a positive WTP for journey information attribute levels of autonomous public transport alternative. Respondents also provide a positive WTP for vehicle interaction attribute level such as 'audio-visual HMI' for autonomous public transport alternative. A negative WTP is obtained for journey information by 'real-time information at bus-stop' and for vehicle interaction by 'driver and vehicle stop buttons' in case of conventional public transport alternative.
- Latent class analysis provides a significant improvement over logit model and show that respondents can be classified in to three classes based on the attitudinal questions. Class one belongs to respondents who have some interest in autonomous public transport

attributes, class two belong to respondents who are more conservative and prefer conventional public transport while class three belong to individuals who value travel time and travel cost differently over the autonomous and conventional public transport alternatives.

8.3.2 Relevance to pilot findings

The results presented in the current section can be examined as complementary to the findings related to the pilot studies presented in Chapters 2 to 7. The latter reflected attitudes and opinions of users who tested certain types of CAVs hence leading to conclusions deriving through direct experience. On the other hand, pilot related results might suffer from representativeness issues due to lower sample sizes. Although the statistical inference to the population level takes to some extent into account the sample size, it could still be the case that low sample sizes might not allow the obtainment of significant results in certain cases. In the aforementioned pilot analysis, it has been already reported that certain response groups were merged into new categories, within an effort to increase their frequencies. In the same direction, different types of statistical tests were also used to address issues related to low sample size. On the other hand, although stated preference data refer to hypothetical scenarios and participants do not experience the system under consideration, it is possible to achieve higher sample size. Hence, a synthesis of both approaches could allow for more insights regarding the issue of acceptance and use.

Initially, the analysis presented in the current chapter focused on intention to use and its determinants. Feeling towards the automated bus use (ranging from very excited to very anxious) had a significant effect. Pilot analysis suggested that feelings were significantly associated to acceptance related questions in all pilots. Most significant results were related to the trustful feeling, however, other feelings such as safe, nervous, careful or insecure also had significant impact. Moreover, the influence of feelings remained significant in cross-pilot analysis. These findings were consistent with the results presented regarding the intention to use the automated bus, suggesting their importance as a potential predictor of acceptance.

Ease of use was another factor that significantly affected the autonomous bus acceptance. This finding is consistent with previous literature regarding the positive influence of ease of use on acceptance but was also consistent with several pilot findings. In particular, some of the pilots examined the “difficulty” in using the CAV which can be treated as the opposite of ease of use. The pilot findings suggested a negative relationship between difficulty to use and acceptance. This finding occurred in pilots related to passenger cars CAVs (pilot 2 and pilot 4). In particular, the cross-pilot analysis of the two aforementioned studies suggested that difficulty to use was associated to the intention to use upon availability and public acceptance.

Finally, improvement of passenger safety was another significant predictor of intention to use. This outcome is consistent with several findings from the pilot analysis. For instance, “safe” was of the feelings positively associated with acceptance related indicators. Also, safety (either as an expected benefit or shortcoming) was significantly related to several indicators of acceptance in pilot 1 and pilot 4. Moreover, in pilots involving passenger car CAVs, there was a positive relation of vehicle behaviour was perceived as better than a human driver and acceptance. Although this is not directly linked to safety it could be an indication that some aspect of “better” could be linked to a perception of safety. However, the latter is an issue that should be further investigated.

Among the results of the logit analysis regarding mode choice, the presence of steward combined with the availability of a mobile app, significantly increased the utility for choosing the automated bus. The results of pilot 1 suggested that the absence of human driver was one of the most significant factors that negatively affected the acceptance of the automated bus. Hence, both studies revealed a common pattern with respect to the importance of the human staff presence even on fully automated system. The latter could be particularly important during the initial stages of use while trust with the technology is still being built.

With respect to journey information, the presence of mobile app as a mean of acquiring trip information was important both for automated and conventional solutions. This could be possibly related to the flexibility and independence these apps could provide. In pilot 5, it was concluded that the acceptance of smart and connected environment apps was related to obstacle frequency and independence in trips. Moreover, it was found that

participants would be willing to pay more, but only up to 5 €/month, for specific types of information.

The two approaches (pilot studies and stated preference survey) led to several similar outcomes, however, the difference between intention to use the former and mode choice in the latter needs to be reported. In particular, acceptance-related questions across the various pilots received positive responses in most cases; participants stated a high likelihood of using the technology. The results of the MNL model on the other hand suggested that, compared to the status quo preferred mode, both conventional and automated buses were less likely to be selected. Another difference is about the gender effect found in the stated preference regarding usefulness, ease of use and safety improvement due to automated public transport (factors that are predictors of acceptance). Although some gender differences were found in the pilots, these were mostly negligible. These differences could be attributed to a series of factors:

Direct experience: Direct experience with the technology increases familiarity and may improve crucial acceptance related predictors such as trust. Participants in the stated preference survey did not experience any type of CAV which may have affected the results. Their preferences relied on hypothetical scenarios. On the other hand participants in pilots not only experienced CAVs as part of the pilot but in some cases (for instance pilot 4) they might have been uses of services such as shared fleet.

Sample size: The stated preference survey consisted of a higher number of participants which may have affected results. Pilots were limited to lower sample sizes.

Sample homogeneity: Within each pilot, participants were living in the same country while the panel of the stated preference survey was global.

Attributes: Ultimately, CAVs will be evaluated not only regarding safety but also their reliability, headway times (for public transport CAVs), travel cost and travel time. These aspects were not investigated thoroughly in the pilots and participants formed their opinion mainly through the CAV experience. Although variables such as income were included, these details were not provided by all participants. Also, sample size might not allow for inference from some individual characteristics. On the other hand, participants in the stated preference survey (current chapter)

reported their mode choice preference considering the travel time and cost. These are possibly some of the most important aspects of acceptance for any transportation system that need to be considered.

8.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations can be made based on the conclusions obtained from the study:

- 'Using mobile applications', 'large fonts on HMI display' and 'auditory communication' are preferred HMI methods by respondents.
- For requirements towards in-vehicle assistance and information, respondents prefer 'communication with the vehicle for special assistance', 'visual communication with the vehicle such as HMI and mobile apps' and the 'presence of steward'.
- A high proportion of individuals responded to 'don't know' for improvement in passenger safety and improvement in other road safety by autonomous bus/shuttle. Further research is required for the effect of autonomous bus on the safety of other road users. Moreover, further experience of autonomous bus/shuttle by the public could alter the perception towards these attitudinal questions.

9 Attitudes to an Autonomous Air Taxi

9.1 Introduction

This section is concerned with assessing and influencing the public perception and acceptance of autonomous air taxi before and after simulated flight trials. The concept is for a short hop autonomous air vehicle to fly individuals or small numbers of people between pre-defined locations. These systems are intended to be fully autonomous. The only input the user is to provide is their choice of destination.

There is likely to be a degree of reluctance in the public use of such systems, in the same way that autonomous cars have. However, the use of autonomous cars, or at least partially autonomous, have become prevalent and more accepted. This project is looking to first determine the perception and attitude of an autonomous air taxi and then to influence them in a positive manner.

As with many aspects of modern life that contain a degree of risk, such as driving, crossing the road, or travelling by air, people are more likely to accept such a risk as they are familiar with it. A similar logic is being applied in this work. The experiment consists of first surveying a participant's attitude to autonomous air taxis, then exposing them to one via a full motion flight simulator and then asking them again how they feel. Thus, the change in the participants opinions can be determined. It can also inform under what parameters such as system will be accepted.

An additional interest is that of the impact of autonomy levels. For fully autonomous systems there is no user interaction other than setting the goal for the system, in this case the destination. A step down from such a system is called autonomy by exception, where the system will carry out actions, unless the user intervenes. Further down still is autonomy by consent, where the system does carry out actions until the user provides consent for its proposed actions. The participants in this work are flying under either of the latter two.

The research questions asked in this work is as follows:

- *What are the current attitudes to Autonomous Air Taxis?*
- *Can these attitudes be improved by a positive experience of a CAV through simulation?*
- *Does the autonomy mode, exception or consent, influence attitudes?*

9.2 Experimental Setup

The experiment starts with the system diagram which shows the physical components used during the simulated flight trial, the information flowing between them, and the information being given to the user. The experimental procedure is listed and then each step is explained in detail in the following subsections.

9.2.1 System diagram

The systems surrounding the user and how they interact are shown in Figure 9.1. The setup consists of four computers each responsible for different parts of the simulation:

- Motion
- Visuals
- Control Desk and Simulation Model
- Audio and User Interface

The inter process communication is performed using a mixture of data streams that use the UDP protocol and ROS network nodes and topics. This allows for the state of the aircraft, commands between the user and the simulation model, and the triggering of events by the operator to be transferred between the different computers.

The visuals are created using the XPlane software package and are projected onto the inside of the dome of the simulation platform.

The graphical User Interface (GUI), see Annex 2, was created using the MATLAB app designer toolbox. Two GUIs were created, one for the user inside the simulation platform and one on the control desk for the operator to control the simulation and the trigger events.

The visual cues to the user take the form of flashing indicator flight in the bottom right of the GUI and new entries in the dialogue box on the right-hand side. The audio cues are played to the user via a headset in the form of pre-recorded messages. The audio message indicates when the mission starts, there is an update in the destination and when the aircraft is diverted.

The simulation model is based on the MyCopter dynamics model with an autopilot built in to allow the vehicle to fly automatically on a pre-determined flight path, defined by a series of waypoints.

Figure 9.1: Systems diagram of the experiment

9.2.2 Experimental procedure

The experimental steps are as follow:

- Opening Brief
 - Purpose of Experiment
 - Scenario being simulated
 - Health and Safety and data Protection
 - Consent Form
- Pre Flight Survey
- Simulated Flight Trials
- Flight Debrief
- Post Flight Survey

Most of the data acquisition is carried out via the online pre and post flight surveys with multiple choice questions. Other data is acquired during flight trial, where the autonomy mode and if the user changes the destination selected by the computer is recorded. The audio and visuals of the experiment were not recorded.

The total flight time for any of the flights is approximately 5 minutes, with flight variations for each route taken and how long the user takes to choose a destination before take-off. The pre-flight survey time is approximately 5 minutes while the post flight survey is approximately 2 minutes. In total, including the opening brief, closing brief, and setting the user up in the simulation platform, each test point took approximately 30 minutes. Total

flight time for all of the experiments, with 56 participants was approximately 4hr 40mins.

9.2.3 Opening Brief

Before the flight trial an opening brief is given to the participant verbally. This was to give them the following details:

- Why the experiment is being conducted
- What scenario is being simulated
- Health and safety precautions
- Details of data protection
- Obtain consent from the participant.

The broad strokes of the opening brief as follows:

Purpose of Experiment

- To determine current attitudes to autonomous air taxis
- To determine the attitudes after a positive experience of such a system
- To determine the impact of the level of autonomy available on these attitudes.

Scenario

- The participant has recently arrived at Liverpool John Lennon airport by air
- The subsequent plan is to go to Liverpool City Centre to meet friends. This journey will be made via air taxi
- The participant is tasked with spotting specific landmarks during air-taxi flight to give the participant a cognitive load during the flight.
- They are pre-warned that they will be required to make some sort of decision on their destination during the flight in response to an event

The full brief can be found in Annex 3.

9.2.4 Flight Trial

The simulated flight trials are carried out between the pre and post flight surveys. It consists of the following stages:

- Route selection by user (audio and visual cues)
- Take off
- Cruise

D7.3 – Data analysis of user acceptance from trials and simulations

- Minor event notifications (visual cues)
- Event trigger (audio and visual cues)
- Decision made by user (visual cues)
- Cruise
- Landing

During the flight, the user is asked to spot landmarks in order to provide them with a distraction task that is to be interrupted by the diversion event. Before the event is triggered, several minor event notifications are sent to the cockpit GUI, such as wind change, heavy traffic and poor weather warnings. The autonomy mode is picked at random before the triggering of the main event, the total number of each of the modes tested was planned for the testing. During the flight, the actions that the user takes is noted, either they press continue to accept the computer-suggested actions or they pick the destination themselves. A sequence of events and actions is shown in Figure 9.2, where each branch is a decision.

Figure 9.2: Sequence of actions, events, and decisions by the user during a flight trial

9.2.5 GUI description

The GUIs, both for inside the cockpit and on the control desk, were created using MATLAB's app designer toolbox. The cockpit GUI has four major components, a control panel, a map panel, a dialogue box and indicator lights. A simplified layout is shown in Figure 9.3. A detailed example is given in Annex 2.

Figure 9.3: Simplified layout of the GUI the user is presented with.

User Control Panel and Event Pop Up

This is the only part of the GUI that the user interacts with. They are able to select a destination, start their journey, update their destination and make decisions during the event. It consists of a set of buttons displayed on a touch screen panel in front of the user during the flight.

Pick Destination and Update Destination

The sequence of picking a destination (A-B) and then updating it (C-D) is shown in Figure 9.4. The user is required to first select a destination and then start the journey. Once the start button is selected, an audio cue is played and the simulation started. The user has the option to change their mind before or during departure.

Figure 9.4: Step by step screen shots of the user selecting and updated their destination

Event Pop Up for Exception and Consent

During the flight, the operator triggers minor notifications to indicate to the user that something is going on. These minor events are simply messages sent to the cockpit display. The three possible minor events are Poor Weather, Heavy Traffic and Wind Change. The minor messages are to give the user a plausible reason why the aircraft is trying to divert to another landing location.

When the event is triggered during the flight the user is given one of two pop-up displays, depending on the autonomy mode being used. Depending on the autonomy mode in use, either the panel in Figure 9.5 A or B is presented to the user. Only the ‘autonomy by exception’ mode has the timer, which give the user 20 seconds to decide whether the aircraft can divert to the planned destination or whether they wish to pick a different destination themselves. For ‘autonomy by consent’, the user has no time limit. If the user does not interact or make the decision, the ‘by exception’ panel will divert whereas the ‘by consent’ panel will continue to the originally selected destination.

Figure 9.5: Comparison between the pop ups that different autonomy modes present the user

Map Display

The map display is shown in Figure 9.6. The purpose of the map is to orientate the user and to clearly indicate the planned flight path of the aircraft. The possible and selected routes are shown as red dotted lines,

selected routes as solid red lines and current location as a blue dot. The starting point and destinations are also labelled on the map.

Figure 9.6: Map display before (left) and after (right) and route is selected. The possible destinations and aircraft location (blue dot) are also shown

Dialogue Box

The dialogue box is shown in Figure 9.7. The purpose of the dialogue box is to give the user a written history of what the system has been doing and why it is carrying out the current action. It consists of a simple time stamp and descriptive text. Each button-press and event results in an entry in the dialogue box being displayed to the user.

Figure 9.7: Dialogue box during a typical mission

9.2.6 Pre Flight Survey

The first survey is completed before the participant undertakes the flight trial. The following information is provided by the participant:

- Basic Information – Gender, Age, Education, Work Status
- Current User Experience of – Mobility Apps, Driving, Piloting
- User Autonomy Experience – Driver Assist, Partial Autonomy, Full Autonomy
- Attitude – Me using CAVS, others using CAVS

The intent behind the survey is to first take basic demographic info from the user, to determine their level of experience and then to find their attitudes to autonomous air taxis. A randomly generated candidate number is assigned to each user and used to match the pre and post flight surveys. Thus the data is anonymised upon acquisition. A total of 27 questions are asked during the pre-flight survey. The full questionnaire can be found in Annex 4.

9.2.7 Closing Brief and Post Flight Survey

At the conclusion of the flight trial the user is reminded of the purpose of the experiment. They are then asked to reflect upon the flight as if it was real, with a focus on the level of control, how safe they felt and the amount of information they received from the system.

They are then asked about the following topics

- Reflection on the Flight Trial
- Reflections on if the flight happened near me

The full de brief is shown in Annex 5 and the post flight survey in Annex 6.

9.3 Results

The results are broken down into four components as follows.

Analysis breakdown:

- Demographics and Bias
- Current Attitudes
- Change in Attitudes
- Influence of Exception / Consent

The results are analysed as aggregate answers and correlations for between age, education level, driving years and driver assist experience are made.

9.3.1 Demographics and Bias

The participants were recruited from the School of Engineering at the University of Liverpool. The recruitment was undertaken using a combination of email advertisement and word of mouth. This meant that the type of person participating is likely to have knowledge of engineering, be younger, and is more likely to be male. Since the email advertisement requires the participant to approach the authors if they are interested, this also creates a tendency of the participant to already be interested in the subject before participating in the experiment.

The basic demographics for the entire test cohort are shown in Figure 9.8. There is clearly a bias in the cohort towards younger, male, and higher educated individuals. The largest age group was 26-35 years old, the largest education level was undergraduate degree and the ratios for male and female was 70% and 30% respectively. Most people are either full time workers or students, a mixture of PhD student and undergraduates, most likely either doing or have completed an engineering degree.

Figure 9.8: Basic Demographic info of cohort

9.3.1.1 Experience

The experience of the participants for piloting is shown in Figure 9.9, for driving in Figure 9.10 and for using mobility applications Figure 9.11. Very few participants had any piloting experience, 98% having none. There was a range of driving experience amongst the participants, where >16 years was the most common and 1-5 years the least. Most people only had experience of routeing and guidance and public transport apps. In later correlations only the driving years from this data set are used as the other

sets are argued to be too bias to be able to provide a meaningful answer.

Figure 9.9: Piloting Experience of the Participants

Figure 9.10: Driving Experience of the Participants

Figure 9.11: Participants Experience using different mobility apps

9.3.1.2 Automation Experience

The levels of automation experience for a range of autonomy levels are shown in Figure 9.12 – Figure 9.14. Very few participants had any experience of a fully autonomous system, where 89% had none, and only a few had some experience of partial autonomy, where 67% had none.

However, there was a range of experience levels for lower-level autonomy systems. Because of this, only driver assist experience is used in future correlations as it is the only correlation from the three autonomy levels that would give meaningful answers.

Figure 9.12: Experience using fully autonomous systems

Figure 9.13: Experience using partially autonomous systems.

Figure 9.14: Experience using low level autonomous systems

9.3.1.3 Correlations and Bias

The bias within the cohort's demographics can be seen in Figure 9.15. The most common group was males, 26-35 and full-time workers. There is a tendency for the demographic to become less educated and less female as the age group increases. Because of the low number of people in the 66-75 and above ages there is uncertainty over the accuracy of any comparisons for those age groups.

Because of the low number of people in the no school or secondary school level education, in later cross correlations, they are omitted due to a trend not being possible to discern.

Figure 9.15: Correlations between age, education, and gender within the cohort

9.3.2 Current attitudes

The current attitudes to autonomous air taxis are shown in the following sections. The results are grouped into aggregate (9.3.2.1) and correlations plots (9.3.2.2).

The following correlations are made

- Age vs attitudes
- Education vs attitudes
- Driver Experience vs Attitudes
- Driver Assist experience vs Attitudes

Only these correlations are made due to low distribution in the answer to other questions or because it was considered that other correlations would not be of interest.

9.3.2.1 Aggregate

The attitudes of the cohort when viewed as a whole are shown in Figure 9.16 – Figure 9.19. As a group, the participants were positive about others using an autonomous air taxi, while in urban areas, and in rural areas.

They were ‘probable’ about their possible future use of such services, but positive about the concept of their use. They cited system failure and risk of accident as the most important issues that they would be concerned about.

In terms of safety, they were neutral but leant towards positive and were almost perfectly split when asked about consent for the system to change its behaviour.

The cohort’s awareness of autonomous air taxi systems was reasonably low and when asked about control they were positive about the system being in complete control but were more positive for the partial control scenario.

Figure 9.16: Aggregate attitude in terms of the use of autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.17: Aggregate attitudes to the future use, concept and issues of concern for autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.18: Aggregate attitudes regarding trust, safety and consent

Figure 9.19: Aggregate attitudes in terms of awareness and control of autonomous air taxis

9.3.2.2 Correlations

The correlations plots were created by assigning a number to each answer given by the participants in ascending order. As an example

- [Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree] becomes [-2 -1 0 1 2]
- [18-25,26-35,36-45,46-55,56-65,65-75] becomes [1 2 3 4 5 6]

To show the density of each combination of variable, such as agree and 18-25, the number is shifted up/down or left/right so that each pairing results in a cluster of points on a scatter plot.

The trendlines and averages were found by simply either averaging or by fitting a linear equation to the unshifted numbers.

9.3.2.2.1 Age vs Attitudes

The results with respect to asking the participants about the use of autonomous air taxis is shown in Figure 9.20. It can be seen that, in all four cases, there is a trend for participants to be less positive about the use of autonomous air taxis with increasing age.

The results related to questions about the level of control, consent and safety are shown in Figure 9.21. For user consent to the system's actions the cohort is neutral, when asked about control they are neutral about complete control and positive about partial control of the system's behaviour. When asked about safety they are again neutral. For all four, the trend is for a more negative opinion as the participant gets older.

The results relating to the questions about the level of awareness and the concept of autonomous air taxi is shown in Figure 9.22. It can be seen that

the awareness is low and gets lower with age. For the concept in general, the opinion is high and stays reasonable high with age.

Table 9.1: Summary of findings from correlations between age and attitudes

	Topic	Mean	Median	Trend with Age
Figure 9.20	Others Use	Neutral – Agree / (25-36) – (36-45)	Agree	Decreasing
	Urban Use	Neutral – Agree / (25-36) – (36-45)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Rural Use	Neutral / (25-36) – (36-45)	Agree	Decreasing
	Future Use	Probably / (25-36) – (36-45)	Probably	Decreasing
Figure 9.21	Consent	Neutral / (25-36) – (36-45)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Partial Control	Agree / (25-36) – (36-45)	Agree	Decreasing
	Complete Control	Neutral / (25-36) – (36-45)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Safety	Neutral / (25-36) – (36-45)	Neutral	Decreasing
Figure 9.22	Awareness	Low - Med / (25-36) – (36-45)	Low	Decreasing
	Concept	Neither - Good / (25-36) – (36-45)	Good	Decreasing

Figure 9.20: Correlations between participant age and attitudes towards use of autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.21: Correlations between participants age and attitudes towards consent, control, and safety.

Figure 9.22: Correlations between participants age and awareness and opinion on concept

9.3.2.2.2 Education vs Attitudes

The correlation between the education level of the participants and their attitudes are shown in Figure 9.23 – Figure 9.25.

When asked about other’s using autonomous air taxis near them the average was from neutral to agree with a trend towards a more positive opinion as the education level increases. For urban use this was closer to neutral and for rural it was closer to agree, while both are still trending upwards with education. When asked about future use participants were positive and this trended upward with education.

When asked about consent the average was neutral with a mostly flat trend with education. For complete and partial control they answered neutral and agree respectively with a trend to a more positive opinion. For safety, participants were between neutral and agree with a slight increase with education level.

A preference for awareness of the systems actions increased with education with an average near low and for the concept between a neutral and good opinion is held. Both of these opinions again increase with education level.

Table 9.2: Summary of findings from correlations between education and attitudes

	Topic	Mean	Median	Trend with Education
Figure 9.23	Others Use	Neutral – Agree / Fur Edu – UG	Agree	Increasing
	Urban Use	Neutral / Fur Edu – UG	Neutral	Increasing
	Rural Use	Agree / Fur Edu – UG	Agree	Increasing
	Future Use	Probably / Fur Edu – UG	Probably	Increasing
Figure 9.24	Consent	Neutral / Fur Edu – UG	Neutral	~Flat
	Partial Control	Agree / Fur Edu – UG	Agree	Increasing
	Complete Control	Neutral / Fur Edu – UG	Neutral	Increasing
	Safety	Neutral - Agree/ Fur Edu – UG	Neutral	Increasing
Figure 9.25		Low - Med / Fur Edu – UG	Low	Increasing
		Neither - Good / Fur Edu – UG	Good	Increasing

Figure 9.23: Correlations between participant education and attitudes towards use of autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.24: Correlations between participants education and attitudes towards consent, control, and safety

Figure 9.25: Correlations between participants education and awareness and opinion on concept

9.3.2.2.3 Driving Experience vs Attitudes

The comparison between the level of driving experience with attitudes is shown in Figure 9.26 – Figure 9.28. The results are similar to age vs attitude, where a more negative opinion increases with age, this is likely due to the natural tendency for people to have driven longer as they get older.

Answers to questions about others using autonomous air taxis show a positive opinion with a trend towards lower with years driven; where for urban and rural use they show neutral and agree respectively. Future use leans towards probable with a decreasing trend with driving years.

The cohort was neutral for consent with a decreasing trend. When considering control they were neutral over complete control and agree over partial control with both having a decreasing trend. For safety the participants were neutral with a decreasing trend.

As with age vs attitude the cohort has low awareness and were ‘neither’ or ‘good’ about the concept. The trend for both was to decrease with number of years driven.

Table 9.3: Summary of findings from correlations between Driving experience and attitudes

	Topic	Mean	Median	Trend with Driving Years
Figure 9.26	Others Use	Neutral - Agree / (6-10) – (11-15)	Agree	Decreasing
	Urban Use	Neutral - Agree / (6-10) – (11-15)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Rural Use	Neutral - Agree / (6-10) – (11-15)	Agree	Decreasing
	Future Use	Probably / (6-10) – (11-15)	Probably	Decreasing

Figure 9.27	Consent	Neutral / (6-10) – (11-15)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Partial Control	Agree / (6-10) – (11-15)	Agree	Decreasing
	Complete Control	Neutral / (6-10) – (11-15)	Neutral	Decreasing
	Safety	Neutral - Agree / (6-10) – (11-15)	Neutral	Decreasing
Figure 9.28	Awareness	Low - Med / (6-10) – (11-15)	Low	Decreasing
	Concept	Neither - Good / (6-10) – (11-15)	Good	Decreasing

Figure 9.26: Correlations between participant driving years and attitudes towards use of autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.27: Correlations between participants driving years and attitudes towards consent, control, and safety

Figure 9.28: Correlations between participants driving years and awareness and opinion on concept

9.3.2.2.4 Driver Assist Experience vs Attitudes

The correlation between attitudes and driver assist experience is shown in Figure 9.29 – Figure 9.31. Others using the autonomous air taxi has a decreasing trend with experience level. Urban and rural use has virtually flat and decreasing in trend. Likely future use decreased as experience increased.

The cohort was neutral about consent with a decreasing trend with experience levels. For partial control and complete control, they were mostly constant for both. For safety the trend was flat with a neutral average.

The awareness trends increased with driver assist experience with a low awareness average. The concept trend is flat with a good average.

Table 9.4: Summary of findings from correlations between driver assist experience and attitudes

	Topic	Mean	Median	Trend with Driver Assist
Figure 9.29	Others Use	Neutral - Agree / rarely – occasionally	Agree	Decreasing
	Urban Use	Neutral / rarely – occasionally	Neutral	~flat
	Rural Use	Agree / rarely – occasionally	Agree	Decreasing
	Future Use	Probably / rarely – occasionally	Probably	Decreasing
Figure 9.30	Consent	Neutral / rarely – occasionally	Neutral	Decreasing
	Partial Control	Agree / rarely – occasionally	Agree	~flat
	Complete Control	Neutral / rarely – occasionally	Neutral	~flat
	Safety	Neutral - Agree / rarely – occasionally	Neutral	~flat
Figure 9.31	Awareness	Low - Med / rarely – occasionally	Low	Increasing
	Concept	Neither - Good / rarely – occasionally	Good	~flat

Figure 9.29: Correlations between participant driver assist experience and attitudes towards use of autonomous air taxis

Figure 9.30: Correlations between participants driver assist experience and attitudes towards consent, control, and safety.

Figure 9.31: Correlations between participants driver assist experience and awareness and opinion on concept

9.3.2.2.5 Cross Correlation Between Age and Education

This section looks at the cross correlation between the participants age and education in terms of their attitudes to consent, control, and safety. Table 9.5 and Figure 9.32 show this cross correlation. The education levels are coloured while the lower education levels are omitted due to low numbers, but represented as hollow markers.

It can be seen that for consent there is not a great deal of difference between the education levels for each age group. There is a slight increase in opinion as the age groups get older and more educated. For control it can be seen that for partial control there is mostly agreement between the education levels for each age group, but not for complete control. This is likely due to the distribution being lower for this set, most are clustered around the 26-35 age group for agree.

When it comes to safety the education level seems to affect the results, where those with further education have a decreasing trend with age, while the undergraduate and post graduates have an increasing trend with age.

Table 9.5: Summary table of cross correlation between age and education

Topic	Further Education	Undergraduate Education	Postgraduate Education
Consent	~flat	Slightly increasing	Increasing
Complete Control	Increasing	Slightly Increasing	Decreasing
Partial Control	Decreasing	Decreasing	Decreasing
Safety	Decreasing	Increasing	Increasing

Figure 9.32: Cross correlations between age and education

9.3.3 Change in attitudes

In this section the attitudes of the participants after they have conducted the flight trial are assessed. The analysis is broken into two parts, the first looks at the aggregate answers that they gave and the second is looking at the change in their opinion when compared to the answer they gave in the pre-flight survey. The same number assignment as used in 9.3.2.2 is used to calculate the change from the pre to post flight answers. The post flight answers were after the participants were asked to reflect on the experience they just had and to answer imagining if it was a real flight.

9.3.3.1 Post Flight Aggregate

In Figure 9.33 how the participants felt about control is shown. They overwhelmingly felt safe and on average felt they were in control. In Figure 9.34 their answers to trust and safety are shown. It can be seen that they felt safe, trusted the actions of the autonomous system.

Figure 9.33: Aggregate opinions when asked about control after flight trial

Figure 9.34: Aggregate opinions when asked about safety and trust after flight trial

The result of asking the participants about their preferences, in terms of control, information, and consent, is shown in Figure 9.35. They reported that on average they would not have felt safer with more control. They on average would have liked more information. They also wanted to give consent to the proposed actions.

In Figure 9.36 the participants report on their preference for autonomous air taxi use. It can be seen that for all four, where the system is used by them, near them, in urban, or in rural areas, the participants were positive about autonomous air taxi use.

Figure 9.35: Aggregate opinions when asked about preferences after flight trial

Figure 9.36: Aggregate opinions when asked about the use after the flight trials

9.3.3.2 Changes from Pre to Post Flight

A comparison between the system operating under autonomy by consent and by exception is made here. The data sets are split between the two, where:

- Blue markers and orange line are for the autonomy by exception
- Yellow markers and purple line are for autonomy by consent.

The pre-flight survey results are shown in the left most plot. The post flight results are shown in the right-hand plots and top row and the change between the pre and post flight are on the bottom row.

9.3.3.2.1 Safety

It can be seen from Figure 9.37 that after the simulated flight trial there is a net increase in the opinion of the participants for question relating to safety. The increase in the opinion is greater for participants that were operating under autonomy by consent.

Figure 9.37: Change in opinion of each participant between questions about safety

9.3.3.2.2 Trust

From Figure 9.38 the change in opinion is shown for questions related to trust. It can be seen that there is a net positive opinion for both. However, there is little difference between the modes when consider the change in opinion from pre to post flight.

Figure 9.38: Change in opinion of each participant between questions about trust

9.3.3.2.3 Control

Questions relating to partial and complete control of the system can be seen in Figure 9.39. It was found that for questions about feeling safe with the vehicle in control there was a net positive opinion but a moderate increase in the opinion but for the feeling on being in control It was mostly neutral with a reduction in the opinion.

When comparing the answers about complete control in Figure 9.40 it was found that increase in opinion from pre to post when asked about feeling safe, while there is little change when asked about feeling in control.

Figure 9.39: Change in opinion of each participant between questions about partial control

Figure 9.40: Change in opinion of each participant between questions about complete control

9.3.3.2.4 Use

When comparing the questions relating to use in Figure 9.41, it can be seen that a net increase in opinion was found for all four questions.

Figure 9.41: Change in opinion of each participant between questions about use

9.4 Discussion

9.4.1 Current Attitudes

9.4.1.1 Aggregate

From the results of this study it was found that people are as a group happy for an autonomous air taxi to operate near them, see Figure 9.16. They feel better about the use in rural areas than in urban ones, although for both the opinions are still positive. They are likely to use such system in the future. This means that the cohort surveyed, young, educated and with engineering backgrounds, are likely to be willing to use the systems.

From Figure 9.17 they report that they are most concerned about system failure (29%) and risks of accident (25%) when considering autonomous air taxis. This is useful as these types of issues can be mitigated using redundancies, safety systems, and operational procedures in the same way that current aviation does. That said there is still a significant proportion (15%) that cite lack of control as an issue of concern.

The cohort reports that they would as a whole trust the system to act safely, Figure 9.18, but are neutral about letting it operate without their consent. This would imply that providing consent to the system's actions is not a large issue on a personal level, as is neither happy nor unhappy with not be able to give consent to the systems actions.

Finally, the cohort reports that they are happy with the system being in full control of their journey, Figure 9.19, but would prefer to have partial

control. this implies that the amount of control is again not such a large issue, but more control is preferable. This means that where it is practical and safe to do so, the system should let the user be, or at least feel as if they are, in control.

9.4.1.2 Correlations

From the correlations drawn 9.3.2.2.1 it was found that negative correlation exists with age. This means that acceptance and use of autonomous air taxis is likely to be higher in younger demographics. However, there is a large scatter in answers for each age group, this implies that there is a large variability in the opinions and that other variables are influencing the opinion of each participant. It was found that there is less correlation with age for the questions about consent, safety and concept. This means regardless of age; the cohort feels the same way about these topics.

From 9.3.2.2.2 a positive correlation with education was found. There was a more moderate scatter than was seen with age. This indicates that higher education levels will result in a better opinion of these systems and that it is a stronger relationship. It was also found as with age that there is less correlation between education for consent and safety.

When consider the years a participant has been driving in 9.3.2.2.3 a negative correlation was found. This means that the longer a person has been driving for, the lower their opinion of autonomous air taxis will be. However, there is a large scatter in the answer for each age group and that all correlations are weak. This implies that even if the opinion drops with driving years, it is not the dominate factor. Since driving years and age are likely to be correlated well, it is suggested that the correlation seen here is more to do with age than driving experience.

A mixed correlation with driver assists experience was seen in 9.3.2.2.4. It is mostly negative for their use, either in urban, rural, or simply near them. There was a neutral correlation for control and safety questions, there the experience with low level autonomy has no impact on the need to control and opinions of safety. There is a decreasing trend for consent with autonomy experience. This indicates that people who have an experience with systems they are using, most likely cars, acting on their own have not liked it. There is again a large scatter in the answer in each group, thus implying that experience with autonomy is not the dominant factor.

When exploring the cross correlation between factors in 9.3.2.2.5 it was found that for consent and partial control, age and education are

independent from one another as both influence the outcome in the same way. However, from 9.3.2.2.1 and 9.3.2.2.2 it was found that age and education both has an almost neutral correlation on consent. This implies that for partial control age is the dominate factor while for consent education is.

When safety is considered, age and education are not independent, where less educated results in a negative correlation with age and for higher education it is positive. This implies old less educated people are more concerned with safety than younger more education participants. For the complete control correlation plot, the low distribution for the post graduate age group is likely causing an anomaly. That said, the trend is for the education to provide a more positive opinion on complete control, implying it is a dominate factor.

9.4.2 Change in Attitudes

The plots in 9.3.3.1 show that after the flight trial there was a positive opinion of the autonomous air taxi. This indicates that the positive experience given to the participants resulting in a positive opinion of the system. There was a strong preference for the ability to give consent. However, there was also an indication that more control was not going to make the participants feel safer. This indicates that there is level of interaction that the user expects, but more is not going to improve how they feel about autonomous systems.

From 9.3.3.2.1 and 9.3.3.2.2, and 9.3.3.2.4 it is clear that there is a net increase in the opinions of the participants for safety, trust and the use of such systems. This means that it is possible to improve people acceptance and likely use of such system by exposing them to a simulated experience as report here. This opens up the possibility of companies, governments, and regulators using simulated flight trials to help the adoption of autonomous flight systems.

From 9.3.3.2.3 the picture is less clear, there is little change when comparing opinions of partial control before and how safe they felt after the trial, but there was a decrease in how much control they felt they had. This indicates that those that were happy with partial control were less affected by the simulation. However, when comparing the answer to the pre flight question about complete control the trend is different, where the flight trial improved the opinion about feeling safe with the system in control while doing little to change how much control they felt they had. Both of these plots indicate that simulated flight trial improved the opinion

of those that were not comfortable with complete control, but did little to affect those who felt less so about partial control.

In 9.3.3.2.4 the difference between pre and post flight answer about the use of autonomous air taxis shows a net increase in opinion. The increase is small, but clearly evident. This indicates that after a relatively short flight trial, where the flight time was only 5 minutes, the opinion of and likely use is improved. This clearly shows that if a strategy of improving public opinion of autonomous air taxi was to be adopted, simulated flight trials would be a possible route.

9.4.3 Impact of autonomy mode

When comparing the answers for the participants operating under with autonomy by exception or consent in 9.3.3.2.1 it was found that for the post flight the answers were virtually the same. However, for the change in opinion there is a distinct difference. This indicates that when the participants are operating under autonomy by consent, there was a larger improvement in their opinion, but only if they had a more negative opinion in the pre-flight survey. This means the participants a felt safer when operating with consent rather that exception. This would point to the possible requirement to include the options for consent with such an autonomous system.

In 9.3.3.2.2 it was found that those operating under autonomy by consent trusted the system less that those under exception. It can also be seen that the change in opinion is virtually the same for both. This indicates that autonomy by consent is trusted less and regardless of what the pre-flight opinion was, it doesn't change. This means that in terms of trust, autonomy by exception is the preference and this preference cannot be influenced by the type of trials reported here. It is argued here that this is the case because this was a positive flight experience, as in nothing bad happens such as crashes or near misses. This means that from the perspective or the participant, the system was completely competent. However, when consent is required to change destination, this may give the impression of the system not knowing what to do.

The opinions on use can be seen in 9.3.3.2.4. it is clear that there is a preference toward the autonomy by consent mode, where a larger improvement in the opinion is found in all four questions. This implies that for future use and acceptance, autonomy by consent is likely to get better results.

10 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the results of the data analysis from the pilot trials, with a specific focus on investigating and providing insights regarding user acceptance. The data from each pilot were examined individually, as each pilot had a different focus and research questions to investigate. However, cross-pilot analysis was conducted to better understand common “global” factors that influence acceptance.

Pilot 1 suggested that the absence of a human driver may be perceived as a major issue that could hinder acceptance. Moreover, unexpected malfunctioning events (doors not opening in this case) may negatively influence acceptance levels. The latter could be an indication of the heightened expectations of users with respect to the performance of automated vehicles. Given the potential negative implications of the automated technology and the absence of human staff, users may be expecting flawless performance to trust and use the technology. Actions need to be considered to compensate these negative implications of unexpected situations. Participants who felt more confident by the presence of the system were also more likely to accept the technology. To that end, enhancing confidence and trust via advanced technological communication solutions could be a future direction.

Pilot 2 mainly focused on the effects of driver training on acceptance. With respect to that aspect, a positive attitude towards the training was correlated with positive responses towards acceptance related questions however, adequacy, efficiency, and whether participants would suggest similar training to others only had few correlations to acceptance related questions. Vehicle reactions and difficulty to use were two additional factors that had a considerable impact on acceptance.

Pilot 3 investigated the acceptance of an automated bus (shuttle) line. An interesting finding regarding this pilot was found regarding performance of the vehicle. Acceptance levels were higher when the latter was perceived as better compared to a human driver. That is, even if performance is perceived as equal, the public might decide to keep using conventional and familiar solutions, unless additional benefits from the CAV use are perceived.

Pilot 4 further highlighted the importance of vehicle performance on acceptance. Performance needs to be perceived as “more comfortable” compared to the conventional experience to ensure acceptance levels. Similarly, the performance of the vehicle needs to be better than a human

driver, as any other outcome (including same as a human driver) may not suffice to ensure acceptance. Moreover, CAV reactions perceived as “very good” were significantly related to acceptance. This is a finding also occurred in pilot 2.

Finally, pilot 5 investigated the acceptance of connected transport environment and apps. Obstacle frequency was significantly and positively correlated to two of the acceptance related questions (willingness to use and willingness to pay). In the same direction, participants who considered independence while travelling as important were also more likely to have higher acceptance levels. These are potentially the attributes that such connected environment applications should promote and highlight as their main functionalities to enhance acceptance levels.

The cross-pilot analysis compared together pilots using public transport modes and passenger cars. Feelings during the experience were in general significantly related to acceptance. The most commonly significant feeling was trustful. Trust is a major concept related to acceptance and it needs to be ensured in order to enhance acceptance. Another shared finding regards anticipation; participants positively surprised by the performance of CAVs were more likely to have higher levels of acceptance (even compared to those who perceived the experience “as expected”). It has been mentioned that CAVs need to outperform conventional solutions and this finding has been observed consistently across pilots. Difficulty to use and general confidence in CAVs were also consistently significant across passenger car CAVs. Finally, it should be mentioned that participants’ background characteristics were significant only in few cases. This finding suggest that the findings presented in the current document may be applicable to the average user regardless their background; factors such as feelings, vehicle performance, safety, difficulty to use and other are more important than demographic characteristics to enhance acceptance.

The non-pilot specific online survey suggested that:

‘Using mobile applications’, ‘large fonts on HMI display’ and ‘auditory communication’ are preferred HMI methods by respondents.

For requirements towards in-vehicle assistance and information, respondents prefer ‘communication with the vehicle for special assistance’, ‘visual communication with the vehicle such as HMI and mobile apps’ and the ‘presence of steward’.

A high proportion of individuals responded to ‘don’t know’ for improvement in passenger safety and improvement in other road safety by autonomous

bus/shuttle. Further research is required for the effect of autonomous bus on the safety of other road users. Moreover, further experience of autonomous bus/shuttle by the public could alter the perception towards these attitudinal questions.

PAsCAL has also explored attitudes to an autonomous air taxi before and after simulated flight. The work contained here aimed to assess the current attitudes of people to autonomous air taxis and the potential to influence these attitudes via simulated flight trials. As a result of this work, the following Conclusions can be drawn.

Current Attitudes:

- People are, on the whole, positive about the concept of an autonomous air taxi. This is in terms of the safety, trust and future use of such systems.
- People are neutral about requiring consent from the user for the system's actions.
- There is a preference for the system to have only partial control over complete control of a user journey.

Correlations:

- There is a positive correlation between the attitudes of people and their increasing education level.
- There is a negative correlation between attitude and the age of the participant and driving experience
- There is no correlation definite correlation between the attitude of people and with the level of autonomy experience they have.

Change in Attitude:

- The simulated flight trials provide a broadly positive increase in opinions of people towards autonomous air taxis.
- Using autonomy by consent provides larger increase in people's opinion that by exception, although both modes still produce a positive increase in opinion.

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Annexes

Annex 1: supplementary tables of pilots analysis

Pilot 1 supplementary tables

Table A.1: The association of bike sharing use with Q1.1

		Bike sharing		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	10	9
		Expected Count	12.3	6.7
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	3.2	1.8

Table A.2: The association of ride sharing use with Q1.1

		Ride sharing		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	16	11
		Expected Count	15.4	11.6
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	8	11
		Expected Count	10.8	8.2
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	2.8	2.2

Table A.3: The association of ACC use with Q1.1

		ACC		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	15	12
		Expected Count	15.9	11.1
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	10	9
		Expected Count	11.2	7.8
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	2.9	2.1

Table A.4: The association of Carpooling use with Q1.1

		Carpooling		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	24	3
		Expected Count	21.2	5.8
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	11	8
		Expected Count	14.9	4.1
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	3.9	1.1

Table A.5: The association of ride sharing use with Q1.3

		Ride_sharing		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	13.6	10.4
	Yes	Count	10	17
		Expected Count	15.4	11.6

Table A.6: The association of ride sharing use with Q1.3

		Driver_assistance		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	14	10
		Expected Count	12.2	14.8
	Yes	Count	9	18
		Expected Count	12.2	14.8

Table A.7: The association of auto steering use with Q1.3

		Auto steering		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	19	5
		Expected Count	15.5	8.5
	Yes	Count	14	13
		Expected Count	17.5	9.5

Table A.8: The association of carpooling use with Q1.3

		Carpooling		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	22	2
		Expected Count	18.8	5.2
	Yes	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	21.2	5.8

Table A.9: The association of carpooling use with Q1.4

		Ride sharing		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	18	6
		Expected Count	13.6	10.4
	Yes	Count	11	16
		Expected Count	15.4	11.6

Table A.10: The association of driver assistance use with Q1.4

		Driver assistance		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	14	10
		Expected Count	10.8	13.2
	Yes	Count	9	18
		Expected Count	12.2	14.8

Table A.11: The association of carpooling use with Q1.4

		Carpooling		
		0	1	
Q1.4	Other than yes	Count	22	2
		Expected Count	18.8	5.2
	Yes	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	21.2	5.8

Table A.12: The association of ride sharing use with Q1.5

		Ride sharing		
		0	1	
Q1.5	I think it is great	Count	6	10
		Expected Count	8.9	7.1
	It feels good	Count	18	9
		Expected Count	15.1	11.9

Table A.13: The association of shared mobility app use with Q1.1

		Shared_mobility_app		
		0	1	
Q1.1	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses only if IT support was available on the bus	Count	19	8
		Expected Count	18.5	8.5
	I would be willing to switch to autonomous buses	Count	11	8
		Expected Count	13.0	6.0
	I would try to avoid autonomous buses as much as possible	Count	5	0
		Expected Count	3.4	1.6

Table A.14: The association of shared mobility app use with Q1.2

		Shared_mobility_app		
		0	1	
Q1.2	.00	Count	18	4
		Expected Count	15.1	6.9
	1.00	Count	17	12
		Expected Count	19.9	9.1

Table A.15: The association of public transport app use with Q1.2

		PT app		
		0	1	
Q1.2	.00	Count	12	10
		Expected Count	7.8	14.2
	1.00	Count	6	23
		Expected Count	10.2	18.8

Table A.16: The association of public transport app use with Q1.3

		PT_app		
		0	1	
Q1.3	Other than yes	Count	12	12
		Expected Count	8.5	15.5
	Yes	Count	6	21
		Expected Count	9.5	17.5

Pilot 4 - Drivers supplementary tables (fleet sub-pilot)

Table A.17: The association of dangerous CAV reactions with Q4.1

		.00	1.00		
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	49	2	51
		Expected Count	50.0	1.0	51.0
	Yes	Count	50	0	50
		Expected Count	49.0	1.0	50.0

Table A.18: The association of very good CAV reactions with Q4.2

		Very_good		
		.00	1.00	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	33	8
		Expected Count	28.8	12.2
	Yes	Count	38	22
		Expected Count	42.2	17.8

Table A.19: The association of neutral CAV reactions with Q4.2

		Neutral		
		.00	1.00	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	24	17
		Expected Count	29.2	11.8

Yes	Count	48	12
	Expected Count	42.8	17.2

Table A.20: The association of dangerous CAV reactions with Q4.2

		Dangerous	
		.00	1.00
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	2
		Expected Count	.8
Yes	Count	60	0
	Expected Count	58.8	1.2

Table A.21: The association of safe CAV reactions with Q4.2

		CAV_safe	
		.00	1.00
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	13
		Expected Count	18.3
Yes	Count	28	32
	Expected Count	33.3	26.7

Table A.22: The association of safe CAV reactions with Q4.3

		Unpredictable	
		.00	1.00
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	3
		Expected Count	4.4
No	Count	25	8
	Expected Count	28.6	4.4
Yes	Count	23	1
	Expected Count	20.8	3.2

Table A.23: The association of very good CAV reactions with Q4.4

		Very_good		
		.00	1.00	
Q4.4	Willing	Count	57	29
		Expected Count	60.5	25.5
	Avoid or not willing	Count	14	1
		Expected Count	10.5	4.5

Table A.24: The association of unpredictable CAV reactions with Q4.4

		Unpredictable		
		.00	1.00	
Q4.4	Willing	Count	77	9
		Expected Count	74.1	11.9
	Avoid or not willing	Count	10	5
		Expected Count	12.9	2.1

Table A.25: The association of ride sharing service use with Q4.1

		Ride_sharing		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	30	21
		Expected Count	25.8	25.2
	Yes	Count	21	29
		Expected Count	25.2	24.8

Table A.26: The association of experience with CAV service use with Q4.1

		No_CAV_tried		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	49	2
		Expected Count	46.5	4.5
	Yes	Count	43	7
		Expected Count	45.5	4.5

Table A.27: The association of driver assistance use with Q4.2

		Driver_assistance		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	12	29
		Expected Count	16.2	24.8
	Yes	Count	28	32
		Expected Count	23.8	36.2

Table A.28: The association of ACC use with Q4.2

		ACC		
		0	1	
Q4.2	Other than yes	Count	14	27
		Expected Count	18.3	22.7
	Yes	Count	31	29
		Expected Count	26.7	33.3

Table A.29: The association of connected features use with Q4.3

		Connected_features		
		0	1	
Q4.3	Depends on how the technology evolves	Count	19	14
		Expected Count	17.2	15.8
No		Count	12	21
		Expected Count	17.2	15.8
Yes		Count	16	8
		Expected Count	12.5	11.5

Table A.30: The association of ride sharing use with Q4.5

		Ride_sharing		
		0	1	
Q4.5	It feels great	Count	14	22
		Expected Count	18.2	17.8
	It feels bad	Count	10	3
		Expected Count	6.6	6.4
	It feels good	Count	27	25
		Expected Count	26.3	25.7

Table A.31: The association of no CAV services use with Q4.5

		No_CAV_tried		
		0	1	
CAV_population	It feels great	Count	33	3
		Expected Count	32.8	3.2
	It feels bad	Count	9	4
		Expected Count	11.8	1.2
	It feels good	Count	50	2

Expected Count	47.4	4.6
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Table A.32: The association of shared mobility app use with Q4.1

		Shared mobility app		
		0	1	
Q4.1	Other than yes	Count	33	18
		Expected Count	28.8	22.2
	Yes	Count	24	26
		Expected Count	28.2	21.8

Pilot 4 – Passengers supplementary tables (shuttle sub-pilot)

Table A.33: The association of neutral CAV reactions with Q4.2.1

		Neutral		
		0	1	
Q4.2.1	Other than yes	Count	15	12
		Expected Count	19.2	7.8
	Yes	Count	17	1
		Expected Count	12.8	5.2

Table A.34: The association of very good CAV reactions with Q4.2.2

		Very good		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	21	3
		Expected Count	18.7	5.3
	Yes	Count	14	7
		Expected Count	16.3	4.7

Table A.35: The association of neutral CAV reactions with Q4.2.2

Neutral

		Neutral		
		0	1	
Q4.2.2	Other than yes	Count	13	11
		Expected Count	17.1	6.9
	Yes	Count	19	2
		Expected Count	14.9	6.1

Table A.36: The association of neutral CAV reactions with Q4.2.4

		Neutral		
		0	1	
Q4.2.4	Not willing	Count	4	5
		Expected Count	6.4	2.6
	Willing to switch	Count	28	8
		Expected Count	25.6	10.4

Table A.37: The association of neutral CAV reactions with Q4.2.5

		Neutral		
		0	1	
Q4.2.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	10	2
		Expected Count	8.5	3.5
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad.	Count	3	7
		Expected Count	7.1	2.9
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	19	4
		Expected Count	16.4	6.6

Table A.38: The association of unpredictable CAV reactions with Q4.2.5

		Unpredictable		
		0	1	
Q4.2.5	I think it is great if large sections of the population use CAVs.	Count	12	0
		Expected Count	10.4	1.6
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels bad.	Count	10	0
		Expected Count	8.7	1.3
	The idea that large sections of the population use CAVs feels good.	Count	17	6
		Expected Count	19.9	3.1

Annex 2: The GUI of an autonomous air taxi

Annex 3: The opening Brief of the air taxi experiment

Purpose of Experiment

To assess the attitudes of potential future users of autonomous air vehicles to varying levels of autonomy and automated decision-making.

Scenario

You have just landed at Liverpool John Lennon airport. You are travelling to meet friends in Liverpool City Centre for a social visit. You decide to take an autonomous air taxi from the airport to the Pier Head in order to meet your friends on time. During the flight, you take the opportunity to spot landmarks from the air. As the flight progresses, you'll be tasked with telling the operator when you think that you have reached particular landmarks (a map with landmarks will be provided). During the flight, you will need to react to any change in the flight plan that may arise.

Health and Safety

COVID-19 Specific

Masks must be worn by all participants throughout the experiment.

Hand sanitiser must be used prior to entering the simulator.

All elements of the simulator that the participant may touch (specifically the touch panels) will be wiped down control before and after each simulated flight.

General

The participant will receive a full briefing on the entry to, the exit from and conduct whilst within the simulator. This forms part of the standard operating procedure. This will include:

Experienced operator – during each flight, there will be a trained operator using the control desk and equipment. There will also be a 'co-passenger' in the simulator cabin. This will be a member of the simulation facility who will be able to react to any unforeseen circumstances that arise whilst the simulator is active.

Comms with control desk – there is a microphone and a headset for the participant to use to communicate with the simulator operator. A web camera is also used to monitor the participant during a flight. The output of the microphone and webcam are not recorded.

Platform motion – if you feel unwell, nervous, stressed, or want the simulator to stop because of the motion, contact the operator to stop.

Enclosed Space – the simulator is an enclosed space and could cause claustrophobic systems, even if the participant has not experienced them before. Inform the operator if you are feeling unwell and the trial will be stopped immediately.

Climbing the ladder – it should be reinforced that both hands should be on the railings when climbing or descending the ladder. Always face the rungs of the ladder.

Buckle up – buckle up the seat belt before the flight starts and remain buckled up until the operator opens the door again.

Flight conclusion - Wait for operator to open sim before you get up and attempt to leave the simulator. The stairs are removed from the door during the flight.

Emergency Stop - If at any time the participant wants the flight to stop, they should call loudly ‘Stop! Stop! Stop!’ and the operator will stop the experiment immediately.

Experiment Process

- Listen to opening brief (2 mins)
- Sign consent form (2mins)
- Complete pre-flight survey (5 mins estimated)
- Carry out scenario (10 mins)
- Complete post flight survey (3 mins estimated)

Notices to participants

Data

- Recordings of the audio will be made during the flight trial. These will be later transcribed, and the audio files deleted permanently.
- The candidate numbers are used to anonymise the questions upon collection.
- Draw attention to section 8 of participant information sheet.

Exclusion Criteria

- Check that the participant does not suffer from claustrophobia or motion sickness
- Check that the participant knows that they can stop the experiment at any point if they experience any symptoms.

Annex 4: The full questionnaire for pre-flight survey

<p>Part A - Basic Information</p> <p>1 – Candidate Number</p> <p>2 – Please indicate your age by ticking the relevant box <input type="checkbox"/> 18-25 <input type="checkbox"/> 26-35 <input type="checkbox"/> 36-45 <input type="checkbox"/> 46-55 <input type="checkbox"/> 56-65 <input type="checkbox"/> 66-75 <input type="checkbox"/> Over 76</p> <p>3 – Please indicate your gender by ticking the relevant box <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to Say</p> <p>4 – Please indicate your employment status <input type="checkbox"/> Student <input type="checkbox"/> Full Time (>30hr pw) <input type="checkbox"/> Part Time (<30Hr pw) <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed <input type="checkbox"/> Not in Work <input type="checkbox"/> Retired</p>	<p>5 – Please indicate your highest level of academic qualification by ticking the relevant box <input type="checkbox"/> No School Certificate <input type="checkbox"/> High/Secondary School (e.g. GCSEs) <input type="checkbox"/> Apprenticeship / Vocational Training (e.g. T Levels) <input type="checkbox"/> Further Education (e.g. A Levels, Diploma) <input type="checkbox"/> Undergraduate degree (Bachelors or Integrated Masters) <input type="checkbox"/> Postgraduate degree (e.g. MSc, PhD)</p>
<p>Part B - Current Experience</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Online Mobility Applications</p> <p>1 - Of the following, which type of online mobility applications do you use and how often?</p> <p>1 - Routing and guidance applications (e.g. google maps) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>2 - Shared Mobility applications (e.g. ZipCar) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>3 - Ride sharing applications (e.g. BlaBlaCar) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>4 - Ride Hailing Applications (e.g. Uber) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>5 - Public transport applications (e.g. TrainLine) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Driving (only if you hold a driving license)</p> <p>2 - What type of driving license do you hold? <input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Provisional <input type="checkbox"/> Valid for motorcycles (Type A) <input type="checkbox"/> Valid for cars (Type B) <input type="checkbox"/> Valid for both, cars and motorcycles (A-B) <input type="checkbox"/> Valid for any form of Light/Heavy-Goods Vehicle (C)</p>	<p>3 - How many years have you held the license? <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/> 1-5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6-10 <input type="checkbox"/> 11-15 <input type="checkbox"/> >16</p> <p>4 - Is driving part of your job? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Piloting (only if you hold a pilot's license)</p> <p>5 - What type of license do you have? <input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Private pilot license (fixed wing) <input type="checkbox"/> Private pilot license (helicopter) <input type="checkbox"/> Professional pilot license (fixed wing) <input type="checkbox"/> Professional pilot license (helicopter)</p> <p>6 - Is piloting part of your job? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>7 - How many total hours do you have flying? <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/> < 50 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 50 – 150 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 150 – 300 hours <input type="checkbox"/> > 300 hours</p> <p>8 - How many total hours do you have flying as pilot in command? <input type="checkbox"/> < 50 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 50 – 150 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 150 – 300 hours <input type="checkbox"/> > 300 hours</p>
<p>Part C - Autonomous Vehicles Experience</p> <p>Have you ever driven/piloted/occupied a vehicle that included some of the following automated features?</p> <p>1 - Driver assistance: The vehicle had additions such as Satellite Navigation, speed limit indicator, blind spot detection, parking collision detection etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>How easy or difficult was it to use the autonomed features? <input type="checkbox"/> very difficult <input type="checkbox"/> difficult <input type="checkbox"/> neither difficult nor easy <input type="checkbox"/> easy <input type="checkbox"/> very easy</p> <p>How safe did you feel with the autonomous features you used? <input type="checkbox"/> very safe <input type="checkbox"/> safe <input type="checkbox"/> neither safe nor unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> very unsafe</p>	<p>How easy or difficult was it to use the autonomous features? <input type="checkbox"/> very hard <input type="checkbox"/> hard <input type="checkbox"/> neither hard nor easy <input type="checkbox"/> easy <input type="checkbox"/> very easy</p> <p>How safe did you feel with the partially autonomous features you used? <input type="checkbox"/> very safe <input type="checkbox"/> safe <input type="checkbox"/> neither safe nor unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> very unsafe</p> <p>3 - Full Autonomy: the car could accelerate/brake AND change direction at the same time (auto-pilot) <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often</p> <p>How easy or difficult was it to use the autonomous features? <input type="checkbox"/> very difficult <input type="checkbox"/> difficult <input type="checkbox"/> neither difficult nor easy <input type="checkbox"/> easy <input type="checkbox"/> very easy</p> <p>How safe did you feel with the autonomous features you used?</p>

<p>2 - Partial automation: the car was able to brake/accelerate OR change direction, but not both things at the same time (adaptative cruise control, lane assistance)</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/> Often </p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> very safe <input type="checkbox"/> safe <input type="checkbox"/> neither safe nor unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> unsafe <input type="checkbox"/> very unsafe </p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Part D – Your Attitudes to Autonomous Vehicles</p> <p>Me using them</p> <p>1 - Prior to participating in this study, what was your level of knowledge about developments in autonomous air vehicle technologies (AAV)?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> None</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I am aware of their existence but do not follow or read about developments in AAV.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I occasionally read or follow news about autonomous air vehicles but do not follow the developments closely.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I follow the field closely read a lot and regularly about autonomous air vehicles.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I follow closely specialised, technical and/or scientific documents or publications about AAVs. Or work/are actively engaged in the field.</p> <p>2 - I would be comfortable with the vehicle being in complete control of my journey.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p> <p>3 - I would be comfortable with the vehicle being in partial control of my journey.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p> <p>4 - I would trust the vehicle to act safely.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p> <p>5 - I'm comfortable with the vehicle changing its behaviour without my consent</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p>	<p>6 – Would you realistically consider using autonomous air vehicles in the future?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – Probably not <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – Indifferent <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – Probably <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – Certainly</p> <p>7 - In principle, I would find the concept of personal air transport and urban air mobility to be a ... (either piloted or autonomous)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – a very bad idea <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – a bad idea <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither a good nor a bad idea <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – a good idea <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – a very good idea</p> <p>8 - Which issues would concern you relating to use of autonomous air vehicles (tick all that apply)?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> System failure <input type="checkbox"/> Human error <input type="checkbox"/> Risk of accident</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Legal liability in case of accident <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of control by passenger / user <input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient information/training for passenger / users</p> <p>Others using them</p> <p>9 - I would feel safe with other people using autonomous air vehicles near me</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p> <p>10 – In general, I think it would be safe for autonomous air vehicles to operate in urban areas.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p> <p>11 - In general, I think it would be safe for autonomous air vehicles to operate rural areas.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 – Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – agree <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – strongly agree</p>
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Annex 5: The debrief of the air taxi experiment

Purpose of Experiment

To assess the attitudes of potential future users of autonomous air vehicles to varying levels of autonomy and automated decision-making.

Reflection on flight trial

We would like you to now reflect on both your positive and negative experiences during the air-taxi scenario and consider how it made you feel about the potential future use of autonomous air vehicles, either for yourself or for others. Consider how you felt during each stage of flight and during each event that occurred.

Process

Please complete the post-flight survey.

Annex 6: The full questionnaire for post-flight survey

<p>Candidate Number</p> <p>Part A - Reflections on the flight trial</p> <p>1 - I felt safe with the vehicle in control (D2,D3) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>2 - I felt like I was in control of what the vehicle was doing <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>3 - I would feel safer if I had more control of the vehicle (D2,D3) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>4 - I would feel safer if I had more awareness of the purpose of the vehicle's actions (D2,D3) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p>	<p>5 - I felt safe with the actions that the vehicle took (D4) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>6 - I would prefer to give consent to the proposed actions prior to the vehicle taking them (D4,D5) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>7 - I trusted the vehicle's actions (D5,D2,D3) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>8 - I would consider using autonomous air vehicles in the future (D6) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p>
<p>Part B - Reflections if the flight trial happened near me</p> <p>9 - I would feel safe if the vehicle was operating near me (D9) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>10- I would feel safe with the vehicle operating in urban areas (D10) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p>	<p>11 - I would feel safe with the vehicle operating in rural areas (D11) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p> <p>12 - I would trust the vehicle to act safely (D9,D12) <input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> disagree <input type="checkbox"/> neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> agree <input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree</p>